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function out = model

model.geom('geom1').create('blk1', 'Block');
model.geom('geom1').feature('blk1').set('size', {'0.02 [m]' '0.02 [m]' '1'});
model.geom('geom1').feature('blk1').setIndex('size', '0.02 [m]', 2);
model.geom('geom1').runPre('fin');
model.geom('geom1').run('blk1');
model.geom('geom1').create('sph1', 'Sphere');
model.geom('geom1').feature('sph1').set('r', '500e-6[m]');
model.geom('geom1').feature('sph1').set('pos', {'0.02 [m]/2' '0' '0'});
model.geom('geom1').feature('sph1').setIndex('pos', '0.02 [m]/2', 1);
model.geom('geom1').feature('sph1').setIndex('pos', '0.02 [m]/2', 2);
model.geom('geom1').run('sph1');
model.geom('geom1').create('unil', 'Union');
model.geom('geom1').feature('unil').selection('input').set({'blk1'});

model.view('view1').hideObjects.create('hide1');
model.view('view1').hideObjects('hide1').init;
model.view('view1').hideObjects('hide1').add({'blk1'});

model.geom('geom1').feature('unil').selection('input').set({'blk1' 'sph1'});

model.view('view1').hideObjects.clear;
model.view('view1').hideObjects.clear;
model.view('view1').hideObjects.clear;

model.geom('geom1').runPre('fin');
model.geom('geom1').run('fin');

model.physics('dode').selection.set([2]);
model.physics('dode').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'alpha*ATR', 0);

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable.create('var1');
model.variable('var1').model('comp1');
model.variable('var1').set('AGT', '483.9[pmol/ml]');
model.variable('var1').set('AngI', '7.5[fmol/ml]');
model.variable('var1').set('AngII', '4.75[fmol/ml]');
model.variable('var1').set('Ang17', '14[fmol/ml]');
model.variable('var1').set('AngIV', '1.29[fmol/ml]');
model.variable('var1').set('AT1bAngII', '16.2[fmol/ml]');
model.variable('var1').set('AT2bAngII', '5.4[fmol/ml]');
model.variable('var1').set('hAGT', '16[h]');
model.variable('var1').set('hAngI', '0.5[min]');
model.variable('var1').set('hAngII', '0.5[min]');
model.variable('var1').set('hAng17', '29[min]');
model.variable('var1').set('AGTsy', '34620[fmol/ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('ACE', '54.1[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('Chymase', '1.1[1/h]');
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model.variable('var1').set('NEP_AngI17', '1.1[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('ACE2', '2.4[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('AngIIctAngIV', '23.5[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('AngIIAt1br', '11.8[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('AngIIAt2br', '39[1/h]');

model.physics.create('dode2', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u2'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode2', true);

model.variable('var1').remove('AGT');

model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode2').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'AGT');
model.physics('dode2').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'kAGT-PRA-(ln(2)/hAGT)*AGT', 0);

model.variable('var1').rename('AGTsy', 'kAGT');
model.variable('var1').set('PRA', '0.97[ng/ml/h]');

model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'g/ml/h');
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');

model.variable('var1').set('PRA', '0.97[ng/ml/h]*1[mol/kg]');

model.physics.create('dode3', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u3'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode3', true);

model.physics('dode3').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode3').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('dode3').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('dode3').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'Ang1');
model.physics('dode3').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'PRA-(cACE+cChym+cNEP)*AngI', 0);
model.physics('dode3').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'AngI');

model.variable('var1').rename('ACE', 'cACE');
model.variable('var1').rename('ACE2', 'cACE2');
model.variable('var1').rename('Chymase', 'cChym');
model.variable('var1').rename('NEP_AngI17', 'NEP');
model.variable('var1').rename('NEP', 'cNEP');

model.physics.create('dode4', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u4'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode4', true);

model.variable('var1').rename('AngIIctAngIV', 'cAngIIAngIV');

model.physics('dode4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(cACE+cChym)*AngI-(cACE2-  
cAngIIAngIV-cAT1-cAT2)*AngII-(ln(2)/)', 0);
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model.physics('dode4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(cACE+cChym)*AngI-(cACE2-  
cAngIIAngIV-cAT1-cAT2)*AngII-(ln(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);  
  
model.variable('var1').rename('AT1bAngII', 'cAT1');  
model.variable('var1').rename('AT2bAngII', 'cAT2');  
model.variable('var1').rename('AngII', 'cAngII');  
model.variable('var1').rename('AngI', 'cAngI');  
  
model.physics('dode4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(cACE+cChym)*AngI', 0);  
model.physics('dode4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(cACE+cChym)*AngI-(cACE2-  
cAngIIAngIV-cAT1-cAT2)*AngII', 0);  
model.physics('dode4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(cACE+cChym)*AngI-(cACE2-  
cAngIIAngIV-cAT1-cAT2)*AngII-(ln(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);  
model.physics('dode4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(cACE+cChym)*AngI-(ln(2)/hAngII)  
*AngII', 0);  
model.physics('dode4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(cACE+cChym)*AngI-(cACE2-  
cAngIIAngIV-cAT1-cAT2)*AngII-(ln(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);  
  
model.variable('var1').rename('cAT1', 'cAT1_');  
model.variable('var1').rename('cAT2', 'cAT2_');  
model.variable('var1').rename('AngIIAt1br', 'cAT1');  
model.variable('var1').rename('AngIIAt2br', 'cAT2');  
  
model.label('Untitled.mph');  
  
model.physics.create('dode5', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u5'});  
  
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode5', true);  
  
model.physics('dode5').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');  
model.physics('dode5').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');  
model.physics('dode5').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');  
model.physics('dode5').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'Ang17');  
  
model.variable('var1').rename('Ang17', 'cAng17');  
  
model.physics('dode5').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cNEP*AngI+cACE2*AngII-(ln(2)  
/hAng17)*Ang17', 0);  
model.physics.create('dode6', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u6'});  
  
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode6', true);  
  
model.physics('dode6').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');  
model.physics('dode6').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');  
model.physics('dode6').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');  
model.physics('dode6').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'AngIV');  
model.physics('dode6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cAngIIAngIV', 0);  
model.physics('dode6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cAngIIAngIV*AngII-(ln(2)/hAngIV)  
*AngIV', 0);  
  
model.variable('var1').set('hAngIV', '0.5[min]');
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model.physics.create('dode7', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u7'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode7', true);

model.physics('dode7').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode7').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('dode7').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('dode7').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'AT1bAngII');
model.physics('dode7').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cAT1', 0);
model.physics('dode7').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cAT1*AngII-(ln(2)/hAT1)', 0);
model.physics('dode7').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cAT1*AngII-(ln(2)/hAT1)
*AT1bAngII', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('hAT1', '12[min]');

model.physics.create('dode8', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u8'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode8', true);

model.physics('dode8').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode8').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('dode8').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('dode8').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'AT2bAngII');
model.physics('dode8').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cAT2*AngII', 0);
model.physics('dode8').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cAT2*AngII-(ln(2)/hAT2)
*AT2bAngII', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('hAT2', '12[min]');
model.variable('var1').rename('kAGT', 'kAGT_');
model.variable('var1').rename('kAGT_', 'kAGT');

model.physics('dode').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'alpha*AT1', 0);
model.physics('dode').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'AT1', 0);
model.physics('dode').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'AT1bAngII', 0);
model.physics('dode').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '1[m^3/mole/s]AT1bAngII', 0);
model.physics('dode').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '1[m^3/mole/s]*AT1bAngII', 0);

model.sol.create('sol1');
model.sol('sol1').study('std1');

model.study('std1').feature('time').set('notlistsolnum', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('time').set('notsolnum', '1');
model.study('std1').feature('time').set('listsolnum', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('time').set('solnum', '1');

model.sol('sol1').create('st1', 'StudyStep');
model.sol('sol1').feature('st1').set('study', 'std1');
model.sol('sol1').feature('st1').set('studystep', 'time');
model.sol('sol1').create('v1', 'Variables');
model.sol('sol1').feature('v1').set('control', 'time');
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model.sol('sol1').create('t1', 'Time');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('tlist', 'range(0,0.1,1)');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('plot', 'off');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('plotgroup', 'Default');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('plotfreq', 'tout');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('probesel', 'all');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('probes', {});
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('probefreq', 'tsteps');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('control', 'time');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').create('sel', 'Segregated');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature.remove('ssDef');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss1', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_lg'});
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss2', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_AGT'});
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss3', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss3').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_AngI'});
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss3').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss4', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss4').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_AngII'});
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss4').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss5', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss5').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_Ang17'});
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss5').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss6', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss6').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_AngIV'});
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss6').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss7', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss7').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_AT1bAngII'});
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss7').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss8', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss8').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_AT2bAngII'});
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss8').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature.remove('fcDef');
model.sol('sol1').attach('std1');

model.physics('dode').tag('growth');
model.physics('dode2').tag('AGT');
model.physics('growth').feature('init1').set('lg', '1');
model.physics('AGT').feature('init1').set('AGT', '483.9[pmol/ml]');
model.physics('dode3').tag('AngI');
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model.physics('AngI').feature('init1').set('AngI', '7.5[fmol/ml]');
model.physics('dode4').tag('AngII');
model.physics('AngII').feature('init1').set('AngII', '4.75[fmol/ml]');
model.physics('dode5').tag('Ang17');
model.physics('Ang17').feature('init1').set('Ang17', '14[fmol/ml]');
model.physics('dode6').tag('AngIV');
model.physics('AngIV').feature('init1').set('AngIV', '1.29');
model.physics('dode7').tag('AT1bAngII');
model.physics('AT1bAngII').feature('init1').set('AT1bAngII', '16.2[fmol/ml]');
model.physics('dode8').tag('AT2bAngII');
model.physics('AT2bAngII').feature('init1').set('AT2bAngII', '5.4[fmol/ml]');

model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('dDef').set('linsolver', 'pardiso');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').create('fcl', 'FullyCoupled');

model.result.create('pg1', 3);
model.result('pg1').set('data', 'dset1');
model.result('pg1').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'lg');
model.result.create('pg2', 3);
model.result('pg2').set('data', 'dset1');
model.result('pg2').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg2').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result.create('pg3', 3);
model.result('pg3').set('data', 'dset1');
model.result('pg3').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg3').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result.create('pg4', 3);
model.result('pg4').set('data', 'dset1');
model.result('pg4').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg4').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result.create('pg5', 3);
model.result('pg5').set('data', 'dset1');
model.result('pg5').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg5').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result.create('pg6', 3);
model.result('pg6').set('data', 'dset1');
model.result('pg6').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg6').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
model.result.create('pg7', 3);
model.result('pg7').set('data', 'dset1');
model.result('pg7').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg7').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result.create('pg8', 3);
model.result('pg8').set('data', 'dset1');
model.result('pg8').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg8').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result.remove('pg8');
model.result.remove('pg7');
model.result.remove('pg2');
model.result.remove('pg1');
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model.result.remove('pg4');
model.result.remove('pg3');
model.result.remove('pg6');
model.result.remove('pg5');

model.variable('var1').rename('AngIV', 'cAngIV');

model.result.create('pg1', 3);
model.result('pg1').set('data', 'dset1');
model.result('pg1').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'lg');
model.result.create('pg2', 3);
model.result('pg2').set('data', 'dset1');
model.result('pg2').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg2').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result.create('pg3', 3);
model.result('pg3').set('data', 'dset1');
model.result('pg3').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg3').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result.create('pg4', 3);
model.result('pg4').set('data', 'dset1');
model.result('pg4').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg4').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result.create('pg5', 3);
model.result('pg5').set('data', 'dset1');
model.result('pg5').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg5').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result.create('pg6', 3);
model.result('pg6').set('data', 'dset1');
model.result('pg6').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg6').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
model.result.create('pg7', 3);
model.result('pg7').set('data', 'dset1');
model.result('pg7').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg7').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result.create('pg8', 3);
model.result('pg8').set('data', 'dset1');
model.result('pg8').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg8').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');

model.sol('sol1').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tunit', 'min');
model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tlist', 'range(0,0.1,12)');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'log(1)');
model.result('pg1').run;
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model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'log(10)');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('AT2bAngII').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'cAT2*AngII-(log(2)/hAT2)
*AT2bAngII', 0);
model.physics('AT1bAngII').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'cAT1*AngII-(log(2)/hAT1)
*AT1bAngII', 0);
model.physics('AngIV').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'cAngIIAngIV*AngII-(log(2)/hAngIV)
*AngIV', 0);
model.physics('Ang17').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'cNEP*AngI+cACE2*AngII-(log(2)
/hAng17)*Ang17', 0);
model.physics('AngII').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '(cACE+cChym)*AngI-(cACE2-
cAngIIAngIV-cAT1-cAT2)*AngII-(log(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('AGT').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'kAGT-PRA-(log(2)/hAGT)*AGT', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result.create('pg9', 'PlotGroup1D');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').create('ptgr1', 'PointGraph');
model.result.dataset.create('cpt1', 'CutPoint3D');
model.result.dataset('cpt1').set('pointx', '0.02 [m]/2');
model.result.dataset('cpt1').set('pointy', '0.02 [m]/2');
model.result.dataset('cpt1').set('pointz', '0.02 [m]/2');
model.result.dataset('cpt1').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('data', 'cpt1');
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('unit', 'fmol/m^3');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg9').run;
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model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg9').run;

model.label('Untitled.mph');

model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result.create('pg10', 'PlotGroup1D');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').create('ptgr1', 'PointGraph');
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('data', 'cpt1');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').run;

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg10').run;

model.physics('AGT').feature('init1').set('AGT', '0*483.9[pmol/ml]');
model.physics('AngI').feature('init1').set('AngI', '0*7.5[fmol/ml]');
model.physics('AngII').feature('init1').set('AngII', '0*4.75[fmol/ml]');
model.physics('Ang17').feature('init1').set('Ang17', '0*14[fmol/ml]');
model.physics('AngIV').feature('init1').set('AngIV', '0*1.29');
model.physics('AT1bAngII').feature('init1').set('AT1bAngII', '0*16.2[fmol/ml]');
model.physics('AT2bAngII').feature('init1').set('AT2bAngII', '0*5.4[fmol/ml]');

model.result('pg10').run;

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg10').run;

model.variable('var1').remove('cAngI');
```

```
model.variable('var1').remove('cAngII');
model.variable('var1').remove('cAng17');
model.variable('var1').remove('cAngIV');
model.variable('var1').remove('cAT1_');
model.variable('var1').remove('cAT2_');
model.variable('var1').set('hAGT', '10[h]');
model.variable('var1').set('hAngII', '0.66[min]');
model.variable('var1').set('hAng17', '30[min]');
model.variable('var1').set('cAT2', '3.9[1/h]');

model.physics('AngI').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'PRA-(cACE+cChym+cNEP)*AngI-(log(2)
/hAngI)*AngI', 0);
model.physics('AngI').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'PRA-(cACE+cChym+cNEP)*AngI-(log(2)
/hAngI)*AngI+23.1[fmol/ml/h]', 0);

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AngI');

model.variable('var1').set('PRA', '0.97[ng/ml/h]*0.0033[fmol/kg]');

model.sol('sol1').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '120', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg10').run;

model.variable('var1').set('PRA', '0.97[ng/ml/h]*0.0033[fmol/ng]');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').run;

model.variable('var1').set('PRA', '0.97[ng/ml/h]*740.74[fmol/ng]');
```

```
model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg10').run;

model.physics('AngI').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'PRA-(cACE+cChym+cNEP)*AngI-(log(2)
/hAngI)*AngI+0*23.1[fmol/ml/h]', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'lg');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg10').run;

model.physics.create('solid', 'SolidMechanics', 'geom1');

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('solid', true);

model.physics('solid').create('hmm1', 'HyperelasticModel', 3);
model.physics('solid').feature('hmm1').set('lambLame_mat', 'userdef');
model.physics('solid').feature('hmm1').set('muLame_mat', 'userdef');
model.physics('solid').feature('hmm1').set('rho_mat', 'userdef');
model.physics('solid').feature('hmm1').set('muLame', 'mi');
model.physics('solid').feature('hmm1').set('lambLame', 'l');

model.variable.create('var2');
model.variable('var2').model('comp1');
model.variable('var2').set('solid.kappa', '2*solid.muLame*(1+poissonr)/(3*(1-
2*poissonr))');
model.variable('var2').set('ri', 'sqrt(x^2+y^2+z^2)');
model.variable('var2').set('phi', 'atan2(y,x)');
model.variable('var2').set('th', 'acos(z/ri)');
model.variable('var2').set('Smat11', '2*solid.Ji*d(Wmat,solid.C111)');
model.variable('var2').set('Smat12', 'solid.Ji*d(Wmat,solid.C112)');
model.variable('var2').set('Smat13', 'solid.Ji*d(Wmat,solid.C113)');
model.variable('var2').set('Smat22', '2*solid.Ji*d(Wmat,solid.C122)');
model.variable('var2').set('Smat23', 'solid.Ji*d(Wmat,solid.C123)');
model.variable('var2').set('Smat33', '2*solid.Ji*d(Wmat,solid.C133)');
model.variable('var2').set('smat11', '(Smat11*(solid.Fdlx1)^2+Smat22*(solid.Fdlx2)
^2+2*Smat23*solid.Fdlx2*solid.Fdlx3+Smat33*(solid.Fdlx3)^2+2*solid.Fdlx1*(Smat12*solid.
Fdlx2+Smat13*solid.Fdlx3))/solid.J');
model.variable('var2').set('smat12', '(solid.Fdlx1*(Smat11*solid.Fdly1+Smat12*solid.
Fdly2+Smat13*solid.Fdly3)+solid.Fdlx2*(Smat12*solid.Fdly1+Smat22*solid.
Fdly2+Smat23*solid.Fdly3)+solid.Fdlx3*(Smat13*solid.Fdly1+Smat23*solid.
Fdly2+Smat33*solid.Fdly3))/solid.J');
```

```
model.variable('var2').set('smat13', '(solid.Fdlx1*(Smat11*solid.Fdlz1+Smat12*solid.Fdlz2+Smat13*solid.Fdlz3)+solid.Fdlx2*(Smat12*solid.Fdlz1+Smat22*solid.Fdlz2+Smat23*solid.Fdlz3)+solid.Fdlx3*(Smat13*solid.Fdlz1+Smat23*solid.Fdlz2+Smat33*solid.Fdlz3))/solid.J');
model.variable('var2').set('smat22', '(Smat11*(solid.Fdly1)^2+Smat22*(solid.Fdly2)^2+2*Smat23*solid.Fdly2*solid.Fdly3+Smat33*(solid.Fdly3)^2+2*solid.Fdly1*(Smat12*solid.Fdly2+Smat13*solid.Fdly3))/solid.J');
model.variable('var2').set('smat23', '(solid.Fdly1*(Smat11*solid.Fdlz1+Smat12*solid.Fdlz2+Smat13*solid.Fdlz3)+solid.Fdly2*(Smat12*solid.Fdlz1+Smat22*solid.Fdlz2+Smat23*solid.Fdlz3)+solid.Fdly3*(Smat13*solid.Fdlz1+Smat23*solid.Fdlz2+Smat33*solid.Fdlz3))/solid.J');
model.variable('var2').set('smat33', '(Smat11*(solid.Fdlz1)^2+Smat22*(solid.Fdlz2)^2+2*Smat23*solid.Fdlz2*solid.Fdlz3+Smat33*(solid.Fdlz3)^2+2*solid.Fdlz1*(Smat12*solid.Fdlz2+Smat13*solid.Fdlz3))/solid.J');
model.variable('var2').set('smatrr', 'smat33*cos(th)*cos(th)+smat11*cos(phi)*cos(phi)*sin(th)*sin(th)+smat13*cos(phi)*sin(2*th)+2*smat12*cos(phi)*sin(th)*sin(th)*sin(phi)+smat23*sin(2*th)*sin(phi)+smat22*sin(th)*sin(th)*sin(phi)*sin(phi)');
model.variable('var2').set('smatrr', 'smat11*cos(th)*cos(th)*cos(phi)*cos(phi)+smat33*sin(th)*sin(th)-smat13*cos(phi)*sin(2*th)-smat23*sin(2*th)*sin(phi)+smat22*cos(th)*cos(th)*sin(phi)*sin(phi)+smat12*cos(th)*cos(th)*sin(2*phi)');
model.variable('var2').set('smatpp', 'smat22*cos(phi)*cos(phi)-2*smat12*cos(phi)*sin(phi)+smat11*sin(phi)*sin(phi)');
model.variable('var2').set('srr', 'solid.sz*cos(th)*cos(th)+solid.sx*cos(phi)*cos(phi)*sin(th)*sin(th)+solid.sxz*cos(phi)*sin(2*th)+2*solid.sxy*cos(phi)*sin(th)*sin(th)*sin(phi)+solid.syz*sin(2*th)*sin(phi)+solid.sy*sin(th)*sin(th)*sin(phi)*sin(phi)');
model.variable('var2').set('stt', 'solid.sx*cos(th)*cos(th)*cos(phi)*cos(phi)+solid.sz*sin(th)*sin(th)-solid.sxz*cos(phi)*sin(2*th)-solid.syz*sin(2*th)*sin(phi)+solid.sy*cos(th)*cos(th)*sin(phi)*sin(phi)+solid.sxy*cos(th)*cos(th)*sin(2*phi)');
model.variable('var2').set('spp', 'solid.sy*cos(phi)*cos(phi)-2*solid.sxy*cos(phi)*sin(phi)+solid.sx*sin(phi)*sin(phi)');
model.variable('var2').set('smatbulk', '(smatrr+smatrr+smatpp)/3');
model.variable('var2').set('sbulk', '(srr+stt+spp)/3');
model.variable('var2').set('Wmat', '0.5*(solid.muLame*(solid.I1CIel-3)+solid.kappa*(solid.Jel-1)^2)');
model.variable.create('var3');
model.variable('var3').model('comp1');
model.variable('var3').selection.geom('geom1', 3);
model.variable('var3').selection.set([1]);
model.variable.duplicate('var4', 'var3');
model.variable('var4').selection.all;
model.variable('var4').selection.set([2]);
model.variable('var4').set('poissonr', '0.45');
model.variable('var4').set('solid.muLame', '70e3 [Pa]');
model.variable('var3').set('poissonr', '0.2');
model.variable('var3').set('solid.muLame', '21e3 [Pa]');

model.physics('solid').feature('hmm1').set('MaterialModel', 'userDefined');
model.physics('solid').feature('hmm1').set('Ws', 'Wmat');

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;
```

```
model.physics('solid').feature('hmm1').selection.all;
model.physics('solid').create('roll1', 'Roller', 2);
model.physics('solid').feature('roll1').selection.all;
model.physics('solid').feature('roll1').selection.set([1 2 3 4 5 14]);

model.variable('var3').set('lg', '1');

model.physics('solid').feature('hmm1').featureInfo('info').set('solid.Fiil11', 0, ✓
{'1/lg'});
model.physics('solid').feature('hmm1').featureInfo('info').set('solid.Fiil33', 0, ✓
{'1/lg'});
model.physics('solid').feature('hmm1').featureInfo('info').set('solid.Fiil22', 0, ✓
{'1/lg'});

model.sol('sol1').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('AGT').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('AngI').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('AngII').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('AngI7').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('AngIV').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('AT1bAngII').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('AT2bAngII').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('growth').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '1[ml/fmole/h]*AT1bAngII', 0);
model.physics('growth').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '1[ml/fmol/h]*AT1bAngII', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'lg');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('quickxnumber', '1');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sbulk');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result.dataset('dset1').set('frametype', 'spatial');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowevalintitle', false);
model.result('pg1').set('title', 'Time=12 min Slice: (N/m<sup>2</sup>)');
model.result('pg1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeunit', 'N/m^2');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormin', -26916.52945040293);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormax', 6596.770525324385);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecoloractive', 'off');
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamin', -26916.52945040293);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamax', 6596.770525324385);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedataactive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeactualminmax', [-26916.52945040293↙
6596.770525324385]);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', true);
model.result.table.create('ev13', 'Table');
model.result.table('ev13').comments('Interactive 3D values');
model.result.table('ev13').label('Evaluation 3D');
model.result.table('ev13').addRow([0.01 0.010376455800678534 0.009382228151963492↙
-26276.16492716103], [0 0 0 0]);

model.variable('var3').set('solid.muLame', '4e3 [Pa]');
model.variable('var3').set('poissonr', '0.35');
model.variable('var4').set('solid.muLame', '40e3 [Pa]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', ('89'));
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var4').set('solid.muLame', '14e3 [Pa]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', ('95'));
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', ('96'));
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', ('95'));
model.result('pg1').run;

model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('initialstepbdfactive', 'on');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdfactive', 'on');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdf', '0.01');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('initialstepbdf', '0.01');
model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.label('RAS model check_zero initial_newPRA solid_real mechanics.mph');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('AT1bAngII').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '(1-b)cAT1*AngII-(log(2)/hAT1) *AT1bAngII', 0);
model.physics('AT1bAngII').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '(1-b)*cAT1*AngII-(log(2)/hAT1) *AT1bAngII', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('b', '0.9');

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result.numerical.create('int1', 'IntVolume');
model.result.numerical('int1').set('expr', {});
model.result.numerical('int1').set('descr', {});
model.result.numerical('int1').setIndex('expr', '1', 0);
model.result.numerical('int1').selection.all;
model.result.numerical('int1').selection.set([2]);
model.result.numerical('int1').setIndex('unit', 'mm^3', 0);
model.result.table.create('tbl1', 'Table');
model.result.table('tbl1').comments('Volume Integration 1 (1)');
model.result.numerical('int1').set('table', 'tbl1');
model.result.numerical('int1').setResult;
model.result.create('pg11', 1);
model.result('pg11').set('data', 'none');
model.result('pg11').create('tblp1', 'Table');
model.result('pg11').feature('tblp1').set('table', 'tbl1');
model.result('pg11').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.view('view1').set('scenelight', 'off');

model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowevalintitle', false);
model.result('pg1').set('title', 'Time=12 min Slice: Dependent variable AngII (fmol/ml)');
model.result('pg1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeunit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormin', 10.777358856309176);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormax', 10.777358899536353);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecoloractive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamin', 10.777358856309176);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamax', 10.777358899536353);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedataactive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeactualminmax', [10.777358856309176, 10.777358899536353]);
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', true);
model.result.table('evl3').addRow([0.01 0.00880883672263116 0.010187157908603972
10.777358857531839], [0 0 0 0]);
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result.export.create('plot1', 'pg10', 'ptgr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg10').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg10').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot1').set('header', 'off');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result.export.create('plot2', 'pg10', 'ptgr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg10').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg10').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot2').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot2').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\block_AngI.txt');
model.result.export('plot2').run;
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg10').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot2').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\block_AngII.txt');
model.result.export('plot2').run;
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg10').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot2').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\block_AT1bAngII.txt');
model.result.export('plot2').run;
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').set('window', 'graphics');
```

```
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg10').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot2').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\block_AT2bAngII.txt');
model.result.export('plot2').run;
model.result('pg11').run;
model.result.export.create('plot3', 'pg11', 'tblp1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg11').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg11').run;
model.result('pg11').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg11').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot3').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\block_block.txt');
model.result.export('plot3').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot3').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\block_volume.txt');
model.result.export('plot3').run;

model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tunit', 'd');
model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tlist', 'range(0,0.1,20)');

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;

model.label('RAS model_ block AT1irbesartan_20d.mph');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.geom('geom1').feature.clear;

model.mesh('mesh1').feature.clear;

model.geom('geom1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').create('impl', 'Import');
model.mesh('mesh1').feature('impl').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01.
UCY\Downloads\one_lung.mphtxt');
model.mesh('mesh1').feature('impl').set('facepartition', 'minimal');
model.mesh('mesh1').feature('impl').importData;
model.mesh('mesh1').feature('impl').importData;
model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('growth').selection.all;
model.physics('growth').selection.set([2]);

model.variable('var3').selection.set([1]);
model.variable('var4').selection.all;
model.variable('var4').selection.set([2]);
```

```
model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;

model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tunit', 'min');
model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tlist', 'range(0,0.1,12)');

model.result('pg2').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', {'3'});
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('solid').feature('roll1').selection.set([1]);
model.physics('solid').feature('roll1').selection.all;
model.physics('solid').feature('roll1').selection.set([1]);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;

model.view('view1').set('showgrid', false);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sbulk');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result.table('tbl1').clearTableData;
model.result.table('tbl1').clearTableData;
model.result.numerical('int1').selection.all;
model.result.numerical('int1').selection.set([2]);
model.result.numerical('int1').set('table', 'tbl1');
model.result.numerical('int1').setResult;
model.result('pg11').run;
model.result.numerical('int1').setIndex('unit', 'm^3', 0);
model.result.numerical('int1').set('table', 'tbl1');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result.create('pg12', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg12').run;
model.result('pg12').create('vol1', 'Volume');
model.result('pg12').run;
model.result('pg12').feature('vol1').set('expr', 'sbulk');
model.result('pg12').run;

model.view('view1').set('scenelight', 'on');
model.view('view1').set('transparency', 'on');
```

```
model.view('view1').set('scenelight', 'on');
model.view('view1').set('transparency', 'off');

model.result('pg12').set('allowtableupdate', false);
model.result('pg12').set('allowevalintitle', false);
model.result('pg12').set('title', 'Time=12 min Volume: (N/m<sup>2</sup>)');
model.result('pg12').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg12').feature('vol1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg12').set('renderdatacached', false);
model.result('pg12').set('allowtableupdate', true);
model.result('pg12').set('renderdatacached', true);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;
model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('b', '0');

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdf', '0.1');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('initialstepbdf', '0.1');

model.result.table('tbl1').clearTableData;

model.label('RAS model_ control_realgeo.mph');

model.mesh('mesh1').feature.remove('impl');
model.mesh('mesh1').create('impl', 'Import');
model.mesh('mesh1').feature('impl').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01.↙
UCY\Desktop\one_lung_m.mphtxt');
model.mesh('mesh1').feature('impl').importData;
model.mesh('mesh1').feature('impl').set('facepartition', 'minimal');
model.mesh('mesh1').feature('impl').importData;
model.mesh('mesh1').run;
model.mesh('mesh1').run;
model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('growth').selection.all;
model.physics('growth').selection.set([2]);
model.physics('solid').feature('roll1').selection.set([1]);

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;

model.variable('var3').selection.set([1]);
model.variable('var4').selection.all;
model.variable('var4').selection.set([2]);

model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.view('view1').set('showgrid', true);

model.result.dataset('cpt1').set('pointx', '0.075');
model.result.dataset('cpt1').set('pointy', '0.08');
model.result.dataset('cpt1').set('pointz', '-1.265');
model.result.dataset('cpt1').run;
model.result('pg11').run;
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg10').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg10').run;

model.label('RAS model_ control_realgeo_new.mph');

model.result('pg10').run;

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;

model.physics.create('dode', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u10'});
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode', true);

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics.create('ge', 'GlobalEquations', 'geom1');

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('ge', true);

model.physics.remove('ge');
model.physics.create('dode2', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u11'});
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode2', true);

model.physics.create('dode3', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u12'});
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode3', true);

model.physics.create('dode4', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u13'});
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode4', true);

model.physics.create('dode5', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u14'});
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode5', true);

model.physics.create('dode6', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u15'});
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode6', true);

model.physics('dode').tag('Cb');
model.physics('Cb').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'Cb');
```

```
model.physics('Cb').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode2').tag('H');
model.physics('H').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'H');
model.physics('H').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode3').tag('m');
model.physics('m').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'm');
model.physics('m').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode4').tag('p');
model.physics('p').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'p');
model.physics('p').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode5').tag('s');
model.physics('s').field('dimensionless').component(1, 's');
model.physics('s').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode6').tag('In');
model.physics('In').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'In');
model.physics('In').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics.create('cdeq', 'ConvectionDiffusionEquation', 'geom1');

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('cdeq', true);

model.physics('cdeq').tag('Ci');
model.physics('Ci').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('Ci').field('dimensionless').field('Ci');
model.physics('Cb').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('Cb').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol');
model.physics('Cb').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/s');
model.physics('Cb').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ p*Cb)/ $\phi$ -Koff*Cb- $\leftarrow$ 
Kd*Cb-Kint*Cb', 0);
model.physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'rH-((Kb*H*Ci)/(Sv+Ci))', 0);
model.physics('m').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kr*Cb-Kb*m', 0);
model.physics('p').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kp*m-Ka*p', 0);
model.physics('s').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'ss*m/(m+Km)-ds*s', 0);
model.physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci/(Sv+Ci)-Di*In*s/(In+Ki)', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dci' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci' '0' '0' '0' $\leftarrow$ 
'Dci'}, 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ p*Cb)/ $\phi$ ', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('Dci', '5e-10[cm^2/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kon', '5e3[1/M/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('Chs', '1.74e-5[M]');
model.variable('var1').set('alp', '1e3');
model.variable('var1').set('phi', '0.05');
model.variable('var1').set('Koff', '8e-3[1/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kd', '4.8e-5[1/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kint', '5.78e-4[1/s]');

model.physics('Ci').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('Ci').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M');
model.physics('Ci').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'M/s');
model.physics('Cb').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M');
model.physics('Cb').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'M/s');
```

```
model.variable('var1').set('r', '0.927[1/d]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kb', '0.038[1/d]');
model.variable('var1').set('Sv', '1[1]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kr', 'Ka');
model.variable('var1').set('Kp', 'Ka');
model.variable('var1').set('Ka', '1.36e5[1/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('ss', '1[1/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('ds', '0.133[1/d]');
model.variable('var1').set('di', '1.8[1/d]');
model.variable('var1').set('Ki', '40[1]');

model.physics('H').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');

model.variable('var1').rename('r', 'rH');
model.variable('var1').set('Sv', '1[M]');

model.physics('m').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');

model.variable('var1').set('Kr', '1.36e5[1/M/s]');

model.physics('p').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('s').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');

model.variable('var1').set('Km', '40[1]');

model.physics('In').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'M/s');
model.physics('In').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('In').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M');

model.variable('var1').rename('di', 'Di');

model.physics('In').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.physics('In').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('H').feature('init1').set('H', '1');
model.physics('Cb').feature('init1').set('Cb', '0');
model.physics('Ci').feature('init1').set('Ci', '100*(z>-1.2[m])');

model.variable('var1').rename('phi', 'ph');

model.physics('Cb').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ p*Cb)/ph-Koff*Cb-Kd*Cb-Kint*Cb', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ p*Cb)/ph', 0);
model.physics('s').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'S');
model.physics('s').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'ss*m/(m+Km)-ds*S', 0);
model.physics('In').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci/(Sv+Ci)-Di*In*S/(In+Ki)', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', {'11'});
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', {'1'});
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', {'11'});
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'm');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'p');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'S');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('Ci').feature('init1').set('Ci', '10*(z>-1.2[m])');
model.physics('Cb').feature('init1').set('Cb', '1');
model.physics('Ci').feature('init1').set('Ci', '10*(z>-1.2[m])+1');
model.physics('Cb').feature('init1').set('Cb', '0');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', {'109'});
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tunit', 'h');

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('initialstepbdf', '0.001');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdf', '0.01');
```

```
model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'lg');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('growth').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '0.1[ml/fmol/h]*AT1bAngII', 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', {'5'});
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', {'4'});
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('growth').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '0.1[ml/fmol/d]*AT1bAngII', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg10').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'mol/m^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tunit', 'd');

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;

model.result.table('tbl1').clearTableData;
model.result.numerical('int1').set('table', 'tbl1');
model.result.numerical('int1').setResult;

model.physics('growth').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '0.01[ml/fmol/d]*AT1bAngII', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'lg');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result.table('tbl1').clearTableData;
model.result.numerical('int1').selection.all;
model.result.numerical('int1').selection.set([2]);
model.result.numerical('int1').set('table', 'tbl1');
model.result.numerical('int1').setResult;
model.result('pg11').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;
model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dci*1000' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci*1000' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci*1000'}, 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('AngII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(cACE+cChym)*AngI-(cACE2*(vi)-cAngIIAngIV-cAT1-cAT2)*AngII-(log(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);

model.variable('var4').set('vi', '((H-In)/H)*(H>In)+0*(H<In)');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('vi', '((H-In)/H)*(H>In)+0*(H<In)');
model.variable('var4').remove('vi');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result.numerical('int1').set('table', 'tbl1');
model.result.numerical('int1').appendResult;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg11').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'p');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'm');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'S');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;
model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('Dci', '5e-10[m^2/s]');

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '51', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '46', 0);
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowevalintitle', false);
model.result('pg1').set('title', 'Time=0.2 d Slice: Dependent variable Cb
(mol/m<sup>3</sup>');
model.result('pg1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeunit', 'mol/m^3');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormin', 1.739924640963283E-5);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormax', 1.740095075898345E-5);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecoloractive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamin', 1.739924640963283E-5);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamax', 1.740095075898345E-5);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedataactive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeactualminmax', [1.739924640963283E-5
1.740095075898345E-5]);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', true);
model.result.table('evl3').addRow([0.07635006713867096 0.11235861059456634
-1.3230521197302894 1.7400126003816982E-5], [0 0 0 0]);

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('growth').active(false);
model.physics('solid').active(false);

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdfactive', 'off');
model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '11', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dci*10' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci*10' '0' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci*10'}, 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'rH');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ *Cb)/ph-Kb', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ *Cb)/ph-Kb*H*Ci/↙
(SH+H)', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ *Cb)/ph-Kb*H*Ci/↙
(sH+H)', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ *Cb)/ph-Kb*H*Ci/↙
(sH+H)-dv*Ci*S/(Kv+Ci)', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('SH', '1[M]');
model.variable('var1').rename('SH', 'sH');
model.variable('var1').set('sH', 'Ki');

model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ *Cb)/ph-Kb*H*Ci/↙
(sH+H)', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ *Cb)/ph-Kb*H*Ci/↙
(sH+H)-dv*Ci*S/(Kv+Ci)', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('dV', 'Di');
model.variable('var1').rename('dV', 'dv');
model.variable('var1').set('Kv', 'Sv');
model.variable('var1').set('dv', 'Di*1[M]');

model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ *Cb)/ph+Koff*Cb-↙
Kd*Ci', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ *Cb)/ph+Koff*Cb-↙
Kd*Ci+Ka*P', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ *Cb)/ph+Koff*Cb-↙
Kd*Ci+Ka*p', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ *Cb)/ph+Koff*Cb-↙
Kd*Ci+Ka*p*1[M]', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ *Cb)/ph+Koff*Cb-↙
Kd*Ci+Ka*p*1[M]-dv*Ci*S', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('dv', 'Di');

model.physics('AngII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(cACE+cChym)*AngI-(cACE2-↙
cAngIIAngIV-cAT1-cAT2)*AngII-(log(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('cACE2', '2.4[1/h]*vi');

model.physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'kH-((Kb*H*Ci)/(Sv+Ci))', 0);
model.physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'kH*H-((Kb*H*Ci)/(Sv+Ci))', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('kH', '1[1/s]');

model.physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'kH*H-((Kb*H*Ci))', 0);
model.physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'kH*H-(Kb*H*Ci)', 0);

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;
```

```
model.label('RAS model_add virus_day_intragro_diffusion meter_disebe solid_new eq.mph');

model.physics('H').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('H').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1/mm^3');
model.physics('H').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/mm^3/s');
model.physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'kH*H-(Kb*H*Ci)-phil*H*n', 0);
model.physics('In').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1/mm^3');
model.physics('In').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/mm^3/s');
model.physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci-Di*In*S/(In+Ki)', 0);
model.physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phil*H*n', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ p*Cb)/ph+Koff*Cb-  
Kd*Ci+Ka*p-dv*Ci*S', 0);
model.physics('m').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('m').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M');
model.physics('m').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'M/s');
model.physics('p').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('p').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M');
model.physics('p').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'M/s');
model.physics('m').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kr*Cb-Kp*m', 0);
model.physics('s').active(false);
model.physics.create('dode', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u16'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode', true);

model.physics('dode').tag('n');
model.physics('n').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'n');
model.physics('n').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('n').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1/mm^3');
model.physics('n').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/mm^3/s');
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c-gan*n', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c-gam_n*n', 0);
model.physics.create('dode', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u17'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode', true);

model.physics('dode').tag('ma');
model.physics('ma').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'ma');
model.physics('ma').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('ma').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1/mm^3');
model.physics('ma').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/mm^3/s');
model.physics('ma').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xm*c-gam_m*ma', 0);
model.physics.create('dode', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u18'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode', true);

model.physics('dode').tag('c');
model.physics('c').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'c');
model.physics('c').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('c').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'pg/mm^3');
model.physics('c').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'pg/mm^3/s');
```

```
model.physics('c').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Sc*ma+SAT1R*AT1bAngII', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Sc*ma+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*n-ds*c', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('kH', '0.00275[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kb', '1*Kon');
model.variable('var1').set('phi1', '1e-6[mm^3/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('dv', '1e-6[mm^3/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kr', '1*gam_c');
model.variable('var1').set('Kp', '1*gam_c');
model.variable('var1').set('xn', '1[1/s/pg]');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_n', '1*gam_c');
model.variable('var1').set('xm', '1[1/s/pg]');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_m', '0.01*gam_c');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_c', '3[1/d]');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_m', '0.01*gam_c');
model.variable('var1').set('Sc', '1*Sgen');
model.variable('var1').set('SAT1R', '1*Sgen');
model.variable('var1').set('Sn', '1*Sgen');
model.variable('var1').set('ds', '1*gam_c');
model.variable('var1').set('Sgen', '1[pg/mol/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('SAT1R', '1[pg/mole/s]');

model.physics('c').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Sc*ma', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Sc*ma+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*n-ds*c', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('Sgen', '1[pg/s]');

model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ p*Cb)/ph+Koff*Cb-  
Kd*Ci+Ka*p-dv*Ci*n', 0);

model.label('RAS model_add virus_day_intragro_diffusion_meter_disebe_solid_new_eq_1.  
mph');

model.physics('n').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('ma').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('c').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');

model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('initialstepbdf', '0.01');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdfactive', 'on');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdf', '0.5');
model.sol('sol1').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '11', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '31', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'm');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('H').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'kH*10*H-(Kb*H*Ci)-phi1*H*n', 0);
model.physics('H').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'kH*10*H-(Kb*H*Ci)-phi1*H*n/10', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ p*Cb)/ph+Koff*10*Cb- $\leftarrow$ 
Kd*Ci+Ka*10*p-dv*Ci*n', 0);
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AgnI');

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'kH*10*H-(Kb*H*Ci)-phi1*H*n*0', 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('In').feature('init1').set('In', '0.01');

model.result('pg2').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;
```

```
model.physics('H').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'kH*10*H-(Kb*H*Ci)*0-phi1*H*n*0', 0);

model.sol('soll').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'p');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg11').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg9').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('Kon', '5e3[1/M/s]');

model.physics('Cb').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kon*Ci*(Chs- alp*Cb)/ph-Koff*Cb-  
Kd*Cb*0-Kint*Cb*0', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- alp*Cb)/ph+Koff*10*Cb-  
Kd*Ci+Ka*10*p-dv*Ci*n/10', 0);
model.physics('Cb').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kon*Ci*(Chs- alp*Cb)/ph-Koff*Cb-Kd*Cb-
```

```
Kint*Cb', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('Kd', '4.8e-5[1/s]/100');
model.variable('var1').set('Kint', '5.78e-4[1/s]/100');
model.variable('var1').set('dv', '1e-6[mm^3/s]/100');
model.variable('var1').set('SAT1R', '1[pg/mole/s]*100');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('gam_c', '3[1/d]/100');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'p');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'm');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.label('RAS model_add virus_day_intragro_diffusion meter_disebe solid_new eq_2.↙
mph');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
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```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'm');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'p');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'kH*10*H-(Kb*H*Ci)-phi1*H*n*0', 0);
model.physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phi1*H*n*0', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- alp*Cb)/ph+Koff*Cb-
Kd*Ci+Ka*10*p-dv*Ci*n', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- alp*Cb)/ph+Koff*Cb-
Kd*Ci+Ka*p-dv*Ci*n*0', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('Kd', '4.8e-5[1/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kint', '5.78e-4[1/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('dv', '1e-6[mm^3/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_c', '3[1/d]');
model.variable('var1').set('SAT1R', '1[pg/mole/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kr', 'Kint');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;

model.label('RAS model_add virus_day_intragro_diffusion meter_disebe solid_new eq_6 -
Copy.mph');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.param.set('a', '1[cfu]');

model.physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'RH*H-(Kb*H*Ci)-phic*H*n', 0);
model.physics('H').feature('init1').set('H', '7.23e8[1/ml]');
model.physics('m').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'Cint');
model.physics('m').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint', 0);
model.physics('p').active(false);
model.physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n', 0);
model.physics('In').feature('init1').set('In', '0');
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- alp*Cb)/ph+Koff*Cb-
Kd*Ci+Ka*Vint', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature.duplicate('init2', 'init1');
model.physics('Ci').feature('init2').set('Ci', '1.27e-9[M]*(z>-1.2[m])');
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma-gam_v*n*V',
0);
model.physics('ma').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xm*c-gam_n1*ma', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*n-ds*c',
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gam_m*n*ma-gam_v*n*V', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*1000[1/ml]*c-gam_n*1[mm^3/pg]*n',
0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*1000[1/ml]*c-gam_n*1[mm^3/pg]*n-
gam_m*n*ma-gam_v*n*V', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*1000[1/ml]*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*1
[mm^3/pg]*n*ma-gam_v*n*V', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*1000[1/ml]*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*1
[mm^3/pg]*n*ma', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*1000[1/ml]*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*1
[mm^3/pg]*n*ma-gam_v*n*V', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*1000[1/ml]*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*1
[mm^3/pg]*n*ma-gam_v*1[mole]*n*V', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*1000[1/ml]*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*1
[mm^3/pg]*n*ma-gam_v*1[mole]*n*Ci', 0);

model.param.set('a', '1[M]');

model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*1000[1/ml]*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*1
[mm^3/pg]*n*ma-gam_v*1[mol]*n*Ci', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('gam_v', '2.5e-7[ml/h/mol]');

model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*1000[1/ml]*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*1
[mm^3/pg]*n*ma-gam_v*n*Ci', 0);
model.physics('ma').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xm*1000[1/ml]*c-gam_n1*ma', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]
+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*n-ds*c', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]+SAT1R*AT1bAngII/1.
27e-9[M]+Sn*n-ds*c', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('SAT1R', '2.1e-2[pg/ml/h]');

model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]+SAT1R*AT1bAngII/1.
27e-9[M]', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]+SAT1R*AT1bAngII/1.
27e-9[M]+Sn*n', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]+SAT1R*AT1bAngII/1.
27e-9[M]+Sn*n*1[ml]', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]+SAT1R*AT1bAngII/1.
27e-9[M]+Sn*n*1[ml]-ds*c', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]+SAT1R*AT1bAngII/1.
27e-9[M]+Sn*n*1[ml]-dsc', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]+SAT1R*AT1bAngII/1.
27e-9[M]+Sn*n*1[ml]-dc*c', 0);

model.label('RAS model_add virus_day_intragro_diffusion_meter_disebe_solid_new_eq_new
parameter.mph');

model.sol('sol1').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;

model.sol('soll').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result('pg9').run;

model.param.set('b', '1000[1/d]');
```

```
model.param.set('c', '0.00275[1/d]');
model.param.remove('c');
model.param.remove('a');
model.param.remove('b');

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('RH', '1000[1/d]');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_v', '2.5e-7[ml/h/fmol]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'M');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'mol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'mole/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'M');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'mol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'mol/m^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'mol/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'mol/cm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'mol/m^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'mol/l');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs-alp*Cb)/ph+Koff*Cb-
Kd*Ci+Ka*Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs-alp*Cb)/ph');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs-alp*Cb)/ph+Koff*Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('vt', '1*(Ci>Cb)+0');

model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs-alp*Cb)*vt/ph+Koff*Cb-
Kd*Ci+Ka*Vint', 0);
model.physics('Cb').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kon*Ci*(Chs-alp*Cb)*vt/ph-Koff*Cb-
Kd*Cb-Kint*Cb', 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tunit', 'min');

model.physics('ma').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xm*1[1/ml]*c-gam_n1*ma', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*1[1/ml]*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*1[mm^3/pg]
*n*ma-gam_v*n*Ci', 0);
model.physics('AGT').active(false);
model.physics('AngI').active(false);
model.physics('AngII').active(false);
model.physics('Ang17').active(false);
model.physics('AngIV').active(false);
model.physics('AT1bAngII').active(false);
model.physics('AT2bAngII').active(false);

model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tunit', 'd');

model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]
+SAT1R*AT1bAngII*0/1.27e-9[M]+Sn*n*1[ml]-dc*c', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]+Sn*n*1[ml]-dc*c',
0);

model.sol('sol1').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('H').active(false);
```

```
model.physics('n').active(false);
model.physics('ma').active(false);
model.physics('c').active(false);
model.physics('In').active(false);

model.sol('sol1').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ p*Cb)/ph+Koff*Cb- $\leftarrow$ 
Kd*Ci+Ka*Vint', 0);
model.physics('Cb').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ p*Cb)/ph-Koff*Cb-Kd*Cb- $\leftarrow$ 
Kint*Cb', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('Ka', 'Kint/100');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('In').active(true);
model.physics('H').active(true);
model.physics('H').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'RH*H-(Kb*H*Ci)', 0);
model.physics('In').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci', 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', {'1'});
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dci*100' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci*100' '0'
'0' '0' 'Dci*100'}, 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', {'2'});
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', {'4'});
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('Kb', '1.36e5[1/M/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('RH', '0.002751[1/h]');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('n').active(true);
model.physics('ma').active(true);
model.physics('c').active(true);
model.physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'RH*H-(Kb*H*Ci)-phic', 0);
model.physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'RH*H-(Kb*H*Ci)-phic*H*n', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('phic', '1[mm^3/s]');

model.physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n', 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('phic', '0[mm^3/s]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', {'51'});
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', {'61'});
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]+Sn*n*1[ml]-dc*c');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', {'51'});
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', {'61'});
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]+Sn*n*1[ml]-dc*c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sc*Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sc*Vint1.27e-9[M]');
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowevalintitle', false);
model.result('pg1').set('title', 'Time=6 d Slice: Sc*Vint1.27e-9[M]');
model.result('pg1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', true);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-10[M]');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-10[M]');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-13[M]');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]+Sn*n*1[ml]-dc*c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]+Sn*n*1e4[ml]-dc*c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-9[M]+Sn*n*1e8[ml]-dc*c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-12[M]+Sn*n*1e8[ml]-dc*c');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('dc', '8.3e-1[1/h]');

model.param.set('a', '3[1/d]');
model.param.set('b', '8.3e-1[1/h]');
model.param.remove('a');
model.param.remove('b');

model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-12[M]+Sn*n*1[ml]-dc*c', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-12[M]+Sn*n*100[ml]-dc*c', 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'xm*1[1/ml]*c-gam_n1*ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'xm*100[1/ml]*c-gam_n1*ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'xm*1e10[1/ml]*c-gam_n1*ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'xm*1[1/ml]*c-gam_n1*ma');

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('gam_n1', 'gam_n');

model.physics('ma').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xm*100[1/ml]*c-gam_n1*ma', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*100[1/ml]*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*1e-5[mm^3/pg]*n*ma-gam_v*n*Ci', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('gam_v', '2.5e-7[ml/h/mol]');

model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-12[M]+Sn*n*1[ml]-dc*c', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-11[M]+Sn*n*1[ml]-dc*c', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*100[1/ml]*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*1[mm^3/g]*n*ma-gam_v*n*Ci', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dci' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci'}, 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', {'14'});
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-11[M]+Sn*n*1[ml]*0- $\leftarrow$ 
dc*c*0', 0);
model.physics('ma').active(false);
model.physics('n').active(false);
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-11[M]+Sn*0*1[ml]*0- $\leftarrow$ 
dc*c*0', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-11[M]', 0);
model.physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci', 0);
model.physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'RH*H-(Kb*H*Ci)', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-11[M]-dc*c', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('AGT').active(true);
model.physics('AngI').active(true);
model.physics('AngII').active(true);
```

```
model.physics('Ang17').active(true);
model.physics('AngIV').active(true);
model.physics('AT1bAngII').active(true);
model.physics('AT2bAngII').active(true);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'kpg/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('c').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-11[M]-dc*c+SAT1', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-11[M]-dc*c+SAT1R*AT1bAngII', 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('SAT1R', '2.1e2[pg*ml/mm^3/h/fmol]');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowevalintitle', false);
model.result('pg1').set('title', 'Time=12 d Slice: Dependent variable In
(1/m<sup>3</sup>');
model.result('pg1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeunit', '1/m^3');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormin', -4.643523359614433E9);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormax', 7.464577783893565E12);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecoloractive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamin', -4.643523359614433E9);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamax', 7.464577783893565E12);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedataactive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeactualminmax', [-4.643523359614433E9
7.464577783893565E12]);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', true);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('SAT1R', '2.1[pg*ml/mm^3/h/fmol]');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('ma').active(true);

model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;
```

```
model.variable('var1').set('xn', '1e2[1/pg/h]');

model.physics('ma').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xm*c-gam_n1*ma', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('xn', '2.1[1/pg/h]');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('xn', '2.1e-2[1/pg/h]');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*1[mm^3/g]*n*ma-  
gam_v*n*Ci', 0);
model.physics('n').active(true);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma-gam_v*n*Ci',  
0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma', 0);
```

```
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma-gam_v*n*Ci', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('gam_n', '6.3e-4[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_m', '2.1e-6[1/mm^3/h]');

model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c-gam_n*n', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma-gam_v*n*Ci', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('gam_m', '2.1e-6[mm^3/h]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'M');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('gam_v', '2.5e-12[ml/h/fmol]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci*gam_v');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/h');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('gam_v', '2.5e-4[ml/h/fmol]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci*gam_v');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/h');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci*2.5e-4[ml/h/fmol]');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci*2.5e-2[ml/h/fmol]');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('gam_v', '2.5e-2[ml/h/fmol]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'gam_m*ma');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '2.1e-6[mm^3/h]*ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '2.1e-3[mm^3/h]*ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '2.1e-1[mm^3/h]*ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '2.1e2[mm^3/h]*ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '2.1e-1[mm^3/h]*ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('gam_m', '2.1e-2[mm^3/h]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'xn*c');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-11[M]-dc*c+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*n', 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '2.1e-2[pg/ml/h]*n');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '2.1e-2[pg/h]*n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/(mm^3*s)');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('Sn', '2.1e-2[pg/h]');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'phic');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('phic', '1e-3[mm^3/s]');

model.physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'RH*H-(Kb*H*Ci)-phic*H', 0);
model.physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'RH*H-(Kb*H*Ci)-phic*H8n', 0);
model.physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'RH*H-(Kb*H*Ci)-phic*H*n', 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'phic*H*n');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '1e-3[mm^3/s]*H*n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '1e-3[mm^3/h]*H*n');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/(mm^3*s)');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '2.3e-4[mm^3/h]*H*n');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('phic', '2.3e-4[mm^3/h]');

model.physics('In').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+-phic*H*n', 0);
model.physics('In').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H-In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '(H-In)/H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics.create('ge', 'GlobalEquations', 'geom1');

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('ge', true);
```

```
model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics.remove('ge');
model.physics.create('dode', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u19'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode', true);

model.physics.create('dode2', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u20'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode2', true);

model.physics('dode').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'Ctl');
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/mm^3');
model.physics('dode').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode').tag('Ctl');
model.physics('Ctl').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pv*In*(t>5[d])', 0);
model.physics('Ctl').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pv*In*(t>5[d])-d', 0);
model.physics('Ctl').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pv*In*(t>5[d])-dcl*Ctl', 0);
model.physics('dode2').active(false);

model.variable('var1').set('pv', '0.05[1/h]');

model.physics('Ctl').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pv*In*(t>5[d])', 0);
model.physics('Ctl').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pv*In', 0);
model.physics('Ctl').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/mm^3/s');
model.physics('Ctl').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('Ctl').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1/mm^3');
model.physics('Ctl').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pv*In*(t>5[d])-dcl*Ctl', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('dcl', '5.54e-3[1/h]');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n-phictl*In*Ctl', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('phictl', '1[mm^3/s]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '1[mm^3/s]*Ctl*In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/(mm^3*s)');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '1[mm^3/h]*Ctl*In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '2.1e-3[mm^3/h]*Ctl*In');

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('phict1', '2.1e-3[mm^3/h]');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('phict1', '2.1e-5[mm^3/h]');

model.physics('dode2').tag('a');
model.physics('a').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'a');
model.physics('a').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('a').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'pg/mm^3');
model.physics('a').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'pg/mm^3/s');
model.physics('a').active(true);
model.physics('a').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kg*phi_a*ma*n+Sang17*Ang17-gam_a*a', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('Kg', 'Sn');
model.variable('var1').set('phi_a', '2.1e-2[1/h]');

model.physics('a').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kg*phi_a*ma*n', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('phi_a', '2.1e-2[mm^3]');

model.physics('a').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kg*phi_a*ma*n+Sang17*Ang17-gam_a*a', 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sn*phi_a*ma*n');

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sn*2.1e-2[mm^3]*ma*n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/(mm^3*s)');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sn*1[mm^3]*ma*n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sn*2.1e5[mm^3]*ma*n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sn*2.1e3[mm^3]*ma*n');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('phi_a', '2.1e3[mm^3]');
model.variable('var1').set('SAng17', '2.1[pg*ml/mm^3/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').rename('SAng17', 'Sang17');

model.physics('a').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kg*phi_a*ma*n+Sang17*Ang17', 0);
model.physics('a').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kg*phi_a*ma*n+Sang17*Ang17-gam_a*a', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('gam_a', '8.3e-1[1/h]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-11[M]');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('phi_a', '2.1e-3[mm^3]');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a/57.85[pg/mm^3]');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '1+a/57.85[pg/mm^3]');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '11', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '(1+a/57.85[pg/mm^3])');

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('xn', '2.1e-2[1/pg/h]/(1+a/57.85[pg/mm^3])');
model.variable('var1').set('xm', '2.1e-2[1/pg/h]');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '106', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('a').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;

model.label('Full run_clear.mph');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('AGT').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'kAGT-Crenin*AGT-(log(2)/hAGT)*AGT', 0);
model.physics('AGT').feature('init1').set('AGT', '1.7e7[nmol/l]');
model.physics.create('dode', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u21'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode', true);
```

```
model.physics.move('dode', 2);
model.physics('dode').tag('Renin');
model.physics('Renin').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('Renin').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'Renin');
model.physics('Renin').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('Renin').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('Renin').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('Renin').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Srenin+Kf*(AngII0-AngII)*(1-
((AngII0-AngII)/f))-(Log(2)/hrenin)*Renin', 0);
model.physics('Renin').feature('init1').set('Renin', '2.06e-4[nmol/L]');
model.physics('AngI').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cRenin*AGT+Krenin*(Renin-Renin0)--
(cACE+cChym+cNEP)*AngI-(log(2)/hAngI)*AngI+0*23.1[fmol/ml/h]', 0);
model.physics('AGT').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'kAGT-cRenin*AGT-(log(2)/hAGT)*AGT',
0);
model.physics('AngI').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cRenin*AGT+Krenin*(Renin-Renin0)-
cACE*AngI-(cNEP+cACE2)*AngI-(log(2)/hAngI)*AngI', 0);
model.physics('AngI').feature('init1').set('AngI', '271[nmol/L]');
model.physics('AngII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(cACE)*AngI-(cACE2-cAngIIAngIV-
cAT1-cAT2)*AngII-(log(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);
model.physics('AngI').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KRenin*AGT+Krenin*(Renin-Renin0)-
cACE*AngI-(cNEP+cACE2)*AngI-(log(2)/hAngI)*AngI', 0);
model.physics('AngI').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cRenin*AGT+Krenin*(Renin-Renin0)-
cACE*AngI-(KNEP+KACE2)*AngI-(log(2)/hAngI)*AngI', 0);
model.physics('AngII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(cACE)*AngI-(cAT1+KAT2+KAPA+KACE2)
*AngII-(log(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);
model.physics('AngII').feature('init1').set('AngII', '21[nmol/L]');
model.physics('Ang17').feature('init1').set('Ang17', '1.2e-7[mol/L]');
model.physics.create('dode', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u22'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode', true);

model.physics.move('dode', 6);
model.physics('dode').tag('Ang19');
model.physics('Ang19').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('Ang19').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('Ang19').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('Ang19').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('Ang19').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cACE2*AngI-(log(2)/hAng19)*Ang19',
0);
model.physics('Ang19').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'Ang19');
model.physics.create('dode', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u23'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode', true);

model.physics.move('dode', 7);
model.physics('dode').tag('AngIII');
model.physics('AngIII').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('AngIII').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('AngIII').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('AngIII').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('AngIII').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'u23');
```

```
model.physics('AngIII').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'ANGIII');
model.physics('AngIII').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'AngIII');
model.physics('AngIII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cAPA*AngII-(log(2)/hAngIII)
*AngIII', 0);
model.physics('AngIII').feature('init1').set('AngIII', '1.3e-8[mol/L]');
model.physics('AngIV').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cAPM*AngIII-(log(2)/hAngIV)
*AngIV', 0);
model.physics('AngIV').feature('init1').set('AngIV', '0.7e-8[mol/L]');
model.physics('AT1bAngII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cAT1*AngII-(log(2)/hAT1)
*AT1bAngII', 0);
model.physics.create('dode', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u24'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode', true);

model.physics.move('dode', 11);
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('dode').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode').tag('AT4bAngIV');
model.physics('AT4bAngIV').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cAT4*AngIV-(log(20/hAT4)
*AT4bAngIV', 0);
model.physics('AT4bAngIV').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'AT4bAngIV');
model.physics('AT4bAngIV').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cAT4*AngIV-(log(2)/hAT4)
*AT4bAngIV', 0);
model.physics.create('dode', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u25'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode', true);

model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('dode').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'MASbAng17');
model.physics('dode').tag('MASbAng17');
model.physics('MASbAng17').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cMAS*Ang17-(log(2)/hMAS)
*MASbAng17', 0);
model.physics.move('MASbAng17', 12);
model.physics('AT1bAngII').feature('init1').set('AT1bAngII', '4.1e-8[mol/L]');
model.physics('AT2bAngII').feature('init1').set('AT2bAngII', '2.1e-8[mol/L]');
model.physics('AT4bAngIV').feature('init1').set('AT4bAngIV', '1.05e-8[mol/L]');
model.physics('MASbAng17').feature('init1').set('MASbAng17', '4.1e-8[mol/L]');

model.variable('var1').set('hAngI', '1.72e-4[h]');
model.variable('var1').set('hAngII', '5e-3[h]');
model.variable('var1').set('kAGT', '2.27e6[nmol/L/h]');

model.param.set('as', '11.8[1/h]');

model.variable('var1').set('KRenin', '6.44e4[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KNEP', '0.583[1/h]');
```

```
model.variable('var1').set('KACE2', '0.382[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAT2', '25.1[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAPA', '43.6[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('hRenin', '0.25[h]');
model.variable('var1').set('hANGIII', '30[s]');
model.variable('var1').rename('hANGIII', 'hAngIII');
model.variable('var1').set('hAng19', '24[min]');
model.variable('var1').set('cAPA', '1.2e-2[1/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('cRenin', '1.8e-14[1/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('cAPM', 'cAPA');
model.variable('var1').set('hAT1', '1.5[min]');
model.variable('var1').set('hAT2', '1.5[min]');
model.variable('var1').set('hAT4', 'hAT1');
model.variable('var1').set('hMAs', 'hAT1');
model.variable('var1').set('cAT4', 'cAT2/3');
model.variable('var1').set('cMAs', 'cAT4/2');
model.variable('var1').set('sRenin', '(log(2)/hRenin)/Renin0');
model.variable('var1').set('Renin0', '2.06e-4[nmol/L]');
model.variable('var1').set('AngII0', '21[nmol/L]');

model.physics('Renin').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'sRenin+Kf*(AngII0-AngII)*(1-
((AngII0-AngII)/f))- (Log(2)/hrenin)*Renin', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('Kf', 'Kfsys*AngII0sysNRF/AngII0');
model.variable('var1').set('f', 'fsys*AngII0/AngII0sysNRF');
model.variable('var1').set('Kfsys', '6.25e-2[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('fsys', '0.397[nmol/L]');
model.variable('var1').set('AngII0sysNRF', '1.65e-2[nmol/L]');

model.physics('Ang19').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cACE2*AngI-(log(2)/hAng19)*Ang19',
0);
model.physics('Renin').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'sRenin', 0);
model.physics('Renin').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'sRenin+Kf*(AngII0-AngII)*(1-
((AngII0-AngII)/f))- (Log(2)/hrenin)*Renin', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('sRenin', '(log(2)/hRenin)*Renin0');

model.physics('Renin').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'sRenin', 0);
model.physics('Renin').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'sRenin+Kf*(AngII0-AngII)*(1-
((AngII0-AngII)/f))', 0);
model.physics('Renin').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'sRenin+Kf*(AngII0-AngII)*(1-
((AngII0-AngII)/f))- (Log(2)/hrenin)*Renin', 0);
model.physics('Renin').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'sRenin+Kf*(AngII0-AngII)*(1-
((AngII0-AngII)/f))- (Log(2)/hRenin)*Renin', 0);
model.physics('AngI').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'cRenin*AGT+KRenin*(Renin-Renin0)-
cACE*AngI-(KNEP+KACE2)*AngI-(log(2)/hAngI)*AngI', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('InACE1', '0');
model.variable('var1').set('InARBs', '0');
model.variable('var1').set('cACE', '54.1[1/h]*(1-InACE1)');
model.variable('var1').set('cAT1', '11.8[1/h]*(1-InARBs)');
```

```
model.label('Full run_clear.mph');

model.sol('sol1').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('Renin').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'sRenin+Kf*(AngII0-AngII)*(1-  
((AngII0-AngII)/f))-(log(2)/hRenin)*Renin', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg2').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang19');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ang19');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang19');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'l/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dci*1000' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci*1000' '0' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci*1000'}, 0);

model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').feature('fcl').set('dtech', 'auto');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('initialstepbdfactive', 'on');
model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('initialstepbdfactive', 'off');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsbAng17');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dci*1000000' '0' '0' '0' '0'
'Dci*1000000' '0' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci*1000000'}, 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'manual', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '1,2', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4,5', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4,5,6', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4,5,6,7', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4,5,6,7,8', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11', 0);
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result.create('pg13', 'PlotGroup1D');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').create('lngr1', 'LineGraph');
model.result.dataset.create('cln1', 'CutLine3D');
model.result.dataset('cln1').setIndex('genpoints', '0.075', 0, 0);
model.result.dataset('cln1').setIndex('genpoints', '0.075', 1, 0);
model.result.dataset('cln1').setIndex('genpoints', '0.1', 1, 1);
model.result.dataset('cln1').setIndex('genpoints', '0.1', 0, 1);
model.result.dataset('cln1').setIndex('genpoints', '-1.45', 0, 2);
model.result.dataset('cln1').setIndex('genpoints', '-1.1', 1, 2);
model.result.dataset('cln1').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('data', 'cln1');
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'manual', 0);
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 0);
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 0);
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,71', 0);
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,71,121', 0);
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,11,71,121', 0);
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('showlegends', true);
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('showlegends', 'on');
model.result('pg13').set('showlegendsmaxmin', 'off');
model.result('pg13').set('legendpos', 'middleright');
```

```
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').setIndex('looplevel', '1,2,11,71,121', 0);
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,11,71,121', 0);
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'AngIII');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('showlegends', true);
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('legend', 'on');
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg13').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;
model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33,34,35,36,37,38,39,40,41,42,43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50,51,52,53,54,55,56,57,58,59,60,61,62,63,64,65,66,67,68,69,70,71,72,73,74,75,76,77,78,79,80,81,82,83,84,85,86,87,88,89,90,91,92,93,94,95,96,97,98,99,100', 0);
```

```
63,64,65,66,67,68,69,70,71,72,73,74,75,76,77,78,79,80,81,82,83,84,85,86,87,88,89,90,91,92
,93,94,95,96,97,98,99,100,101,102,103,104,105,106,107,108,109,110,111,112,113,114,115,116
,117,118,119,120,121', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'vi');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 0);
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot4', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot4').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot4').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\AGT.txt');
model.result.export('plot4').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,121', 0);
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,21,121', 0);
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,21,41,121', 0);
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,21,41,61,121', 0);
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,21,41,61,81,121', 0);
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,21,41,61,81,101,121', 0);
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot5', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot5').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot5').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\AGT_full.txt');
model.result.export('plot5').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot6', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
```

```
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot6').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot6').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\Renin.txt');
model.result.export('plot6').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot7', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot7').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot7').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\AngI.txt');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot8', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot8').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot8').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\AngII.txt');
model.result.export('plot8').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot9', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot9').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot9').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\AngI.txt');
model.result.export('plot9').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'AngIII');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot10', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot10').set('header', 'off');
```

```
model.result.export('plot10').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of  
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\AngIII.txt');  
model.result.export('plot10').run;  
model.result('pg13').run;  
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'Ang17');  
model.result('pg13').run;  
model.result.export.create('plot11', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');  
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');  
model.result('pg13').run;  
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');  
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');  
model.result.export('plot11').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of  
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\Ang17.txt');  
model.result.export('plot11').set('header', 'off');  
model.result.export('plot11').run;  
model.result('pg13').run;  
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'Ang19');  
model.result('pg13').run;  
model.result.export.create('plot12', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');  
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');  
model.result('pg13').run;  
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');  
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');  
model.result.export('plot12').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of  
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\Ang19.txt');  
model.result.export('plot12').set('header', 'off');  
model.result.export('plot12').run;  
model.result('pg13').run;  
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'AngIV');  
model.result('pg13').run;  
model.result.export.create('plot13', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');  
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');  
model.result('pg13').run;  
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');  
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');  
model.result.export('plot13').set('header', 'off');  
model.result.export('plot13').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of  
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\AngIV.txt');  
model.result.export('plot13').run;  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg13').run;  
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');  
model.result('pg13').run;  
model.result.export.create('plot14', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');  
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');  
model.result('pg13').run;  
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');  
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');  
model.result.export('plot14').set('header', 'off');  
model.result.export('plot14').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of  
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\AT1bAngII.txt');
```

```
model.result.export('plot14').run;
model.result.export('plot14').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lng1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot15', 'pg13', 'lng1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot15').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot15').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\AT2bAngII.txt');
model.result.export('plot15').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lng1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot16', 'pg13', 'lng1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot16').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot16').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\AT4bAngIV.txt');
model.result.export('plot16').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lng1').set('expr', 'MASbAng17');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot17', 'pg13', 'lng1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot17').set('header', 'off');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot17').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot17').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\MASbAng17.txt');
model.result.export('plot17').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lng1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot18', 'pg13', 'lng1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
```

```
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot18').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot18').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\Ci.txt');
model.result.export('plot18').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot19', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot19').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot19').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\Cb.txt');
model.result.export('plot19').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot20', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot20').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot20').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\Vint.txt');
model.result.export('plot20').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot21', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot21').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot21').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\Healthy cell.txt');
model.result.export('plot21').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot22', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
```

```
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot22').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot22').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\Infected Cell.txt');
model.result.export('plot22').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot23', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot23').set('header', 'off');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot24', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot24').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot24').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\neutrophils.txt');
model.result.export('plot24').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot25', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot25').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot25').set('alwaysask', 'off');
model.result.export('plot25').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\macrophages.txt');
model.result.export('plot25').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot26', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot26').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot26').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\cytokines.txt');
```

```
model.result.export('plot26').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot27', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot27').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot27').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\T cells.txt');
model.result.export('plot27').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg13').feature('lngr1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result.export.create('plot28', 'pg13', 'lngr1', 'Plot');
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg13').set('window', 'graphics');
model.result('pg13').set('windowtitle', '');
model.result.export('plot28').set('header', 'off');
model.result.export('plot28').set('filename', 'C:\Users\cvouto01\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\Model\results Line\antiflamatori.txt');
model.result.export('plot28').run;
model.result.export('plot28').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4,5', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4,5,6', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4,5,6,7', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4,5,6,7,8', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12',
0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13',
0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel',
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel',
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel',
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel',
```

```
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32', ↙
0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33' ↙
, 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33, ↙
34', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33, ↙
34,35', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33, ↙
34,35,36', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33, ↙
34,35,36,37', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33, ↙
34,35,36,37,38', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↙
```



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34,35,36,37,38,39,40,41,42,43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50,51,52,53,54,55,56,57,58,59,60,61,62,63
,64,65,66,67,68,69,70,71,72,73,74,75,76,77,78,79,80,81,82,83,84,85,86,87,88,89,90,91,92,9
3,94,95,96,97,98,99,100,101,102,103,104,105,106,107,108,109,110,111,112,113,114,115', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel',
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33,
34,35,36,37,38,39,40,41,42,43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50,51,52,53,54,55,56,57,58,59,60,61,62,63
,64,65,66,67,68,69,70,71,72,73,74,75,76,77,78,79,80,81,82,83,84,85,86,87,88,89,90,91,92,9
3,94,95,96,97,98,99,100,101,102,103,104,105,106,107,108,109,110,111,112,113,114,115,116',
0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel',
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33,
34,35,36,37,38,39,40,41,42,43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50,51,52,53,54,55,56,57,58,59,60,61,62,63
,64,65,66,67,68,69,70,71,72,73,74,75,76,77,78,79,80,81,82,83,84,85,86,87,88,89,90,91,92,9
3,94,95,96,97,98,99,100,101,102,103,104,105,106,107,108,109,110,111,112,113,114,115,116,1
17', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel',
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33,
34,35,36,37,38,39,40,41,42,43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50,51,52,53,54,55,56,57,58,59,60,61,62,63
,64,65,66,67,68,69,70,71,72,73,74,75,76,77,78,79,80,81,82,83,84,85,86,87,88,89,90,91,92,9
3,94,95,96,97,98,99,100,101,102,103,104,105,106,107,108,109,110,111,112,113,114,115,116,1
17,118', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel',
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33,
34,35,36,37,38,39,40,41,42,43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50,51,52,53,54,55,56,57,58,59,60,61,62,63
,64,65,66,67,68,69,70,71,72,73,74,75,76,77,78,79,80,81,82,83,84,85,86,87,88,89,90,91,92,9
3,94,95,96,97,98,99,100,101,102,103,104,105,106,107,108,109,110,111,112,113,114,115,116,1
17,118,119', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel',
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33,
34,35,36,37,38,39,40,41,42,43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50,51,52,53,54,55,56,57,58,59,60,61,62,63
,64,65,66,67,68,69,70,71,72,73,74,75,76,77,78,79,80,81,82,83,84,85,86,87,88,89,90,91,92,9
3,94,95,96,97,98,99,100,101,102,103,104,105,106,107,108,109,110,111,112,113,114,115,116,1
17,118,119,120', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel',
'2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33,
34,35,36,37,38,39,40,41,42,43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50,51,52,53,54,55,56,57,58,59,60,61,62,63
,64,65,66,67,68,69,70,71,72,73,74,75,76,77,78,79,80,81,82,83,84,85,86,87,88,89,90,91,92,9
3,94,95,96,97,98,99,100,101,102,103,104,105,106,107,108,109,110,111,112,113,114,115,116,1
17,118,119,120,121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MASbAng17');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('InACE1', '0.98');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('InACE1', '0');
model.variable('var1').set('InARBs', '0.98');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/m');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('Kint', '5.78e-4[1/s]/2');
model.variable('var1').set('Ka', 'Kint/10');
model.variable('var1').set('InARBs', '0');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('Ci').feature('init2').set('Ci', '1.27e-8[M]*(z>-1.2[m])');
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dci*10000' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci*10000'
'0' '0' '0' 'Dci*10000'}, 0);

model.variable('var1').set('pv', '0.05[1/h]/2');
model.variable('var1').set('dcl', '5.54e-3[1/h]*2');
model.variable('var1').set('dc', '8.3e-1[1/h]*2');

model.physics('Ci').feature('init2').set('Ci', '1.27e-9[M]*(z>-1.2[m])');

model.variable('var1').set('pv', '0.05[1/h]');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dci*1000000' '0' '0' '0'
'Dci*1000000' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci*1000000'}, 0);

model.variable('var1').set('Kint', '5.78e-4[1/s]/3');
model.variable('var1').set('Ka', 'Kint');
model.variable('var1').set('Kint', '5.78e-4[1/s]/4');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('dc', '8.3e-1[1/h]*4');
model.variable('var1').set('dcl', '5.54e-3[1/h]*8');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/l');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1/1e6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('KAT2', '25.1[1/h]/4');
model.variable('var1').set('KAPA', '43.6[1/h]/4');
model.variable('var1').set('KACE2', '0.382[1/h]/4');
model.variable('var1').set('dc', '8.3e-1[1/h]*10');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').set('inherithide', 'off');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowevalintitle', false);
model.result('pg1').set('title', 'Time=12 d Slice: Dependent variable c (pg/ml)');
model.result('pg1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeunit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormin', 195.2891737157793);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormax', 195.2891740136277);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecoloractive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamin', 195.2891737157793);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamax', 195.2891740136277);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedataactive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeactualminmax', [195.2891737157793↵
195.2891740136277]);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', true);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '81', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowevalintitle', false);
model.result('pg1').set('title', 'Time=8 d Slice: Dependent variable AngII (fmol/ml)');
model.result('pg1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('actuallevels', [0.07635006713867086]);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeunit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormin', 1.8131619003189927);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormax', 1.8131619003189927);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecoloractive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamin', 1.8131619003189927);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamax', 1.8131619003189927);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedataactive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeactualminmax', [1.8131619003189927↵
1.8131619003189927]);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', true);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '81', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1.7*100');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1.5*100');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1.5*100*1046.2[g/mol]/1000');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1.5*100*1046.2[g/mol]');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/l');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1/1000000');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1046[g/mol]*1.5*100');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '81', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb*1e4');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci*1e4');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint*1e4');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/l');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H/1e6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In/1e6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a/1e6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a/100');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a/200');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/l');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('gam_a', '8.3e-1[1/h]/100');
model.variable('var1').set('Koff', '8e-3[1/s]*100');
model.variable('var1').set('Kint', '5.78e-4[1/s]/10');

model.physics('Ang17').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KNEP*AngI+cACE2*AngII-(log(2)
/hAng17)*Ang17', 0);
model.physics('Ang17').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KNEP*AngI+KACE2*AngII-cMAs-(log(2)
/hAng17)*Ang17', 0);
model.physics('Ang17').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KNEP*AngI+KACE2*AngII-cMAs*Anh17-
(log(2)/hAng17)*Ang17', 0);
model.physics('Ang17').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KNEP*AngI+KACE2*AngII-cMAs*Ang17-
(log(2)/hAng17)*Ang17', 0);
model.physics('Ang19').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KACE2*AngI-(log(2)/hAng19)*Ang19',
0);
model.physics('AngIII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KAPA*AngII-(log(2)/hAngIII)
*AngIII', 0);
model.physics('AngIII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KAPA*AngII-KAPM-(log(2)/hAngIII)
*AngIII', 0);
model.physics('AngIII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KAPA*AngII-kAPM-(log(2)/hAngIII)
*AngIII', 0);
model.physics('AngIII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KAPA*AngII-KAPM*AngII-(log(2)
/hAngIII)*AngIII', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('KAPM', 'cAPM');

model.physics('AngIII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KAPA*AngII-KAPM*AngIII-(log(2)
/hAngIII)*AngIII', 0);
model.physics('AngIV').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KAPM*AngIII-(log(2)/hAngIV)
*AngIV', 0);
model.physics('AngIV').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KAPM*AngIII-KAT4-(log(2)/hAngIV)
*AngIV', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('KAT4', 'cAT4');

model.physics('AngIV').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KAPM*AngIII-KAT4*AngIV-(log(2)
/hAngIV)*AngIV', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('gam_a', '8.3e-1[1/h]*100');
model.variable('var1').set('Kon', '5e3[1/M/s]/100');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.physics('a').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kg*phi_a*ma*n+Sang17*MAsAng17-↙
gam_a*a', 0);
model.physics('Ctl').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pv*In*(t>5[d])-dcl*Ctl-gam_v*n*Ci', ↙
0);

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol1').runAll;
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.label('Full run_new eq.mph');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n*1e5');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecoloractive', 'on');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormin', '2.45833120578347E9');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormax', '2.45833120578347E9');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecoloractive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl*4');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl*3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl*3.2');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl*3.1');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl*3.15');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c*0.4');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c*0.4/4');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c*0.4/10');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecoloractive', 'on');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormax', '7.81218759770573');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormin', '7.81218759770573');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1046.2[g/mol]');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1046.2[g/mol]*38.5');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1046.2[g/mol]');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeColorActive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1046.2[g/mol]*100');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1046.2[g/mol]*150');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a*10');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cRenin');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/h');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Kf');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'f');

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'nmol/l');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'nmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cACE');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/h');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cAT1');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/h');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cMAs');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'SAT1R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/(h*fmol)');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sn');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/s');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/h');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Kg');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'phi_a');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'SAng17');

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sang17');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/(h*fmol)');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Kb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/M/s');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'phic');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'ml/h');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'phim');

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'phict1');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'ml/h');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'RH');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/h');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'xn');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/(pg*h)');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'gam_n');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/h');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'gam_m');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'ml/h');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'gam_v');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'ml/(h*fmol)');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'xm');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/(pg*h)');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'gam');

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'gam_n1');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/h');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'pv');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'dv');

model.mesh('mesh1').run;

model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'dcl');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/h');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').run;
model.mesh('mesh1').feature('impl').active(false);
model.mesh('mesh1').feature.clear;
model.mesh('mesh1').clearMesh;
```

```
model.geom('geom1').create('blk1', 'Block');
model.geom('geom1').feature('blk1').set('size', {'0.1' '0.1' '0.1'});
model.geom('geom1').run('blk1');
model.geom('geom1').runPre('fin');
model.geom('geom1').feature('blk1').set('size', {'0.1' '0.1' '0.1'});
model.geom('geom1').runPre('fin');
model.geom('geom1').run('fin');

model.physics('Ci').feature('init2').set('Ci', '1.27e-9[M]*(z>0.9[m])');

model.sol('sol1').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('Ci').feature('init2').set('Ci', '1.27e-9[M]*(z>0.09[m])');

model.sol('sol1').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.label('Full run new geometry_new eq - Copy.mph');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('AngI').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'cRenin*AGT+KRenin*(Renin-Renin0)-
cACE*AngI-(KNEP)*AngI-KonACE2AngI*AngI*ACE2+KoffACE2AngI*ACE2AngI-(log(2)/hAngI)*AngI', 0);
model.physics('AngII').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '(cACE)*AngI-
KonAT1*AngII*AT1R+KoffAT1*AT1RangII-KonAT2AngII*AT2R+KoffAT2*AT2RangII-(KAPA)*AngII-
KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2AngII*ACE2AngII-(log(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);
model.physics('Ang17').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'KNEP*AngI+KACE2*ACE2AngII+KAng17Ang19*Ang19-KonMAS*Ang17*MAs+KoffMAS*MAsAng17-(log(2)
/hAng17)*Ang17', 0);
model.physics('AngI').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'cRenin*AGT+KRenin*(Renin-Renin0)-
cACE*AngI-(KNEP)*AngI-KonACE2AngI*AngI*ACE2+KoffACE2AngI*ACE2bAngI-(log(2)/hAngI)*AngI', 0);
model.physics('AngII').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '(cACE)*AngI-
KonAT1*AngII*AT1R+KoffAT1*AT1bAngII-KonAT2AngII*AT2R+KoffAT2*AT2bAngII-(KAPA)*AngII-
KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2bAngII*ACE2AngII-(log(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);
model.physics('Ang17').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'KNEP*AngI+KACE2*ACE2bAngII+KAng17Ang19*Ang19-KonMAS*Ang17*MAs+KoffMAS*MAsbAng17-(log(2)
/hAng17)*Ang17', 0);
model.physics('Ang19').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KACE2*ACE2bAngI-(log(2)/hAng19)
*Ang19', 0);
model.physics('AT1bAngII').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KonAT1AngII*AT1R*AngII-(log(2)
/hAT1)*AT1bAngII-KoffAT1*AT1bAngII', 0);
```

```
model.physics('AT2bAngII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonAt2*AngII*AT2R-(log(2)
/hAT2)*AT2bAngII-KoffAT2*AT2bAngII', 0);
model.physics('AT4bAngIV').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonAT4R*AngIV*AT4R-(log(2)
/hAT4)*AT4bAngIV-KoffAT4*AT4bAngIV', 0);
model.physics('MAsbAng17').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonMAs*Ang17*MAs-(log(2)/hMAs)
*MAsbAng17-KoffMAs*AT4bAngI17', 0);
model.physics.create('dode', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u26'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode', true);

model.physics.create('dode2', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u27'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode2', true);

model.physics.create('dode3', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u28'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode3', true);

model.physics.create('dode4', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u29'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode4', true);

model.physics.create('dode5', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u30'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode5', true);

model.physics.create('dode6', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u31'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode6', true);

model.physics.create('dode7', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u32'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode7', true);

model.physics('dode').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'AT1R');
model.physics('dode').tag('AT1R');
model.physics('AT1R').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('AT1R').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('AT1R').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('AT1R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SAT1R-KonAT1', 0);
model.physics('AT1R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SAT1R-KonAT1*AngII*AT1R-
KAT1RMAsR*MAsR+KoffAT1*AT1bAngII-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R', 0);
model.physics('dode2').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode2').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'AT2R');
model.physics('dode2').tag('AT');
model.physics('AT').tag('AT2R');
model.physics('AT2R').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('AT2R').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('AT2R').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/H');
model.physics('AT2R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SAT2R-
```

```
KonAT2*AngII*AT2R+KoffAT2*AT2BAngII', 0);
model.physics('dode3').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'MAsR');
model.physics('dode3').tag('MAsR');
model.physics('MAsR').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('MAsR').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('MAsR').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/H');
model.physics('MAsR').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('MAsR').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SMAsR-KoffMAs*Ang17*MAsR+KoffMAs',
0);
model.physics('MAsR').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SMAsR-
KonMAs*Ang17*MAsR+KoffMAs*MAsBAng17', 0);
model.physics('dode4').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode4').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('dode4').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('MAsR').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('AT2R').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('dode4').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'AT4R');
model.physics('dode4').tag('AT4R');
model.physics('AT4R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SAT4R-
KonAT4*AngIV*AT4R+KoffAT4*AT4bAngIV', 0);
model.physics('dode5').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'ACE2');
model.physics('dode5').tag('ACE2');
model.physics('ACE2').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('ACE2').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('ACE2').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('ACE2').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SACE2-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2-
KonACE2AngI*AngI*ACE2-KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb+KonACE', 0);
model.physics('ACE2').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SACE2-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2-
KonACE2AngI*AngI*ACE2-
KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb+KoffACE2AngI*ACE2BAngI+KoffACE2AngII*ACE2bAngII',
0);
model.physics('dode6').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode6').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('dode6').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('dode6').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'ACE2bAngI');
model.physics('dode6').tag('ACE2bAngI');
model.physics('ACE2bAngI').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KonACE2AngI*AngI*ACE2-(log(2)
/hACE2AngI)*ACE2bAngI-KoffACE2AngI-', 0);
model.physics('ACE2bAngI').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KonACE2AngI*AngI*ACE2-(log(2)
/hACE2AngI)*ACE2bAngI-KoffACE2AngI-KoffACE2AngI*ACE2AngI', 0);
model.physics('dode7').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode7').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('dode7').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('dode7').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2-(log(2)
/hACE2AngII)*ACE2bAngII-KoffACE2AngII*ACE2AngII', 0);
model.physics('ACE2bAngI').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KonACE2AngI*AngI*ACE2-(log(2)
/hACE2AngI)*ACE2bAngI-KoffACE2AngI*ACE2AngI', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('KonACE2AngI', 'gam_v');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2AngI', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var1').set('KonAT1', 'gam_v');
```

```
model.variable('var1').set('KoffAT1', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var1').set('KonAT2', 'gam_v');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffAT2', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var1').set('KonACE2AngII', 'gam_v');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2AngII', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var1').rename('KonAT1', 'KonAT1AngII');
model.variable('var1').rename('KoffAT1', 'KoffAT1AngII');
model.variable('var1').rename('KonAT2', 'KonAT2AngII');
model.variable('var1').rename('KoffAT2', 'KoffAT2AngII');

model.physics('AngII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(cACE)*AngI-
KonAT1AngII*AngII*AT1R+KoffAT1*AT1bAngII-KonAT2AngII*AT2R+KoffAT2*AT2bAngII-(KAPA)*AngII-
KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2bAngII*ACE2AngII-(log(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);
model.physics('AngII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(cACE)*AngI-
KonAT1AngII*AngII*AT1R+KoffAT1AngII*AT1bAngII-KonAT2AngII*AT2R+KoffAT2*AT2bAngII-(KAPA)
*AngII-KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2bAngII*ACE2AngII-(log(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);
model.physics('AngII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(cACE)*AngI-
KonAT1AngII*AngII*AT1R+KoffAT1AngII*AT1bAngII-KonAT2AngII*AT2R*AngII+KoffAT2*AT2bAngII-
(KAPA)*AngII-KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2bAngII*ACE2AngII-(log(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);
model.physics('AngII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(cACE)*AngI-
KonAT1AngII*AngII*AT1R+KoffAT1AngII*AT1bAngII-
KonAT2AngII*AT2R*AngII+KoffAT2AngII*AT2bAngII-(KAPA)*AngII-
KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2bAngII*ACE2AngII-(log(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);
model.physics('AngII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(cACE)*AngI-
KonAT1AngII*AngII*AT1R+KoffAT1AngII*AT1bAngII-
KonAT2AngII*AT2R*AngII+KoffAT2AngII*AT2bAngII-(KAPA)*AngII-
KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2AngII*ACE2AngII-(log(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);
model.physics('AngII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(cACE)*AngI-
KonAT1AngII*AngII*AT1R+KoffAT1AngII*AT1bAngII-
KonAT2AngII*AT2R*AngII+KoffAT2AngII*AT2bAngII-(KAPA)*AngII-
KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2AngII*ACE2bAngII-(log(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);
model.physics('dode7').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'ACE2bAngII');
model.physics('dode7').tag('ACE2bAngII');
model.physics('ACE2bAngII').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');

model.variable('var1').set('KAng17Ang19', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var1').set('KonMAs', 'gam_v');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffMAs', 'KACE2');

model.physics('Ang17').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'KNEP*AngI+KACE2*ACE2bAngII+KAng17Ang19*Ang19-KonMAs*Ang17*MAsR+KoffMAs*MAsbAng17-(log(2)
/hAng17)*Ang17', 0);
model.physics('AT1bAngII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonAT1AngII*AT1R*AngII-(log(2)
/hAT1)*AT1bAngII-KoffAT1AngII*AT1bAngII', 0);
model.physics('AT2bAngII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonAT2AngII*AngII*AT2R-(log(2)
/hAT2)*AT2bAngII-KoffAT2*AT2bAngII', 0);
model.physics('AT2bAngII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonAT2AngII*AngII*AT2R-(log(2)
/hAT2)*AT2bAngII-KoffAT2AngII*AT2bAngII', 0);
model.physics('AT4bAngIV').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonAT4R*AngIV*AT4R-(log(2)
/hAT4)*AT4bAngIV-KoffAT4R*AT4bAngIV', 0);
model.physics('AT4bAngIV').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonAT4R*AngIV*AT4R-(log(2)
```

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/hAT4R)*AT4bAngIV-KoffAT4R*AT4bAngIV', 0);
model.physics('AngIV').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KAPM*AngIII-KonAT4R*AngIV*AT4R-
(log(2)/hAngIV)*AngIV', 0);
model.physics('AngIV').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KAPM*AngIII-KonAT4R*AngIV*AT4R-
(log(2)/hAngIV)*AngIV+KoffAT4R*AT4bAngIV', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('KonAT4R', 'gam_v');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffAT4R', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var1').set('hAT4R', 'hAT1');

model.physics('MAsbAng17').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonMAs*Ang17*MAsR-(log(2)
/hMAs)*MAsbAng17-KoffMAs*AT4bAngI17', 0);
model.physics('AT1R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SAT1R-KonAT1AngII*AngII*AT1R-
KAT1RMAsR*MAsR+KoffAT1*AT1bAngII-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R', 0);
model.physics('AT1R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SAT1-KonAT1AngII*AngII*AT1R-
KAT1RMAsR*MAsR+KoffAT1*AT1bAngII-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('SAT1', 'sRenin');

model.physics('MAsbAng17').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonMAs*Ang17*MAsR-(log(2)
/hMAs)*MAsbAngIV-KoffMAs*AT4bAngI17', 0);
model.physics('MAsbAng17').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonMAs*Ang17*MAsR-(log(2)
/hMAs)*MAsbAng17-KoffMAs*AT4bAngI17', 0);
model.physics('MAsbAng17').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonMAs*Ang17*MAsR-(log(2)
/hMAs)*MAsbAng17-KoffMAs*AT4bAng17', 0);
model.physics('MAsbAng17').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonMAs*Ang17*MAsR-(log(2)
/hMAs)*MAsbAng17-KoffMAs*AT4bAngIV', 0);
model.physics('AT1R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SAT1-KonAT1AngII*AngII*AT1R-
KAT1RMAsR*MAsR+KoffAT1AngII*AT1bAngII-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('KAT1RMAsR', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var1').set('KAT1RAT2R', 'KACE2');

model.physics('AT2R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SAT2R-
KonAT2AngII*AngII*AT2R+KoffAT2AngII*AT2bAngII', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('SAT2R', 'SAT1');

model.physics('MAsR').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SMAsR-
KonMAs*Ang17*MAsR+KoffMAs*MAsbAng17', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('SMAsR', 'SAT1');
model.variable('var1').set('SAT4R', 'SAT1');

model.physics('AT4R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SAT4R-
KonAT4R*AngIV*AT4R+KoffAT4R*AT4bAngIV', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('SACE2R', 'SAT1');

model.physics('ACE2').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SACE2R-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2-
KonACE2AngI*AngI*ACE2-
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KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb+KoffACE2AngI*ACE2BAngI+KoffACE2AngII*ACE2bAngII', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('KonACE2V', 'gam_v');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2V', 'KACE2');

model.physics('ACE2').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SACE2R-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2-  
KonACE2AngI*AngI*ACE2-  
KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb+KoffACE2AngI*ACE2bAngI+KoffACE2AngII*ACE2bAngII', 0);
model.physics('ACE2bAngI').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('ACE2').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('AT4R').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');

model.variable('var1').set('hACE2AngI', 'hAT1');
model.variable('var1').set('hACE2AngII', 'hAT1');

model.physics('ACE2bAngI').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KonACE2AngI*AngI*ACE2-(log(2)  
/hACE2AngI)*ACE2bAngI-KoffACE2AngI*ACE2bAngI', 0);
model.physics('ACE2bAngII').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2-(log  
(2)/hACE2AngII)*ACE2bAngII-KoffACE2AngII*ACE2bAngII', 0);

model.label('Full run new geometry_new eq - Copynew receptor.mph');

model.sol('sol1').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;

model.label('Full run new geometry_new eq - Copynew receptor.mph');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('AngI').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'cRenin*AGT+KRenin*(Renin-Renin0)-  
KACE*AngI-(KNEP)*AngI-KonACE2AngI*AngI*ACE2+KoffACE2AngI*ACE2bAngI-(log(2)/hAngI)*AngI', 0);
model.physics('AngI').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'cRenin*AGT+KRenin*(Renin-Renin0)-  
kACE*AngI-(KNEP)*AngI-KonACE2AngI*AngI*ACE2+KoffACE2AngI*ACE2bAngI-(log(2)/hAngI)*AngI', 0);
model.physics('AngI').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'cRenin*AGT+KRenin*(Renin-Renin0)-  
KACE*AngI-(KNEP)*AngI-KonACE2AngI*AngI*ACE2+KoffACE2AngI*ACE2bAngI-(log(2)/hAngI)*AngI', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('KACE', 'cACE');

model.physics('AngII').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '(KACE)*AngI-  
KonAT1AngII*AngII*AT1R+KoffAT1AngII*AT1bAngII-  
KonAT2AngII*AT2R*AngII+KoffAT2AngII*AT2bAngII-(KAPA)*AngII-
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KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2AngII*ACE2bAngII-(log(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);
model.physics('Cb').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ *Cb)/ph-KoffACE2V- $\leftarrow$ 
Kd*Cb-Kint*Cb', 0);
model.physics('Cb').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ *Cb)/ph-KoffACE2V*Cb- $\leftarrow$ 
Kd*Cb-Kint*Cb', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ *Cb)/ph+KoffACE2V*Cb- $\leftarrow$ 
Kd*Ci+Ka*Vint', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a_n)-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma- $\leftarrow$ 
gam_v*n*Ci', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('a_n', '1e-3');

model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a_n)-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma- $\leftarrow$ 
gam_v*n*Ci+xIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('ma').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xm*c-gam_n1*ma+gam_v*ma*Ci', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-11[M]- $\leftarrow$ 
dc*c+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)', 0);
model.physics('Ctl').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pv*In*(t>5[d])*(t-5[d])-dcl*Ctl- $\leftarrow$ 
gam_v*n*Ci', 0);
model.physics('Ctl').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pv*In-dcl*Ctl-gam_v*n*Ci', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-Kon*Ci*(Chs- $\alpha$ *Cb)/ph+KoffACE2V*Cb- $\leftarrow$ 
KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+Ka*Vint', 0);
model.physics.create('dode', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u33'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode', true);

model.physics.create('dode2', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u34'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode2', true);

model.physics.create('dode3', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u35'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode3', true);

model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('dode').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'IL6');
model.physics('dode').tag('IL6');
model.physics('IL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-gam_IL6*IL6- $\leftarrow$ 
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('dode2').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'IL6r');
model.physics('dode2').tag('IL');
model.physics('IL').tag('IL6R');
model.physics('IL6R').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('IL6R').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('IL6R').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('IL6R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SIL6- $\leftarrow$ 
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('IL6R').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
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model.physics('dode3').tag('IL6RbIL6');
model.physics('IL6RbIL6').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('IL6RbIL6').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('IL6RbIL6').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('IL6RbIL6').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('IL6RbIL6').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'IL6RbIL6');
model.physics('IL6RbIL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonIL6*IL6*IL6R-  
KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6-(log(2)/hIL6R)*IL6bIL6', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('xIL6', 'SAT1');

model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a_n)-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma-  
gam_v*n*Ci', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a_n)-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma-  
gam_v*n*Ci+xIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('xIL6', '10[fmol/h/mm^3]');
model.variable('var1').set('aa', 'xIL6*IL6RbIL6');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6', '10[1/fmol/h]');
model.variable('var1').remove('aa');
model.variable('var1').set('KIL6', '10[1/h/mm^3]');

model.physics('IL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci', 0);
model.physics('IL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-gam_IL6*IL6-  
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('KIL6', '10[mm^3/h]');

model.physics('IL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci', 0);
model.physics('IL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-gam_IL6*IL6-  
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('gam_IL6', 'KACE2');

model.physics('IL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-gam_IL6*IL6', 0);
model.physics('IL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-gam_IL6*IL6-  
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('KonIL6', 'gam_v');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffIL6', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var1').set('SIL6', 'SAT1');
model.variable('var1').set('hIL6', 'hAT1');

model.physics('IL6R').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'IL6R');

model.variable('var1').rename('hIL6', 'hIL6R');

model.physics('IL6RbIL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonIL6*IL6*IL6R-  
KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6-(log(2)/hIL6R)*IL6RbIL6', 0);

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;
```

```
model.label('Full run new geometry_new eq_new receptor_addIL6.mph');

model.physics.remove('solid');
model.physics.remove('p');
model.physics.remove('s');
model.physics.remove('growth');
model.physics('Ang19').feature('init1').set('Ang19', '1.2e-7[mol/L]');
model.physics('IL6').feature('init1').set('IL6', '1.2e-7[mol/L]');
model.physics('IL6RbIL6').feature('init1').set('IL6RbIL6', '1.05e-8[mol/L]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', ('53'));
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang19');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MASbAng17');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
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```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsR');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('Ang19').feature('init1').set('Ang19', '5.9e-8[mol/L]');
model.physics('ACE2bAngI').feature('init1').set('ACE2bAngI', '04.1e-8[mol/L]');
model.physics('ACE2bAngII').feature('init1').set('ACE2bAngII', '2.1e-8[mol/L]');
model.physics('IL6').feature('init1').set('IL6', '2.7e-7[mol/L]');
model.physics('IL6RbIL6').feature('init1').set('IL6RbIL6', '2.1e-8[mol/L]');
model.physics('IL6R').feature('init1').set('IL6R', '8e-8[mol/L]');
model.physics('AT1R').feature('init1').set('AT1R', '8e-8[mol/L]');
model.physics('AT2R').feature('init1').set('AT2R', '8e-8[mol/L]');
model.physics('MAsR').feature('init1').set('MAsR', '8e-8[mol/L]');
model.physics('AT4R').feature('init1').set('AT4R', '8e-8[mol/L]');
model.physics('ACE2').feature('init1').set('ACE2', '8e-8[mol/L]');
model.physics('n').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'xn*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma-
gam_v*n*Ci+xIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('Ctl').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'pv*In*(t>5[d])-dcl*Ctl-gam_v*n*Ci',
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0);
model.physics('AT1R').feature('init1').set('AT1R', '0');
model.physics('AT2R').feature('init1').set('AT2R', '0');
model.physics('MAsR').feature('init1').set('MAsR', '0');
model.physics('AT4R').feature('init1').set('AT4R', '0');
model.physics('ACE2').feature('init1').set('ACE2', '0');
model.physics('IL6R').feature('init1').set('IL6R', '0');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang19');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsbAng17');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsR');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('AT1R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SAT1*100-KonAT1AngII*AngII*AT1R-
KAT1RMAsR*MAsR+KoffAT1AngII*AT1bAngII-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R', 0);
model.physics('IL6').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-gam_IL6*IL6/100-
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('IL6R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SIL6*100-
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```

model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.label('Full run new geometry_new eq_new receptor_addIL6_parameter_run - Copy.mph');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '+KoffACE2V*Cb-
KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+Ka*Vint-Kd*Ci', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '+KoffACE2V*Cb-
KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+Ka*Vint-Kd*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci', 0);
model.physics('Cb').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '-KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Cb-
Kint*Cb+KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2', 0);
model.physics('ma').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'xm*c-
gam_n1*ma+gam_v*ma*Ci+xIL6ma*IL6bIL6', 0);
model.physics('ma').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'xm*c-
gam_n1*ma+gam_v*ma*Ci+xIL6ma*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('Ctl').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'pv*In*(t>5[d])-dcl*Ctl-
gam_v*n*Ci+xIL6ctl*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('IL6').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-gam_IL6*IL6/100-
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6+KsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics.create('dode', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode', true);

model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('dode').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'sIL6RbIL6');
model.physics('dode').tag('sIL6RbIL6');
model.physics('sIL6RbIL6').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SsIL6R+KonsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6',
0);
model.physics.create('dode2', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u9'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode2', true);

model.physics('dode2').identifier('dode2');
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('dode2').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode2').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'VEGF');
model.physics('dode2').tag('VEGF');
model.physics('VEGF').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SVEGF+KVEGF*sIL6bIL6', 0);
model.physics.create('dode', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u13'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode', true);

```

```
model.physics('dode').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'sIL6R');
model.physics('dode').tag('sIL6R');
model.physics('sIL6R').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('sIL6R').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('sIL6R').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('sIL6R').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('sIL6R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Ssil6R', 0);
model.physics('sIL6RbIL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SsIL6RbIL6+KonsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('sIL6R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SsIL6R', 0);
model.physics('sIL6R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SsIL6R+KsIL6R*IL6R-KsIL6rbIL6*sIL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('sIL6R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SsIL6R+KsIL6R*IL6R-KsIL6RbIL6*sIL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics.create('dode2', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u14'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode2', true);

model.physics('dode2').identifier('dode2');
model.physics('dode2').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('dode2').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'sACE2');
model.physics('dode2').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SsACE2-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci+KAdam17*ACE2', 0);
model.physics('dode2').tag('sACE2');

model.variable('var1').set('KsACE2', 'gam_v');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6ma', 'xIL6');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6ct1', 'xIL6');
model.variable('var1').set('KsIL6R', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var1').set('KonsIL6R', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var1').set('KsIL6RbIL6', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var1').set('KAdam17', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var1').set('SIL6RbIL6', 'SAT1');
model.variable('var1').set('SsIL6R', 'SAT1');
model.variable('var1').set('SVEGF', 'SAT1');
model.variable('var1').set('SsIL6RbIL6', 'SAT1');
model.variable('var1').set('SsACE2', 'SAT1');
model.variable('var1').set('KVEGF', 'KACE2');

model.physics('VEGF').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SVEGF+KVEGF*sIL6RbIL6', 0);

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;

model.label('Full run new geometry_addsIL6R_sACE2.mph');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'VEGF');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sACE2');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('sIL6R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SsIL6R+KsIL6R*IL6R-  
KsIL6RbIL6*sIL6RbIL6/100', 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MASR');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MASbAng17');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('ma').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'xm*c-
gam_n1*ma+gam_v*ma*Ci+xIL6ma*IL6RbIL6/100', 0);
model.physics('ma').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'xm*c-
gam_n1*ma+gam_v*ma*Ci+xIL6ma*IL6RbIL6/1000', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '+KoffACE2V*Cb-
KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+Ka*Vint*1000-Kd*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci/100', 0);
model.physics('Cb').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '-KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Cb-
Kint*Cb+KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2/100', 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('sIL6R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SsIL6R+KsIL6R*IL6R-
KsIL6RbIL6*sIL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('ma').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'xm*c-
gam_n1*ma+gam_v*ma*Ci+xIL6ma*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '+KoffACE2V*Cb-
KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+Ka*Vint-Kd*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci', 0);
model.physics('Cb').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '-KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Cb-
Kint*Cb+KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2', 0);
model.physics('sIL6R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SsIL6R+KsIL6R*IL6R-
KsIL6RbIL6*sIL6RbIL6/100', 0);
model.physics('ma').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'xm*c-
gam_n1*ma+gam_v*ma*Ci+xIL6ma*IL6RbIL6/100', 0);
model.physics('sIL6R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SsIL6R*100+KsIL6R*IL6R-
KsIL6RbIL6*sIL6RbIL6', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;

model.label('Full run new geometry_addsIL6R_sACE2_run.mph');

model.physics('AT1bAngII').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KonAT1AngII*AT1R*AngII-
KoffAT1AngII*AT1bAngII-(log(2)/hAT1)*AT1bAngII', 0);
model.physics('AT2bAngII').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KonAT2AngII*AngII*AT2R-
KoffAT2AngII*AT2bAngII-(log(2)/hAT2)*AT2bAngII', 0);
model.physics('MASbAng17').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KonMAS*Ang17*MAsR-
KoffMAS*MAsbAng17-(log(2)/hMAS)*MASbAng17', 0);
```

```
model.physics('AngIV').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KAPM*AngIII-  
KonAT4R*AngIV*AT4R+KoffAT4R*AT4bAngIV-(log(2)/hAngIV)*AngIV', 0);  
model.physics('AT4bAngIV').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonAT4R*AngIV*AT4R-  
KoffAT4R*AT4bAngIV-(log(2)/hAT4R)*AT4bAngIV', 0);  
model.physics('ACE2bAngI').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonACE2AngI*AngI*ACE2-  
KoffACE2AngI*ACE2bAngI-KACE2*ACE2bAngI', 0);  
model.physics('ACE2bAngII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2-  
KoffACE2AngII*ACE2bAngII-KACE2*ACE2bAngII', 0);  
model.physics('ACE2bAngII').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2-  
KoffACE2AngII*ACE2bAngII-KACE2*ACE2bAngII', 0);  
model.physics('AT1R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SAT1*100-  
KonAT1AngII*AngII*AT1R+KoffAT1AngII*AT1bAngII-KAT1RMAsR*MasR-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R', 0);  
model.physics('IL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-gam_IL6*IL6/100-  
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6+KsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6-KsIL6R*sIL6R*IL6', 0);  
model.physics('IL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-gam_IL6*IL6/100-  
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6+KsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6-KlsIL6R*sIL6R*IL6', 0);  
  
model.variable('var1').set('KlsIL6R', 'gam_v');  
  
model.physics('IL6R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SIL6*100-  
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6-KsIL6R*IL6R', 0);  
model.physics('sIL6R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SsIL6R*100+KsIL6R*IL6R-  
KsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6', 0);  
model.physics('sIL6RbIL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6-  
KsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6', 0);  
model.physics('ACE2').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SACE2R-  
KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-KAdam17*ACE2-KonACE2AngI*AngI*ACE2-  
KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2AngI*ACE2bAngI+KoffACE2AngII*ACE2bAngII', 0);  
model.physics('ACE2').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SACE2R-  
KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-KAdam17*ACE2-KonACE2AngI*AngI*ACE2+KoffACE2AngI*ACE2bAngI-  
KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2AngII*ACE2bAngII', 0);  
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-  
KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci+Ka*Vint', 0);  
model.physics('Cb').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '+KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2-KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Cb-  
Kint*Cb', 0);  
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint/1.27e-11 [M]  
+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)-dc*c', 0);  
  
model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;  
  
model.label('Full run new geometry_addsIL6R_sACE2_check.mph');  
  
model.sol('sol1').runAll;  
  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV*1046.2 [g/mol]');  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1046.2 [g/mol]');  
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.variable('var1').set('KACE', '54.1[1/h]*(1-InACE1)');

model.physics('Cb').active(false);
model.physics('Vint').active(false);
model.physics('Ci').active(false);

model.variable('var1').set('Cb', '0');
model.variable('var1').set('Ci', '0');
model.variable('var1').set('Vint', '0');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1046.2 [g/mol]');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('KACE', '54.1[1/h]*(1-InACE1)*100');
model.variable('var1').set('cRenin', '1.8e-14[1/s]*100');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('kAGT', '2.27e6[nmol/L/h]*100');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1046.2 [g/mol]');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('cRenin', '1.8e-14[1/s]*50');
model.variable('var1').set('kAGT', '2.27e6[nmol/L/h]*50');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('KACE', '54.1[1/h]*(1-InACE1)*70');
model.variable('var1').set('cRenin', '1.8e-14[1/s]*40');
model.variable('var1').set('KACE', '54.1[1/h]*(1-InACE1)*100');
model.variable('var1').set('kAGT', '2.27e6[nmol/L/h]*40');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('Cb').active(true);
model.physics('Vint').active(true);
model.physics('Ci').active(true);

model.variable('var1').remove('Cb');
model.variable('var1').remove('Ci');
model.variable('var1').remove('Vint');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl/1e6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('pv', '0.05[1/h]*10');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('Cb').active(false);
model.physics('Vint').active(false);
model.physics('Ci').active(false);

model.variable('var1').set('Ci', '0');
model.variable('var1').set('Cb', '0');
model.variable('var1').set('Vint', '0');
model.variable('var1').set('Ci', '0[M]');
model.variable('var1').set('Cb', '0[M]');
model.variable('var1').set('Vint', '0[M]');
model.variable('var1').set('xn', '2.1e-2[1/pg/h]/(1+a/57.85[pg/mm^3])*100');
```

```
model.variable('var1').set('gam_m', '2.1e-2[mm^3/h]/10');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_v', '2.5e-2[ml/h/fmol]/10');

model.sol('soll').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('dcl', '5.54e-3[1/h]/10');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c/1e6');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('gam_n', '6.3e-4[1/h]/10');
model.variable('var1').set('Sn', '2.1e-2[pg/h]*10');
model.variable('var1').set('Sc', '2.9e-2[pg/ml/h]*10');

model.sol('soll').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c/1e6');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e9');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('pv', '0.05[1/h]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('dcl', '5.54e-3[1/h]');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('xn', '2.1e-2[1/pg/h]/(1+a/57.85[pg/mm^3])*100');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_m', '2.1e-2[mm^3/h]/100');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_n', '6.3e-4[1/h]/100');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_v', '2.5e-2[ml/h/fmol]/100');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('pv', '0.05[1/h]/2');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_a', '8.3e-1[1/h]*1000');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_m', '2.1e-2[mm^3/h]/1000');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_v', '2.5e-2[ml/h/fmol]/1000');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c/1e6');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e9');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('xn', '2.1e-2[1/pg/h]/(1+a/57.85[pg/mm^3])*200');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c/1e6');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1/1e9');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('pv', '0.05[1/h]/10');
```

```
model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('pv', '0.05[1/h]/30');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1046.2 [g/mol]');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl/1e9');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6*23717.965 [g/mol]');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '60', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('showhiddenobjects', 'on');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('pv', '0.05[1/h]/60');
model.variable('var1').set('xn', '2.1e-2[1/pg/h]/(1+a/57.85[pg/mm^3])*400');
```

```
model.physics('IL6').feature('init1').set('IL6', '27[pg/ml]/23717.965 [g/mol]');

model.variable('var1').set('Kg', '2.1e-2[pg/h]/10');
model.variable('var1').set('phi_a', '2.1e-3[mm^3]/10');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1/1e9');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('pv', '0.05[1/h]/80');
model.variable('var1').set('xn', '2.1e-2[1/pg/h]/(1+a/57.85[pg/mm^3])*300');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('IL6').feature('init1').set('IL6', '100[pg/ml]/23717.965 [g/mol]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('Kg', '2.1e-2[pg/h]/30');
model.variable('var1').set('phi_a', '2.1e-3[mm^3]/30');
model.variable('var1').set('Sang17', '2.1[pg*ml/mm^3/h/fmol]/5');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1/1e9');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'mol/ml');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6*23717.965 [g/mol]');
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('Kg', '2.1e-2[pg/h]/80');
model.variable('var1').set('phi_a', '2.1e-3[mm^3]/50');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e9');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('xn', '2.1e-2[1/pg/h]/(1+a/57.85[pg/mm^3])*350');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('xn', '2.1e-2[1/pg/h]/(1+a/57.85[pg/mm^3])*450');
model.variable('var1').set('Kg', '2.1e-2[pg/h]/100');
model.variable('var1').set('phi_a', '2.1e-3[mm^3]/80');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e9');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6*23717.965 [g/mol]');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('Cb').active(true);
model.physics('Vint').active(true);
model.physics('Ci').active(true);

model.variable('var1').remove('Ci');
model.variable('var1').remove('Cb');
model.variable('var1').remove('Vint');
model.variable('var1').set('Ka', '5.78e-4[1/s]*1e6');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1046.2 [g/mol]');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');

model.variable('var1').set('KonACE2V', 'gam_v/1000');
model.variable('var1').set('KIL6', '10[mm^3/h]/100');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2V', 'KACE2/100');
model.variable('var1').set('KonACE2V', 'gam_v/100');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('Sc', '2.9e-2[pg/ml/h]/100');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', ('48'));
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('Ctl').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pv*In*(t>5[d])*(t-5[d])/1[d]-
dcl*Ctl-gam_v*n*Ci+xIL6ctl*IL6RbIL6', 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('IL6RbIL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KonIL6*IL6*IL6R-
```

```
KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6-(log(2)/hIL6R)*IL6RbIL6/100', 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', {'51'});
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('KIL6', '10[mm^3/h]/10');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('looplevel', {'44'});
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang19');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsbAng17');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsR');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'VEGF');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sACE2');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('KsIL6R', 'KACE2/100');
model.variable('var1').set('KonIL6', 'gam_v/100');

model.physics('IL6').feature('init1').set('IL6', '0');

model.variable('var1').set('K1sIL6R', 'gam_v/100');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6ctl', 'xIL6*10');
model.variable('var1').set('phic', '2.3e-4[mm^3/h]/10');
model.variable('var1').set('KsACE2', 'gam_v/10');
model.variable('var1').set('KonACE2V', 'gam_v/10');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1046.2[g/mol]');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang19');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MASbAng17');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsR');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6*23717.965 [g/mol]');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'VEGF');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sACE2');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '71', 0);
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '70', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '36', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 0);
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '12', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '21', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '41', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '62', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '60', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '52', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('Kd', '4.8e-5[1/s]*0');

model.physics('sIL6RbIL6').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KonsIL6R*sIL6R*IL6-  
KsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('KonsIL6R', 'gam_v');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('KonsIL6R', 'gam_v*100');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang19');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsbAng17');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('phic', '2.3e-4[mm^3/h]/100');
model.variable('var1').set('RH', '0.002751[1/h]*10');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('Kb', '1.36e5[1/M/s]/100');
model.variable('var1').set('phict1', '2.1e-5[mm^3/h]/100');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('dcl', '5.54e-3[1/h]/10');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsR');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6*23717.965[g/mol]');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('KIL6', '10[mm^3/h]/1000');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'VEGF');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sACE2');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '120', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6*23717.965 [g/mol]');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6*23717.965 [g/mol]*4e-6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowevalintitle', false);
model.result('pg1').set('title', 'Time=12 d Slice: IL6*23717.965 [g/mol]*4e-6 (pg/ml)');
model.result('pg1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeunit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormin', 45.01202833915263);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormax', 45.014634521382334);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecoloractive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamin', 45.01202833915263);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamax', 45.014634521382334);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedataactive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeactualminmax', [45.01202833915263↵
45.014634521382334]);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', true);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '50', 0);
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '41', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '61', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '11', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a*0.4');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a*0.6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a*0.3');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowevalintitle', false);
model.result('pg1').set('title', 'Time=12 d Slice: a*0.3 (pg/ml)');
model.result('pg1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeunit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormin', 10.44709394905868);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormax', 10.447534320182758);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecoloractive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamin', 10.44709394905868);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamax', 10.447534320182758);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedataactive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeactualminmax', [10.44709394905868↵
10.447534320182758]);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', true);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '11', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a*0.8');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a*0.1');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a*0.05');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a*0.01');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a*0.02');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1046.2[g/mol]');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII*1046.2[g/mol]*3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl/1e9*0.002');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '11', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl/1e9*0.02');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl/1e9*0.03');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl/1e9*0.025');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl/1e9*0.015');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowevalintitle', false);
model.result('pg1').set('title', 'Time=1 d Slice: Ctl/1e9*0.015 (1/L)');
model.result('pg1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeunit', '1/L');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormin', -1.0402210841761927);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormax', -1.0401384690751407);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecoloractive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamin', -1.0402210841761927);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamax', -1.0401384690751407);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedataactive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeactualminmax', [-1.0402210841761927↵
-1.0401384690751407]);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', true);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e9*0.6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowevalintitle', false);
model.result('pg1').set('title', 'Time=12 d Slice: n/1e9*0.6 (1/L)');
model.result('pg1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeunit', '1/L');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormin', 7.070785252294278);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormax', 7.07081608944477);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecoloractive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamin', 7.070785252294278);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamax', 7.07081608944477);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedataactive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeactualminmax', [7.070785252294278↵
7.07081608944477]);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', true);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '11', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e9*0.006');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e9*0.002');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowevalintitle', false);
model.result('pg1').set('title', 'Time=1 d Slice: n/1e9*0.002 (1/L)');
model.result('pg1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeunit', '1/L');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormin', 2.609412112184766);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormax', 2.609944321569946);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecoloractive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamin', 2.609412112184766);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamax', 2.609944321569946);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedataactive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeactualminmax', [2.609412112184766↵
2.609944321569946]);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', true);

model.physics('IL6R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SIL6*100*4e-6-↵
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6-KsIL6R*IL6R', 0);
model.physics('a').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kg*phi_a*ma*n/10+Sang17*MAsbAng17/10-↵
gam_a*a', 0);
model.physics('AngII').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '(KACE)*AngI-↵
KonAT1AngII*AngII*AT1R+KoffAT1AngII*AT1bAngII-↵
KonAT2AngII*AT2R*AngII+KoffAT2AngII*AT2bAngII-(KAPA)*AngII-↵
KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2AngII*ACE2bAngII-(log(2)/hAngII)*AngII/3', 0);
model.physics('AngII').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '(KACE)*AngI-↵
KonAT1AngII*AngII*AT1R+KoffAT1AngII*AT1bAngII-↵
KonAT2AngII*AT2R*AngII+KoffAT2AngII*AT2bAngII-(KAPA)*AngII-↵
KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2AngII*ACE2bAngII-(log(2)/hAngII)*AngII', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2AngII', 'KACE2*3');
model.variable('var1').set('pv', '0.05[1/h]/80/20');

model.physics('n').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'xn*c*0.6-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma-↵
gam_v*n*Ci+xIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'xn*c*0.2-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma-↵
gam_v*n*Ci+xIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n/1e9');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1/1e9');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.label('Full run_without virus_ ANGII and neutrophils and Lymphocyte validation and IL6 10_virus_fulRun2.mph');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics.create('dode', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode', true);

model.physics('dode').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1/mm^3');
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/mm^3/h');
model.physics('dode').field('dimensionless').field('ec');
model.physics('dode').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'ec');
model.physics('dode').tag('ec');
model.physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-Kiec*Ci*ec', 0);
model.physics.create('dode2', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode2', true);

model.physics('dode2').identifier('dode2');
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1/mm^3');
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/mm^3/h');
model.physics('dode2').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode2').field('dimensionless').field('iec');
model.physics('dode2').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'iec');
model.physics('dode2').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kiec*Ci*ec', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('Kec', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var1').set('Kiec', 'gam_v');
model.variable('var1').set('Sv', '(ec/ec0)*Sv0');
model.variable('var1').set('ec0', '7.23e8[1/ml]');
model.variable('var1').set('Sv0', '70[1/cm]');

model.physics.create('cdeq', 'ConvectionDiffusionEquation', 'geom1');

model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('cdeq', true);

model.physics('cdeq').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('cdeq').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('cdeq').field('dimensionless').field('cox');
model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dox' '0' '0' '0' 'Dox' '0' '0' '0' 'Dox' '0' '0' '0' 'Dox'}, 0);
model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dox-cells*' '0' '0' '0' 'Dox-cells*' '0' '0' '0' 'Dox-cells*'}, 0);
```

```
model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dox-cells*(k18cox/)' '0' '0' '0' '0'  
'Dox-cells*(k18cox/)' '0' '0' '0' 'Dox-cells*(k18cox/)'}, 0);  
model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dox-cells*(k1+cox/)' '0' '0' '0' '0'  
'Dox-cells*(k1+cox/)' '0' '0' '0' 'Dox-cells*(k1+cox/)'}, 0);  
model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dox-cells*(k1*cox/)' '0' '0' '0' '0'  
'Dox-cells*(k1*cox/)' '0' '0' '0' 'Dox-cells*(k1*cox/)'}, 0);  
model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dox-cells*(k1*cox/k2-)' '0' '0' '0' '0'  
'0' 'Dox-cells*(k1*cox/k2-)' '0' '0' '0' 'Dox-cells*(k1*cox/k2-)'}, 0);  
model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dox-cells*(k1*cox/k2-cov*cox)' '0' '0' '0'  
'0' '0' 'Dox-cells*(k1*cox/k2-cov*cox)' '0' '0' '0' 'Dox-cells*(k1*cox/k2-cov*cox)'}, 0);  
model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dox-cells*(k1*cox/k2-cov*cox)'  
+Per*Sv' '0' '0' '0' 'Dox-cells*(k1*cox/k2-cov*cox)+Per*Sv' '0' '0' '0' 'Dox-cells*'  
(k1*cox/k2-cov*cox)+Per*Sv'}, 0);  
model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dox-cells*(k1*cox/k2-cov*cox)'  
+Per*Sv*(1-co)' '0' '0' '0' 'Dox-cells*(k1*cox/k2-cov*cox)+Per*Sv*(1-co)' '0' '0' '0' '0'  
'Dox-cells*(k1*cox/k2-cov*cox)+Per*Sv*(1-co)'}, 0);  
model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dox' '0' '0' '0' '0' 'Dox' '0' '0' '0' '0'  
'Dox'}, 0);  
model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-cells*(k1*cox/k2-cov*cox)+Per*Sv*'  
(1-cox)', 0);  
  
model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;  
  
model.variable('var1').set('cells', 'H+In+n+ec+iec');  
model.variable('var1').set('Dox', '1.78e-9 [m^2/s]');  
model.variable('var1').set('k1', '2200 [mole/m^3/d]');  
model.variable('var1').set('k2', '0.00464 [mole/m^3]');  
model.variable('var1').set('Per', '3.58e-4 [m/s]');  
  
model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-cells*(k1*cox/k2-coxv*cox)+Per*Sv*'  
(1-cox)', 0);  
  
model.variable('var1').set('cox', '0.2 [mole/m^3]');  
model.variable('var1').rename('cox', 'coxv');  
model.variable('var1').set('coxv', '6.4 [g/m^3]');  
  
model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-cells*(k1*cox/(k2-coxv*cox))'  
+Per*Sv*(1-cox)', 0);  
model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*cox/(k2-coxv*cox))'  
+Per*Sv*(1-cox)', 0);  
model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*cox/(k2-  
coxv*cox))', 0);  
model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', 'Per*Sv*(1-cox)', 0);  
model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*cox/(k2-coxv*cox))'  
+Per*Sv*(1-cox)', 0);  
  
model.variable('var1').set('coxv', '0.2 [mole/m^3]');  
  
model.mesh('mesh1').autoMeshSize(6);  
  
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdfactive', 'off');
```

```
model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('ec').feature('init1').set('ec', 'ec0');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/mm^3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cells');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 0);
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '15', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '34', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '90', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '121', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('cdeq').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*100*cox/(k2-  
coxv*cox))+Per*Sv*(1-cox)', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.label('baseline_oxygen1.mph');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('dode2').tag('iec');
model.physics('cdeq').tag('cox_oxygen');
model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*10*cox/(k2-  
coxv*cox))+Per*Sv*(1-cox)', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec/100-Kiec*Ci*ec', 0);
model.physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec/1000-Kiec*Ci*ec', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*100*cox/(k2-  
coxv*cox))+Per*Sv*(1-cox)', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*30*cox/(k2-  
coxv*cox))+Per*Sv*(1-cox)', 0);

model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tlist', 'range(0,0.5,12)');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '25', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*90*cox/(k2-  
coxv*cox))+Per*Sv*(1-cox)', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*80*cox/(k2-  
coxv*cox))+Per*Sv*(1-cox)', 0);  
  
model.sol('sol1').runAll;  
  
model.result('pg1').run;  
  
model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*70*cox/(k2-  
coxv*cox))+Per*Sv*(1-cox)', 0);  
  
model.sol('sol1').runAll;  
  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').run;  
  
model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*60*cox/(k2-  
coxv*cox))+Per*Sv*(1-cox)', 0);  
  
model.sol('sol1').runAll;  
  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').run;  
  
model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*50*cox/(k2-  
coxv*cox))+Per*Sv*(1-cox)', 0);  
  
model.sol('sol1').runAll;  
  
model.result('pg1').run;  
  
model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*55*cox/(k2-  
coxv*cox))+Per*Sv*(1-cox)', 0);  
  
model.sol('sol1').runAll;  
  
model.result('pg1').run;  
  
model.label('baseline_oxygen1_k155.mph');  
  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', false);  
model.result('pg1').set('allowevalintitle', false);  
model.result('pg1').set('title', 'Time=12 d Slice: Dependent variable cox (1)');  
model.result('pg1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeunit', '1');  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormin', 0.003045958919896244);  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormax', 0.0030461182900486895);  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecoloractive', 'off');  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamin', 0.003045958919896244);  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamax', 0.0030461182900486895);
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedataactive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeactualminmax', [0.003045958919896244↵
0.0030461182900486895]);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', true);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec/1000-Kiec*Ci*ec*100', 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '23', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '19', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '9', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*cox/(k2-↵
coxv*cox))+Per*Sv*(1-cox)', 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '25', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cells-ec');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Sv');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/cm');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*cox/(k2-
coxv*cox))*0+Per*Sv*(1-cox)', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('cox_oxygen').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('cox_oxygen').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/ml');
model.physics('cox_oxygen').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/ml/h');
model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*cox/(k2-
coxv*cox))*0+Per*Sv*(coxv-cox)', 0);
model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', 'Per*Sv*(coxv-cox)', 0);
model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', 'Per*Sv*(coxv-cox)-(cells/ec0)
*(k1*cox/(k2-coxv*cox))*0', 0);
model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', 'Per*Sv*(coxv-cox)', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('oxygenExtra', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*cox/(k2-coxv*cox))*0');

model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', 'Per*Sv*(coxv-cox)-Aox*cox/
(cox-kox)*fc', 0);
model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', 'Per*Sv*(coxv-cox)-Aox*cox/
(cox+kox)*fc', 0);
model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', 'Per*Sv*(coxv-cox)-Aox*cox/
(cox+kox)*fc', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('Aox', '2200[mol/m^3/day]');
model.variable('var1').set('kox', '0.00464[mol/m^3]');
model.variable('var1').set('fc', 'cells/ec0');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cells');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cells/ec0');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'fc');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', 'Per*Sv*(coxv-cox)-Aox*cox/
(cox+kox)*fc/1.2', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', 'Per*Sv*(coxv-cox)-Aox*cox/
(cox+kox)*fc/2', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', 'Per*Sv*(coxv-cox)-Aox*cox/
(cox+kox)*fc/5', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', 'Per*Sv*(coxv-cox)-Aox*cox/
(cox+kox)*fc/8', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '21', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '16', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '6', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', 'Per*Sv*(coxv-cox)-Aox*cox/
(cox+kox)*fc/100', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '25', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', 'Per*Sv*(coxv-cox)-Aox*cox/
(cox+kox)*fc/80', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', 'Per*Sv*(coxv-cox)-Aox*cox/
(cox+kox)*fc/70', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', 'Per*Sv*(coxv-cox)-Aox*cox/
(cox+kox)*fc/50', 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.label('baseline_new oxygen.mph');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('IL6').feature('init1').set('IL6', '6.83[pg/ml]/23717.965[g/mol]');
model.physics('a').feature('init1').set('a', '3[pg/ml]');
model.physics('n').feature('init1').set('n', '4.2e9[l/L]');
model.physics('Ctl').feature('init1').set('Ctl', '2.17e9[l/L]');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6*23717.965[g/mol]');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dci*1000' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci*1000' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci*1000'}, 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*sACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci/100+Ka*Vint', 0);

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('c').feature('init1').set('c', '0');
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dci*100000' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci*100000' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci*100000'}, 0);

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '25', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.param.set('bKa', '1');
model.param.set('bSIL6', '1');
model.param.set('bSsACE2', '1');
model.param.set('bSAT1R', '1');

model.variable('var1').set('Ka', '5.78e-4[1/s]*1e6/bKa');
model.variable('var1').set('SIL6', 'SAT1/bSIL6');
model.variable('var1').set('SsACE2', 'SAT1*bSsACE2');

model.param.set('bKa', '1e4');

model.label('baseline_new oxygen_initial_BlockKa_1e4.mph');

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;

model.param.set('bKa', '1');

model.study('std1').create('param', 'Parametric');
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'as', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('punit', '', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'as', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '', 0);
```

```
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('punit', '', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bKa', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '1,10,100,1000,10000', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'as', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('punit', '', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'as', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('punit', '', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bSIL6', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '1,10,100,1000,10000', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').set('sweeptype', 'filled');
```

```
model.batch.create('p1', 'Parametric');
model.batch('p1').study('std1');
model.batch('p1').create('sol1', 'Solutionseq');
model.batch('p1').feature('sol1').set('seq', 'sol1');
model.batch('p1').feature('sol1').set('store', 'on');
model.batch('p1').feature('sol1').set('clear', 'on');
model.batch('p1').feature('sol1').set('psol', 'none');
model.batch('p1').set('pname', {'bKa' 'bSIL6'});
model.batch('p1').set('plistarr', {'1,10,100,1000,10000' '1,10,100,1000,10000'});
model.batch('p1').set('sweeptype', 'filled');
model.batch('p1').set('probesel', 'all');
model.batch('p1').set('probes', {});
model.batch('p1').set('plot', 'off');
model.batch('p1').set('err', 'on');
model.batch('p1').attach('std1');
model.batch('p1').set('control', 'param');
```

```
model.sol.create('sol2');
model.sol('sol2').study('std1');
model.sol('sol2').label('Parametric Solutions 1');
```

```
model.batch('p1').feature('sol1').set('psol', 'sol2');
```

```
model.result.create('pg14', 3);
model.result('pg14').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg14').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg14').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result.create('pg15', 3);
model.result('pg15').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg15').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg15').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result.create('pg16', 3);
model.result('pg16').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg16').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg16').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result.create('pg17', 3);
model.result('pg17').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg17').create('slc1', 'Slice');
```

```
model.result('pg17').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result.create('pg18', 3);
model.result('pg18').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg18').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg18').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result.create('pg19', 3);
model.result('pg19').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg19').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg19').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang19');
model.result.create('pg20', 3);
model.result('pg20').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg20').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg20').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIII');
model.result.create('pg21', 3);
model.result('pg21').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg21').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg21').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
model.result.create('pg22', 3);
model.result('pg22').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg22').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg22').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result.create('pg23', 3);
model.result('pg23').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg23').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg23').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result.create('pg24', 3);
model.result('pg24').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg24').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg24').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
model.result.create('pg25', 3);
model.result('pg25').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg25').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg25').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsbAng17');
model.result.create('pg26', 3);
model.result('pg26').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg26').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg26').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result.create('pg27', 3);
model.result('pg27').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg27').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg27').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result.create('pg28', 3);
model.result('pg28').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg28').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg28').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result.create('pg29', 3);
model.result('pg29').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg29').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg29').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result.create('pg30', 3);
model.result('pg30').set('data', 'dset2');
```

```
model.result('pg30').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg30').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result.create('pg31', 3);
model.result('pg31').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg31').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg31').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result.create('pg32', 3);
model.result('pg32').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg32').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg32').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result.create('pg33', 3);
model.result('pg33').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg33').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg33').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result.create('pg34', 3);
model.result('pg34').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg34').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg34').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1');
model.result.create('pg35', 3);
model.result('pg35').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg35').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg35').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result.create('pg36', 3);
model.result('pg36').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg36').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg36').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result.create('pg37', 3);
model.result('pg37').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg37').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg37').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2R');
model.result.create('pg38', 3);
model.result('pg38').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg38').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg38').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsR');
model.result.create('pg39', 3);
model.result('pg39').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg39').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg39').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4R');
model.result.create('pg40', 3);
model.result('pg40').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg40').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg40').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2');
model.result.create('pg41', 3);
model.result('pg41').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg41').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg41').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngI');
model.result.create('pg42', 3);
model.result('pg42').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg42').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg42').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngII');
model.result.create('pg43', 3);
```

```
model.result('pg43').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg43').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg43').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result.create('pg44', 3);
model.result('pg44').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg44').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg44').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result.create('pg45', 3);
model.result('pg45').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg45').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg45').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result.create('pg46', 3);
model.result('pg46').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg46').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg46').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6RbIL6');
model.result.create('pg47', 3);
model.result('pg47').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg47').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg47').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'VEGF');
model.result.create('pg48', 3);
model.result('pg48').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg48').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg48').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result.create('pg49', 3);
model.result('pg49').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg49').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg49').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sACE2');
model.result.create('pg50', 3);
model.result('pg50').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg50').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg50').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result.create('pg51', 3);
model.result('pg51').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg51').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg51').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'iec');
model.result.create('pg52', 3);
model.result('pg52').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg52').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg52').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result.remove('pg41');
model.result.remove('pg20');
model.result.remove('pg42');
model.result.remove('pg21');
model.result.remove('pg43');
model.result.remove('pg22');
model.result.remove('pg44');
model.result.remove('pg40');
model.result.remove('pg27');
model.result.remove('pg49');
model.result.remove('pg28');
model.result.remove('pg29');
```

```
model.result.remove('pg23');
model.result.remove('pg45');
model.result.remove('pg24');
model.result.remove('pg46');
model.result.remove('pg25');
model.result.remove('pg47');
model.result.remove('pg26');
model.result.remove('pg48');
model.result.remove('pg30');
model.result.remove('pg52');
model.result.remove('pg31');
model.result.remove('pg32');
model.result.remove('pg33');
model.result.remove('pg50');
model.result.remove('pg51');
model.result.remove('pg16');
model.result.remove('pg38');
model.result.remove('pg17');
model.result.remove('pg39');
model.result.remove('pg18');
model.result.remove('pg19');
model.result.remove('pg34');
model.result.remove('pg35');
model.result.remove('pg14');
model.result.remove('pg36');
model.result.remove('pg15');
model.result.remove('pg37');

model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'as', 2);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '', 2);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('punit', '', 2);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'as', 2);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '', 2);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('punit', '', 2);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bSsACE2', 2);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '1,10,100,1000,10000', 2);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'as', 3);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '', 3);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('punit', '', 3);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'as', 3);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '', 3);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('punit', '', 3);
model.study('std1').feature('param').remove('pname', 3);
model.study('std1').feature('param').remove('punit', 3);
model.study('std1').feature('param').remove('plistarr', 3);

model.param.remove('as');

model.result.create('pg14', 3);
model.result('pg14').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg14').create('slc1', 'Slice');
```

```
model.result('pg14').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result.create('pg15', 3);
model.result('pg15').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg15').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg15').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result.create('pg16', 3);
model.result('pg16').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg16').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg16').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result.create('pg17', 3);
model.result('pg17').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg17').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg17').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result.create('pg18', 3);
model.result('pg18').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg18').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg18').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result.create('pg19', 3);
model.result('pg19').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg19').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg19').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang19');
model.result.create('pg20', 3);
model.result('pg20').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg20').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg20').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIII');
model.result.create('pg21', 3);
model.result('pg21').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg21').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg21').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
model.result.create('pg22', 3);
model.result('pg22').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg22').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg22').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result.create('pg23', 3);
model.result('pg23').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg23').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg23').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result.create('pg24', 3);
model.result('pg24').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg24').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg24').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
model.result.create('pg25', 3);
model.result('pg25').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg25').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg25').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsbAng17');
model.result.create('pg26', 3);
model.result('pg26').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg26').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg26').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result.create('pg27', 3);
model.result('pg27').set('data', 'dset2');
```

```
model.result('pg27').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg27').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result.create('pg28', 3);
model.result('pg28').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg28').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg28').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result.create('pg29', 3);
model.result('pg29').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg29').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg29').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result.create('pg30', 3);
model.result('pg30').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg30').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg30').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result.create('pg31', 3);
model.result('pg31').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg31').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg31').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result.create('pg32', 3);
model.result('pg32').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg32').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg32').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result.create('pg33', 3);
model.result('pg33').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg33').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg33').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result.create('pg34', 3);
model.result('pg34').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg34').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg34').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result.create('pg35', 3);
model.result('pg35').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg35').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg35').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result.create('pg36', 3);
model.result('pg36').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg36').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg36').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result.create('pg37', 3);
model.result('pg37').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg37').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg37').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2R');
model.result.create('pg38', 3);
model.result('pg38').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg38').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg38').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsR');
model.result.create('pg39', 3);
model.result('pg39').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg39').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg39').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4R');
model.result.create('pg40', 3);
```

```
model.result('pg40').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg40').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg40').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2');
model.result.create('pg41', 3);
model.result('pg41').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg41').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg41').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngI');
model.result.create('pg42', 3);
model.result('pg42').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg42').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg42').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngII');
model.result.create('pg43', 3);
model.result('pg43').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg43').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg43').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result.create('pg44', 3);
model.result('pg44').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg44').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg44').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result.create('pg45', 3);
model.result('pg45').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg45').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg45').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result.create('pg46', 3);
model.result('pg46').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg46').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg46').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6RbIL6');
model.result.create('pg47', 3);
model.result('pg47').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg47').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg47').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'VEGF');
model.result.create('pg48', 3);
model.result('pg48').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg48').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg48').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result.create('pg49', 3);
model.result('pg49').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg49').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg49').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sACE2');
model.result.create('pg50', 3);
model.result('pg50').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg50').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg50').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result.create('pg51', 3);
model.result('pg51').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg51').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg51').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'iec');
model.result.create('pg52', 3);
model.result('pg52').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg52').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg52').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
```

```
model.result.remove('pg41');
model.result.remove('pg20');
model.result.remove('pg42');
model.result.remove('pg21');
model.result.remove('pg43');
model.result.remove('pg22');
model.result.remove('pg44');
model.result.remove('pg40');
model.result.remove('pg27');
model.result.remove('pg49');
model.result.remove('pg28');
model.result.remove('pg29');
model.result.remove('pg23');
model.result.remove('pg45');
model.result.remove('pg24');
model.result.remove('pg46');
model.result.remove('pg25');
model.result.remove('pg47');
model.result.remove('pg26');
model.result.remove('pg48');
model.result.remove('pg30');
model.result.remove('pg52');
model.result.remove('pg31');
model.result.remove('pg32');
model.result.remove('pg33');
model.result.remove('pg50');
model.result.remove('pg51');
model.result.remove('pg16');
model.result.remove('pg38');
model.result.remove('pg17');
model.result.remove('pg39');
model.result.remove('pg18');
model.result.remove('pg19');
model.result.remove('pg34');
model.result.remove('pg35');
model.result.remove('pg14');
model.result.remove('pg36');
model.result.remove('pg15');
model.result.remove('pg37');

model.study('std1').feature('param').remove('pname', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').remove('punit', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').remove('plistarr', 1);

model.result.create('pg14', 3);
model.result('pg14').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg14').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg14').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result.create('pg15', 3);
model.result('pg15').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg15').create('slc1', 'Slice');
```

```
model.result('pg15').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result.create('pg16', 3);
model.result('pg16').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg16').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg16').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result.create('pg17', 3);
model.result('pg17').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg17').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg17').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result.create('pg18', 3);
model.result('pg18').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg18').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg18').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result.create('pg19', 3);
model.result('pg19').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg19').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg19').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang19');
model.result.create('pg20', 3);
model.result('pg20').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg20').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg20').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIII');
model.result.create('pg21', 3);
model.result('pg21').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg21').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg21').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
model.result.create('pg22', 3);
model.result('pg22').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg22').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg22').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result.create('pg23', 3);
model.result('pg23').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg23').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg23').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result.create('pg24', 3);
model.result('pg24').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg24').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg24').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
model.result.create('pg25', 3);
model.result('pg25').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg25').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg25').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsbAng17');
model.result.create('pg26', 3);
model.result('pg26').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg26').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg26').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result.create('pg27', 3);
model.result('pg27').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg27').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg27').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result.create('pg28', 3);
model.result('pg28').set('data', 'dset2');
```

```
model.result('pg28').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg28').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result.create('pg29', 3);
model.result('pg29').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg29').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg29').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result.create('pg30', 3);
model.result('pg30').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg30').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg30').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result.create('pg31', 3);
model.result('pg31').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg31').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg31').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result.create('pg32', 3);
model.result('pg32').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg32').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg32').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result.create('pg33', 3);
model.result('pg33').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg33').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg33').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result.create('pg34', 3);
model.result('pg34').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg34').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg34').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result.create('pg35', 3);
model.result('pg35').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg35').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg35').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result.create('pg36', 3);
model.result('pg36').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg36').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg36').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result.create('pg37', 3);
model.result('pg37').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg37').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg37').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2R');
model.result.create('pg38', 3);
model.result('pg38').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg38').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg38').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsR');
model.result.create('pg39', 3);
model.result('pg39').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg39').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg39').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4R');
model.result.create('pg40', 3);
model.result('pg40').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg40').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg40').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2');
model.result.create('pg41', 3);
```

```
model.result('pg41').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg41').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg41').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngI');
model.result.create('pg42', 3);
model.result('pg42').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg42').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg42').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngII');
model.result.create('pg43', 3);
model.result('pg43').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg43').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg43').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result.create('pg44', 3);
model.result('pg44').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg44').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg44').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result.create('pg45', 3);
model.result('pg45').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg45').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg45').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result.create('pg46', 3);
model.result('pg46').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg46').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg46').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6RbIL6');
model.result.create('pg47', 3);
model.result('pg47').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg47').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg47').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'VEGF');
model.result.create('pg48', 3);
model.result('pg48').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg48').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg48').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result.create('pg49', 3);
model.result('pg49').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg49').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg49').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sACE2');
model.result.create('pg50', 3);
model.result('pg50').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg50').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg50').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result.create('pg51', 3);
model.result('pg51').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg51').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg51').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'iec');
model.result.create('pg52', 3);
model.result('pg52').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg52').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg52').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');

model.batch('p1').run;

model.result('pg14').run;
```

```
model.label('baseline_clearparametric Ka_hrsACE2.mph');

model.result('pg14').run;

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol2').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol3').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol4').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol5').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol6').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol7').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol8').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol9').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol10').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol11').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol12').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol13').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol14').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol15').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol16').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol17').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol18').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol19').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol20').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol21').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol22').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol23').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol24').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol25').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol26').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol27').clearSolutionData;

model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('c', {'Dci' '0' '0' '0' 'Dci' '0' '0' '0'}
'Dci'), 0);
model.physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-
KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci+Ka*Vint', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma-
gam_v*n*Ci+xIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a)-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma-
gam_v*n*Ci+xIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('xn', '2.1e-2[1/pg/h]');

model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'c/(1+a)-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma-
gam_v*n*Ci+xIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a)-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma-
gam_v*n*Ci+xIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('da', '1+a', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('da', '1', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma-
```

```

gam_v*n*Ci+xIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('a0', '4.2e9[1/L]');
model.variable('var1').set('xn', '2.1e-2[1/h]');

model.physics('ma').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'xm*c-gam_n1*ma-
gam_v*ma*Ci+xIL6ma*IL6RbIL6/100', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Sc*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)-
dc*c', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '(Sc/Vo)*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*
(n+ma+In)-dc*c', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0)*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*
(n+ma+In)-dc*c', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('V0', '1.27e-9[M]');

model.physics('a').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kg*phi_a*ma*n+Sang17*MAAsbAng17/10-
gam_a*a', 0);
model.physics('a').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kg*phi_a*ma*n+Sang17*MAAsbAng17-
gam_a*a', 0);
model.physics('AT1R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SAT1-
KonAT1AngII*AngII*AT1R+KoffAT1AngII*AT1bAngII-KAT1RMAsR*MAAsR-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R', 0);
model.physics('IL6').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-gam_IL6*IL6-
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6+KsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6-KlsIL6R*sIL6R*IL6', 0);
model.physics('IL6R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SIL6-
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6-KsIL6R*IL6R', 0);
model.physics('IL6RbIL6').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KonIL6*IL6*IL6R-
KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6-(log(2)/hIL6R)*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('sIL6R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SsIL6R+KsIL6R*IL6R-
KsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-Kiec*Ci*ec', 0);
model.physics('cox_oxygen').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', 'Per*Sv*(coxv-cox)-Aox*cox/
(cox+kox)*fc', 0);

model.variable('var1').remove('a_n');
model.variable('var1').set('kAGT', '2.27e6[nmol/L/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('cRenin', '1.8e-14[1/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kf', '4.91e-5[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('f', '0.51[nmol/ml]');
model.variable('var1').set('KACE', '185.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAPA', '43.6[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAPM', '43.6[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kd', '4.8e-5[1/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('Ka', '5.78e2[1/s]/bKa');
model.variable('var1').set('Kint', '5.78e-4[1/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('Sc', '2.9e-2[pg/ml/h]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sRenin');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('data', 'dset2');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('Sn', '2.1e-2[pg/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('dc', '8.3e-1[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kg', '2.1e-2[pg/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('phi_a', '2.1e-6[ml]');
model.variable('var1').set('SAT1', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('Sang17', '4.2e2[pg/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_a', '3[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kb', '1.36e5[1/M/s]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '2.3e-4[mm^3/h]/100');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'ml/h');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('phic', '2.3e-9[ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('RH', '2.75e-3[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_n', '6.3e-4[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_m', '2.1e-5[ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_v', '0.03[ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('xm', '0.02[1/pg/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_a', '6.3e-4[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('pv', '0.05[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('dcl', '0.04[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonACE2AngI', '3.24e-2 [ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2AngI', '0.095 [ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonAT1AngII', '3.24e-2 [ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffAT1AngII', '0.095 [ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonAT2AngII', '3.24e-2 [ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffAT2AngII', '0.095 [ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonACE2AngI', '2.5e-5 [ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2AngI', '0.1 [1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonAT1AngII', '2.53-5[ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonAT2AngII', '2.53-5[ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonAT4R', '2.53-5[ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonIL6', '2.53-7[ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonMAs', '2.53-5[ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonsIL6R', '2.53-3[ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonACE2AngII', '2.53-5[ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonACE2V', '2.53-6[ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KsACE2', '2.53-6[ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('K1sIL6R', '2.53-7[ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAng17Ang19', '0.1[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAT1RAT2R', '0.1[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAT1RMAsR', '0.1[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kec', '0.1[1/h]');
```

```
model.variable('var1').set('Kiec', '2.5e-5[ml/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2AngII', '0.3[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2V', '0.1e-2[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffAT4R', '0.1[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffIL6', '0.1[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffMAs', '0.1[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KsIL6R', '0.e-21[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KsIL6RbIL6', '0.1[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KVEGF', '0.1[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KsIL6R', '0.1e-2[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SAT2R', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SAT4R', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SIL6RbIL6', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SMAsR', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SIL6', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]/bSIL6');
model.variable('var1').set('SsACE2', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]*bSsACE2');
model.variable('var1').set('SsIL6R', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SsIL6RbIL6', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SVEGF', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6ctl', '10[1/fmol/h]*10');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6ma', '10[1/fmol/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SACE2R', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('hAT4', '1.5[min]');
model.variable('var1').set('hAT4R', '1.5[min]');
model.variable('var1').set('hIL6R', '1.5[min]');
model.variable('var1').set('hMAs', '1.5[min]');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_IL6', '0.1[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KACE2', '0.095[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffAT1AngII', '0.095 [1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffAT2AngII', '0.095 [1/h]');
model.variable('var1').remove('cACE');
model.variable('var1').remove('cACE2');
model.variable('var1').set('KAdam17', '0.095[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonACE2V', '17[ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonIL6', '15[ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonsIL6R', '50[ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KsACE2', '17[ml/h/nmol]');

model.study('std1').feature('param').active(false);

model.sol('sol1').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg2').run;

model.batch.remove('p1');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('data', 'dset1');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('KIL6', '10[mm^3/h]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '10[mm^3/h]');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'ml/h');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sACE2');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('KIL6', '10[mm^3/h]/10');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('IL6').feature('init1').set('IL6', '6.83[pg/ml]/23717.965[g/mol]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', '1[pg]');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'pg');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'ng');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('IL6').feature('init1').set('IL6', '6.83e-12[g/ml]/23717.965[g/mol]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'KIL6*ma*Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('KIL6', '1 [ml/h]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-gam_IL6*IL6-  
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6+KsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6-KlsIL6R*sIL6R*IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.label('baseline_clearparametric clearSolution_pre_.mph');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('Dci', '5e-3[cm^2/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2AngII', '385.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonACE2AngII', '25 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2AngI', '65.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonACE2AngI', '25 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2V', '65.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonACE2V', '17 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAng17Ang19', '65.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAPA', '43.6 [1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAT1RAT2R', '65.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAT1RMAsR', '65.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffAT1AngII', '65.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffAT2AngII', '65.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonAT1AngII', '25 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonAT2AngII', '25 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffAT4R', '65.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonAT4R', '25 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAdam17', '65.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KIL6', '0.5 [ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffIL6', '65.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonIL6', '15 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffMAs', '65.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonMAs', '25 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KVEGF', '65.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kec', '65.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kiec', '25 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KsIL6R', '50 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KsIL6RbIL6', '65.22[1/h]');
```

```
model.variable('var1').set('K1sIL6R', '50 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('KonsIL6R', '17 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('SAT1R', '25 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('SAT2R', '2.27e6 [nmol/L/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SAT4R', '2.27e6 [nmol/L/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('Sang17', '4.2e2 [pg/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('SIL6', '2.27e6 [nmol/L/h]/bSIL6');
model.variable('var1').set('SMAsR', '2.27e6 [nmol/L/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SIL6RbIL6', '2.27e6 [nmol/L/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SVEGF', '1.14e6 [nmol/L/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SsACE2', '2.27e6 [nmol/L/h]*bSsACE2');
model.variable('var1').set('gam_IL6', '6.3e-4 [1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6ct1', '35 [1/fmol/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6ma', '65.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6', '65.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SsIL6R', '2.27e6 [nmol/L/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SsIL6RbIL6', '2.27e6 [nmol/L/h]');

model.physics('sIL6R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SsIL6R+KsIL6R*IL6R-  
KsIL6RbIL6*sIL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('sIL6R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SsIL6R+KsIL6R*IL6R-  
KsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('KsIL6R', '65.22[1/h]');

model.physics('sIL6R').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SsIL6R+KsIL6R*IL6R-  
KsIL6RbIL6*sIL6RbIL6', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('KsIL6RbIL6', '25.12[1/h]');

model.physics('IL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-gam_IL6*IL6-  
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6+KsIL6RbIL6*sIL6RbIL6-K1sIL6R*sIL6R*IL6', 0);
model.physics('IL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-gam_IL6*IL6-  
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6+KsIL6RbIL6*sIL6RbIL6-KsIL6R*sIL6R*IL6', 0);
model.physics('IL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-gam_IL6*IL6-  
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6+KsIL6RbIL6*sIL6RbIL6-K1sIL6R*sIL6R*IL6', 0);

model.variable.create('var5');
model.variable('var5').model('comp1');
model.variable('var5').label('Initial');
model.variable('var5').set('AGT0', '1.7e-7[nmol/L]');
model.variable('var5').set('Renini0', '2.06e-4[nmol/L]');
model.variable('var5').set('ANGI0', '271[nmol/L]');
model.variable('var5').set('ANGII', '21[nmol/L]');
model.variable('var5').set('ANGIII', '1.3e-8[mol/L]');
model.variable('var5').rename('ANGII', 'ANGII0');
model.variable('var5').rename('ANGIII', 'ANGIII0');
model.variable('var5').set('ANGIV0', '1.29[fmol/ml]');
model.variable('var5').set('ANG170', '1.2e-7[mol/L]');
model.variable('var5').set('ANG190', '5.9e-8[mol/L]');
model.variable('var5').set('AT1RbANGII__0', '4.1e-8[mol/L]');
```

```
model.variable('var5').set('AT2RbANGII__0', '2.1e-8[mol/L]');

model.physics('AT1bAngII').feature('init1').set('AT1bAngII', 'AT1RbANGII__0');
model.physics('AT2bAngII').feature('init1').set('AT2bAngII', 'AT1RbANGII__0');
model.physics('AGT').feature('init1').set('AGT', 'AGT0');
model.physics('Renin').feature('init1').set('Renin', 'Renin0');

model.variable('var5').rename('Renini0', 'Renini_0');

model.physics('Renin').feature('init1').set('Renin', 'Renin_0');

model.variable('var5').rename('Renini_0', 'Renin_0');

model.physics('AngI').feature('init1').set('AngI', 'ANGI0');
model.physics('AngII').feature('init1').set('AngII', 'ANGII0');
model.physics('Ang17').feature('init1').set('Ang17', 'ANG170');
model.physics('Ang19').feature('init1').set('Ang19', 'ANG190');
model.physics('AngIII').feature('init1').set('AngIII', 'ANGIII0');
model.physics('AngIV').feature('init1').set('AngIV', 'ANGIV0');
model.physics('AT2bAngII').feature('init1').set('AT2bAngII', 'AT2RbANGII__0');
model.physics('AT4bAngIV').feature('init1').set('AT4bAngIV', 'AT4RbANGIV__0');

model.variable('var5').set('AT4RbANGIV__0', '1.1e-8[mol/L]');

model.physics('MASbAng17').feature('init1').set('MASbAng17', 'MASbAng17_0');

model.variable('var5').set('MASbAng17_0', '2.1e-8[mol/L]');

model.physics('H').feature('init1').set('H', 'H0');

model.variable('var5').set('H0', '7.23e8[1/ml]');
model.variable('var5').set('n0', '4.2e9[1/L]');

model.physics('ma').feature('init1').set('ma', 'ma0');
model.physics('n').feature('init1').set('n', 'n0');

model.variable('var5').set('ma0', '4.2e9[1/L]');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var5').set('ma0', '2.17e9[1/L]');

model.physics('c').feature('init1').set('c', 'c0');

model.variable('var5').set('c0', '4.96e4[pg/ml]');

model.physics('Ct1').feature('init1').set('Ct1', 'Ct10');
```

```
model.variable('var5').set('Ctl0', '2.17e9[1/L]');

model.physics('a').feature('init1').set('a', 'a0');

model.variable('var5').set('a0', '716.35[pg/ml]');
model.variable('var5').descr('a0', '3 normal range');
model.variable('var5').set('AT1R0', '2.26[fmol/ml]');
model.variable('var5').set('AT2R0', '1.14[fmol/ml]');
model.variable('var5').set('MAsR0', '2.23[fmol/ml]');
model.variable('var5').set('AT4R0', '0.57[fmol/ml]');
model.variable('var5').set('ACE20', '5.17[fmol/ml]');
model.variable('var5').set('ACE2bAngI_0', '4.1e-8[mol/L]');
model.variable('var5').set('ACE2bAngII_0', '2.1e-8[mol/L]');
model.variable('var5').rename('ACe2bAngI_0', 'ACE2bAngI_0');
model.variable('var5').set('IL60', '16[fmol/ml]');
model.variable('var5').set('IL6R0', '1.15[fmol/ml]');
model.variable('var5').set('IL6RbIL6_0', '2.1e-8[mol/L]');
model.variable('var5').set('sIL6RbIL6_0', '1.05e-8[mol/L]');
model.variable('var5').set('VEGF0', '3.29e-4[fmol/ml]');
model.variable('var5').set('sIL6R', '0.03[fmol/ml]');
model.variable('var5').set('sACE20', '0.03[fmol/ml]');

model.physics('AT1R').feature('init1').set('AT1R', 'AT1R0');
model.physics('AT2R').feature('init1').set('AT2R', 'AT2R0');
model.physics('MAsR').feature('init1').set('MAsR', 'MAsR0');
model.physics('AT4R').feature('init1').set('AT4R', 'AT4R0');
model.physics('ACE2').feature('init1').set('ACE2', 'ACE20');
model.physics('ACE2bAngI').feature('init1').set('ACE2bAngI', 'ACE2bAngI_0');
model.physics('ACE2bAngII').feature('init1').set('ACE2bAngII', 'ACE2bAngII_0');
model.physics('IL6').feature('init1').set('IL6', 'IL60');
model.physics('IL6R').feature('init1').set('IL6R', 'IL6R0');
model.physics('IL6RbIL6').feature('init1').set('IL6RbIL6', 'IL6RbIL6_0');
model.physics('sIL6RbIL6').feature('init1').set('sIL6RbIL6', 'sIL6RbIL6_0');
model.physics('VEGF').feature('init1').set('VEGF', 'VEGF0');
model.physics('sIL6R').feature('init1').set('sIL6R', 'sIL6R0');

model.variable('var5').rename('sIL6R', 'sIL6R0');

model.physics('sACE2').feature('init1').set('sACE2', 'sACE20');

model.variable('var5').rename('a0', 'a_0');

model.physics('a').feature('init1').set('a', 'a_0');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('KACE2', '65.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').active(false);
model.variable.create('var6');
model.variable('var6').model('comp1');
model.variable('var6').set('a_n', '1e-3');
model.variable('var6').set('alp', '1e3');
model.variable('var6').set('AngII0', '21[nmol/L]');
model.variable('var6').set('AngII0sysNRF', '1.65e-2[nmol/L]');
model.variable('var6').set('Aox', '2200[mol/m^3/day]');
model.variable('var6').set('b', '0');
model.variable('var6').set('cACE', '54.1[1/h]*(1-InACE1)');
model.variable('var6').set('cACE2', '2.4[1/h]*vi');
model.variable('var6').set('cAngIIAngIV', '23.5[1/h]');
model.variable('var6').set('cAPA', '1.2e-2[1/s]');
model.variable('var6').set('cAPM', 'cAPA');
model.variable('var6').set('cAT1', '11.8[1/h]*(1-InARBs)');
model.variable('var6').set('cAT2', '3.9[1/h]');
model.variable('var6').set('cAT4', 'cAT2/3');
model.variable('var6').set('cChym', '1.1[1/h]');
model.variable('var6').set('cells', 'H+In+n+ec+iec');
model.variable('var6').set('Chs', '1.74e-5[M]');
model.variable('var6').set('cMAs', 'cAT4/2');
model.variable('var6').set('cNEP', '1.1[1/h]');
model.variable('var6').set('coxv', '0.2 [mole/m^3]');
model.variable('var6').set('cRenin', '1.8e-14[1/s]*40');
model.variable('var6').set('dc', '8.3e-1[1/h]*10');
model.variable('var6').set('Dci', '5e-7[cm^2/s]');
model.variable('var6').set('dcl', '5.54e-3[1/h]/10');
model.variable('var6').set('Dox', '1.78e-9 [m^2/s]');
model.variable('var6').set('ec0', '7.23e8[1/ml]');
model.variable('var6').set('f', 'fsys*AngII0/AngII0sysNRF');
model.variable('var6').set('fc', 'cells/ec0');
model.variable('var6').set('fsys', '0.397[nmol/L]');
model.variable('var6').set('gam_a', '8.3e-1[1/h]*1000');
model.variable('var6').set('gam_c', '3[1/d]');
model.variable('var6').set('gam_IL6', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var6').set('gam_m', '2.1e-2[mm^3/h]/1000');
model.variable('var6').set('gam_n', '6.3e-4[1/h]/100');
model.variable('var6').set('gam_n1', 'gam_n');
model.variable('var6').set('gam_v', '2.5e-2[ml/h/fmol]/1000');
model.variable('var6').set('hACE2AngI', 'hAT1');
model.variable('var6').set('hACE2AngII', 'hAT1');
model.variable('var6').set('hAGT', '10[h]');
model.variable('var6').set('hAng17', '30[min]');
model.variable('var6').set('hAng19', '24[min]');
model.variable('var6').set('hAngI', '1.72e-4[h]');
model.variable('var6').set('hAngII', '5e-3[h]');
model.variable('var6').set('hAngIII', '30[s]');
```

```
model.variable('var6').set('hAngIV', '0.5[min]');
model.variable('var6').set('hAT1', '1.5[min]');
model.variable('var6').set('hAT2', '1.5[min]');
model.variable('var6').set('hAT4', 'hAT1');
model.variable('var6').set('hAT4R', 'hAT1');
model.variable('var6').set('hIL6R', 'hAT1');
model.variable('var6').set('hMAs', 'hAT1');
model.variable('var6').set('hRenin', '0.25[h]');
model.variable('var6').set('InACE1', '0');
model.variable('var6').set('InARBs', '0');
model.variable('var6').set('k1', '2200 [mole/m^3/d]');
model.variable('var6').set('K1sIL6R', 'gam_v/100');
model.variable('var6').set('k2', '0.00464 [mole/m^3]');
model.variable('var6').set('Ka', '5.78e-4[1/s]*1e6');
model.variable('var6').set('KACE', '54.1[1/h]*(1-InACE1)*100');
model.variable('var6').set('KACE2', '0.382[1/h]/4');
model.variable('var6').set('KAdam17', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var6').set('kAGT', '2.27e6[nmol/L/h]*40');
model.variable('var6').set('KAng17Ang19', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var6').set('KAPA', '43.6[1/h]/4');
model.variable('var6').set('KAPM', 'cAPM');
model.variable('var6').set('KAT1RAT2R', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var6').set('KAT1RMAsR', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var6').set('KAT2', '25.1[1/h]/4');
model.variable('var6').set('KAT4', 'cAT4');
model.variable('var6').set('Kb', '1.36e5[1/M/s]/100');
model.variable('var6').set('Kd', '4.8e-5[1/s]*0');
model.variable('var6').set('Kec', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var6').set('Kf', 'Kfsys*AngII0sysNRF/AngII0');
model.variable('var6').set('Kfsys', '6.25e-2[1/h]');
model.variable('var6').set('Kg', '2.1e-2[pg/h]/100');
model.variable('var6').set('Kiec', 'gam_v');
model.variable('var6').set('KIL6', '10[mm^3/h]/1000');
model.variable('var6').set('Kint', '5.78e-4[1/s]/10');
model.variable('var6').set('KNEP', '0.583[1/h]');
model.variable('var6').set('Koff', '8e-3[1/s]*100');
model.variable('var6').set('KoffACE2AngI', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var6').set('KoffACE2AngII', 'KACE2*3');
model.variable('var6').set('KoffACE2V', 'KACE2/100');
model.variable('var6').set('KoffAT1AngII', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var6').set('KoffAT2AngII', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var6').set('KoffAT4R', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var6').set('KoffIL6', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var6').set('KoffMAs', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var6').set('Kon', '5e3[1/M/s]/100');
model.variable('var6').set('KonACE2AngI', 'gam_v');
model.variable('var6').set('KonACE2AngII', 'gam_v');
model.variable('var6').set('KonACE2V', 'gam_v/10');
model.variable('var6').set('KonAT1AngII', 'gam_v');
model.variable('var6').set('KonAT2AngII', 'gam_v');
model.variable('var6').set('KonAT4R', 'gam_v');
```

```
model.variable('var6').set('KonIL6', 'gam_v/100');
model.variable('var6').set('KonMAs', 'gam_v');
model.variable('var6').set('KonsIL6R', 'gam_v*100');
model.variable('var6').set('kox', '0.00464[mol/m^3]');
model.variable('var6').set('KRenin', '6.44e4[1/h]');
model.variable('var6').set('KsACE2', 'gam_v/10');
model.variable('var6').set('KsIL6R', 'KACE2/100');
model.variable('var6').set('KsIL6RbIL6', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var6').set('KVEGF', 'KACE2');
model.variable('var6').set('oxygenExtra', '-(cells/ec0)*(k1*cox/(k2-coxv*cox))*0');
model.variable('var6').set('Per', '3.58e-4 [m/s]');
model.variable('var6').set('ph', '0.05');
model.variable('var6').set('phi_a', '2.1e-3[mm^3]/80');
model.variable('var6').set('phi1', '1e-6[mm^3/s]');
model.variable('var6').set('phic', '2.3e-4[mm^3/h]/100');
model.variable('var6').set('phict1', '2.1e-5[mm^3/h]/100');
model.variable('var6').set('PRA', '0.97[ng/ml/h]*740.74[fmol/ng]');
model.variable('var6').set('pv', '0.05[1/h]/80/20');
model.variable('var6').set('Renin0', '2.06e-4[nmol/L]');
model.variable('var6').set('RH', '0.002751[1/h]*10');
model.variable('var6').set('SACE2R', 'SAT1');
model.variable('var6').set('Sang17', '2.1[pg*ml/mm^3/h/fmol]/5');
model.variable('var6').set('SAT1', 'sRenin');
model.variable('var6').set('SAT1R', '2.1[pg*ml/mm^3/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var6').set('SAT2R', 'SAT1');
model.variable('var6').set('SAT4R', 'SAT1');
model.variable('var6').set('Sc', '2.9e-2[pg/ml/h]/100');
model.variable('var6').set('SIL6', 'SAT1');
model.variable('var6').set('SIL6RbIL6', 'SAT1');
model.variable('var6').set('SMAsR', 'SAT1');
model.variable('var6').set('Sn', '2.1e-2[pg/h]*10');
model.variable('var6').set('sRenin', '(log(2)/hRenin)*Renin0');
model.variable('var6').set('SsACE2', 'SAT1');
model.variable('var6').set('SsIL6R', 'SAT1');
model.variable('var6').set('SsIL6RbIL6', 'SAT1');
model.variable('var6').set('Sv', '(ec/ec0)*Sv0');
model.variable('var6').set('Sv0', '70[1/cm]');
model.variable('var6').set('SVEGF', 'SAT1');
model.variable('var6').set('vi', '((H-In)/H)*(H>In)+0*(H<In)');
model.variable('var6').set('vt', '1*(Ci>Cb)+0');
model.variable('var6').set('xIL6', '10[1/fmol/h]');
model.variable('var6').set('xIL6ctl', 'xIL6*10');
model.variable('var6').set('xIL6ma', 'xIL6');
model.variable('var6').set('xm', '2.1e-2[1/pg/h]');
model.variable('var6').set('xn', '2.1e-2[1/pg/h]/(1+a/57.85[pg/mm^3])*450');
model.variable('var6').set('a0', '4.2e9[1/L]');
model.variable('var6').set('V0', '1.27e-9[M]');
model.variable('var5').set('ma0', '1.17e9[1/L]');
model.variable('var5').set('AGT0', '1.7e7[nmol/L]');
model.variable('var5').set('ANGI0', '19.6[nmol/L]');
model.variable('var5').set('ANGII0', '152[nmol/L]');
```

```
model.variable('var5').set('ANGIII0', '12.94[mol/L]');
model.variable('var5').set('ANGIV0', '6.99[mol/L]');
model.variable('var5').set('ANGIII0', '12.94[nmol/L]');
model.variable('var5').set('ANGIV0', '6.99[nmol/L]');
model.variable('var5').set('ma0', '2.17e9[1/L]');
model.variable('var6').active(false);
model.variable('var1').active(true);
model.variable('var1').set('Kec', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KVEGF', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAdam17', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KsIL6RbIL6', '5.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KsIL6R', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6ma', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffIL6', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2V', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SACE2R', '2.27e6 [nmol/L/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAT1RAT2R', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAT1RMAsR', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffAT4R', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffMAs', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAng17Ang19', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2AngII', '45.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffAT2AngII', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffAT1AngII', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2AngI', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAT2', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kec', '5.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KVEGF', '5.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAdam17', '5.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KsIL6RbIL6', '2.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KsIL6R', '5.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6ma', '5.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffIL6', '5.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6', '5.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2V', '5.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAT1RAT2R', '5.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAT1RMAsR', '5.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffAT4R', '5.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffMAs', '5.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAng17Ang19', '5.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2AngII', '15.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffAT1AngII', '5.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffAT2AngII', '5.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KoffACE2AngI', '5.22[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SAT2R', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SMAsR', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SAT4R', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SACE2R', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SIL6RbIL6', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SsIL6R', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]');
```

```
model.variable('var1').set('SVEGF', '0.235[fmol/ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SsIL6RbIL6', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SsACE2', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]*bSsACE2');

model.sol('soll').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '25', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang19');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsbAng17');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'l/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsR');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'VEGF');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sACE2');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'iec');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma- $\leftarrow$ 
gam_v*n*Ci+xIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma- $\leftarrow$ 
gam_v*n*Ci+xIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)-gam_n*n', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma- $\leftarrow$ 
gam_v*n*Ci', 0);
model.physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)-gam_n*n-gam_m*n*ma- $\leftarrow$ 
gam_v*n*Ci+xIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('xIL6', '5.26e-6[1/fmol/h]');

model.physics('ma').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xm*c-gam_n1*ma- $\leftarrow$ 
gam_v*ma*Ci+xIL6ma*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.physics('ma').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xm*c-gam_n1*ma-gam_v*ma*Ci', 0);
model.physics('ma').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xm*c-gam_n1*ma- $\leftarrow$ 
gam_v*ma*Ci+xIL6ma*IL6RbIL6', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('xIL6ma', '35 [1/fmol/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6ctl', '5.25e-3 [1/fmol/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6ma', '5.25e-3 [1/fmol/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6', '5.26[1/fmol/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6ctl', '5.26[1/fmol/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('xIL6ma', '5.26[1/fmol/h]');

model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0)*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0)*Vint', 0);
model.physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0)*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn* $\leftarrow$ 
(n+ma+In)-dc*c', 0);

model.variable('var1').set('SAT1R', '4.2e2 [pg/h/fmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kec', '5.22e-4[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kiec', '25e-4 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('phictl', '2.3e-10[ml/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('SIL6', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]/bSIL6');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↵
'1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result.dataset('cpt1').set('pointx', '0.05');
model.result.dataset('cpt1').set('pointy', '0.05');
model.result.dataset('cpt1').set('pointz', '0.05');
model.result.dataset('cpt1').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'iec');
model.result('pg9').run;

model.variable('var1').set('Kiec', '25 [ml/h/nmol]');

model.label('baseline_clearparametric clearSolution_pre_may10_niitial_old_new_1.mph');

model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg9').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/ml');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '4,5', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '4,5,6', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '4,5,6,7', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '4,5,6,7,8', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '4,5,6,7,8,9', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '4,5,6,7,8,9,10', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', '4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14', ↵
0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↵
'4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↵
'4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↵
'4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↵
'4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↵
'4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↵
'4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↵
'4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↵
'4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↵
'4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↵
'4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24', 0);
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↵
'4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25', 0);
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').setIndex('looplevel', ↵
'5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25', 0);
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.physics('IL6R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SIL6R-  
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6-KsIL6R*IL6R', 0);  
  
model.variable('var1').rename('SIL6', 'SIL6R');  
  
model.physics('sIL6RbIL6').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KonsIL6R*sIL6R*IL6-  
KsIL6RbIL6*sIL6RbIL6', 0);  
model.physics('IL6').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-gam_IL6*IL6-  
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6+KsIL6RbIL6*sIL6RbIL6-KonsIL6R*sIL6R*IL6', 0);  
model.physics('IL6').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-gam_IL6*IL6-  
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6+KoffsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6-KonsIL6R*sIL6R*IL6', 0);  
model.physics('sIL6RbIL6').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KonsIL6R*sIL6R*IL6-  
KoffsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6', 0);  
model.physics('sIL6R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SsIL6R+KsIL6R*IL6R-  
KoffsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6', 0);  
  
model.variable('var1').rename('KsIL6RbIL6', 'KoffsIL6R');  
model.variable('var1').remove('KlsIL6R');  
  
model.sol('sol1').runAll;  
  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6R');  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIII');  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang19');  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');  
model.result('pg1').run;  
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsbAng17');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MASR');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sACE2');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'iec');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Sv');
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg9').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg9').run;

model.variable('var1').set('Kiec', '25 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kec', '5.22e-5[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAT1RAT2R', '5.22e-1[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAT1RMAsR', '5.22e-1[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kd', '2.4e-5[1/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('KsACE2', '8.5[ml/h/nmol]');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var1').set('Kec', '5.22e-6[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kd', '2.4e-6[1/s]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAT1RMAsR', '5.22e-2[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('KAT1RAT2R', '5.22e-2[1/h]');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg2').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.variable('var1').set('Kiec', '50 [ml/h/nmol]');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'iec');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.sol('sol1').runAll;
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.variable('var1').set('Kec', '5.22e-7[1/h]');
model.variable('var1').set('Kiec', '70 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.variable('var1').set('ec0', '7.23e6[1/ml]');
```

```
model.sol('sol1').runAll;
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.variable('var1').set('Kd', '2.4e-8[1/s]');
```

```
model.sol('sol1').runAll;
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'iec');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'iec');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sRenin');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/(ml*h)');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'KsACE2');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'gam_v');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.label('baseline_checkVAribles.mph');

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol2').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol3').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol4').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol5').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol6').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol7').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol8').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol9').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol10').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol11').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol12').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol13').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol14').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol15').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol16').clearSolutionData;
```

```
model.sol('sol17').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol18').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol19').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol20').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol21').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol22').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol23').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol24').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol25').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol26').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol27').clearSolutionData;

model.param.set('bACE', '1');
model.param.rename('bSIL6', 'bSIL6R');
model.param.set('bIL6', '1');
model.param.set('bSn', '1');

model.variable('var1').set('SAT1', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]/bSAT1R');
model.variable('var1').set('KACE', '185.22[1/h]/bACE');
model.variable('var1').set('KIL6', '0.5 [ml/h]/bIL6');
model.variable('var1').set('SIL6R', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]/bSIL6R');
model.variable('var1').set('SsIL6R', '0.57[fmol/ml/h]/bSIL6R');
model.variable('var1').set('Sn', '2.1e-2[pg/h]/bSn');

model.study('std1').feature('param').active(true);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '2', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bSAT1R', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '1,2,100,1000', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bSIL6R', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bSsACE2', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bIL6', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '1,2,100,1000', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bSn', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', '', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bKa', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bSn', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '1,10,100,1000', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bSIL6R', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '1,2,100,1000', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bKa', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '1,10,100,1000,10000', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '1,2,10,100,1000', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bIL6', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '1,2,10,100,1000', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bKa', 2);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '', 2);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('punit', '', 2);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bKa', 2);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '', 2);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('punit', '', 2);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '1,10,100,1000,10000', 2);
```



```
model.study('std1').feature('param').remove('punit', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').remove('plistarr', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').remove('pname', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').remove('punit', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').remove('plistarr', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bKa', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('punit', '', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bKa', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('punit', '', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bSAT1R', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '1,2,10,100,1000', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bKa', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('punit', '', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bKa', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('punit', '', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '1,10,100,1000,1000', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').remove('pname', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').remove('punit', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').remove('plistarr', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bSIL6R', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('punit', '', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bSIL6R', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('punit', '', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bSAT1R', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '2', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '1,2,10,100,1000', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bSIL6R', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('plistarr', '1,2,10,100,1000', 0);
model.study('std1').feature('param').setIndex('pname', 'bSsACE2', 0);

model.label('ste1_hrsACE2 ALL_ ARBS ALL.mph');

model.geom('geom1').feature('blk1').set('size', {'0.05' '0.05' '0.05'});
model.geom('geom1').run;

model.mesh('mesh1').autoMeshSize(7);

model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tlist', 'range(0,1,12)');

model.batch.create('p1', 'Parametric');
model.batch('p1').study('std1');
model.batch('p1').create('sol', 'Solutionseq');
model.batch('p1').feature('sol').set('seq', 'sol1');
model.batch('p1').feature('sol').set('store', 'on');
model.batch('p1').feature('sol').set('clear', 'on');
```

```
model.batch('p1').feature('sol1').set('psol', 'none');
model.batch('p1').set('pname', {'bSsACE2' 'bSAT1R'});
model.batch('p1').set('plistarr', {'1,2,10,100,1000' '1,2,10,100,1000'});
model.batch('p1').set('sweeptype', 'filled');
model.batch('p1').set('probesel', 'all');
model.batch('p1').set('probes', {});
model.batch('p1').set('plot', 'off');
model.batch('p1').set('err', 'on');
model.batch('p1').attach('std1');
model.batch('p1').set('control', 'param');
```

```
model.sol.create('sol28');
model.sol('sol28').study('std1');
model.sol('sol28').label('Parametric Solutions 2');
```

```
model.batch('p1').feature('sol1').set('psol', 'sol28');
```

```
model.result.create('pg53', 3);
model.result('pg53').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg53').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result.create('pg54', 3);
model.result('pg54').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg54').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg54').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result.create('pg55', 3);
model.result('pg55').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg55').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg55').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result.create('pg56', 3);
model.result('pg56').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg56').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg56').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result.create('pg57', 3);
model.result('pg57').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg57').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg57').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result.create('pg58', 3);
model.result('pg58').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg58').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg58').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang19');
model.result.create('pg59', 3);
model.result('pg59').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg59').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg59').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIII');
model.result.create('pg60', 3);
model.result('pg60').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg60').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg60').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
model.result.create('pg61', 3);
model.result('pg61').set('data', 'dset3');
```

```
model.result('pg61').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg61').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result.create('pg62', 3);
model.result('pg62').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg62').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg62').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result.create('pg63', 3);
model.result('pg63').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg63').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg63').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
model.result.create('pg64', 3);
model.result('pg64').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg64').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg64').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MASbAng17');
model.result.create('pg65', 3);
model.result('pg65').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg65').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg65').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result.create('pg66', 3);
model.result('pg66').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg66').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg66').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result.create('pg67', 3);
model.result('pg67').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg67').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg67').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result.create('pg68', 3);
model.result('pg68').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg68').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg68').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result.create('pg69', 3);
model.result('pg69').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg69').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg69').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result.create('pg70', 3);
model.result('pg70').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg70').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg70').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result.create('pg71', 3);
model.result('pg71').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg71').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg71').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result.create('pg72', 3);
model.result('pg72').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg72').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg72').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result.create('pg73', 3);
model.result('pg73').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg73').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg73').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1');
model.result.create('pg74', 3);
```

```
model.result('pg74').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg74').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg74').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result.create('pg75', 3);
model.result('pg75').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg75').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg75').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result.create('pg76', 3);
model.result('pg76').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg76').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg76').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2R');
model.result.create('pg77', 3);
model.result('pg77').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg77').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg77').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsR');
model.result.create('pg78', 3);
model.result('pg78').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg78').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg78').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4R');
model.result.create('pg79', 3);
model.result('pg79').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg79').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg79').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2');
model.result.create('pg80', 3);
model.result('pg80').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg80').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg80').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngI');
model.result.create('pg81', 3);
model.result('pg81').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg81').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg81').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngII');
model.result.create('pg82', 3);
model.result('pg82').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg82').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg82').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result.create('pg83', 3);
model.result('pg83').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg83').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg83').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result.create('pg84', 3);
model.result('pg84').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg84').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg84').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result.create('pg85', 3);
model.result('pg85').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg85').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg85').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6RbIL6');
model.result.create('pg86', 3);
model.result('pg86').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg86').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg86').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'VEGF');
```

```
model.result.create('pg87', 3);
model.result('pg87').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg87').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg87').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result.create('pg88', 3);
model.result('pg88').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg88').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg88').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sACE2');
model.result.create('pg89', 3);
model.result('pg89').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg89').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg89').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result.create('pg90', 3);
model.result('pg90').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg90').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg90').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'iec');
model.result.create('pg91', 3);
model.result('pg91').set('data', 'dset3');
model.result('pg91').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg91').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');

model.batch('p1').run;

model.result('pg53').run;

model.label('set1_hrsACE2 ALL_ ARBS ALL.mph');

model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg52').run;
model.result('pg51').run;
model.result('pg50').run;
model.result('pg49').run;
model.result('pg48').run;
model.result('pg47').run;
model.result('pg46').run;
model.result('pg45').run;
model.result('pg44').run;
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result('pg42').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg39').run;
model.result('pg52').run;
model.result('pg51').run;
model.result('pg50').run;
model.result('pg49').run;
model.result('pg48').run;
model.result('pg47').run;
model.result('pg46').run;
model.result('pg45').run;
model.result('pg14').run;
```

```
model.result.remove('pg14');
model.result.remove('pg15');
model.result.remove('pg16');
model.result.remove('pg17');
model.result.remove('pg18');
model.result.remove('pg19');
model.result.remove('pg20');
model.result.remove('pg21');
model.result.remove('pg22');
model.result.remove('pg23');
model.result.remove('pg24');
model.result.remove('pg25');
model.result.remove('pg26');
model.result.remove('pg27');
model.result.remove('pg28');
model.result.remove('pg29');
model.result.remove('pg30');
model.result.remove('pg31');
model.result.remove('pg32');
model.result.remove('pg33');
model.result.remove('pg34');
model.result.remove('pg35');
model.result.remove('pg36');
model.result.remove('pg37');
model.result.remove('pg38');
model.result.remove('pg39');
model.result.remove('pg40');
model.result.remove('pg41');
model.result.remove('pg42');
model.result.remove('pg43');
model.result.remove('pg44');
model.result.remove('pg45');
model.result.remove('pg46');
model.result.remove('pg47');
model.result.remove('pg48');
model.result.remove('pg49');
model.result.remove('pg50');
model.result.remove('pg51');
model.result.remove('pg52');
model.result('pg54').run;
model.result.remove('pg54');
model.result.remove('pg55');
model.result.remove('pg56');
model.result.remove('pg57');
model.result.remove('pg58');
model.result.remove('pg59');
model.result.remove('pg60');
model.result.remove('pg61');
model.result.remove('pg62');
model.result.remove('pg63');
model.result.remove('pg64');
```

```
model.result.remove('pg65');
model.result.remove('pg66');
model.result.remove('pg67');
model.result.remove('pg68');
model.result.remove('pg69');
model.result.remove('pg70');
model.result.remove('pg71');
model.result.remove('pg72');
model.result.remove('pg73');
model.result.remove('pg74');
model.result.remove('pg75');
model.result.remove('pg76');
model.result.remove('pg77');
model.result.remove('pg78');
model.result.remove('pg79');
model.result.remove('pg80');
model.result.remove('pg81');
model.result.remove('pg82');
model.result.remove('pg83');
model.result.remove('pg84');
model.result.remove('pg85');
model.result.remove('pg86');
model.result.remove('pg87');
model.result.remove('pg88');
model.result.remove('pg89');
model.result.remove('pg90');
model.result.remove('pg91');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('quickxnumber', '1');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 2);
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 2);
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 1);
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 1);
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
```

```
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 2);
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 1);
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '8', 0);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '11', 0);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 1);
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 1);
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 2);
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 2);
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ct1');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'mol/ml');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'coxv');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'mol/mm^3');
```

```
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'mol/m^3');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 2);
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 2);
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg53').run;
```

```
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
```

```
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature.duplicate('slc2', 'slc1');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature.duplicate('slc3', 'slc2');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature.duplicate('slc4', 'slc3');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature.duplicate('slc5', 'slc4');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc2').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg53').feature('slc2').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg53').run;
```

```
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc4').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').feature('slc5').set('expr', 'cox');
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 2);
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 2);
```

```
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 2);
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 2);
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '3', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
```

```
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '4', 2);
model.result('pg53').run;
model.result('pg53').setIndex('looplevel', '5', 1);
model.result('pg53').run;

model.label('set1_hrsACE2 ALL_ ARBS ALL.mph');

model.result('pg53').run;

model.study('std1').feature('param').active(false);

model.sol('sol1').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol2').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol3').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol4').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol5').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol6').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol7').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol8').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol9').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol10').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol11').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol12').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol13').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol14').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol15').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol16').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol17').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol18').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol19').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol20').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol21').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol22').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol23').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol24').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol25').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol26').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol27').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol28').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol29').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol30').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol31').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol32').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol33').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol34').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol35').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol36').clearSolutionData;
```

```
model.sol('sol37').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol38').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol39').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol40').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol41').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol42').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol43').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol44').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol45').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol46').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol47').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol48').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol49').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol50').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol51').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol52').clearSolutionData;
model.sol('sol53').clearSolutionData;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result.remove('pg1');
model.result.remove('pg2');
model.result.remove('pg3');
model.result.remove('pg4');
model.result.remove('pg5');
model.result.remove('pg6');
model.result.remove('pg7');
model.result.remove('pg8');
model.result.remove('pg9');
model.result.remove('pg10');
model.result.remove('pg11');
model.result.remove('pg12');
model.result.remove('pg13');
model.result.remove('pg53');

model.variable.remove('var2');
model.variable.remove('var3');
model.variable.remove('var4');
model.variable('var5').label('Initial Value');
model.variable('var1').label('Variables');
model.variable('var1').remove('oxygenExtra');
model.variable.remove('var6');

model.physics('Ci').feature.remove('init2');
model.physics('Ci').feature('init1').set('Ci', '1.27e-9[M]*(z>0.04[m])');

model.sol('sol1').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result.create('pg1', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('quickxnumber', '1');
```

```
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('Ci').feature('init1').set('Ci', '1.27e-9[M]*(z>0.045[m])');

model.sol('sol1').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.batch.remove('p1');

model.sol('sol1').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '13', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;

model.label('Baseline_solution.mph');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2R');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'KRenin');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'KRenin*(Renin-Renin0)');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sRenin');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result.create('pg2', 'PlotGroup1D');
model.result('pg2').run;
model.result('pg2').create('ptgr1', 'PointGraph');
model.result('pg2').feature('ptgr1').set('data', 'cpt1');
```

```
model.result('pg2').run;
model.result('pg2').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result('pg2').run;
model.result('pg2').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result('pg2').run;
model.result('pg2').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'KRenin*(Renin-Renin0)');
model.result('pg2').run;
model.result('pg2').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', '(Renin-Renin0)');
model.result('pg2').run;
model.result('pg2').run;

model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdfactive', 'on');
model.sol('sol1').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdf', '1[h]');
model.sol('sol1').detach;
model.sol.create('sol54');
model.sol('sol54').study('std1');

model.study('std1').feature('time').set('notlistsolnum', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('time').set('notsolnum', '1');
model.study('std1').feature('time').set('listsolnum', 1);
model.study('std1').feature('time').set('solnum', '1');

model.sol('sol54').create('st1', 'StudyStep');
model.sol('sol54').feature('st1').set('study', 'std1');
model.sol('sol54').feature('st1').set('studystep', 'time');
model.sol('sol54').create('v1', 'Variables');
model.sol('sol54').feature('v1').set('control', 'time');
model.sol('sol54').create('t1', 'Time');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').set('tlist', 'range(0,1,12)');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').set('plot', 'off');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').set('plotgroup', 'pg1');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').set('plotfreq', 'tout');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').set('probesel', 'all');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').set('probes', {});
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').set('probefreq', 'tsteps');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').set('control', 'time');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').create('sel', 'Segregated');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature.remove('ssDef');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss1', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_a'});
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss2', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_ACE2'});
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss3', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss3').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_ACE2bAngI'});
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss3').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss4', 'SegregatedStep');
```

```
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss4').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_ACE2bAngII'});
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss4').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss5', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss5').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_AGT'});
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss5').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss6', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss6').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_Ang17'});
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss6').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss7', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss7').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_Ang19'});
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss7').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss8', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss8').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_AngI'});
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss8').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss9', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss9').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_AngII'});
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss9').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss10', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss10').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_AngIII'});
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss10').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss11', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss11').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_AngIV'});
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss11').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss12', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss12').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_AT1bAngII'});
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss12').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss13', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss13').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_AT1R'});
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss13').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss14', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss14').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_AT2bAngII'});
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss14').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss15', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss15').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_AT2R'});
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss15').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss16', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss16').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_AT4bAngIV'});
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss16').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
```

```
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss17', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss17').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_AT4R'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss17').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss18', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss18').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_c'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss18').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss19', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss19').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_Cb'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss19').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss20', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss20').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_Ci'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss20').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss21', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss21').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_cox'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss21').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss22', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss22').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_Ctl'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss22').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss23', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss23').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_ec'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss23').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss24', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss24').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_H'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss24').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss25', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss25').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_iec'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss25').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss26', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss26').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_IL6'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss26').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss27', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss27').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_IL6R'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss27').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss28', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss28').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_IL6RbIL6'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss28').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss29', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss29').set('segvar', ↵
{'compl_In'});
```

```
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss29').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss30', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss30').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_ma'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss30').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss31', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss31').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_MAsbAng17'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss31').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss32', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss32').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_MAsR'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss32').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss33', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss33').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_n'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss33').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss34', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss34').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_Renin'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss34').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss35', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss35').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_sACE2'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss35').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss36', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss36').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_sIL6R'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss36').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss37', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss37').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_sIL6RbIL6'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss37').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss38', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss38').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_VEGF'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss38').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss39', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss39').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_Vint'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss39').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature.remove('fcDef');
model.sol('sol154').attach('std1');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdfactive', 'on');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdf', '1[h]');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').create('fc1', 'FullyCoupled');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature.remove('sel');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('dDef').set('linsolver', 'pardiso');
model.sol.remove('sol1');
model.sol.remove('sol2');
model.sol.remove('sol28');
```

```
model.result.create('pg1', 3);
model.result('pg1').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg1').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result.create('pg2', 3);
model.result('pg2').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg2').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg2').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result.create('pg3', 3);
model.result('pg3').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg3').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg3').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result.create('pg4', 3);
model.result('pg4').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg4').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg4').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result.create('pg5', 3);
model.result('pg5').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg5').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg5').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result.create('pg6', 3);
model.result('pg6').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg6').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg6').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang19');
model.result.create('pg7', 3);
model.result('pg7').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg7').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg7').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIII');
model.result.create('pg8', 3);
model.result('pg8').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg8').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg8').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
model.result.create('pg9', 3);
model.result('pg9').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg9').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg9').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result.create('pg10', 3);
model.result('pg10').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg10').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg10').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result.create('pg11', 3);
model.result('pg11').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg11').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg11').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
model.result.create('pg12', 3);
model.result('pg12').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg12').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg12').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsbAng17');
model.result.create('pg13', 3);
model.result('pg13').set('data', 'dset4');
```

```
model.result('pg13').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg13').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result.create('pg14', 3);
model.result('pg14').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg14').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg14').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result.create('pg15', 3);
model.result('pg15').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg15').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg15').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result.create('pg16', 3);
model.result('pg16').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg16').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg16').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result.create('pg17', 3);
model.result('pg17').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg17').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg17').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result.create('pg18', 3);
model.result('pg18').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg18').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg18').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result.create('pg19', 3);
model.result('pg19').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg19').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg19').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result.create('pg20', 3);
model.result('pg20').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg20').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg20').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result.create('pg21', 3);
model.result('pg21').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg21').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg21').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result.create('pg22', 3);
model.result('pg22').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg22').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg22').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result.create('pg23', 3);
model.result('pg23').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg23').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg23').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result.create('pg24', 3);
model.result('pg24').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg24').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg24').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2R');
model.result.create('pg25', 3);
model.result('pg25').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg25').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg25').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsR');
model.result.create('pg26', 3);
```

```
model.result('pg26').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg26').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg26').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4R');
model.result.create('pg27', 3);
model.result('pg27').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg27').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg27').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2');
model.result.create('pg28', 3);
model.result('pg28').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg28').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg28').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngI');
model.result.create('pg29', 3);
model.result('pg29').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg29').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg29').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngII');
model.result.create('pg30', 3);
model.result('pg30').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg30').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg30').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result.create('pg31', 3);
model.result('pg31').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg31').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg31').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result.create('pg32', 3);
model.result('pg32').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg32').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg32').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result.create('pg33', 3);
model.result('pg33').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg33').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg33').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6RbIL6');
model.result.create('pg34', 3);
model.result('pg34').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg34').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg34').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'VEGF');
model.result.create('pg35', 3);
model.result('pg35').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg35').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg35').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result.create('pg36', 3);
model.result('pg36').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg36').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg36').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sACE2');
model.result.create('pg37', 3);
model.result('pg37').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg37').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg37').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result.create('pg38', 3);
model.result('pg38').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg38').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg38').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'iec');
```

```
model.result.create('pg39', 3);
model.result('pg39').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg39').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg39').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'cox');

model.sol('sol54').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;

model.label('Baseline_solution_Time step.mph');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg2').run;
model.result('pg3').run;
model.result('pg5').run;
model.result('pg4').run;
model.result('pg5').run;
model.result('pg6').run;
model.result('pg7').run;
model.result('pg8').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg11').run;
model.result('pg12').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg14').run;
model.result('pg15').run;
model.result('pg16').run;
model.result('pg17').run;
model.result('pg18').run;
model.result('pg19').run;
model.result('pg20').run;
model.result('pg21').run;
model.result('pg22').run;
model.result('pg23').run;
model.result('pg24').run;
model.result('pg25').run;
model.result('pg26').run;
model.result('pg27').run;
model.result('pg28').run;
model.result('pg29').run;
model.result('pg30').run;
model.result('pg31').run;
model.result('pg32').run;
model.result('pg33').run;
model.result('pg34').run;
model.result('pg35').run;
model.result('pg37').run;
model.result('pg36').run;
model.result('pg37').run;
model.result('pg39').run;
```

```
model.result('pg38').run;

model.label('Baseline_solution_Time step.mph');

model.result('pg38').run;
model.result.create('pg40', 'PlotGroup1D');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').create('ptgr1', 'PointGraph');
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('data', 'dset4');

model.param.set('bKa', '1');
model.param.remove('bKa');

model.variable.create('var6');
model.variable('var6').model('comp1');
model.variable('var6').label('Block');
model.variable('var6').set('bKa', '1*(t<4[d])+1e4*(t>4[d])');

model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tlist', 'range(0,1,18)');

model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdfactive', 'off');

model.variable('var6').set('bKa', '1*(t<=4[d])+1e4*(t>4[d])');

model.sol('sol54').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg2').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg2').run;
model.result('pg3').run;
model.result('pg4').run;
model.result('pg5').run;
model.result('pg6').run;
model.result('pg7').run;
model.result('pg8').run;
model.result('pg9').run;
model.result('pg10').run;
model.result('pg11').run;
model.result('pg12').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg14').run;
model.result('pg13').run;
model.result('pg14').run;
model.result('pg15').run;
model.result('pg16').run;
```

```
model.result('pg17').run;
model.result.dataset.create('cpt1', 'CutPoint3D');
model.result.dataset('cpt1').set('pointx', '0.025');
model.result.dataset('cpt1').set('pointy', '0.025');
model.result.dataset('cpt1').set('pointz', '0.025');
model.result.dataset('cpt1').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('data', 'cpt1');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('Baseline_solution_Time step_new therapy.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.variable('var1').set('Vo2max', '3700[ml/min]');
model.variable('var1').set('PA', '100[mmHg]');
model.variable('var1').set('Dlo2_1', 'Dmo2^-1+Deo2^-1');
model.variable('var1').set('SA', '130[m^2]');
model.variable('var1').set('SC', '115[m^2]');
model.variable('var1').set('Dmo2', 'Ko2*0.5*(SA+SC)/thb');
model.variable('var1').set('Ko2', '3.3e-8[cm^2/min/mmHg]');
model.variable('var1').set('thb', '1[um]');
model.variable('var1').set('Deo2', 'tho2*VC');
model.variable('var1').set('tho2', '1.8[ml/ml/min/mmHg]');
model.variable('var1').set('VC', '194[ml]');
model.variable('var1').set('Deo2', 'tho2*VC');
model.variable('var1').set('Pb', 'PA-Vo2max/Dlo2');
model.variable('var1').set('Dlo2', 'Dlo2_1^-1');
model.variable('var1').set('SPb', '((Pb/P50)^n)/(1+(Pb/P50)^n)');
model.variable('var1').set('n', '2.7');
model.variable('var1').set('P50', '26.3 [mmHg]');
model.variable('var1').rename('n', 'ni');
model.variable('var1').set('SPb', '((Pb/P50)^ni)/(1+(Pb/P50)^ni)');

model.sol('sol54').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Pb');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'mmHg');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'SPb');
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable.create('var7');
model.variable('var7').model('comp1');
model.variable('var7').label('Attachment rates for control case');
model.variable('var7').set('dd', '10 [ml/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_spleen', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_liver', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min]');
```

```
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Upper_body', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Torso', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_lung', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_intestin', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Lower_body', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_brain', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_kidney', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min]');
model.variable('var7').remove('dd');
model.variable.create('var8');
model.variable('var8').model('comp1');
model.variable('var8').label('Detachment rates for control case');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_spleen', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_liver', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_Upper_body', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_Torso', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_lung', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_intestin', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_Lower_body', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_brain', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_kidney', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable.create('var9');
model.variable('var9').model('comp1');
model.variable('var9').label('disinfection rate of free virus');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_lung', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_liver', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_spleen', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Upper_body', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Torso', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Intestine', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Lower_body', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Brain', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_kidney', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable.create('var10');
model.variable('var10').model('comp1');
model.variable('var10').label('disinfection rate of attached virus');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_lung', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_liver', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_spleen', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Upper_body', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Torso', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Intestine', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Lower_body', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Brain', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_kidney', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable.create('var11');
model.variable('var11').model('comp1');
model.variable('var11').label('Proliferation rate of activated (attached) virus');
model.variable('var11').set('p_liver', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_lung', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_spleen', '0.1 [1/d]');
```

```
model.variable('var11').set('p_Upper_body', ' 1.1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Torso', ' 2 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Intestine', ' 0.7 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Lower_body', ' 0.9 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Brain', ' 1.4 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_kidney', ' 1.1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_liver');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_lung');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_spleen');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_Upper_body');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_Torso');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_Intestine');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_Lower_body');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_Brain');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_kidney');
model.variable('var11').set('p_liver', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_lung', ' 1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_spleen', ' 0.1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Upper_body', ' 1.1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Torso', ' 2 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Intestine', ' 0.7 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Lower_body', ' 0.9 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Brain', ' 1.4 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_kidney', ' 1.1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Cardiac_vessels', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Cardiac_vessels', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Cardiac_vessels', '1.8 [1/d]');
model.variable.create('var12');
model.variable('var12').model('comp1');
model.variable('var12').label('Recirculated fraction');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_IL2_Ltumor', ' 1');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_kidney', ' 1');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_Cardiac_vessels', ' 1');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_LUpper_body', ' 0.018');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_LTorso', ' 0.018');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_Llung', ' 0.018');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_Lintestin', ' 0.018');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_Ltumor', ' 0.018');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_LLower_body', ' 0.018');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_Lbrain', ' 0.018');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_Lkidney', ' 0.018');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_aLUpper_body', ' 0.18');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_aLTorso', ' 0.18');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_aLlung', ' 0.18');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_aLintestin', ' 0.18');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_aLtumor', ' 0.18');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_aLLower_body', ' 0.18');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_aLbrain', ' 0.18');
model.variable('var12').set('rf_aLkidney', ' 0.18');
model.variable.create('var13');
```

```
model.variable('var13').model('comp1');
model.variable('var13').label('maximum rate of micro-thrombus generation');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_lung', ' 1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_liver', ' 1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_spleen', ' 1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Upper_body', ' 1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Torso', ' 1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Intestine', ' 1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Lower_body', ' 1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Brain', ' 1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_kidney', ' 1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Cardiac_vessels', ' 1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable.create('var14');
model.variable('var14').model('comp1');
model.variable('var14').label('Decay rate of micro-thrombus');
model.variable('var14').set('d_lung', ' 1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_liver', ' 1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_spleen', ' 1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Upper_body', ' 1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Torso', ' 1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Intestine', ' 1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Lower_body', ' 1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Brain', ' 1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_kidney', ' 1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Cardiac_vessels', ' 1 [1/d]');
model.variable.create('var15');
model.variable('var15').model('comp1');
model.variable('var15').label('%Blood flow rate');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_spleen', '138*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_liver', '800*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Upper_body', '138*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Torso', '220*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_intestin', '468*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_kidney', '630*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Lower_body', '413*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Cardiac_vessels', '120*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').remove('Q_spleen');
model.variable('var15').remove('Q_liver');
model.variable('var15').remove('Q_Upper_body');
model.variable('var15').remove('Q_Torso');
model.variable('var15').remove('Q_intestin');
model.variable('var15').remove('Q_kidney');
model.variable('var15').remove('Q_Lower_body');
model.variable('var15').remove('Q_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_spleen', '138*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_liver', '800*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Upper_body', '138*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Torso', '220*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_intestin', '468*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_kidney', '630*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Lower_body', '413*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
```

```
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Cardiac_vessels', '120*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_brain', '300*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable.create('var16');
model.variable('var16').model('comp1');
model.variable('var16').label('Lymph flow rate');
model.variable('var16').set('L_spleen', '8.7e-4*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_liver', '8.7e-2*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Upper_body', '2.6e-2*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Torso', '4.3e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_lung', '4.3e-2*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_intestin', '3e-1*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_kidney', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lower_body', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Cardiac_vessels', '4.3e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lspleen', '0 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lliver', '1.5e-6*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_LUpper_body', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_LTorso', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_LLung', '1.8e-6*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lintestin', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Ltumor', '1e-3*1.1*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_LLower_body', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_brain', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lkidney', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lbrain', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable.create('var17');
model.variable('var17').model('comp1');
model.variable('var17').label('Vascular volume');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_spleen', '17*1e-3 [L]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_liver', '180.9*1e-3 [L]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_Upper_body', '150*1e-3 [L]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_Torso', '462*1e-3 [L]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_lung', '99.9*1e-3 [L]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_intestin', '43*1e-3 [L]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_Lower_body', '700*1e-3 [L]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_brain', '150*1e-3 [L]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_kidney', '28.4*1e-3 [L]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_Cardiac_vessels', '100*1e-3 [L]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_ventricle', '200*1e-3 [L]');
model.variable.create('var18');
model.variable('var18').model('comp1');
model.variable('var18').label('just to develop');
model.variable('var18').set('freeTcell_traffickidney', '1');
model.variable('var18').set('freeTcell_trafficTorso', '1');
model.variable('var18').set('freeTcell_trafficspleen', '1');
model.variable('var18').set('freeTcell_trafficbrain', '1');
model.variable('var18').set('freeTcell_trafficLower_body', '1');
model.variable('var18').set('freeTcell_trafficintestine', '1');
model.variable('var18').set('freeTcell_trafficliver', '1');
model.variable('var18').set('freeTcell_trafficUpper_body', '1');
model.variable('var1').set('Ko2', '3.3e-8[cm^2/min/mmHg]*((ec/ec0)^8)');
```

```
model.variable.create('var19');
model.variable('var19').model('comp1');
model.variable('var19').set('Q_lung',
'L_lung+Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_
brain+Q_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode');
model.variable('var19').set('Q_tumor', '0');

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var19').set('Q_Lnode', '0');
model.variable('var19').set('L_tumor', '0');

model.physics.create('dode', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode', true);

model.physics('dode').label('free virus in Left ventricle, Arterial blood');
model.physics('dode').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((Q_lung-L_lung)*y(6)-
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney)', 0);
model.physics('dode').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((Q_lung-L_lung)*y(6)-
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q_
_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode)*y(5))/vv_ventricle', 0);
model.physics.remove('dode');

model.variable.create('var20');
model.variable('var20').model('comp1');
model.variable('var20').set('f5', '((Q_lung-L_lung)*y6-
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q_
_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode)*y5)/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var20').set('f78', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y(10)+(Q_liver-L_liver)*y14+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)*y(34)+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)*y(38)+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)*y(1)+(Q_Lnode/8-
L_LTorso)*y(42)+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)*y(46)+(Q_Upper_body-
L_Upper_body)*y22+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y(50)+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y(58)+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)*y(66)+(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y70+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y74+L_Cardiac_vessels*y(77)
*rf_Cardiac_vessels+(L_lung+L_Llung)*y(13)*rf_Llung+
(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y(37)*rf_Lintestin+(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*(rf_Ltumor*y
(41)*heaviside(-y(41)+500)+1*y(41)*heaviside(y(41)-501))+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)*y(45)
*rf_LTorso+(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y(49)*rf_LUpper_body+(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)
*y(53)*rf_LLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y(61)*rf_Lbrain+(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)*y(69)
*rf_Lkidney-(Q_lung)*y78)/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var20').set('f85', '((Q_lung-L_lung)*y105-
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q_
_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode)*y85)/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var20').set('f86', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y(106)+(Q_liver-L_liver)*y107+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)*y(112)+((Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)*y(113))+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)*y(104)+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_LTorso)*y(114)+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y110+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)*y(115)+
(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y109+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y(116)+(Q_Lower_body-
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L_Lower_body)*y117+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y(118)+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y119+(Q_Lnode/8-  
L_Lkidney)*y(120)+(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y121+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y124+  
(L_Cardiac_vessels*y125*rf_kidney)*heaviside(y125-1e-3*first)+(L_lung+L_Llung)*y(99)  
*rf_aLlung+(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y(101)*rf_aLintestin+(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)  
*y(80)*rf_aLtumor+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)*y(89)*rf_aLTorso+(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y(91)  
*rf_aLUpper_body+(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)*y(93)*rf_aLLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y  
(95)*rf_aLbrain+(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)*y(97)*rf_aLkidney-(Q_lung)*y86*heaviside(y86-1e-  
3*first))/vv_ventricle');  
model.variable('var20').set('f6', '(Q_lung*y78-(Q_lung-L_lung)*y6-  
ka_lung*y100*y6*vv_lung+kd_lung*y7*vv_lung-disinf_lung*y6*vv_lung)/vv_lung');  
model.variable('var20').set('f7', '(ka_lung*y100*y6*vv_lung-  
kd_lung*y7*vv_lung+p_lung/kk*y7*vv_lung-disinfa_lung*y7*vv_lung)/vv_lung');  
model.variable('var20').set('f105', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)*y105+mt_lung*ac*y7/  
(y100+1)*vv_lung-d_lung*y105*vv_lung)/vv_lung');  
model.variable('var20').set('f100', '-ka_lung*y100*y6+kd_lung*y7');  
model.variable('var20').set('f14', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30+(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y18+  
(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y5*freeTcell_trafficliver-(Q_liver-  
L_liver)*y14-ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver+kd_liver*y15*vv_liver-disinf_liver*y14*vv_liver)  
/vv_liver');  
model.variable('var20').set('f15', '(ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver-  
kd_liver*y15*vv_liver+p_liver/kk*y15*vv_liver-disinfa_liver*y15*vv_liver)/vv_liver;');  
model.variable('var20').set('f107', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y111+(Q_spleen-L_spleen)  
*y108+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y85-(Q_liver-L_liver)  
*y107+mt_liver*ac*y15/(y87+1)*vv_liver-d_liver*y107*vv_liver)/vv_liver');  
model.variable('var20').set('f87', '-ka_liver*y87*y14+kd_liver*y15');  
model.variable('var20').set('f18', '(Q_spleen*y5*freeTcell_traffic spleen-(Q_spleen-  
L_spleen)*y18-ka_spleen*y102*y18*vv_spleen+kd_spleen*y19*vv_spleen-  
disinf_spleen*y18*vv_spleen)/vv_spleen');  
model.variable('var20').set('f19', '(ka_spleen*y102*y18*vv_spleen-  
kd_spleen*y19*vv_spleen+p_spleen/kk*y19*vv_spleen-disinfa_spleen*y19*vv_spleen)  
/vv_spleen');  
model.variable('var20').set('f108', '(Q_spleen*y85-(Q_spleen-L_spleen)  
*y108+mt_spleen*ac*y19/(y102+1)*vv_spleen-d_spleen*y108*vv_spleen)/vv_spleen');  
model.variable('var20').set('f102', '-ka_spleen*y102*y18+kd_spleen*y19');  
model.variable('var20').set('f22', '(Q_Upper_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficUpper_body-  
(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y22-  
ka_Upper_body*y92*y22*vv_Upper_body+kd_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body-  
disinf_Upper_body*y22*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body');  
model.variable('var20').set('f23', '(ka_Upper_body*y92*y22*vv_Upper_body-  
kd_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body+p_Upper_body/kk*y23*vv_Upper_body-  
disinfa_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body');  
model.variable('var20').set('f109', '(Q_Upper_body*y85-(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)  
*y109+mt_Upper_body*ac*y23/(y92+1)*vv_Upper_body-d_Upper_body*y109*vv_Upper_body', '  
/vv_Upper_body');  
model.variable('var20').set('f92', '-ka_Upper_body*y92*y22+kd_Upper_body*y23');  
model.variable('var20').set('f26', '(Q_Torso*y5*freeTcell_trafficTorso-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)  
*y26-ka_Torso*y90*y26*vv_Torso+kd_Torso*y27*vv_Torso-disinf_Torso*y26*vv_Torso)  
/vv_Torso');  
model.variable('var20').set('f27', '(ka_Torso*y90*y26*vv_Torso-  
kd_Torso*y27*vv_Torso+p_Torso/kk*y27*vv_Torso-disinfa_Torso*y27*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso');  
model.variable('var20').set('f110', '(Q_Torso*y85-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y110+mt_Torso*ac*y27/
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(y90+1)*vv_Torso-d_Torso*y110*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso');
model.variable('var20').set('f90', '-ka_Torso*y90*y26+kd_Torso*y27');
model.variable('var20').set('f30', '(Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30-ka_intestin*y103*y30*vv_intestin+kd_intestin*y31*vv_intestin-
disinf_Intestine*y30*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin');
model.variable('var20').set('f31', '(ka_intestin*y103*y30*vv_intestin-
kd_intestin*y31*vv_intestin+p_Intestine/kk*y31*vv_intestin-
disinfa_Intestine*y31*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin');
model.variable('var20').set('f111', '(Q_intestin*y85-(Q_intestin-L_intestin)
*y111+mt_Intestine*ac*y31/(y103+1)*vv_intestin', '-d_Intestine*y111*vv_intestin)
/vv_intestin');
model.variable('var20').set('f103', '-ka_intestin*y103*y30+kd_intestin*y31');
model.variable('var20').set('f54', '(Q_Lower_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficLower_body-
(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54-
ka_Lower_body*y94*y54*vv_Lower_body+kd_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body-
disinf_Lower_body*y54*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.variable('var20').set('f55', '(ka_Lower_body*y94*y54*vv_Lower_body-
kd_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body+p_Lower_body/kk*y55*vv_Lower_body-
disinfa_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.variable('var20').set('f117', '(Q_Lower_body*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_Lower_body-
L_Lower_body)*y117*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Lower_body*ac*y55/(y94+1)*vv_Lower_body', '-
d_Lower_body*y117*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.variable('var20').set('f94', '-ka_Lower_body*y94*y54+kd_Lower_body*y55');
model.variable('var20').set('f62', '(Q_brain*y5*freeTcell_trafficbrain-(Q_brain-L_brain)
*y62-ka_brain*y96*y62*vv_brain+kd_brain*y63*vv_brain-disinf_Brain*y62*vv_brain)
/vv_brain');
model.variable('var20').set('f63', '(ka_brain*y96*y62*vv_brain-
kd_brain*y63*vv_brain+p_Brain/kk*y63*vv_brain-disinfa_Brain*y63*vv_brain)/vv_brain');
model.variable('var20').set('f119', '(Q_brain*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_brain-L_brain)
*y119*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Brain*ac*y63/(y96+1)*vv_brain', '-d_Brain*y119*vv_brain)
/vv_brain');
model.variable('var20').set('f96', '-ka_brain*y96*y62+kd_brain*y63');
model.variable('var20').set('f70', '(Q_kidney*y5*freeTcell_traffickidney-(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y70-ka_kidney*y98*y70*vv_kidney+kd_kidney*y71*vv_kidney-
disinf_kidney*y70*vv_kidney)/vv_kidney');
model.variable('var20').set('f71', '(ka_kidney*y98*y70*vv_kidney-
kd_kidney*y71*vv_kidney+p_kidney/kk*y71*vv_kidney-disinfa_kidney*y71*vv_kidney)
/vv_kidney');
model.variable('var20').set('f121', '(Q_kidney*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_kidney-L_kidney)
*y121*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_kidney*ac*y71/(y98+1)*vv_kidney-d_kidney*y121*vv_kidney)
/vv_kidney');
model.variable('var20').set('f98', '-ka_kidney*y98*y70+kd_kidney*y71');
model.variable('var20').set('f74', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y5-(Q_Cardiac_vessels-
L_Cardiac_vessels)*y74-
ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels+kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
disinf_Cardiac_vessels*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var20').set('f75', '(ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels+p_Cardiac_vessels/kk*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
disinfa_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var20').set('f124', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-
(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y124*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Cardiac_vessels*ac*y75/
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(y125+1)*vv_Cardiac_vessels-d_Cardiac_vessels*y124*vv_Cardiac_vessels)↵
/vv_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var20').set('f125', '-↵
ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74+kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75');
model.variable('var20').set('f15', '(ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver-↵
kd_liver*y15*vv_liver+p_liver/kk*y15*vv_liver-disinfa_liver*y15*vv_liver)/vv_liver');
model.variable('var20').descr('f109', '');
model.variable('var20').set('f109', '(Q_Upper_body*y85-(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)↵
*y109+mt_Upper_body*ac*y23/(y92+1)*vv_Upper_body-d_Upper_body*y109*vv_Upper_body)↵
/vv_Upper_body');
model.variable('var20').descr('f111', '');
model.variable('var20').set('f111', '(Q_intestin*y85-(Q_intestin-L_intestin)↵
*y111+mt_Intestine*ac*y31/(y103+1)*vv_intestin-d_Intestine*y111*vv_intestin)↵
/vv_intestin');
model.variable('var20').set('f117', '(Q_Lower_body*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_Lower_body-↵
L_Lower_body)*y117*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Lower_body*ac*y55/(y94+1)*vv_Lower_body-↵
d_Lower_body*y117*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.variable('var20').descr('f117', '');
model.variable('var20').descr('f119', '');
model.variable('var20').set('f119', '(Q_brain*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_brain-L_brain)↵
*y119*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Brain*ac*y63/(y96+1)*vv_brain-d_Brain*y119*vv_brain)/vv_brain');

model.physics.create('dode', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode', true);

model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode').field('dimensionless').field('y5');
model.physics('dode').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y5');
model.physics('dode').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f5', 0);
model.physics.create('dode2', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode2', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode2', true);

model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode2').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode2').field('dimensionless').field('y78');
model.physics('dode2').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y78');
model.physics('dode2').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f78', 0);
model.physics.create('dode3', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode3', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode3', true);
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model.physics('dode3').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode3').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode3').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode3').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode3').field('dimensionless').field('y85');
model.physics('dode3').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y85');
model.physics('dode3').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f85', 0);
model.physics.create('dode4', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode4', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode4', true);

model.physics('dode4').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode4').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode4').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode4').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode4').field('dimensionless').field('y86');
model.physics('dode4').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y86');
model.physics('dode4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f86', 0);
model.physics.create('dode5', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode5', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode5', true);

model.physics('dode5').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode5').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode5').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode5').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode5').field('dimensionless').field('y6');
model.physics('dode5').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y6');
model.physics('dode5').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f6', 0);
model.physics.create('dode6', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode6', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode6', true);

model.physics('dode6').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode6').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode6').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode6').field('dimensionless').field('y7');
model.physics('dode6').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y7');
model.physics('dode6').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f7', 0);
model.physics.create('dode7', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode7', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode7', true);

model.physics('dode7').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode7').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode7').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
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model.physics('dode7').field('dimensionless').field('y105');
model.physics('dode7').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y105');
model.physics('dode7').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode7').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f105', 0);
model.physics.create('dode8', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode8', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode8', true);

model.physics('dode8').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode8').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode8').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode8').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode8').field('dimensionless').field('y100');
model.physics('dode8').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y100');
model.physics('dode8').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f100', 0);

model.variable('var19').set('ac', '1');
model.variable('var19').set('kk', '1');

model.physics.create('dode9', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode9', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode9', true);

model.physics('dode9').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode9').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode9').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode9').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode9').field('dimensionless').field('y14');
model.physics('dode9').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y14');
model.physics('dode9').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f14', 0);
model.physics.create('dode10', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode10', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode10', true);

model.physics('dode10').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode10').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode10').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode10').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode10').field('dimensionless').field('y15');
model.physics('dode10').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y15');
model.physics('dode10').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f15', 0);
model.physics.create('dode11', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode11', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode11', true);

model.physics('dode11').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode11').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
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model.physics('dode11').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode11').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode11').field('dimensionless').field('y107');
model.physics('dode11').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y107');
model.physics('dode11').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f107', 0);
model.physics.create('dode12', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode12', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode12', true);

model.physics('dode12').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode12').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode12').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode12').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode12').field('dimensionless').field('y87');
model.physics('dode12').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y87');
model.physics('dode12').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f87', 0);
model.physics.create('dode13', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode13', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode13', true);

model.physics('dode13').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode13').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode13').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode13').field('dimensionless').field('y18');
model.physics('dode13').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y18');
model.physics('dode13').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode13').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f18', 0);
model.physics.create('dode14', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode14', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode14', true);

model.physics('dode14').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode14').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode14').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode14').field('dimensionless').field('y19');
model.physics('dode14').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y19');
model.physics('dode14').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f19', 0);
model.physics('dode14').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics.create('dode15', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode15', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode15', true);

model.physics('dode15').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode15').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode15').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode15').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode15').field('dimensionless').field('y19');
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model.physics('dode15').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f19', 0);
model.physics('dode15').field('dimensionless').field('y108');
model.physics('dode15').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f108', 0);
model.physics.create('dode16', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode16', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode16', true);

model.physics('dode16').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode16').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode16').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode16').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode16').field('dimensionless').field('y102');
model.physics('dode16').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y102');
model.physics('dode16').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f102', 0);
model.physics.create('dode17', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode17', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode17', true);

model.physics('dode17').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode17').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode17').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode17').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode17').field('dimensionless').field('y22');
model.physics('dode17').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y22');
model.physics('dode17').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f22', 0);
model.physics.create('dode18', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode18', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode18', true);

model.physics('dode18').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode18').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode18').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode18').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode18').field('dimensionless').field('y23');
model.physics('dode18').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y23');
model.physics('dode18').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f23', 0);
model.physics.create('dode19', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode19', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode19', true);

model.physics('dode19').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode19').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode19').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode19').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y109');
model.physics('dode19').field('dimensionless').field('y109');
model.physics('dode19').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f109', 0);
model.physics.create('dode20', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u37'});
```

```
model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode20', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode20', true);

model.physics('dode20').field('dimensionless').field('u37');
model.physics('dode20').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode20').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode20').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode20').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode20').field('dimensionless').field('y92');
model.physics('dode20').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y92');
model.physics('dode20').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f92', 0);
model.physics.create('dode21', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode21', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode21', true);

model.physics('dode21').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode21').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode21').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode21').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode21').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y26');
model.physics('dode21').field('dimensionless').field('u36');
model.physics('dode21').field('dimensionless').field('y26');
model.physics('dode21').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f26', 0);
model.physics.create('dode22', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u37'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode22', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode22', true);

model.physics('dode22').field('dimensionless').field('u37');
model.physics('dode22').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode22').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode22').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode22').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode22').field('dimensionless').field('y27');
model.physics('dode22').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y27');
model.physics('dode22').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f27', 0);
model.physics.create('dode23', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode23', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode23', true);

model.physics('dode23').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode23').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode23').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode23').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode23').field('dimensionless').field('Y110');
model.physics('dode23').field('dimensionless').field('y110');
model.physics('dode23').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y110');
model.physics('dode23').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f110', 0);
```

```
model.physics.create('dode24', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode24', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode24', true);

model.physics('dode24').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode24').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode24').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode24').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode24').field('dimensionless').field('y90');
model.physics('dode24').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y90');
model.physics('dode24').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f90', 0);
model.physics.create('dode25', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode25', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode25', true);

model.physics('dode25').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode25').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode25').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode25').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode25').field('dimensionless').field('y30');
model.physics('dode25').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y30');
model.physics('dode25').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f30', 0);
model.physics.create('dode26', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode26', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode26', true);

model.physics('dode26').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode26').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode26').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode26').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode26').field('dimensionless').field('y31');
model.physics('dode26').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y31');
model.physics('dode26').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f31', 0);
model.physics.create('dode27', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode27', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode27', true);

model.physics('dode27').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode27').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode27').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode27').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode27').field('dimensionless').field('y111');
model.physics('dode27').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y111');
model.physics('dode27').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f111', 0);
model.physics.create('dode28', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode28', true);
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model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode28', true);

model.physics('dode28').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode28').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode28').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode28').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode28').field('dimensionless').field('y103');
model.physics('dode28').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y103');
model.physics('dode28').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f103', 0);
model.physics.create('dode29', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode29', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode29', true);

model.physics('dode29').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode29').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode29').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode29').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode29').field('dimensionless').field('y54');
model.physics('dode29').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y54');
model.physics('dode29').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f54', 0);
model.physics.create('dode30', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode30', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode30', true);

model.physics('dode30').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode30').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode30').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode30').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode30').field('dimensionless').field('y55');
model.physics('dode30').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y55');
model.physics('dode30').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f55', 0);
model.physics.create('dode31', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode31', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode31', true);

model.physics('dode31').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode31').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode31').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode31').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode31').field('dimensionless').field('y117');
model.physics('dode31').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y117');
model.physics('dode31').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f117', 0);
model.physics.create('dode32', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode32', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode32', true);

model.physics('dode32').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
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model.physics('dode32').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode32').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode32').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode32').field('dimensionless').field('y94');
model.physics('dode32').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y94');
model.physics('dode32').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f94', 0);
model.physics.create('dode33', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode33', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode33', true);

model.physics('dode33').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode33').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode33').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode33').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode33').field('dimensionless').field('y6');
model.physics('dode33').field('dimensionless').field('y62');
model.physics('dode33').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f62', 0);
model.physics.create('dode34', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode34', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode34', true);

model.physics('dode34').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode34').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode34').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode34').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode34').field('dimensionless').field('y63');
model.physics('dode34').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y63');
model.physics('dode34').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f63', 0);
model.physics.create('dode35', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode35', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode35', true);

model.physics('dode35').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode35').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode35').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode35').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode35').field('dimensionless').field('y119');
model.physics('dode35').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y1198');
model.physics('dode35').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y119');
model.physics('dode35').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f119', 0);
model.physics.create('dode36', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode36', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode36', true);

model.physics('dode36').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode36').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode36').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
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model.physics('dode36').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode36').field('dimensionless').field('y96');
model.physics('dode36').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y96');
model.physics('dode36').field('dimensionless').field('y70');
model.physics('dode36').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y70');
model.physics('dode36').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f70', 0);
model.physics.create('dode37', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode37', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode37', true);

model.physics('dode37').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode37').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode37').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode37').field('dimensionless').field('y71');
model.physics('dode37').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y71');
model.physics('dode37').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f71', 0);
model.physics.create('dode38', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode38', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode38', true);

model.physics('dode38').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode38').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode38').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode38').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode38').field('dimensionless').field('y121');
model.physics('dode38').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y121');
model.physics('dode38').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f121', 0);
model.physics.create('dode39', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode39', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode39', true);

model.physics('dode39').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode39').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode39').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode39').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode39').field('dimensionless').field('y98');
model.physics('dode39').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y98');
model.physics('dode39').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f98', 0);
model.physics.create('dode40', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode40', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode40', true);

model.physics('dode40').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode40').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode40').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode40').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode40').field('dimensionless').field('y74');
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model.physics('dode40').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y74');
model.physics('dode40').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f74', 0);
model.physics.create('dode41', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode41', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode41', true);

model.physics('dode41').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode41').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode41').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode41').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode41').field('dimensionless').field('y75');
model.physics('dode41').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y75');
model.physics('dode41').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f75', 0);
model.physics.create('dode42', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode42', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode42', true);

model.physics('dode42').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode42').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode42').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode42').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode42').field('dimensionless').field('y124');
model.physics('dode42').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y124');
model.physics('dode42').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f124', 0);
model.physics.create('dode43', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode43', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode43', true);

model.physics('dode43').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode43').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode43').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
model.physics('dode43').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode43').field('dimensionless').field('y125');
model.physics('dode43').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y125');
model.physics('dode43').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f125', 0);

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var20').set('aaa', 'y125-1e-3*first');
model.variable('var20').remove('aaa');
model.variable('var20').remove('f125');
model.variable.remove('var20');
model.variable.create('var20');
model.variable('var20').model('comp1');
model.variable('var20').set('f5', '(Q_lung-L_lung)*y6-
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q
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_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode)*y5)/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var20').set('f78', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*
(Q_liver-L_liver)*y14+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)* y34+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)* y38+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)* y1+(Q_Lnode/8-
L_LTorso)* y42+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)* y46+(Q_Upper_body-
L_Upper_body)*y22+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y50+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y58+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)*y66+(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y70+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)
*y74+L_Cardiac_vessels*y77*rf_Cardiac_vessels+(L_lung+L_Llung)*y13*rf_Llung+
(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y37*rf_Lintestin+(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*
(rf_Ltumor*y41*heaviside(-y41+500)+1*y41*heaviside(y41-501))+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)
*y45*rf_LTorso+(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y49*rf_LUpper_body+
(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)*y53*rf_LLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y61*rf_Lbrain+
(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)*y69*rf_Lkidney-(Q_lung)*y78)/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var20').set('f85', '((Q_lung-L_lung)*y105-
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q
_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode)*y85)/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var20').set('f86', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y106+(Q_liver-L_liver)*y107+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)*y112+((Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)*y113)+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)*y104+(Q_Lnode/8-
L_LTorso)*y114+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y110+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)*y115+(Q_Upper_body-
L_Upper_body)*y109+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y116+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y117+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y118+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y119+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)*y120+(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y121+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y124+
(L_Cardiac_vessels*y125*rf_kidney)*heaviside(y125-1e-3*first)+(L_lung+L_Llung)
*y99*rf_aLlung+(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y101*rf_aLintestin+
(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*y80*rf_aLtumor+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)*y89*rf_aLTorso+
(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y91*rf_aLUpper_body+(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)
*y93*rf_aLLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y95*rf_aLbrain+(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)
*y97*rf_aLkidney-(Q_lung)*y86*heaviside(y86-1e-3*first))/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var20').set('f6', '(Q_lung*y78-(Q_lung-L_lung)*y6-
ka_lung*y100*y6*vv_lung+kd_lung*y7*vv_lung-disinf_lung*y6*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.variable('var20').set('f7', '(ka_lung*y100*y6*vv_lung-
kd_lung*y7*vv_lung+p_lung/kk*y7*vv_lung-disinfa_lung*y7*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.variable('var20').set('f105', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)*y105+mt_lung*ac*y7/
(y100+1)*vv_lung-d_lung*y105*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.variable('var20').set('f100', '-ka_lung*y100*y6+kd_lung*y7');
model.variable('var20').set('f14', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30+(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y18+
(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y5*freeTcell_trafficliver-(Q_liver-
L_liver)*y14-ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver+kd_liver*y15*vv_liver-disinf_liver*y14*vv_liver)
/vv_liver');
model.variable('var20').set('f15', '(ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver-
kd_liver*y15*vv_liver+p_liver/kk*y15*vv_liver-disinfa_liver*y15*vv_liver)/vv_liver');
model.variable('var20').set('f107', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y111+(Q_spleen-L_spleen)
*y108+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y85-(Q_liver-L_liver)
*y107+mt_liver*ac*y15/(y87+1)*vv_liver-d_liver*y107*vv_liver)/vv_liver');
model.variable('var20').set('f87', '-ka_liver*y87*y14+kd_liver*y15');
model.variable('var20').set('f18', '(Q_spleen*y5*freeTcell_trafficspleen-(Q_spleen-
L_spleen)*y18-ka_spleen*y102*y18*vv_spleen+kd_spleen*y19*vv_spleen-
disinf_spleen*y18*vv_spleen)/vv_spleen');
model.variable('var20').set('f19', '(ka_spleen*y102*y18*vv_spleen-
kd_spleen*y19*vv_spleen+p_spleen/kk*y19*vv_spleen-disinfa_spleen*y19*vv_spleen)
/vv_spleen');
```

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model.variable('var20').set('f108', '(Q_spleen*y85-(Q_spleen-L_spleen)
*y108+mt_spleen*ac*y19/(y102+1)*vv_spleen-d_spleen*y108*vv_spleen)/vv_spleen');
model.variable('var20').set('f102', '-ka_spleen*y102*y18+kd_spleen*y19');
model.variable('var20').set('f22', '(Q_Upper_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficUpper_body-
(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y22-
ka_Upper_body*y92*y22*vv_Upper_body+kd_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body-
disinf_Upper_body*y22*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body');
model.variable('var20').set('f23', '(ka_Upper_body*y92*y22*vv_Upper_body-
kd_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body+p_Upper_body/kk*y23*vv_Upper_body-
disinfa_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body');
model.variable('var20').set('f109', '(Q_Upper_body*y85-(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)
*y109+mt_Upper_body*ac*y23/(y92+1)*vv_Upper_body-d_Upper_body*y109*vv_Upper_body)
/vv_Upper_body');
model.variable('var20').set('f92', '-ka_Upper_body*y92*y22+kd_Upper_body*y23');
model.variable('var20').set('f26', '(Q_Torso*y5*freeTcell_trafficTorso-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)
*y26-ka_Torso*y90*y26*vv_Torso+kd_Torso*y27*vv_Torso-disinf_Torso*y26*vv_Torso)
/vv_Torso');
model.variable('var20').set('f27', '(ka_Torso*y90*y26*vv_Torso-
kd_Torso*y27*vv_Torso+p_Torso/kk*y27*vv_Torso-disinfa_Torso*y27*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso');
model.variable('var20').set('f110', '(Q_Torso*y85-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y110+mt_Torso*ac*y27/
(y90+1)*vv_Torso-d_Torso*y110*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso');
model.variable('var20').set('f90', '-ka_Torso*y90*y26+kd_Torso*y27');
model.variable('var20').set('f30', '(Q_intestin*y5*freeTcell_trafficintestine-
(Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30-ka_intestin*y103*y30*vv_intestin+kd_intestin*y31*vv_intestin-
disinf_Intestine*y30*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin');
model.variable('var20').set('f31', '(ka_intestin*y103*y30*vv_intestin-
kd_intestin*y31*vv_intestin+p_Intestine/kk*y31*vv_intestin-
disinfa_Intestine*y31*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin');
model.variable('var20').set('f111', '(Q_intestin*y85-(Q_intestin-L_intestin)
*y111+mt_Intestine*ac*y31/(y103+1)*vv_intestin', '-d_Intestine*y111*vv_intestin)
/vv_intestin');
model.variable('var20').set('f103', '-ka_intestin*y103*y30+kd_intestin*y31');
model.variable('var20').set('f54', '(Q_Lower_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficLower_body-
(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54-
ka_Lower_body*y94*y54*vv_Lower_body+kd_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body-
disinf_Lower_body*y54*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.variable('var20').set('f55', '(ka_Lower_body*y94*y54*vv_Lower_body-
kd_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body+p_Lower_body/kk*y55*vv_Lower_body-
disinfa_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.variable('var20').set('f117', '(Q_Lower_body*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_Lower_body-
L_Lower_body)*y117*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Lower_body*ac*y55/(y94+1)*vv_Lower_body', '-
d_Lower_body*y117*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.variable('var20').set('f94', '-ka_Lower_body*y94*y54+kd_Lower_body*y55');
model.variable('var20').set('f62', '(Q_brain*y5*freeTcell_trafficbrain-(Q_brain-L_brain)
*y62-ka_brain*y96*y62*vv_brain+kd_brain*y63*vv_brain-disinf_Brain*y62*vv_brain)
/vv_brain');
model.variable('var20').set('f63', '(ka_brain*y96*y62*vv_brain-
kd_brain*y63*vv_brain+p_Brain/kk*y63*vv_brain-disinfa_Brain*y63*vv_brain)/vv_brain');
model.variable('var20').set('f119', '(Q_brain*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_brain-L_brain)
*y119*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Brain*ac*y63/(y96+1)*vv_brain', '-d_Brain*y119*vv_brain)
/vv_brain');
```

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model.variable('var20').set('f96', '-ka_brain*y96*y62+kd_brain*y63');
model.variable('var20').set('f70', '(Q_kidney*y5*freeTcell_traffickidney-(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y70-ka_kidney*y98*y70*vv_kidney+kd_kidney*y71*vv_kidney-
disinf_kidney*y70*vv_kidney)/vv_kidney');
model.variable('var20').set('f71', '(ka_kidney*y98*y70*vv_kidney-
kd_kidney*y71*vv_kidney+p_kidney/kk*y71*vv_kidney-disinfa_kidney*y71*vv_kidney)
/vv_kidney');
model.variable('var20').set('f121', '(Q_kidney*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_kidney-L_kidney)
*y121*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_kidney*ac*y71/(y98+1)*vv_kidney-d_kidney*y121*vv_kidney)
/vv_kidney');
model.variable('var20').set('f98', '-ka_kidney*y98*y70+kd_kidney*y71');
model.variable('var20').set('f74', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y5-(Q_Cardiac_vessels-
L_Cardiac_vessels)*y74-
ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels+kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
disinf_Cardiac_vessels*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var20').set('f75', '(ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels+p_Cardiac_vessels/kk*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
disinfa_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var20').set('f124', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-
(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y124*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Cardiac_vessels*ac*y75/
(y125+1)*vv_Cardiac_vessels-d_Cardiac_vessels*y124*vv_Cardiac_vessels)
/vv_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var20').set('f125', '-
ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74+kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75');
model.variable('var20').descr('f78', '');
model.variable('var20').set('f78', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y10+(Q_liver-L_liver)*y14+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)* y34+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)* y38+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)* y1+(Q_Lnode/8-
L_LTorso)* y42+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)* y46+(Q_Upper_body-
L_Upper_body)*y22+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y50+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y58+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)*y66+(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y70+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)
*y74+L_Cardiac_vessels*y77*rf_Cardiac_vessels+(L_lung+L_Llung)*y13*rf_Llung+
(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y37*rf_Lintestin+(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*
(rf_Ltumor*y41*heaviside(-y41+500)+1*y41*heaviside(y41-500))+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)
*y45*rf_LTorso+(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y49*rf_LUpper_body+
(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)*y53*rf_LLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y61*rf_Lbrain+
(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)*y69*rf_Lkidney-(Q_lung)*y78)/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var20').set('f15', '(ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver-
kd_liver*y15*vv_liver+p_liver/kk*y15*vv_liver-disinfa_liver*y15*vv_liver)/vv_liver');
model.variable('var20').descr('f111', '');
model.variable('var20').set('f111', '(Q_intestin*y85-(Q_intestin-L_intestin)
*y111+mt_Intestine*ac*y31/(y103+1)*vv_intestin-d_Intestine*y111*vv_intestin)
/vv_intestin');
model.variable('var20').descr('f117', '');
model.variable('var20').set('f117', '(Q_Lower_body*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_Lower_body-
L_Lower_body)*y117*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Lower_body*ac*y55/(y94+1)*vv_Lower_body-
d_Lower_body*y117*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.variable('var20').descr('f119', '');
model.variable('var20').set('f119', '(Q_brain*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_brain-L_brain)
*y119*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Brain*ac*y63/(y96+1)*vv_brain-d_Brain*y119*vv_brain)/vv_brain');
model.variable.create('var21');
```

```
model.variable('var21').model('comp1');
model.variable('var21').label('zero');
model.variable('var21').set('y10', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y34', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y38', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y1', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y42', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y46', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y50', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y58', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y66', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y77', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y13', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y37', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y41', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y45', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y49', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y53', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y61', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y69', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y106', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y112', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y113', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y104', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y114', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y115', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y116', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y118', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y120', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y99', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y101', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y80', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y89', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y91', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y93', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y95', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y97', '0');

model.physics('dode5').feature('init1').set('y6', '1');
model.physics('dode8').feature('init1').set('y100', '1');
model.physics('dode12').feature('init1').set('y87', '1');
model.physics('dode43').feature('init1').set('y125', '1');
model.physics('dode39').feature('init1').set('y98', '1');
model.physics.create('dode44', 'DomainODE', 'geom1', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode44', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode44', true);

model.physics('dode44').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.physics('dode44').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'mol/L');
model.physics('dode44').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'mol/L/min');
```

```
model.physics('dode44').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode44').field('dimensionless').field('y96');
model.physics('dode44').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y96');
model.physics('dode44').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f96', 0);
model.physics('dode44').feature('init1').set('y96', '1');
model.physics('dode32').feature('init1').set('y94', '1');
model.physics('dode28').feature('init1').set('y103', '1');
model.physics('dode24').feature('init1').set('y90', '1');
model.physics('dode20').feature('init1').set('y92', '1');
model.physics('dode16').feature('init1').set('y102', '1');

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.physics('dode19').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');
model.physics('dode37').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');

model.label('Baseline_solution_Time step_new therapy_oxygen_flow.mph');

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var15').label('Blood flow rate');
model.variable('var21').set('heaviside', '0');
model.variable('var21').remove('heaviside');
model.variable('var20').remove('f5');
model.variable('var20').remove('f78');
model.variable('var20').remove('f85');
model.variable('var20').remove('f86');
model.variable('var20').remove('f6');
model.variable('var20').remove('f7');
model.variable('var20').remove('f105');
model.variable.remove('var20');
model.variable.create('var22');
model.variable('var22').model('comp1');
model.variable('var22').set('f5', '((Q_lung-L_lung)*y6-
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q
_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode)*y5)/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var22').set('f78', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y10+(Q_liver-L_liver)*y14+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)* y34+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)* y38+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)* y1+(Q_Lnode/8-
L_LTorso)* y42+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)* y46+(Q_Upper_body-
L_Upper_body)*y22+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y50+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y58+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)*y66+(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y70+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)
*y74+L_Cardiac_vessels*y77*rf_Cardiac_vessels+(L_lung+L_Llung)*y13*rf_Llung+
(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y37*rf_Lintestin+(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*
(rf_Ltumor*y41*1(-y41+500)+1*y41*1(y41-501))+L_Torso+L_LTorso)*y45*rf_LTorso+
(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y49*rf_LUpper_body+(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)
*y53*rf_LLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y61*rf_Lbrain+(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)*y69*rf_Lkidney-
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(Q_lung)*y78)/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var22').set('f85', '((Q_lung-L_lung)*y105-
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q
_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode)*y85)/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var22').set('f86', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y106+(Q_liver-L_liver)*y107+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)*y112+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)*y113)+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)*y104+(Q_Lnode/8-
L_LTorso)*y114+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y110+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)*y115+(Q_Upper_body-
L_Upper_body)*y109+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y116+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y117+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y118+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y119+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)*y120+(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y121+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y124+
(L_Cardiac_vessels*y125*rf_kidney)*1*(y125-1e-3*first)+(L_lung+L_Llung)*y99*rf_aLlung+
(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y101*rf_aLintestin+(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)
*y80*rf_aLtumor+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)*y89*rf_aLTorso+(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)
*y91*rf_aLUpper_body+(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)*y93*rf_aLLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)
*y95*rf_aLbrain+(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)*y97*rf_aLkidney-(Q_lung)*y86*1*(y86-1e-3*first)
/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var22').set('f6', '(Q_lung*y78-(Q_lung-L_lung)*y6-
ka_lung*y100*y6*vv_lung+kd_lung*y7*vv_lung-disinf_lung*y6*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.variable('var22').set('f7', '(ka_lung*y100*y6*vv_lung-
kd_lung*y7*vv_lung+p_lung/kk*y7*vv_lung-disinfa_lung*y7*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.variable('var22').set('f105', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)*y105+mt_lung*ac*y7/
(y100+1)*vv_lung-d_lung*y105*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.variable('var22').set('f100', '-ka_lung*y100*y6+kd_lung*y7');
model.variable('var22').set('f14', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30+(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y18+
(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y5*freeTcell_trafficliver-(Q_liver-
L_liver)*y14-ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver+kd_liver*y15*vv_liver-disinf_liver*y14*vv_liver)
/vv_liver');
model.variable('var22').set('f15', '(ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver-
kd_liver*y15*vv_liver+p_liver/kk*y15*vv_liver-disinfa_liver*y15*vv_liver)/vv_liver');
model.variable('var22').set('f107', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y111+(Q_spleen-L_spleen)
*y108+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y85-(Q_liver-L_liver)
*y107+mt_liver*ac*y15/(y87+1)*vv_liver-d_liver*y107*vv_liver)/vv_liver');
model.variable('var22').set('f87', '-ka_liver*y87*y14+kd_liver*y15');
model.variable('var22').set('f18', '(Q_spleen*y5*freeTcell_traffic spleen-(Q_spleen-
L_spleen)*y18-ka_spleen*y102*y18*vv_spleen+kd_spleen*y19*vv_spleen-
disinf_spleen*y18*vv_spleen)/vv_spleen');
model.variable('var22').set('f19', '(ka_spleen*y102*y18*vv_spleen-
kd_spleen*y19*vv_spleen+p_spleen/kk*y19*vv_spleen-disinfa_spleen*y19*vv_spleen)
/vv_spleen');
model.variable('var22').set('f108', '(Q_spleen*y85-(Q_spleen-L_spleen)
*y108+mt_spleen*ac*y19/(y102+1)*vv_spleen-d_spleen*y108*vv_spleen)/vv_spleen');
model.variable('var22').set('f102', '-ka_spleen*y102*y18+kd_spleen*y19');
model.variable('var22').set('f22', '(Q_Upper_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficUpper_body-
(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y22-
ka_Upper_body*y92*y22*vv_Upper_body+kd_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body-
disinf_Upper_body*y22*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body');
model.variable('var22').set('f23', '(ka_Upper_body*y92*y22*vv_Upper_body-
kd_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body+p_Upper_body/kk*y23*vv_Upper_body-
disinfa_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body');
model.variable('var22').set('f109', '(Q_Upper_body*y85-(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)
*y109+mt_Upper_body*ac*y23/(y92+1)*vv_Upper_body-d_Upper_body*y109*vv_Upper_body)
/vv_Upper_body');
```

```
/vv_Upper_body');
model.variable('var22').set('f92', '-ka_Upper_body*y92*y22+kd_Upper_body*y23');
model.variable('var22').set('f26', '(Q_Torso*y5*freeTcell_trafficTorso-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)
*y26-ka_Torso*y90*y26*vv_Torso+kd_Torso*y27*vv_Torso-disinf_Torso*y26*vv_Torso)
/vv_Torso');
model.variable('var22').set('f27', '(ka_Torso*y90*y26*vv_Torso-
kd_Torso*y27*vv_Torso+p_Torso/kk*y27*vv_Torso-disinfa_Torso*y27*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso');
model.variable('var22').set('f110', '(Q_Torso*y85-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y110+mt_Torso*ac*y27/
(y90+1)*vv_Torso-d_Torso*y110*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso');
model.variable('var22').set('f90', '-ka_Torso*y90*y26+kd_Torso*y27');
model.variable('var22').set('f30', '(Q_intestin*y5*freeTcell_trafficintestine-
(Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30-ka_intestin*y103*y30*vv_intestin+kd_intestin*y31*vv_intestin-
disinf_Intestine*y30*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin');
model.variable('var22').set('f31', '(ka_intestin*y103*y30*vv_intestin-
kd_intestin*y31*vv_intestin+p_Intestine/kk*y31*vv_intestin-
disinfa_Intestine*y31*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin');
model.variable('var22').set('f111', '(Q_intestin*y85-(Q_intestin-L_intestin)
*y111+mt_Intestine*ac*y31/(y103+1)*vv_intestin-d_Intestine*y111*vv_intestin)
/vv_intestin');
model.variable('var22').set('f103', '-ka_intestin*y103*y30+kd_intestin*y31');
model.variable('var22').set('f54', '(Q_Lower_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficLower_body-
(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54-
ka_Lower_body*y94*y54*vv_Lower_body+kd_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body-
disinf_Lower_body*y54*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.variable('var22').set('f55', '(ka_Lower_body*y94*y54*vv_Lower_body-
kd_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body+p_Lower_body/kk*y55*vv_Lower_body-
disinfa_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.variable('var22').set('f117', '(Q_Lower_body*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_Lower_body-
L_Lower_body)*y117*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Lower_body*ac*y55/(y94+1)*vv_Lower_body-
d_Lower_body*y117*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.variable('var22').set('f94', '-ka_Lower_body*y94*y54+kd_Lower_body*y55');
model.variable('var22').set('f62', '(Q_brain*y5*freeTcell_trafficbrain-(Q_brain-L_brain)
*y62-ka_brain*y96*y62*vv_brain+kd_brain*y63*vv_brain-disinf_Brain*y62*vv_brain)
/vv_brain');
model.variable('var22').set('f63', '(ka_brain*y96*y62*vv_brain-
kd_brain*y63*vv_brain+p_Brain/kk*y63*vv_brain-disinfa_Brain*y63*vv_brain)/vv_brain');
model.variable('var22').set('f119', '(Q_brain*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_brain-L_brain)
*y119*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Brain*ac*y63/(y96+1)*vv_brain-d_Brain*y119*vv_brain)/vv_brain');
model.variable('var22').set('f96', '-ka_brain*y96*y62+kd_brain*y63');
model.variable('var22').set('f70', '(Q_kidney*y5*freeTcell_traffickidney-(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y70-ka_kidney*y98*y70*vv_kidney+kd_kidney*y71*vv_kidney-
disinf_kidney*y70*vv_kidney)/vv_kidney');
model.variable('var22').set('f71', '(ka_kidney*y98*y70*vv_kidney-
kd_kidney*y71*vv_kidney+p_kidney/kk*y71*vv_kidney-disinfa_kidney*y71*vv_kidney)
/vv_kidney');
model.variable('var22').set('f121', '(Q_kidney*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_kidney-L_kidney)
*y121*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_kidney*ac*y71/(y98+1)*vv_kidney-d_kidney*y121*vv_kidney)
/vv_kidney');
model.variable('var22').set('f98', '-ka_kidney*y98*y70+kd_kidney*y71');
model.variable('var22').set('f74', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y5-(Q_Cardiac_vessels-
L_Cardiac_vessels)*y74-
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ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels+kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
disinf_Cardiac_vessels*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var22').set('f75', '(ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels+p_Cardiac_vessels/kk*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
disinfa_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var22').set('f124', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-
(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y124*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Cardiac_vessels*ac*y75/
(y125+1)*vv_Cardiac_vessels-d_Cardiac_vessels*y124*vv_Cardiac_vessels)
/vv_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var22').set('f125', '-
ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74+kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75');
model.variable.remove('var22');
model.variable.create('var22');
model.variable('var22').model('comp1');
model.variable('var22').set('f5', '((Q_lung-L_lung)*y6-
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q
_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode)*y5)/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var22').set('f78', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y10+(Q_liver-L_liver)*y14+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)* y34+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)* y38+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)* y1+(Q_Lnode/8-
L_LTorso)* y42+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)* y46+(Q_Upper_body-
L_Upper_body)*y22+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y50+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y58+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)*y66+(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y70+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)
*y74+L_Cardiac_vessels*y77*rf_Cardiac_vessels+(L_lung+L_Llung)*y13*rf_Llung+
(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y37*rf_Lintestin+(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*
(rf_Ltumor*y41*heaviside(-y41+500)+1*y41*heaviside(y41-501))+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)
*y45*rf_LTorso+(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y49*rf_LUpper_body+
(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)*y53*rf_LLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y61*rf_Lbrain+
(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)*y69*rf_Lkidney-(Q_lung)*y78)/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var22').set('f85', '((Q_lung-L_lung)*y105-
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q
_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode)*y85)/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var22').set('f86', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y106+(Q_liver-L_liver)*y107+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)*y112+((Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)*y113)+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)*y104+(Q_Lnode/8-
L_LTorso)*y114+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y110+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)*y115+(Q_Upper_body-
L_Upper_body)*y109+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y116+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y117+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y118+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y119+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)*y120+(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y121+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y124+
(L_Cardiac_vessels*y125*rf_kidney)*heaviside(y125-1e-3*first)+(L_lung+L_Llung)
*y99*rf_aLlung+(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y101*rf_aLintestin+
(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*y80*rf_aLtumor+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)*y89*rf_aLTorso+
(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y91*rf_aLUpper_body+(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)
*y93*rf_aLLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y95*rf_aLbrain+(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)
*y97*rf_aLkidney-(Q_lung)*y86*heaviside(y86-1e-3*first))/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var22').set('f6', '(Q_lung*y78-(Q_lung-L_lung)*y6-
ka_lung*y100*y6*vv_lung+kd_lung*y7*vv_lung-disinf_lung*y6*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.variable('var22').set('f7', '(ka_lung*y100*y6*vv_lung-
kd_lung*y7*vv_lung+p_lung/kk*y7*vv_lung-disinfa_lung*y7*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.variable('var22').set('f105', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)*y105+mt_lung*ac*y7/
(y100+1)*vv_lung-d_lung*y105*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.variable('var22').set('f100', '-ka_lung*y100*y6+kd_lung*y7');

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model.variable('var22').set('f14', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30+(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y18+
(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y5*freeTcell_trafficliver-(Q_liver-
L_liver)*y14-ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver+kd_liver*y15*vv_liver-disinf_liver*y14*vv_liver)
/vv_liver');
model.variable('var22').set('f15', '(ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver-
kd_liver*y15*vv_liver+p_liver/kk*y15*vv_liver-disinfa_liver*y15*vv_liver)/vv_liver');
model.variable('var22').set('f107', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y111+(Q_spleen-L_spleen)
*y108+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y85-(Q_liver-L_liver)
*y107+mt_liver*ac*y15/(y87+1)*vv_liver-d_liver*y107*vv_liver)/vv_liver');
model.variable('var22').set('f87', '-ka_liver*y87*y14+kd_liver*y15');
model.variable('var22').set('f18', '(Q_spleen*y5*freeTcell_traffic spleen-(Q_spleen-
L_spleen)*y18-ka_spleen*y102*y18*vv_spleen+kd_spleen*y19*vv_spleen-
disinf_spleen*y18*vv_spleen)/vv_spleen');
model.variable('var22').set('f19', '(ka_spleen*y102*y18*vv_spleen-
kd_spleen*y19*vv_spleen+p_spleen/kk*y19*vv_spleen-disinfa_spleen*y19*vv_spleen)
/vv_spleen');
model.variable('var22').set('f108', '(Q_spleen*y85-(Q_spleen-L_spleen)
*y108+mt_spleen*ac*y19/(y102+1)*vv_spleen-d_spleen*y108*vv_spleen)/vv_spleen');
model.variable('var22').set('f102', '-ka_spleen*y102*y18+kd_spleen*y19');
model.variable('var22').set('f22', '(Q_Upper_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficUpper_body-
(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y22-
ka_Upper_body*y92*y22*vv_Upper_body+kd_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body-
disinf_Upper_body*y22*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body');
model.variable('var22').set('f23', '(ka_Upper_body*y92*y22*vv_Upper_body-
kd_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body+p_Upper_body/kk*y23*vv_Upper_body-
disinfa_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body');
model.variable('var22').set('f109', '(Q_Upper_body*y85-(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)
*y109+mt_Upper_body*ac*y23/(y92+1)*vv_Upper_body-d_Upper_body*y109*vv_Upper_body)
/vv_Upper_body');
model.variable('var22').set('f92', '-ka_Upper_body*y92*y22+kd_Upper_body*y23');
model.variable('var22').set('f26', '(Q_Torso*y5*freeTcell_trafficTorso-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)
*y26-ka_Torso*y90*y26*vv_Torso+kd_Torso*y27*vv_Torso-disinf_Torso*y26*vv_Torso)
/vv_Torso');
model.variable('var22').set('f27', '(ka_Torso*y90*y26*vv_Torso-
kd_Torso*y27*vv_Torso+p_Torso/kk*y27*vv_Torso-disinfa_Torso*y27*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso');
model.variable('var22').set('f110', '(Q_Torso*y85-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y110+mt_Torso*ac*y27/
(y90+1)*vv_Torso-d_Torso*y110*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso');
model.variable('var22').set('f90', '-ka_Torso*y90*y26+kd_Torso*y27');
model.variable('var22').set('f30', '(Q_intestin*y5*freeTcell_trafficintestine-
(Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30-ka_intestin*y103*y30*vv_intestin+kd_intestin*y31*vv_intestin-
disinf_Intestine*y30*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin');
model.variable('var22').set('f31', '(ka_intestin*y103*y30*vv_intestin-
kd_intestin*y31*vv_intestin+p_Intestine/kk*y31*vv_intestin-
disinfa_Intestine*y31*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin');
model.variable('var22').set('f111', '(Q_intestin*y85-(Q_intestin-L_intestin)
*y111+mt_Intestine*ac*y31/(y103+1)*vv_intestin-d_Intestine*y111*vv_intestin)
/vv_intestin');
model.variable('var22').set('f103', '-ka_intestin*y103*y30+kd_intestin*y31');
model.variable('var22').set('f54', '(Q_Lower_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficLower_body-
(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54-
ka_Lower_body*y94*y54*vv_Lower_body+kd_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body-

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disinf_Lower_body*y54*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.variable('var22').set('f55', '(ka_Lower_body*y94*y54*vv_Lower_body-
kd_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body+p_Lower_body/kk*y55*vv_Lower_body-
disinfa_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.variable('var22').set('f117', '(Q_Lower_body*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_Lower_body-
L_Lower_body)*y117*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Lower_body*ac*y55/(y94+1)*vv_Lower_body-
d_Lower_body*y117*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.variable('var22').set('f94', '-ka_Lower_body*y94*y54+kd_Lower_body*y55');
model.variable('var22').set('f62', '(Q_brain*y5*freeTcell_trafficbrain-(Q_brain-L_brain)
*y62-ka_brain*y96*y62*vv_brain+kd_brain*y63*vv_brain-disinf_Brain*y62*vv_brain)
/vv_brain');
model.variable('var22').set('f63', '(ka_brain*y96*y62*vv_brain-
kd_brain*y63*vv_brain+p_Brain/kk*y63*vv_brain-disinfa_Brain*y63*vv_brain)/vv_brain');
model.variable('var22').set('f119', '(Q_brain*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_brain-L_brain)
*y119*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Brain*ac*y63/(y96+1)*vv_brain-d_Brain*y119*vv_brain)/vv_brain');
model.variable('var22').set('f96', '-ka_brain*y96*y62+kd_brain*y63');
model.variable('var22').set('f70', '(Q_kidney*y5*freeTcell_traffickidney-(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y70-ka_kidney*y98*y70*vv_kidney+kd_kidney*y71*vv_kidney-
disinf_kidney*y70*vv_kidney)/vv_kidney');
model.variable('var22').set('f71', '(ka_kidney*y98*y70*vv_kidney-
kd_kidney*y71*vv_kidney+p_kidney/kk*y71*vv_kidney-disinfa_kidney*y71*vv_kidney)
/vv_kidney');
model.variable('var22').set('f121', '(Q_kidney*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_kidney-L_kidney)
*y121*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_kidney*ac*y71/(y98+1)*vv_kidney-d_kidney*y121*vv_kidney)
/vv_kidney');
model.variable('var22').set('f98', '-ka_kidney*y98*y70+kd_kidney*y71');
model.variable('var22').set('f74', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y5-(Q_Cardiac_vessels-
L_Cardiac_vessels)*y74-
ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels+kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
disinf_Cardiac_vessels*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var22').set('f75', '(ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels+p_Cardiac_vessels/kk*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
disinfa_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var22').set('f124', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-
(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y124*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Cardiac_vessels*ac*y75/
(y125+1)*vv_Cardiac_vessels-d_Cardiac_vessels*y124*vv_Cardiac_vessels)
/vv_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var22').set('f125', '-
ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74+kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75');

model.func.create('step1', 'Step');
model.func('step1').model('comp1');
model.func('step1').set('funcname', 'heaviside');

model.variable('var21').set('first', '1');

model.sol('sol54').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '19', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
```

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model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y3');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y5');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y78');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y85');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y6');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y7');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y105');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y100');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y14');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y15');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('unit', 'mol/L');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y107');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y87');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y18');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y19');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y125');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y124');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y96');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y125');
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;

model.variable('var22').set('f78', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y10)/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var21').set('y10', '0 [mol/L]');
model.variable('var22').set('f78', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y10+(Q_liver-L_liver)*y14+↵
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(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)* y34+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)* y38+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)* y1+(Q_Lnode/8-  
L_LTorso)* y42+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)* y46+(Q_Upper_body-  
L_Upper_body)*y22+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y50+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54+  
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y58+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)*y66+(Q_kidney-  
L_kidney)*y70+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)  
*y74+L_Cardiac_vessels*y77*rf_Cardiac_vessels+(L_lung+L_Llung)*y13*rf_Llung+  
(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y37*rf_Lintestin+(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*  
(rf_Ltumor*y41*heaviside(-y41+500[mol/L])+1*y41*heaviside(y41-501[mol/L]))+  
(L_Torso+L_LTorso)*y45*rf_LTorso+(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y49*rf_LUpper_body+  
(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)*y53*rf_LLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y61*rf_Lbrain+  
(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)*y69*rf_Lkidney-(Q_lung)*y78)/vv_ventricle');  
model.variable('var19').set('Q_tumor', '0 [L/d]');  
model.variable('var19').set('Q_Lnode', '0 [L/d]');  
model.variable('var19').set('L_tumor', '0 [L/d]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y34', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y38', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y1', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y42', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y46', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y50', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y58', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y66', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y77', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y13', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y37', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y41', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y45', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y49', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y53', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y61', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y69', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y106', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y112', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y113', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y104', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y114', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y115', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y116', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y118', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y120', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y99', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y101', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y80', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y89', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y91', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y93', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y95', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var21').set('y97', '0[mol/L]');  
model.variable('var22').set('f78', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y10+(Q_liver-L_liver)*y14+  
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)* y34+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)* y38+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)* y1+(Q_Lnode/8-  
L_LTorso)* y42+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)* y46+(Q_Upper_body-
```

```
L_Upper_body)*y22+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y50+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y58+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)*y66+(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y70+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)
*y74+L_Cardiac_vessels*y77*rf_Cardiac_vessels+(L_lung+L_Llung)*y13*rf_Llung+
(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y37*rf_Lintestin+(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*
(rf_Ltumor*y41*heaviside(-y41+500[mol/L])+1*y41*heaviside(y41-501[mol/L]))+
(L_Torso+L_LTorso)*y45*rf_LTorso+(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y49*rf_LUpper_body+
(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)*y53*rf_LLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y61*rf_Lbrain+
(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)*y69*rf_Lkidney-(Q_lung)*y78)/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var22').set('aaa', 'rf_Lbrain');
model.variable('var22').remove('aaa');
model.variable('var22').set('aasd', 'heaviside(-y41/1[mol/L]+500)');
model.variable('var22').set('f78', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y10+(Q_liver-L_liver)*y14+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)* y34+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)* y38+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)* y1+(Q_Lnode/8-
L_LTorso)* y42+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)* y46+(Q_Upper_body-
L_Upper_body)*y22+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y50+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y58+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)*y66+(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y70+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)
*y74+L_Cardiac_vessels*y77*rf_Cardiac_vessels+(L_lung+L_Llung)*y13*rf_Llung+
(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y37*rf_Lintestin+(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*
(rf_Ltumor*y41*heaviside(-y41/1[mol/L]+500))+1*y41*heaviside(y41/1[mol/L]-501))+
(L_Torso+L_LTorso)*y45*rf_LTorso+(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y49*rf_LUpper_body+
(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)*y53*rf_LLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y61*rf_Lbrain+
(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)*y69*rf_Lkidney-(Q_lung)*y78)/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var22').set('f86', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y106+(Q_liver-L_liver)*y107+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)*y112+((Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)*y113)+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)*y104+(Q_Lnode/8-
L_LTorso)*y114+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y110+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)*y115+(Q_Upper_body-
L_Upper_body)*y109+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y116+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y117+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y118+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y119+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)*y120+(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y121+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y124+
(L_Cardiac_vessels*y125*rf_kidney)*heaviside(y125/1[mol/L]-1e-3*first)+(L_lung+L_Llung)
*y99*rf_aLlung+(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y101*rf_aLintestin+
(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*y80*rf_aLtumor+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)*y89*rf_aLTorso+
(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y91*rf_aLUpper_body+(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)
*y93*rf_aLLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y95*rf_aLbrain+(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)
*y97*rf_aLkidney-(Q_lung)*y86*heaviside(y86/1[mol/L]-1e-3*first))/vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var22').set('f6', '(Q_lung*y78-(Q_lung-L_lung)*y6+kd_lung*y7*vv_lung-
disinf_lung*y6*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.variable('var22').set('aasd', '-ka_lung*y100*y6*vv_lung');
model.variable('var22').remove('aasd');
model.variable('var22').set('f6', '(Q_lung*y78-(Q_lung-L_lung)*y6-
ka_lung*y100*y6*vv_lung+kd_lung*y7*vv_lung-disinf_lung*y6*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.variable('var22').set('f7', '(ka_lung*y100*y6*vv_lung-
kd_lung*y7*vv_lung+p_lung/kk*y7*vv_lung-disinfa_lung*y7*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.variable('var22').set('f100', '-ka_lung*y100*y6+kd_lung*y7');
model.variable('var22').set('aaaa', '-ka_lung*y100*y6');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_lung', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
model.variable('var22').remove('aaaa');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_spleen', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_liver', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Upper_body', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
```

```
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Torso', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_intestin', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Lower_body', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_brain', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_kidney', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y125');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y5');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdfactive', 'on');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdf', '0.1');
model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'f5');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'f125');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('Baseline_solution_Time_step_new_therapy_oxygen_flow_stepFunction_runTest.↙
mph');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.physics('dode43').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '2');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'f125');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.physics('dode44').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y125');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.variable('var7').set('ka_spleen', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/fmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_liver', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/fmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Upper_body', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/fmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Torso', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/fmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_lung', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/fmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_intestin', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/fmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Lower_body', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/fmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_brain', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/fmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_kidney', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/fmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/fmol]');

model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode3').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode3').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode4').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode4').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode5').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode5').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode6').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode6').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode7').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode7').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode8').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode8').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode9').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode9').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode10').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode10').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode11').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode11').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode12').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode12').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode13').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode13').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode14').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode14').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode15').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode15').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode16').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode16').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode17').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode17').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
```



```
model.physics('dode43').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode44').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'fmol/L');
model.physics('dode44').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'fmol/L/min');
model.physics('dode43').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');

model.variable('var7').set('ka_spleen', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_liver', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Upper_body', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Torso', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_lung', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_intestin', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Lower_body', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_brain', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_kidney', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mol]');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '19', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('unit', 'mol/L');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowevalintitle', false);
model.result('pg1').set('title', 'Time=0 d Slice: Dependent variable y125 (mol/L)');
model.result('pg1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeunit', 'mol/L');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormin', 9.999999994520158E-4);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecolormax', 9.99999999452016E-4);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangecoloractive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamin', 9.999999994520158E-4);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedatamax', 9.99999999452016E-4);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangedataactive', 'off');
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('rangeactualminmax', [9.999999994520158E-4↵
9.99999999452016E-4]);
model.result('pg1').feature('slc1').set('hasbeenplotted', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', false);
model.result('pg1').set('allowtableupdate', true);
model.result('pg1').set('renderdatacached', true);
model.result.table('evl3').addRow([0.025000000000133235 0.004123423430781769↵
0.024677348129283162 9.999999994520158E-4], [0 0 0 0]);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '2', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;

model.physics('dode5').feature('init1').set('y6', '100');
model.physics('dode8').feature('init1').set('y100', '100');
model.physics('dode12').feature('init1').set('y87', '100');
model.physics('dode16').feature('init1').set('y102', '100');
model.physics('dode20').feature('init1').set('y92', '100');
model.physics('dode24').feature('init1').set('y90', '100');
model.physics('dode28').feature('init1').set('y103', '100');
model.physics('dode32').feature('init1').set('y94', '100');
model.physics('dode39').feature('init1').set('y98', '100');
model.physics('dode43').feature('init1').set('y125', '100');
model.physics('dode44').feature('init1').set('y96', '100');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '1', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').setIndex('looplevel', '19', 0);
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('unit', 'mol/m^3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('unit', 'fmol/m^3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.physics('dode44').feature('init1').set('y96', '1000');
model.physics('dode43').feature('init1').set('y125', '1000');
model.physics('dode39').feature('init1').set('y98', '1000');
model.physics('dode32').feature('init1').set('y94', '1000');
model.physics('dode28').feature('init1').set('y103', '1000');
model.physics('dode24').feature('init1').set('y90', '1000');
model.physics('dode20').feature('init1').set('y92', '1000');
model.physics('dode16').feature('init1').set('y102', '1000');
model.physics('dode12').feature('init1').set('y87', '1000');
model.physics('dode5').feature('init1').set('y6', '1000');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('unit', 'mol/ml');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('unit', 'mol/L');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('unit', 'mol/m^3');
model.result('pg40').run;
```

```
model.variable('var7').set('ka_spleen', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_liver', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Upper_body', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Torso', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_lung', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_intestin', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Lower_body', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_brain', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_kidney', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');

model.sol('sol54').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y125/1000');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.physics('dode5').feature('init1').set('y6', '1');
model.physics('dode12').feature('init1').set('y87', '1');
model.physics('dode16').feature('init1').set('y102', '1');
model.physics('dode20').feature('init1').set('y92', '1');
model.physics('dode24').feature('init1').set('y90', '1');
model.physics('dode28').feature('init1').set('y103', '1');
model.physics('dode32').feature('init1').set('y94', '1');
model.physics('dode39').feature('init1').set('y98', '1');
model.physics('dode43').feature('init1').set('y125', '1');
model.physics('dode44').feature('init1').set('y96', '1');

model.sol('sol54').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y125');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.physics('dode44').feature('init1').set('y96', '1000');
model.physics('dode43').feature('init1').set('y125', '1000');
model.physics('dode39').feature('init1').set('y98', '1000');
model.physics('dode32').feature('init1').set('y94', '1000');
model.physics('dode28').feature('init1').set('y103', '1000');
model.physics('dode24').feature('init1').set('y90', '1000');
model.physics('dode20').feature('init1').set('y92', '1000');
model.physics('dode16').feature('init1').set('y102', '1000');
model.physics('dode5').feature('init1').set('y6', '1000');

model.sol('sol54').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
```

```
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y5');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.variable('var7').set('ka_spleen', '1e-3*60*24');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_liver', '1e-3*60*24');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Upper_body', '1e-3*60*24');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Torso', '1e-3*60*24');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_lung', '1e-3*60*24');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_intestin', '1e-3*60*24');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Lower_body', '1e-3*60*24');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_brain', '1e-3*60*24');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_kidney', '1e-3*60*24');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3*60*24');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_spleen', '1e-3*2/3*60*24');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_liver', '1e-3*2/3*60*24');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_Upper_body', '1e-3*2/3*60*24');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_Torso', '1e-3*2/3*60*24');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_lung', '1e-3*2/3*60*24');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_intestin', '1e-3*2/3*60*24');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_Lower_body', '1e-3*2/3*60*24');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_brain', '1e-3*2/3*60*24');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_kidney', '1e-3*2/3*60*24');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3*2/3*60*24');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_lung', '1');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_liver', '1');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_spleen', '1');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Upper_body', '1');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Torso', '1');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Intestine', '1');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Brain', '1');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Lower_body', '1');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_kidney', '1');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Cardiac_vessels', '1');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_lung', '1');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_liver', '1');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_spleen', '1');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Upper_body', '1');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Torso', '1');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Intestine', '1');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Lower_body', '1');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Brain', '1');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_kidney', '1');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Cardiac_vessels', '1');
model.variable('var11').set('p_liver', '1');
model.variable('var11').set('p_lung', '1');
model.variable('var11').set('p_spleen', '0.1');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Upper_body', '1.1');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Torso', '2');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Intestine', '0.7');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Lower_body', '0.9');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Brain', '1.4');
```

```
model.variable('var11').set('p_kidney', '1.1');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Cardiac_vessels', '1.8');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_lung', '1');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_liver', '1');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_spleen', '1');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Upper_body', '1');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Torso', '1');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Intestine', '1');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Lower_body', '1');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Brain', '1');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_kidney', '1');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Cardiac_vessels', '1');
model.variable('var14').set('d_lung', '1');
model.variable('var14').set('d_liver', '1');
model.variable('var14').set('d_spleen', '1');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Upper_body', '1');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Torso', '1');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Intestine', '1');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Lower_body', '1');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Brain', '1');
model.variable('var14').set('d_kidney', '1');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Cardiac_vessels', '1');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Cardiac_vessels', '120*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_spleen', '138*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Upper_body', '138*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Torso', '220*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_brain', '300*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Lower_body', '413*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_intestin', '468*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_kidney', '630*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_liver', '800*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var16').set('L_lung', '4.3e-2*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var16').set('L_intestin', '3e-1*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var16').set('L_kidney', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lower_body', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Cardiac_vessels', '4.3e-3*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lspleen', '0');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lliver', '1.5e-6*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var16').set('L_LUpper_body', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var16').set('L_LTorso', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Llung', '1.8e-6*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lintestin', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Ltumor', '1e-3*1.1*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var16').set('L_LLower_body', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var16').set('L_brain', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lkidney', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lbrain', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_spleen', '17*1e-3');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_liver', '180.9*1e-3');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_Upper_body', '150*1e-3');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_Torso', '462*1e-3');
```

```
model.variable('var17').set('vv_lung', '99.9*1e-3');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_intestin', '43*1e-3');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_Lower_body', '700*1e-3');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_brain', '150*1e-3');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_kidney', '28.4*1e-3');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_Cardiac_vessels', '100*1e-3');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_ventricle', '200*1e-3');
model.variable('var19').set('Q_tumor', '0');
model.variable('var19').set('Q_Lnode', '0');
model.variable('var19').set('L_tumor', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y10', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y34', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y38', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y1', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y42', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y46', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y50', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y58', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y66', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y77', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y13', '0');
model.variable('var21').remove('y13');
model.variable('var21').set('y13', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y37', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y41', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y45', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y49', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y53', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y61', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y69', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y106', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y112', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y113', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y104', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y114', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y115', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y116', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y118', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y120', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y99', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y101', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y80', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y89', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y91', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y93', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y95', '0');
model.variable('var21').set('y97', '0');
model.variable('var22').set('f78', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y10+(Q_liver-L_liver)*y14+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)* y34+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)* y38+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)* y1+(Q_Lnode/8-
L_LTorso)* y42+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)* y46+(Q_Upper_body-
L_Upper_body)*y22+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y50+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54+
```

```
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y58+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)*y66+(Q_kidney-  
L_kidney)*y70+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)  
*y74+L_Cardiac_vessels*y77*rf_Cardiac_vessels+(L_lung+L_Llung)*y13*rf_Llung+  
(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y37*rf_Lintestin+(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*  
(rf_Ltumor*y41*heaviside(-y41+500)+1*y41*heaviside(y41-501))+ (L_Torso+L_LTorso)  
*y45*rf_LTorso+(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y49*rf_LUpper_body+  
(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)*y53*rf_LLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y61*rf_Lbrain+  
(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)*y69*rf_Lkidney-(Q_lung)*y78)/vv_ventricle');  
model.variable('var22').set('f86', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y106+(Q_liver-L_liver)*y107+  
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)*y112+((Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)*y113)+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)*y104+(Q_Lnode/8-  
L_LTorso)*y114+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y110+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)*y115+(Q_Upper_body-  
L_Upper_body)*y109+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y116+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y117+  
(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y118+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y119+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)*y120+(Q_kidney-  
L_kidney)*y121+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y124+  
(L_Cardiac_vessels*y125*rf_kidney)*heaviside(y125-1e-3*first)+(L_lung+L_Llung)  
*y99*rf_aLlung+(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y101*rf_aLintestin+  
(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*y80*rf_aLtumor+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)*y89*rf_aLTorso+  
(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y91*rf_aLUpper_body+(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)  
*y93*rf_aLLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y95*rf_aLbrain+(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)  
*y97*rf_aLkidney-(Q_lung)*y86*heaviside(y86-1e-3*first))/vv_ventricle');  
model.variable('var16').set('L_spleen', '8.7e-4*60*24*1e-3');  
model.variable('var16').set('L_liver', '8.7e-2*60*24*1e-3');  
model.variable('var16').set('L_Upper_body', '2.6e-2*60*24*1e-3');  
model.variable('var16').set('L_Torso', '4.3e-3*60*24*1e-3');  
  
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode3').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode3').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode4').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode4').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode5').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode5').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode5').feature('init1').set('y6', '1');  
model.physics('dode6').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode6').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode7').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode7').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode8').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode8').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode9').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode9').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode10').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode10').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode11').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode11').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode12').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode12').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');  
model.physics('dode13').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
```



```
model.physics('dode36').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode36').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode37').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode37').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode38').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode38').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode39').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode39').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode39').feature('init1').set('y98', '1');
model.physics('dode40').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode40').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode41').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode41').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode42').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode42').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode43').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode43').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode43').feature('init1').set('y125', '1');
model.physics('dode44').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode44').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1');
model.physics('dode44').feature('init1').set('y96', '1');
```

```
model.sol('sol54').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');
```

```
model.result('pg1').run;
```

```
model.physics('dode').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode2').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode3').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode4').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode5').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode6').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode7').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode8').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode9').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode10').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode11').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode12').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode13').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode14').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode15').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode16').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode17').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode18').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode19').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode20').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode21').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode22').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode24').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode23').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode25').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
```

```
model.physics('dode26').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode27').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode28').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode29').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode30').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode31').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode32').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode33').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode34').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode35').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode36').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode37').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode38').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode39').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode40').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode41').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode42').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode43').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');
model.physics('dode44').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', '1/s');

model.variable('var7').remove('ka_spleen');
model.variable('var7').remove('ka_liver');
model.variable('var7').remove('ka_Upper_body');
model.variable('var7').remove('ka_Torso');
model.variable('var7').remove('ka_lung');
model.variable('var7').remove('ka_intestin');
model.variable('var7').remove('ka_Lower_body');
model.variable('var7').remove('ka_brain');
model.variable('var7').remove('ka_kidney');
model.variable('var7').remove('ka_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_spleen', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_liver', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Upper_body', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Torso', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_lung', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_intestin', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Lower_body', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_brain', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_kidney', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3*60*24 [ml/min/mmol]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_spleen', '1e-3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_liver', '1e-3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Upper_body', '1e-3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Torso', '1e-3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_lung', '1e-3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_intestin', '1e-3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Lower_body', '1e-3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_brain', '1e-3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_kidney', '1e-3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').remove('kd_spleen');
```

```
model.variable('var8').remove('kd_liver');
model.variable('var8').remove('kd_Upper_body');
model.variable('var8').remove('kd_Torso');
model.variable('var8').remove('kd_lung');
model.variable('var8').remove('kd_intestin');
model.variable('var8').remove('kd_Lower_body');
model.variable('var8').remove('kd_brain');
model.variable('var8').remove('kd_kidney');
model.variable('var8').remove('kd_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_spleen', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_liver', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_Upper_body', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_Torso', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_lung', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_intestin', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_Lower_body', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_brain', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_kidney', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/min]');
model.variable('var9').remove('disinf_lung');
model.variable('var9').remove('disinf_liver');
model.variable('var9').remove('disinf_spleen');
model.variable('var9').remove('disinf_Upper_body');
model.variable('var9').remove('disinf_Torso');
model.variable('var9').remove('disinf_Intestine');
model.variable('var9').remove('disinf_Lower_body');
model.variable('var9').remove('disinf_Brain');
model.variable('var9').remove('disinf_kidney');
model.variable('var9').remove('disinf_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_lung', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_liver', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_spleen', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Upper_body', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Torso', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Intestine', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Lower_body', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Brain', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_kidney', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var9').set('disinf_Cardiac_vessels', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').remove('disinfa_lung');
model.variable('var10').remove('disinfa_liver');
model.variable('var10').remove('disinfa_spleen');
model.variable('var10').remove('disinfa_Upper_body');
model.variable('var10').remove('disinfa_Torso');
model.variable('var10').remove('disinfa_Intestine');
model.variable('var10').remove('disinfa_Lower_body');
model.variable('var10').remove('disinfa_Brain');
model.variable('var10').remove('disinfa_kidney');
model.variable('var10').remove('disinfa_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_lung', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_liver', '1 [1/d]');
```

```
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_spleen', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Upper_body', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Torso', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Intestine', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Lower_body', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Brain', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_kidney', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var10').set('disinfa_Cardiac_vessels', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_liver');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_lung');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_spleen');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_Upper_body');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_Torso');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_Intestine');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_Lower_body');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_Brain');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_kidney');
model.variable('var11').remove('p_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var11').set('p_liver', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_lung', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_spleen', '0.1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Upper_body', '1.1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Torso', '2 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Intestine', '0.7 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Lower_body', '0.9 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Brain', '1.4 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_kidney', '1.1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var11').set('p_Cardiac_vessels', '1.8 [1/d]');
model.variable('var13').remove('mt_lung');
model.variable('var13').remove('mt_liver');
model.variable('var13').remove('mt_spleen');
model.variable('var13').remove('mt_Upper_body');
model.variable('var13').remove('mt_Torso');
model.variable('var13').remove('mt_Intestine');
model.variable('var13').remove('mt_Lower_body');
model.variable('var13').remove('mt_Brain');
model.variable('var13').remove('mt_kidney');
model.variable('var13').remove('mt_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_lung', '1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_liver', '1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_spleen', '1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Upper_body', '1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Torso', '1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Intestine', '1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Lower_body', '1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Brain', '1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_kidney', '1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Cardiac_vessels', '1 [mol/L/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_lung', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_liver', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_spleen', '1 [1/d]');
```

```
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Upper_body', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Torso', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Intestine', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Lower_body', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Brain', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_kidney', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var13').set('mt_Cardiac_vessels', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').remove('d_lung');
model.variable('var14').remove('d_liver');
model.variable('var14').remove('d_spleen');
model.variable('var14').remove('d_Upper_body');
model.variable('var14').remove('d_Torso');
model.variable('var14').remove('d_Intestine');
model.variable('var14').remove('d_Lower_body');
model.variable('var14').remove('d_Brain');
model.variable('var14').remove('d_kidney');
model.variable('var14').remove('d_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var14').set('d_lung', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_liver', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_spleen', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Upper_body', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Torso', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Intestine', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Lower_body', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Brain', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_kidney', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var14').set('d_Cardiac_vessels', '1 [1/d]');
model.variable('var15').remove('Q_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var15').remove('Q_spleen');
model.variable('var15').remove('Q_Upper_body');
model.variable('var15').remove('Q_Torso');
model.variable('var15').remove('Q_brain');
model.variable('var15').remove('Q_Lower_body');
model.variable('var15').remove('Q_intestin');
model.variable('var15').remove('Q_kidney');
model.variable('var15').remove('Q_liver');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Cardiac_vessels', '120*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_spleen', '138*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Upper_body', '138*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Torso', '220*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_brain', '300*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Lower_body', '413*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_intestin', '468*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_kidney', '630*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_liver', '800*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Cardiac_vessels', '120*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_spleen', '138*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Upper_body', '138*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Torso', '220*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_brain', '300*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_Lower_body', '413*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
```

```
model.variable('var15').set('Q_intestin', '468*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_kidney', '630*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var15').set('Q_liver', '800*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_spleen');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_liver');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_Upper_body');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_Torso');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_lung');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_intestin');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_kidney');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_Lower_body');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_Lspleen');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_Lliver');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_LUpper_body');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_LTorso');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_Llung');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_Lintestin');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_Ltumor');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_LLower_body');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_brain');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_Lkidney');
model.variable('var16').remove('L_Lbrain');
model.variable('var16').set('L_spleen', '8.7e-4*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_liver', '8.7e-2*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Upper_body', '2.6e-2*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Torso', '4.3e-3*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_lung', '4.3e-2*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_intestin', '3e-1*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_kidney', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lower_body', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Cardiac_vessels', '4.3e-3*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lspleen', '0 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lliver', '1.5e-6*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_LUpper_body', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_LTorso', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Llung', '1.8e-6*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lintestin', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Ltumor', '1e-3*1.1*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_LLower_body', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_brain', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lkidney', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var16').set('L_Lbrain', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [1/d]');
model.variable('var17').remove('vv_spleen');
model.variable('var17').remove('vv_liver');
model.variable('var17').remove('vv_Upper_body');
model.variable('var17').remove('vv_Torso');
model.variable('var17').remove('vv_lung');
model.variable('var17').remove('vv_intestin');
model.variable('var17').remove('vv_Lower_body');
model.variable('var17').remove('vv_brain');
```

```
model.variable('var17').remove('vv_kidney');
model.variable('var17').remove('vv_Cardiac_vessels');
model.variable('var17').remove('vv_ventricle');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_spleen', '17*1e-3 [1]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_liver', '180.9*1e-3 [1]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_Upper_body', '150*1e-3 [1]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_Torso', '462*1e-3 [1]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_lung', '99.9*1e-3 [1]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_intestin', '43*1e-3 [1]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_Lower_body', '700*1e-3 [1]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_brain', '150*1e-3 [1]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_kidney', '28.4*1e-3 [1]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_Cardiac_vessels', '100*1e-3 [1]');
model.variable('var17').set('vv_ventricle', '200*1e-3 [1]');
model.variable('var19').set('Q_tumor', '0[1/d]');
model.variable('var19').set('Q_Lnode', '0[1/d]');
model.variable('var19').set('L_tumor', '0[1/d]');

model.label('Baseline_solution_Time step_new↙
therapy_oxygen_flow_stepFunction_runTest1_diemensiolensnonTime.mph');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y125');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdf', '2.6618e-09');

model.result('pg1').run;

model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdf', '2.6618e-4');

model.label('Baseline_solution_Time step_new↙
therapy_oxygen_flow_stepFunction_runTest1_diemensiolensnonTime_minstep.mph');

model.variable('var7').set('ka_spleen', '1e-3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_liver', '1e-3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Upper_body', '1e-3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Torso', '1e-3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_lung', '1e-3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_intestin', '1e-3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Lower_body', '1e-3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_brain', '1e-3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_kidney', '1e-3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var7').set('ka_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_spleen', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_liver', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_Upper_body', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/d]');
```

```
model.variable('var8').set('kd_Torso', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_lung', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_intestin', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_Lower_body', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_brain', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_kidney', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/d]');
model.variable('var8').set('kd_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3*2/3*60*24 [1/d]');

model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdfactive', 'off');
model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y5');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y125');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.physics('dode').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', '1');

model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tlist', 'range(0,1,15)');

model.physics('dode8').feature('init1').set('y100', '1');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg1').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y5');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y8');

model.label('Baseline add Matlab EQ_clear.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol154').clearSolutionData;

model.result('pg39').run;
model.result('pg1').run;
model.result.remove('pg1');
model.result.remove('pg2');
model.result.remove('pg3');
model.result.remove('pg4');
model.result.remove('pg5');
model.result.remove('pg6');
model.result.remove('pg7');
model.result.remove('pg8');
```

```
model.result.remove('pg9');
model.result.remove('pg10');
model.result.remove('pg11');
model.result.remove('pg12');
model.result.remove('pg13');
model.result.remove('pg14');
model.result.remove('pg15');
model.result.remove('pg16');
model.result.remove('pg17');
model.result.remove('pg18');
model.result.remove('pg19');
model.result.remove('pg20');
model.result.remove('pg21');
model.result.remove('pg22');
model.result.remove('pg23');
model.result.remove('pg24');
model.result.remove('pg25');
model.result.remove('pg26');
model.result.remove('pg27');
model.result.remove('pg28');
model.result.remove('pg29');
model.result.remove('pg30');
model.result.remove('pg31');
model.result.remove('pg32');
model.result.remove('pg33');
model.result.remove('pg34');
model.result.remove('pg35');
model.result.remove('pg36');
model.result.remove('pg37');
model.result.remove('pg38');
model.result.remove('pg39');

model.label('Baseline add Matlab EQ_clear.mph');

model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('fcl').set('dtech', 'auto');
model.sol('sol54').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y111');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y5');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y125');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol54').clearSolutionData;

model.label('Baseline add Matlab EQ_clear_Method and Termination Autoimatic Newton.mph');
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').set('timemethod', 'bdf');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f105', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*y105+mt_lung*ac*Ci/(ACE2+1)*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_lung-d_lung*y105*vv_lung)
/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f107', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y111+
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y108+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y85-(Q_liver-
L_liver)*y107+mt_liver*ac*y15/(y87+1)*vv_liver+mt_liver*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_liver-
d_liver*y107*vv_liver)/vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f108', '(Q_spleen*y85-(Q_spleen-L_spleen)
*y108+mt_spleen*ac*y19/(y102+1)*vv_spleen+mt_spleen*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_spleen-
d_spleen*y108*vv_spleen)/vv_spleen');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f109', '(Q_Upper_body*y85-(Q_Upper_body-
L_Upper_body)*y109+mt_Upper_body*ac*y23/(y92+1)*vv_Upper_body+mt_Upper_body*ac*IL6/
(IL6+1)*vv_Upper_body-d_Upper_body*y109*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f110', '(Q_Torso*y85-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)
*y110+mt_Torso*ac*y27/(y90+1)*vv_Torso+mt_Torso*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_Torso-
d_Torso*y110*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f111', '(Q_intestin*y85-(Q_intestin-
L_intestin)*y111+mt_Intestine*ac*y31/(y103+1)*vv_intestin+mt_Intestine*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)
*vv_Intestine-d_Intestine*y111*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin');
model.component('comp1').variable('var17').rename('vv_intestin', 'vv_intestine');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f111', '(Q_intestin*y85-(Q_intestin-
L_intestin)*y111+mt_Intestine*ac*y31/(y103+1)*vv_intestin+mt_Intestine*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)
*vv_Intestin-d_Intestine*y111*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin');
model.component('comp1').variable('var17').rename('vv_intestine', 'vv_intestin');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f111', '(Q_intestin*y85-(Q_intestin-
L_intestin)*y111+mt_Intestine*ac*y31/(y103+1)*vv_intestin+mt_Intestine*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)
*vv_intestin-d_Intestine*y111*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f117', '(Q_Lower_body*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-
(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y117*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Lower_body*ac*y55/(y94+1)
*vv_Lower_body+mt_Lower_body*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_Lower_body-
d_Lower_body*y117*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f119', '(Q_brain*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-
(Q_brain-L_brain)*y119*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Brain*ac*y63/(y96+1)*vv_brain+mt_Brain*ac*IL6/
(IL6+1)*vv_brain-d_Brain*y119*vv_brain)/vv_brain');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f121', '(Q_kidney*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-
(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y121*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_kidney*ac*y71/(y98+1)
*vv_kidney+mt_kidney*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_kidney-d_kidney*y121*vv_kidney)/vv_kidney');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f124',
'(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)
*y124*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Cardiac_vessels*ac*y75/(y125+1)
*vv_Cardiac_vessels+mt_Cardiac_vessels*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
d_Cardiac_vessels*y124*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y111');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('dode8').active(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode6').active(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').active(false);

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f5', '((Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci-
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q
_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode)*y5)/vv_ventricle');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f105', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*y105+mt_lung*ac*Cb/(ACE2+1)*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_lung-d_lung*y105*vv_lung)
/vv_lung');

model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci+Ka*Vint',
0);

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y34', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y10', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y1', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y38', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y42', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y46', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y50', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y58', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y66', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y77', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y13', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y37', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y41', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y45', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y49', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y53', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y61', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y69', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y106', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y112', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y113', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y104', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y114', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y115', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y116', '0 [M]');
```

```
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y118', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y120', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y99', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y101', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y80', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y89', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y91', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y93', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y95', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y97', '0 [M]');
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y78');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('data', 'cpt1');
model.result('pg40').run;
```

```
model.component('comp1').physics('dode2').prop('Units').setIndex✔
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode').prop('Units').setIndex✔
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode3').prop('Units').setIndex✔
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode4').prop('Units').setIndex✔
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').prop('Units').setIndex✔
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode6').prop('Units').setIndex✔
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode7').prop('Units').setIndex✔
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode8').prop('Units').setIndex✔
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode9').prop('Units').setIndex✔
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode10').prop('Units').setIndex✔
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode11').prop('Units').setIndex✔
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode12').prop('Units').setIndex✔
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode13').prop('Units').setIndex✔
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode14').prop('Units').setIndex✔
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode15').prop('Units').setIndex✔
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
```



```
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode42').prop('Units').setIndex✓
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode44').prop('Units').setIndex✓
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode43').prop('Units').setIndex✓
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var15').set('Q_Cardiac_vessels', '120*60*24*1e-3✓
[L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var15').set('Q_spleen', '138*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var15').set('Q_Upper_body', '138*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var15').set('Q_Torso', '220*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var15').set('Q_brain', '300*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var15').set('Q_Lower_body', '413*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var15').set('Q_intestin', '468*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var15').set('Q_kidney', '630*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var15').set('Q_liver', '800*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_spleen', '8.7e-4*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_liver', '8.7e-2*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_Upper_body', '2.6e-2*60*24*1e-3✓
[L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_Torso', '4.3e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_lung', '4.3e-2*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_intestin', '3e-1*60*24*1e-3[L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_kidney', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3[L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_Lower_body', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_Cardiac_vessels', '4.3e-3*60*24*1e-3✓
[L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_Lspleen', '0 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_Lliver', '1.5e-6*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_LUpper_body', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_LTorso', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_Llung', '1.8e-6*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_Lintestin', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_Ltumor', '1e-3*1.1*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_LLower_body', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_brain', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_Lkidney', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var16').set('L_Lbrain', '1e-3*60*24*1e-3 [L/d]');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y10');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y2', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y3', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y4', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y5', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y6', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y7', '0 [M]');
```



```
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y115', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y116', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y117', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y118', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y119', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y120', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y121', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y122', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y123', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y124', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y125', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y126', '0 [M]');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var17').set('vv_spleen', '17*1e-3 [L]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var17').set('vv_liver', '180.9*1e-3 [L]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var17').set('vv_Upper_body', '150*1e-3 [L]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var17').set('vv_Torso', '462*1e-3 [L]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var17').set('vv_lung', '99.9*1e-3 [L]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var17').set('vv_intestin', '43*1e-3 [L]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var17').set('vv_Lower_body', '700*1e-3 [L]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var17').set('vv_brain', '150*1e-3 [L]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var17').set('vv_kidney', '28.4*1e-3 [L]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var17').set('vv_Cardiac_vessels', '100*1e-3 [L]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var17').set('vv_ventricle', '200*1e-3 [L]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var19').set('L_tumor', '0 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var19').set('Q_Lnode', '0 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var19').set('Q_tumor', '0 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_spleen', '1e-3*60*24 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_liver', '1e-3*60*24 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_Upper_body', '1e-3*60*24 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_Torso', '1e-3*60*24 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_lung', '1e-3*60*24 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_intestin', '1e-3*60*24 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_Lower_body', '1e-3*60*24 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_brain', '1e-3*60*24 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_kidney', '1e-3*60*24 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3*60*24 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f87', '-ka_liver*y87*y14+kd_liver*y15');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_spleen', '1e-3*60*24 [1/M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_liver', '1e-3*60*24 [1/M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_Upper_body', '1e-3*60*24 [1/M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_Torso', '1e-3*60*24 [1/M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_lung', '1e-3*60*24 [1/M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_intestin', '1e-3*60*24 [1/M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_Lower_body', '1e-3*60*24 [1/M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_brain', '1e-3*60*24 [1/M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_kidney', '1e-3*60*24 [1/M/d]');
```

```
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3*60*24  
[1/M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_lung', '1 [L/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_liver', '1 [L/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_spleen', '1 [L/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Upper_body', '1 [L/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Torso', '1 [L/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Intestine', '1 [L/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Lower_body', '1 [L/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Brain', '1 [L/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_kidney', '1 [L/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Cardiac_vessels', '1 [L/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_lung', '1 [M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_liver', '1 [M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_spleen', '1 [M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Upper_body', '1 [M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Torso', '1[M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Intestine', '1 [M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Lower_body', '1[M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Brain', '1 [M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_kidney', '1 [M/d]');  
  
model.component('comp1').physics('Cb').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '+KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2-  
KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Cb-Kint*Cb+p_lung/kk*y7-disinfa_lung*y7', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Cb').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '+KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2-  
KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Cb-Kint*Cb+p_lung/kk*Cb-disinfa_lung*Cb', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').active(true);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode6').active(true);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode8').active(true);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode8').active(false);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode6').active(false);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').active(false);  
  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('first', '1');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').active(false);  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').active(true);  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').clear;  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y1', '0 [M]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y2', '0 [M]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y3', '0 [M]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y4', '0 [M]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y5', '0 [M]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y6', '0 [M]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y7', '0 [M]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y8', '0 [M]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y9', '0 [M]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y10', '0 [M]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y11', '0 [M]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y12', '0 [M]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y13', '0 [M]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y14', '0 [M]');
```



```
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y1', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y42', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y46', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y50', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y58', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y66', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y77', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y13', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y37', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y41', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y45', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y49', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y53', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y61', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y69', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y106', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y112', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y113', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y104', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y114', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y115', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y116', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y118', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y120', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y99', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y101', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y80', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y89', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y91', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y93', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y95', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('y97', '0 [M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('first', '1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_lung', '0 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_liver', '0 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_spleen', '0 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Upper_body', '0 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Torso', '0 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Intestine', '0 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Lower_body', '0 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Brain', '0 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_kidney', '0 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Cardiac_vessels', '0 [L/d]');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Cardiac_vessels', '1 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_kidney', '1 [M/d]');
```

```
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Brain', '1e-3 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_kidney', '1e-3 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3[L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Lower_body', '1e-3[M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Intestine', '1e-3[M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Torso', '1e-3[M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Upper_body', '1e-3 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_spleen', '1e-3 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_liver', '1e-3 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_lung', '1e-3 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3 [L/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Intestine', '1e-3 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Torso', '1e-3 [M/d]');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f105', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*y105+mt_lung*ac*Vint/(ACE2+1)*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_lung-
d_lung*y105*vv_lung)/vv_lung');

model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(('Vint'
'u122'));
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(('Vint' 'u122'
'u123'));
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(('Vint' 'u122'
'u123' 'u124'));
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(('Vint' 'u122'
'u123' 'u124' 'u125'));
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(('Vint' 'u122'
'u123' 'u124' 'u125' 'u126'));
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(('Vint' 'u122'
'u123' 'u124' 'u125' 'u126' 'u127'));
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(('Vint' 'u122'
'u123' 'u124' 'u125' 'u126' 'u127' 'u128'));
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(('Vint' 'u122'
'u123' 'u124' 'u125' 'u126' 'u127' 'u128' 'u129'));
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(('Vint' 'u122'
'u123' 'u124' 'u125' 'u126' 'u127' 'u128' 'u129' 'u1210'));
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(2, 'Vint1');
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(3, 'Vint2');
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(4, 'Vint3');
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(5, 'Vint4');
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(6, 'Vint5');
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(7, 'Vint6');
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(8, 'Vint7');
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(9, 'Vint8');
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').field('dimensionless').component(10, 'Vint9');
model.component('comp1').physics('Cb').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '+KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2-
KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Cb-Kint*Cb-disinfa_lung*Cb', 0);
```

```
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Cb+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Cb+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint1', 1);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Cb+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint2', 2);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Cb+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint3', 3);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Cb+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint4', 4);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Cb+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint5', 5);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Cb+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint6', 6);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Cb+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint7', 7);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Cb+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint8', 8);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Cb+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint9', 9);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Vint+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Vint1+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint1', 1);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Vint2+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint2', 2);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Vint3+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint3', 3);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Vint4+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint4', 4);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Vint5+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint5', 5);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Vint6+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint6', 6);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Vint7+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint7', 7);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Vint8+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint8', 8);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Vint9+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint9', 9);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Vint1+Kint*y15-Ka*Vint1', 1);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Vint2+Kint*y19-Ka*Vint2', 2);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Vint3+Kint*y23-Ka*Vint3', 3);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Vint4+Kint*y27-Ka*Vint4', 4);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓  
'p_lung/kk*Vint5+Kint*y31-Ka*Vint5', 5);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
```

```
'p_lung/kk*Vint6+Kint*y55-Ka*Vint6', 6);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'p_lung/kk*Vint7+Kint*y63-Ka*Vint7', 7);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'p_lung/kk*Vint8+Kint*y71-Ka*Vint8', 8);

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f15', '(ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver-
kd_liver*y15*vv_liver+p_liver/kk*y15*vv_liver-disinfa_liver*y15*vv_liver)/vv_liver-
Kint*y15');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f19', '(ka_spleen*y102*y18*vv_spleen-
kd_spleen*y19*vv_spleen+p_spleen/kk*y19*vv_spleen-disinfa_spleen*y19*vv_spleen)
/vv_spleen-Kint*y19');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f23',
'(ka_Upper_body*y92*y22*vv_Upper_body-
kd_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body+p_Upper_body/kk*y23*vv_Upper_body-
disinfa_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body-Kint*y23');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f27', '(ka_Torso*y90*y26*vv_Torso-
kd_Torso*y27*vv_Torso+p_Torso/kk*y27*vv_Torso-disinfa_Torso*y27*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso-
Kint*y27');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f31', '(ka_intestin*y103*y30*vv_intestin-
kd_intestin*y31*vv_intestin+p_Intestine/kk*y31*vv_intestin-
disinfa_Intestine*y31*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin-Kint*y31');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f55',
'(ka_Lower_body*y94*y54*vv_Lower_body-
kd_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body+p_Lower_body/kk*y55*vv_Lower_body-
disinfa_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body-Kint*y55');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f63', '(ka_brain*y96*y62*vv_brain-
kd_brain*y63*vv_brain+p_Brain/kk*y63*vv_brain-disinfa_Brain*y63*vv_brain)/vv_brain-
Kint*y63');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f71', '(ka_kidney*y98*y70*vv_kidney-
kd_kidney*y71*vv_kidney+p_kidney/kk*y71*vv_kidney-disinfa_kidney*y71*vv_kidney)
/vv_kidney-Kint*y71');

model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'p_lung/kk*Vint9+Kint*75-Ka*Vint9', 9);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'p_lung/kk*Vint9+Kint*y75-Ka*Vint9', 9);

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f75',
'(ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels+p_Cardiac_vessels/kk*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
disinfa_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels-Kint*y75');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f14', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30+
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y18+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)
*y5*freeTcell_trafficliver-(Q_liver-L_liver)*y14-
ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver+kd_liver*y15*vv_liver-disinf_liver*y14*vv_liver)
/vv_liver+Ka*Vint1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f18',
'(Q_spleen*y5*freeTcell_trafficspleen-(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y18-
ka_spleen*y102*y18*vv_spleen+kd_spleen*y19*vv_spleen-disinf_spleen*y18*vv_spleen)
/vv_spleen+Ka*Vint2');
```

```
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f22', ✓
'(Q_Upper_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficUpper_body-(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y22-✓
ka_Upper_body*y92*y22*vv_Upper_body+kd_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body-✓
disinf_Upper_body*y22*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body+Ka*Vint3');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f26', ✓
'(Q_Torso*y5*freeTcell_trafficTorso-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26-✓
ka_Torso*y90*y26*vv_Torso+kd_Torso*y27*vv_Torso-disinf_Torso*y26*vv_Torso) ✓
/vv_Torso+Ka*Vint4');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f30', ✓
'(Q_intestin*y5*freeTcell_trafficintestine-(Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30-✓
ka_intestin*y103*y30*vv_intestin+kd_intestin*y31*vv_intestin-✓
disinf_Intestine*y30*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin+Ka*Vint5');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f54', ✓
'(Q_Lower_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficLower_body-(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54-✓
ka_Lower_body*y94*y54*vv_Lower_body+kd_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body-✓
disinf_Lower_body*y54*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body+Ka*Vint6');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f62', ✓
'(Q_brain*y5*freeTcell_trafficbrain-(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62-✓
ka_brain*y96*y62*vv_brain+kd_brain*y63*vv_brain-disinf_Brain*y62*vv_brain) ✓
/vv_brain+Ka*Vint7');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f70', ✓
'(Q_kidney*y5*freeTcell_traffickidney-(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y70-✓
ka_kidney*y98*y70*vv_kidney+kd_kidney*y71*vv_kidney-disinf_kidney*y70*vv_kidney) ✓
/vv_kidney+Ka*Vint8');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f74', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y5-✓
(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y74-✓
ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels+kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels-✓
disinf_Cardiac_vessels*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels+Ka*Vint9');

model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'p_Cardiac_vessels/kk*Vint9+Kint*y75-Ka*Vint9', 9);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'p_kidney/kk*Vint8+Kint*y71-Ka*Vint8', 8);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'p_Brain/kk*Vint7+Kint*y63-Ka*Vint7', 7);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'p_Lower_body/kk*Vint6+Kint*y55-Ka*Vint6', 6);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'p_Intestine/kk*Vint5+Kint*y31-Ka*Vint5', 5);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'p_Torso/kk*Vint4+Kint*y27-Ka*Vint4', 4);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'p_Upper_body/kk*Vint3+Kint*y23-Ka*Vint3', 3);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'p_spleen/kk*Vint2+Kint*y19-Ka*Vint2', 2);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'p_liver/kk*Vint1+Kint*y15-Ka*Vint1', 1);

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f107', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y111+✓
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y108+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y85- (Q_liver-✓
L_liver)*y107+mt_liver*ac*Vint1/(y87+1)*vv_liver+mt_liver*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_liver-✓
```

```
d_liver*y107*vv_liver)/vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f108', '(Q_spleen*y85-(Q_spleen-L_spleen)
*y108+mt_spleen*ac*Vint2/(y102+1)*vv_spleen+mt_spleen*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_spleen-
d_spleen*y108*vv_spleen)/vv_spleen');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f109', '(Q_Upper_body*y85-(Q_Upper_body-
L_Upper_body)*y109+mt_Upper_body*ac*Vint3/(y92+1)*vv_Upper_body+mt_Upper_body*ac*IL6/
(IL6+1)*vv_Upper_body-d_Upper_body*y109*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f110', '(Q_Torso*y85-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)
*y110+mt_Torso*ac*Vint4/(y90+1)*vv_Torso+mt_Torso*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_Torso-
d_Torso*y110*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f111', '(Q_intestin*y85-(Q_intestin-
L_intestin)*y111+mt_Intestine*ac*Vint5/(y103+1)*vv_intestin+mt_Intestine*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)
*vv_intestin-d_Intestine*y111*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f117', '(Q_Lower_body*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-
(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y117*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Lower_body*ac*Vint6/(y94+1)
*vv_Lower_body+mt_Lower_body*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_Lower_body-
d_Lower_body*y117*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f119', '(Q_brain*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-
(Q_brain-L_brain)*y119*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Brain*ac*Vint7/(y96+1)*vv_brain+mt_Brain*ac*IL6/
(IL6+1)*vv_brain-d_Brain*y119*vv_brain)/vv_brain');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f121', '(Q_kidney*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-
(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y121*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_kidney*ac*Vint8/(y98+1)
*vv_kidney+mt_kidney*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_kidney-d_kidney*y121*vv_kidney)/vv_kidney');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f124',
'(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)
*y124*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Cardiac_vessels*ac*Vint9/(y125+1)
*vv_Cardiac_vessels+mt_Cardiac_vessels*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
d_Cardiac_vessels*y124*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3 [M/d]');

model.sol('sol54').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Vint1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f14', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30+
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y18+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)
*y5*freeTcell_trafficliver-(Q_liver-L_liver)*y14-
ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver+kd_liver*y15*vv_liver-disinf_liver*y14*vv_liver)
/vv_liver+Ka*Vint1-KsACE2*sACE2*y14');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f18',
'(Q_spleen*y5*freeTcell_trafficspleen-(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y18-
ka_spleen*y102*y18*vv_spleen+kd_spleen*y19*vv_spleen-disinf_spleen*y18*vv_spleen)
/vv_spleen+Ka*Vint2-KsACE2*sACE2*y18');
```

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model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f22', ✓
'(Q_Upper_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficUpper_body-(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y22-✓
ka_Upper_body*y92*y22*vV_Upper_body+kd_Upper_body*y23*vV_Upper_body-✓
disinf_Upper_body*y22*vV_Upper_body)/vV_Upper_body+Ka*Vint3-KsACE2*sACE2*y22');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f26', ✓
'(Q_Torso*y5*freeTcell_trafficTorso-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26-✓
ka_Torso*y90*y26*vV_Torso+kd_Torso*y27*vV_Torso-disinf_Torso*y26*vV_Torso) ✓
/vV_Torso+Ka*Vint4-KsACE2*sACE2*y26');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f30', ✓
'(Q_intestin*y5*freeTcell_trafficintestine-(Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30-✓
ka_intestin*y103*y30*vV_intestin+kd_intestin*y31*vV_intestin-✓
disinf_Intestine*y30*vV_intestin)/vV_intestin+Ka*Vint5-KsACE2*sACE2*y30');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f54', ✓
'(Q_Lower_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficLower_body-(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54-✓
ka_Lower_body*y94*y54*vV_Lower_body+kd_Lower_body*y55*vV_Lower_body-✓
disinf_Lower_body*y54*vV_Lower_body)/vV_Lower_body+Ka*Vint6-KsACE2*sACE2*y54');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f62', ✓
'(Q_brain*y5*freeTcell_trafficbrain-(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62-✓
ka_brain*y96*y62*vV_brain+kd_brain*y63*vV_brain-disinf_Brain*y62*vV_brain) ✓
/vV_brain+Ka*Vint7-KsACE2*sACE2*y62');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f70', ✓
'(Q_kidney*y5*freeTcell_traffickidney-(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y70-✓
ka_kidney*y98*y70*vV_kidney+kd_kidney*y71*vV_kidney-disinf_kidney*y70*vV_kidney) ✓
/vV_kidney+Ka*Vint8-KsACE2*sACE2*y70');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f74', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y5-✓
(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y74-✓
ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74*vV_Cardiac_vessels+kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vV_Cardiac_vessels-✓
disinf_Cardiac_vessels*y74*vV_Cardiac_vessels)/vV_Cardiac_vessels+Ka*Vint9-✓
KsACE2*sACE2*y74');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y14');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Vint2');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f14', '(Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30+✓
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y18+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen) ✓
*y5*freeTcell_trafficliver-(Q_liver-L_liver)*y14-✓
ka_liver*y87*y14*vV_liver+kd_liver*y15*vV_liver-disinf_liver*y14*vV_liver) ✓
/vV_liver+Ka*Vint1-0*KsACE2*sACE2*y14');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f18', ✓
'(Q_spleen*y5*freeTcell_trafficspleen-(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y18-✓
ka_spleen*y102*y18*vV_spleen+kd_spleen*y19*vV_spleen-disinf_spleen*y18*vV_spleen) ✓
/vV_spleen+Ka*Vint2-0*KsACE2*sACE2*y18');
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model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f22',
'(Q_Upper_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficUpper_body-(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y22-
ka_Upper_body*y92*y22*vv_Upper_body+kd_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body-
disinf_Upper_body*y22*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body+Ka*Vint3-0*KsACE2*sACE2*y22');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f26',
'(Q_Torso*y5*freeTcell_trafficTorso-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26-
ka_Torso*y90*y26*vv_Torso+kd_Torso*y27*vv_Torso-disinf_Torso*y26*vv_Torso)
/vv_Torso+Ka*Vint4-0*KsACE2*sACE2*y26');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f30',
'(Q_intestin*y5*freeTcell_trafficintestine-(Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30-
ka_intestin*y103*y30*vv_intestin+kd_intestin*y31*vv_intestin-
disinf_Intestine*y30*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin+Ka*Vint5-0*KsACE2*sACE2*y30');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f54',
'(Q_Lower_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficLower_body-(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54-
ka_Lower_body*y94*y54*vv_Lower_body+kd_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body-
disinf_Lower_body*y54*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body+Ka*Vint6-0*KsACE2*sACE2*y54');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f62',
'(Q_brain*y5*freeTcell_trafficbrain-(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62-
ka_brain*y96*y62*vv_brain+kd_brain*y63*vv_brain-disinf_Brain*y62*vv_brain)
/vv_brain+Ka*Vint7-0*KsACE2*sACE2*y62');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f70',
'(Q_kidney*y5*freeTcell_traffickidney-(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y70-
ka_kidney*y98*y70*vv_kidney+kd_kidney*y71*vv_kidney-disinf_kidney*y70*vv_kidney)
/vv_kidney+Ka*Vint8-0*KsACE2*sACE2*y70');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f74', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y5-
(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y74-
ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels+kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
disinf_Cardiac_vessels*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels+Ka*Vint9-
0*KsACE2*sACE2*y74');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f74', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y5-
(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y74-
ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels+kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
disinf_Cardiac_vessels*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels+Ka*Vint9-0.1
*KsACE2*sACE2*y74');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f70',
'(Q_kidney*y5*freeTcell_traffickidney-(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y70-
ka_kidney*y98*y70*vv_kidney+kd_kidney*y71*vv_kidney-disinf_kidney*y70*vv_kidney)
/vv_kidney+Ka*Vint8-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y70');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f62',
'(Q_brain*y5*freeTcell_trafficbrain-(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62-
ka_brain*y96*y62*vv_brain+kd_brain*y63*vv_brain-disinf_Brain*y62*vv_brain)
/vv_brain+Ka*Vint7-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y62');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f54',
'(Q_Lower_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficLower_body-(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54-
ka_Lower_body*y94*y54*vv_Lower_body+kd_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body-
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disinf_Lower_body*y54*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body+Ka*Vint6-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y54');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f30',
'(Q_intestin*y5*freeTcell_trafficintestine-(Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30-
ka_intestin*y103*y30*vv_intestin+kd_intestin*y31*vv_intestin-
disinf_Intestine*y30*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin+Ka*Vint5-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y30');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f26',
'(Q_Torso*y5*freeTcell_trafficTorso-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26-
ka_Torso*y90*y26*vv_Torso+kd_Torso*y27*vv_Torso-disinf_Torso*y26*vv_Torso)
/vv_Torso+Ka*Vint4-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y26');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f22',
'(Q_Upper_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficUpper_body-(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y22-
ka_Upper_body*y92*y22*vv_Upper_body+kd_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body-
disinf_Upper_body*y22*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body+Ka*Vint3-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y22');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f18',
'(Q_spleen*y5*freeTcell_trafficspleen-(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y18-
ka_spleen*y102*y18*vv_spleen+kd_spleen*y19*vv_spleen-disinf_spleen*y18*vv_spleen)
/vv_spleen+Ka*Vint2-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y18');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f14', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30+
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y18+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)
*y5*freeTcell_trafficliver-(Q_liver-L_liver)*y14-
ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver+kd_liver*y15*vv_liver-disinf_liver*y14*vv_liver)
/vv_liver+Ka*Vint1-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y14');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('Coupled Baseline add Matlab EQ_clear_Method and Termination Autoimatic
Newton.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('sACE2').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SsACE2-
KsACE2*sACE2*Ci+KAdam17*ACE2-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-
KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-
KsACE2*sACE2*Ci', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('sACE2').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SsACE2-
KsACE2*sACE2*Ci+KAdam17*ACE2-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-
KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-
KsACE2*sACE2*y74', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('sACE2').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SsACE2-
KsACE2*sACE2*Ci+KAdam17*ACE2-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-
KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*y-KsACE2*sACE2*y70-
KsACE2*sACE2*y74', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('sACE2').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SsACE2-
KsACE2*sACE2*Ci+KAdam17*ACE2-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-
KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*y62-KsACE2*sACE2*y70-
KsACE2*sACE2*y74', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('sACE2').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SsACE2-
KsACE2*sACE2*Ci+KAdam17*ACE2-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-
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KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*y54-KsACE2*sACE2*y62-KsACE2*sACE2*y70-  
KsACE2*sACE2*y74', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('sACE2').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SsACE2-  
KsACE2*sACE2*Ci+KAdam17*ACE2-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-  
KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*y30-KsACE2*sACE2*y54-KsACE2*sACE2*y62-KsACE2*sACE2*y70-  
KsACE2*sACE2*y74', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('sACE2').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SsACE2-  
KsACE2*sACE2*Ci+KAdam17*ACE2-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-  
KsACE2*sACE2*y26-KsACE2*sACE2*y30-KsACE2*sACE2*y54-KsACE2*sACE2*y62-KsACE2*sACE2*y70-  
KsACE2*sACE2*y74', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('sACE2').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SsACE2-  
KsACE2*sACE2*Ci+KAdam17*ACE2-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*y22-  
KsACE2*sACE2*y26-KsACE2*sACE2*y30-KsACE2*sACE2*y54-KsACE2*sACE2*y62-KsACE2*sACE2*y70-  
KsACE2*sACE2*y74', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('sACE2').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SsACE2-  
KsACE2*sACE2*Ci+KAdam17*ACE2-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KsACE2*sACE2*y18-KsACE2*sACE2*y22-  
KsACE2*sACE2*y26-KsACE2*sACE2*y30-KsACE2*sACE2*y54-KsACE2*sACE2*y62-KsACE2*sACE2*y70-  
KsACE2*sACE2*y74', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('sACE2').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SsACE2-  
KsACE2*sACE2*Ci+KAdam17*ACE2-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y14-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y18-0.1  
*KsACE2*sACE2*y22-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y26-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y30-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y54-0.1  
*KsACE2*sACE2*y62-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y70-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y74', 0);  
  
model.sol('sol154').runAll;  
  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y14');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
  
model.label('Coupled Baseline add Matlab EQ_clear_Method and Termination Autoimatic  
Newton.mph');  
  
model.result('pg40').run;  
  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_lung', '1e-1 [M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_liver', '1e-1 [M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_spleen', '1e-1 [M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Upper_body', '1e-1 [M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Torso', '1e-1 [M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Intestine', '1e-1 [M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Lower_body', '1e-1 [M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Brain', '1e-1 [M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_kidney', '1e-1 [M/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-1 [M/d]');  
  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y105');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
  
model.sol('sol154').runAll;
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model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'ACE2');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y92');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y90');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y26');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y27');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_spleen', '1e-3*60*24 [1/mM/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_liver', '1e-3*60*24 [1/mM/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_Upper_body', '1e-3*60*24 [1/mM/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_Torso', '1e-3*60*24 [1/mM/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_lung', '1e-3*60*24 [1/mM/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_intestin', '1e-3*60*24 [1/mM/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_Lower_body', '1e-3*60*24 [1/mM/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_brain', '1e-3*60*24 [1/mM/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_kidney', '1e-3*60*24 [1/mM/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var7').set('ka_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-3*60*24
[1/mM/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_lung', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_liver', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_spleen', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Upper_body', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Torso', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Intestine', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Lower_body', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Brain', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_kidney', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-1 [1/d]');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y105');
model.result('pg40').run;
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model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').set('xlog', true);
model.result('pg40').set('ylog', true);
model.result('pg40').set('xlog', false);
model.result('pg40').set('ylog', false);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Vint5');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y105');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_liver', '1*1000 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_lung', '1*1000 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_spleen', '0.1*1000 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_Upper_body', '1.1*1000 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_Torso', '2*1000 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_Intestine', '0.7*1000 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_Lower_body', '0.9*1000 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_Brain', '1.4*1000 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_kidney', '1.1*1000 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_Cardiac_vessels', '1.8*1000 [1/d]');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_lung', '1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_liver', '1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_spleen', '1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Upper_body', '1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Torso', '1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Intestine', '1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Lower_body', '1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Brain', '1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_kidney', '1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Cardiac_vessels', '1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_lung', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_liver', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_spleen', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Upper_body', '1e-1 [1/d]');
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```
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Torso', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Intestine', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Lower_body', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Brain', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_kidney', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var14').set('d_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-1 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_lung', '1e-2 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_liver', '1e-2 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_spleen', '1e-2 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Upper_body', '1e-2 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Torso', '1e-2 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Intestine', '1e-2 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Lower_body', '1e-2 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Brain', '1e-2 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_kidney', '1e-2 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-2 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_liver', '1*10 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_lung', '1*10 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_spleen', '0.1*10 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_Upper_body', '1.1*10 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_Torso', '2*10 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_Intestine', '0.7*10 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_Lower_body', '0.9*10 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_Brain', '1.4*10 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_kidney', '1.1*10 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var11').set('p_Cardiac_vessels', '1.8*10 [1/d]');
```

```
model.sol('sol54').runAll;
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Vint2');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y14');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y15');
model.result('pg40').run;
```

```
model.label('New Coupled Baseline add Matlab EQ_clear_Method and Termination Automatic  
Newton.mph');
```

```
model.setGroupByType(false);
model.component('comp1').setGroupByType(false);

model.component('comp1').physics('AGT').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('Renin').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('AngI').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('AngII').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ang17').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ang19').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('AngIII').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('AngIV').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('AT1bAngII').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('AT2bAngII').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('AT4bAngIV').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('MAsbAng17').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('Cb').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('H').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('n').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('ma').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('c').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ct1').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('a').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('AT1R').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('AT2R').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('MASR').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('AT4R').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('ACE2').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('ACE2bAngI').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('ACE2bAngII').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('IL6').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('IL6R').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('IL6RbIL6').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('sIL6RbIL6').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('VEGF').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('sIL6R').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('sACE2').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('cox_oxygen').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode2').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode3').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode4').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode6').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode7').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode8').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode9').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
```

```
model.component('comp1').physics('dode10').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode11').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode12').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode13').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode14').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode15').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode16').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode17').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode18').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode19').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode20').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode21').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode22').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode24').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode23').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode25').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode26').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode27').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode28').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode29').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode30').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode31').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode32').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode33').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode34').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode35').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode36').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode37').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode38').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode39').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode40').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode41').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode42').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode43').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode44').setGroupBySpaceDimension(false);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y105');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var6').remove('bKa');

model.param.set('bKa', '1');

model.sol('sol54').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Cb');
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y125');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('New Coupled Baseline add Matlab EQ_clear_Method and Termination Autoimatic
Newton_run.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KonACE2V', '17 [ml/h/nmol]*0');

model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-
Kd*Ci+Kin*In*bin', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n-
phict1*In*Ctl-+Kin*In', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kin', '1/24[1/h]');

model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n-
phict1*In*Ctl-Kin*In', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kin', '(1/24)[1/h]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('bin', '1e12[fmol/ml]');

model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', 'Kin*In*bin', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-
Kd*Ci+Kin*In*bin', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('bin', '1e12[fmol]');

model.study('std1').feature('time').set('plot', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').set('plotfreq', 'tsteps');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci');

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('bin', '1e12[mol]');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('init1').set('Ci', '1.27e-9[M]');

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('New Coupled Baseline add Matlab EQ_clear_Method and Termination Autoimatic
Newton_run_infVirus - Copy.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KsACE2', '8.5[ml/h/nmol]/100');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kd', '2.4e-8[1/s]/100');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'y78');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78*0-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci*0)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-
Kd*Ci+Kin*In*bin', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78*0-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci*0)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci*0-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2*0+KoffACE2V*Cb-
Kd*Ci*0+Kin*In*bin', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature.duplicate('ptgr2', 'ptgr1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('legend', true);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('legend', true);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('autodescr', true);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('autopoint', false);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('autodescr', true);
```

```
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('autopoint', false);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').active(false);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Kin*In*bin');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', '(Q_lung*y78*(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci+Kin*In*bin');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci+Kin*In*bin', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci+Kin*In*bin', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('bin', '1e6[fmol]');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('New Coupled Baseline add Matlab EQ_clear_Method and Termination Autoimatic Newton_run_infVirus - Copy.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').set('ylog', true);
model.result('pg40').set('showmanualgrid', true);
```

```
model.result('pg40').set('showxspacing', true);
model.result('pg40').set('showyspacing', false);
model.result('pg40').set('showsecyspacing', false);
model.result('pg40').set('showsecyextra', false);
model.result('pg40').set('ylog', false);
model.result('pg40').set('showmanualgrid', true);
model.result('pg40').set('showxspacing', true);
model.result('pg40').set('showyspacing', true);
model.result('pg40').set('showsecyspacing', false);
model.result('pg40').set('showsecyextra', false);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kin', '(1/24)[1/h]/1000');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').active(true);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', 'fmol/m^3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('bin', '1e1[fmol]');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').set('ylog', false);
model.result('pg40').set('showmanualgrid', true);
model.result('pg40').set('showxspacing', true);
model.result('pg40').set('showyspacing', true);
model.result('pg40').set('showsecyspacing', false);
model.result('pg40').set('showsecyextra', false);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').active(false);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').active(true);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').active(false);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').active(true);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ct1');
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').active(false);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)-  
gam_n*n/1000-gam_m*n*ma/100-gam_v*n*Ci/100+xIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)-  
gam_n*n/1000-gam_m*n*ma/100-gam_v*n*Ci/100+xIL6*IL6RbIL6*10', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)-  
gam_n*n/1000-gam_m*n*ma/1000-gam_v*n*Ci/100+xIL6*IL6RbIL6*1000', 0);

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n-  
phictl*In*Ctl/100-Kin*In', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n-  
phictl*In*Ctl*0-Kin*In', 0);

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)-  
gam_n*n*0-gam_m*n*ma*0-gam_v*n*Ci*0+xIL6*IL6RbIL6*1000', 0);

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('New Coupled Baseline add Matlab EQ_clear_Method and Termination Autoimatic
Newton_run_infVirus_neutrophil3 - Copy.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6/IL60');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6/IL60/1e8');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6/IL60/1e8+1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(IL6/IL60/1e8+1)*exp(10)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'exp(10)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'exp(Ci)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'exp(y105)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(IL6/IL60/1e8+1)*y105');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(IL6/IL60/1e8+1)*(y105^5)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(IL6/IL60/1e8+1)*(y105^2)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(IL6/IL60/1e8+1)*(y105^1.5)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(IL6/IL60/1e8+1)*(y105^1.5)/200');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(IL6/IL60/1e8)*(y105^1.5)/200');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(IL6/IL60/1e8)*(y105^1.5)/200+1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result.export.create('plot1', 'pg40', 'ptgr2', 'Plot');
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').active(false);
```

```
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').active(false);
model.result.export('plot1').set('header', false);
model.result.export('plot1').set('filename', 'C:\Users\valan\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\new model_combination\comsol Model\IL6_partenr1.txt');
model.result.export('plot1').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('IL6p', '(IL6/IL60/1e8)*(y105^1.5)/200');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('IL6p', '(IL6/IL60/1e8)*(y105^1.5)
/200+1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').rename('IL6p', 'aaa');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(IL6/IL60/1e8)*(y105^2)/200+1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(IL6/IL60/1e8)*(y105^2)/200[mol^2/m^6]
+1');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('aaa', '(IL6/IL60/1e8)*(y105^2)/200
[mol^2/m^6]+1');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Pb');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'manual', 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [1], 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12
13 14], 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12
13], 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [13], 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [12], 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [11 12], 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [10 11 12], 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [7], 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [1], 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', 'kPa');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [2], 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
```

```
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [3], 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [4], 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [3], 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16], 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '((ec/ec0)^8)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '((ec/ec0))');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'iec');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Pbp', 'PA-Vo2max/(((3.3e-8 [cm^2/min/mmHg])*0.5*(SA+SC)/thb)^-1+Deo2^-1)^-1)');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'all', 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PA-Vo2max/(((3.3e-8 [cm^2/min/mmHg])*0.5*(SA+SC)/thb)^-1+Deo2^-1)^-1)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', 'kPa');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PA-Vo2max/(((3.3e-8 [cm^2/min/mmHg]*(1/iec/ec0))*0.5*(SA+SC)/thb)^-1+Deo2^-1)^-1)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PA-Vo2max/(((3.3e-8 [cm^2/min/mmHg]*(1/iec))*0.5*(SA+SC)/thb)^-1+Deo2^-1)^-1)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PA-Vo2max/(((3.3e-8 [cm^2/min/mmHg])*0.5*(SA+SC)/thb)^-1+Deo2^-1)^-1)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(PA-Vo2max/(((3.3e-8 [cm^2/min/mmHg])*0.5*(SA+SC)/thb)^-1+Deo2^-1)^-1)*y105)');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('Pbp', '(PA-Vo2max/(((3.3e-8 [cm^2/min/mmHg])*0.5*(SA+SC)/thb)^-1+Deo2^-1)^-1)*y105)');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').rename('aaa', 'IL6p');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ctl');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '((PA-Vo2max/(((3.3e-8 [cm^2/min/mmHg])*0.5*(SA+SC)/thb)^-1+Deo2^-1)^-1)*y105)*abs(Ctl/4e18[1/m^3])');
model.result('pg40').run;
```

```
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '((PA-Vo2max/(((3.3e-8[cm^2/min/mmHg])  
*0.5*(SA+SC)/thb)^-1+Deo2^-1)^-1))*abs(Ctl/4e18[1/m^3])');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '((PA-Vo2max/(((3.3e-8[cm^2/min/mmHg])  
*0.5*(SA+SC)/thb)^-1+Deo2^-1)^-1))* (Ctl/4e18[1/m^3])');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '((PA-Vo2max/(((3.3e-8[cm^2/min/mmHg])  
*0.5*(SA+SC)/thb)^-1+Deo2^-1)^-1))* (-Ctl/4e18[1/m^3])');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '((PA-Vo2max/(((3.3e-8[cm^2/min/mmHg])  
*0.5*(SA+SC)/thb)^-1+Deo2^-1)^-1))* (Ctl/-4e18[1/m^3])');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '((PA-Vo2max/(((3.3e-8[cm^2/min/mmHg])  
*0.5*(SA+SC)/thb)^-1+Deo2^-1)^-1))* (Ctl/4e18[1/m^3])');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').active(false);  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').active(true);  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', '1/Ci');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci-70e-15');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci-70e-5');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ci/70e-5');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'n');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ctl');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', '-Ctl');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', '1/(-Ctl)');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', '(-Ctl)');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ctl');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'Ctl+5e18');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', '(Ctl+5e18)/5e18');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', '(Ctl+5e18)/5e18');  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '((PA-Vo2max/(((3.3e-8[cm^2/min/mmHg])  
*0.5*(SA+SC)/thb)^-1+Deo2^-1)^-1))* ((Ctl+5e18)/5e18)');  
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').active(true);
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').active(false);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '((PA-Vo2max/(((3.3e-8[cm^2/min/mmHg])
*0.5*(SA+SC)/thb)^-1+Deo2^-1)^-1))*((Ct1+5e18[1/m^3])/5e18[1/m^3])');
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', 'kPa');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result.export.create('plot2', 'pg40', 'ptgr2', 'Plot');
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').active(false);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').active(false);
model.result.export('plot2').set('filename', 'C:\Users\valan\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\new model_combination\comsol Model\Po2_partenr1.txt');
model.result.export('plot2').set('header', false);
model.result.export('plot2').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('Po2p', '((PA-Vo2max/(((3.3e-8
[cm^2/min/mmHg]) *0.5*(SA+SC)/thb)^-1+Deo2^-1)^-1))*((Ct1+5e18[1/m^3])/5e18[1/m^3])');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y119');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result.export.create('plot3', 'pg40', 'ptgr2', 'Plot');
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').active(false);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').active(false);
model.result.export('plot3').set('header', false);
model.result.export('plot3').set('filename', 'C:\Users\valan\Dropbox\Univercity of
Cyprus\3a.Project\34. Covic-19\new model_combination\comsol Model\brain_thro.txt');
model.result.export('plot3').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').active(false);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').active(false);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(IL6/IL60/1e8)*(y105^2)/200[mol^2/m^6]
+1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '((IL6/IL60/1e8)*(y105^2)/200
[mol^2/m^6]+1)*Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(IL6/IL60/1e8)*(y105^2)/200
[mol^2/m^6]+1)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '((PA-Vo2max/(((3.3e-8[cm^2/min/mmHg])
*0.5*(SA+SC)/thb)^-1+Deo2^-1)^-1))*((Ct1+5e18[1/m^3])/5e18[1/m^3])');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vi');
```

```
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('Vi', '(y105/5e14)*(Ci^5)/(1.27e-9[M])5');
model.component('comp1').variable('var21').remove('Pbp');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('New Coupled Baseline add Matlab EQ_patient1.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').label('Virus');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vi+1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('expr', 'IL6p');
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').active(true);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('autodescr', true);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('autopoint', false);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('descraactive', true);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').set('descr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr1').label('IL6');
model.result('pg40').feature.remove('ptgr1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result.duplicate('pg41', 'pg40');
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6p');
model.result('pg41').feature('ptgr2').set('descraactive', true);
model.result('pg41').feature('ptgr2').set('descr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6p/2');
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6p/2+1');
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6p/2.2+1');
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6p/2.5+1');
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').feature('ptgr2').label('IL6');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').label('1D Plot (Virus)');
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').label('1D Plot IL6');
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
```

```
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result.duplicate('pg42', 'pg41');
model.result('pg42').run;
model.result('pg42').label('1D Plot Po2');
model.result('pg42').run;
model.result('pg42').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Po2p');
model.result('pg42').run;
model.result('pg42').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', 'kPa');
model.result('pg42').run;
model.result('pg42').run;
model.result('pg42').run;
model.result('pg42').feature('ptgr2').label('Po2');
model.result('pg42').feature('ptgr2').set('descr', 'Po2');
model.result('pg42').run;
model.result('pg42').run;
model.result.duplicate('pg43', 'pg42');
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result('pg43').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y119');
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result('pg43').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y119/10');
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result('pg43').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y119/9');
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result('pg43').label('1D Plot y119');
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result('pg43').feature('ptgr2').label('y119');
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result.remove('pg43');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg42').run;
model.result.duplicate('pg43', 'pg42');
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result('pg43').label('1D Plot y119');
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result('pg43').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y119/9');
model.result('pg43').feature('ptgr2').set('descr', 'y119');
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('Vip', 'Vi+1');

model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('IL6p1', 'IL6p/2.5+1');
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vip');
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6p1');
model.result('pg42').run;
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result('pg43').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'mtB');

model.component('comp1').variable('var21').set('mtB', 'y119');

model.result('pg42').run;

model.sol('sol54').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg42').run;
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result('pg43').feature('ptgr2').label('y119');

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('bin', '1e1[fmol]/bKa');

model.param.set('bKa', '1000');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vip');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol54').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vip');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.param.set('bKa', '1');
model.param.remove('bKa');

model.component('comp1').variable('var6').set('bKa', '999*(t>4[d])+1');

model.sol('sol54').runAll;
```

```

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var6').set('bKa', '999*(t>7[d])+1');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('New Coupled Baseline add Matlab EQ_patient1_remdesivir_day7.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_lung', '1e-2 [M/d]/bHe');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_liver', '1e-2 [M/d]/bHe');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_spleen', '1e-2 [M/d]/bHe');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Upper_body', '1e-2 [M/d]/bHe');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Torso', '1e-2 [M/d]/bHe');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Intestine', '1e-2 [M/d]/bHe');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Lower_body', '1e-2 [M/d]/bHe');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Brain', '1e-2 [M/d]/bHe');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_kidney', '1e-2 [M/d]/bHe');
model.component('comp1').variable('var13').set('mt_Cardiac_vessels', '1e-2 [M/d]/bHe');
model.component('comp1').variable('var6').set('bHe', '999*(t>7[d])+1');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('New Coupled Baseline add Matlab EQ_patient1_remdesivir HeParin_day7.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').clear;
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f5', '(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci-
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q
_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode)*y5)/vv_ventricle');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f78', '(Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y10+(Q_liver-
L_liver)*y14+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)* y34+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)* y38+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)* y1+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_LTorso)* y42+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)* y46+
(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y22+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y50+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)
*y54+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y58+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)*y66+(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y70+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)
*y74+L_Cardiac_vessels*y77*rf_Cardiac_vessels+(L_lung+L_Llung)*y13*rf_Llung+
(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y37*rf_Lintestin+(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*
(rf_Ltumor*y41*heaviside(-y41+500)+1*y41*heaviside(y41-501))+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)
*y45*rf_LTorso+(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y49*rf_LUpper_body+
(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)*y53*rf_LLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y61*rf_Lbrain+
(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)*y69*rf_Lkidney-(Q_lung)*y78)/vv_ventricle');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f85', '(Q_lung-L_lung)*y105-
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q
_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode)*y85)/vv_ventricle');

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```
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f86', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y106+
(Q_liver-L_liver)*y107+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)*y112+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)*y113)+(Q_tumor-
L_tumor)*y104+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LTorso)*y114+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y110+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)
*y115+(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y109+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y116+(Q_Lower_body-
L_Lower_body)*y117+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y118+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y119+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)
*y120+(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y121+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y124+
(L_Cardiac_vessels*y125*rf_kidney)*heaviside(y125-1e-3*first)+(L_lung+L_Llung)
*y99*rf_aLlung+(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y101*rf_aLintestin+
(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*y80*rf_aLtumor+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)*y89*rf_aLTorso+
(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y91*rf_aLUpper_body+(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)
*y93*rf_aLLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y95*rf_aLbrain+(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)
*y97*rf_aLkidney-(Q_lung)*y86*heaviside(y86-1e-3*first))/vv_ventricle');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f6', '(Q_lung*y78-(Q_lung-L_lung)*y6-
ka_lung*y100*y6*vv_lung+kd_lung*y7*vv_lung-disinf_lung*y6*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f7', '(ka_lung*y100*y6*vv_lung-
kd_lung*y7*vv_lung+p_lung/kk*y7*vv_lung-disinfa_lung*y7*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f105', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*y105+mt_lung*ac*Vint/(ACE2+1)*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_lung-
d_lung*y105*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f100', '-ka_lung*y100*y6+kd_lung*y7');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f14', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30+
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y18+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)
*y5*freeTcell_trafficliver-(Q_liver-L_liver)*y14-
ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver+kd_liver*y15*vv_liver-disinf_liver*y14*vv_liver)
/vv_liver+Ka*Vint1-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y14');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f15', '(ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver-
kd_liver*y15*vv_liver+p_liver/kk*y15*vv_liver-disinfa_liver*y15*vv_liver)/vv_liver-
Kint*y15');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f107', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y111+
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y108+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y85-(Q_liver-
L_liver)*y107+mt_liver*ac*Vint1/(y87+1)*vv_liver+mt_liver*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_liver-
d_liver*y107*vv_liver)/vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f87', '-ka_liver*y87*y14+kd_liver*y15');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f18',
'(Q_spleen*y5*freeTcell_traffic spleen-(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y18-
ka_spleen*y102*y18*vv_spleen+kd_spleen*y19*vv_spleen-disinf_spleen*y18*vv_spleen)
/vv_spleen+Ka*Vint2-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y18');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f19', '(ka_spleen*y102*y18*vv_spleen-
kd_spleen*y19*vv_spleen+p_spleen/kk*y19*vv_spleen-disinfa_spleen*y19*vv_spleen)
/vv_spleen-Kint*y19');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f108', '(Q_spleen*y85-(Q_spleen-L_spleen)
*y108+mt_spleen*ac*Vint2/(y102+1)*vv_spleen+mt_spleen*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_spleen-
d_spleen*y108*vv_spleen)/vv_spleen');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f102', '-
ka_spleen*y102*y18+kd_spleen*y19');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f22',
'(Q_Upper_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficUpper_body-(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y22-
ka_Upper_body*y92*y22*vv_Upper_body+kd_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body-
disinf_Upper_body*y22*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body+Ka*Vint3-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y22');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f23',
'(ka_Upper_body*y92*y22*vv_Upper_body-
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kd_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body+p_Upper_body/kk*y23*vv_Upper_body-  
disinfa_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body-Kint*y23');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f109', '(Q_Upper_body*y85-(Q_Upper_body-  
L_Upper_body)*y109+mt_Upper_body*ac*Vint3/(y92+1)*vv_Upper_body+mt_Upper_body*ac*IL6/  
(IL6+1)*vv_Upper_body-d_Upper_body*y109*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f92', '-  
ka_Upper_body*y92*y22+kd_Upper_body*y23');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f26',  
'(Q_Torso*y5*freeTcell_trafficTorso-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26-  
ka_Torso*y90*y26*vv_Torso+kd_Torso*y27*vv_Torso-disinf_Torso*y26*vv_Torso)/  
vv_Torso+Ka*Vint4-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y26');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f27', '(ka_Torso*y90*y26*vv_Torso-  
kd_Torso*y27*vv_Torso+p_Torso/kk*y27*vv_Torso-disinfa_Torso*y27*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso-  
Kint*y27');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f110', '(Q_Torso*y85-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)  
*y110+mt_Torso*ac*Vint4/(y90+1)*vv_Torso+mt_Torso*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_Torso-  
d_Torso*y110*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f90', '-ka_Torso*y90*y26+kd_Torso*y27');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f30',  
'(Q_intestin*y5*freeTcell_trafficintestine-(Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30-  
ka_intestin*y103*y30*vv_intestin+kd_intestin*y31*vv_intestin-  
disinf_Intestine*y30*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin+Ka*Vint5-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y30');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f31', '(ka_intestin*y103*y30*vv_intestin-  
kd_intestin*y31*vv_intestin+p_Intestine/kk*y31*vv_intestin-  
disinfa_Intestine*y31*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin-Kint*y31');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f111', '(Q_intestin*y85-(Q_intestin-  
L_intestin)*y111+mt_Intestine*ac*Vint5/(y103+1)*vv_intestin+mt_Intestine*ac*IL6/  
(IL6+1)*vv_intestin-d_Intestine*y111*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f103', '-  
ka_intestin*y103*y30+kd_intestin*y31');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f54',  
'(Q_Lower_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficLower_body-(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54-  
ka_Lower_body*y94*y54*vv_Lower_body+kd_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body-  
disinf_Lower_body*y54*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body+Ka*Vint6-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y54');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f55',  
'(ka_Lower_body*y94*y54*vv_Lower_body-  
kd_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body+p_Lower_body/kk*y55*vv_Lower_body-  
disinfa_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body-Kint*y55');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f117', '(Q_Lower_body*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-  
(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y117*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Lower_body*ac*Vint6/(y94+1)  
*vv_Lower_body+mt_Lower_body*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_Lower_body-  
d_Lower_body*y117*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f94', '-  
ka_Lower_body*y94*y54+kd_Lower_body*y55');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f62',  
'(Q_brain*y5*freeTcell_trafficbrain-(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62-  
ka_brain*y96*y62*vv_brain+kd_brain*y63*vv_brain-disinf_Brain*y62*vv_brain)/  
vv_brain+Ka*Vint7-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y62');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f63', '(ka_brain*y96*y62*vv_brain-  
kd_brain*y63*vv_brain+p_Brain/kk*y63*vv_brain-disinfa_Brain*y63*vv_brain)/vv_brain-  
Kint*y63');
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model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f119', '(Q_brain*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-  
(Q_brain-L_brain)*y119*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Brain*ac*Vint7/(y96+1)*vv_brain+mt_Brain*ac*IL6/  
(IL6+1)*vv_brain-d_Brain*y119*vv_brain)/vv_brain');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f96', '-ka_brain*y96*y62+kd_brain*y63');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f70',  
'(Q_kidney*y5*freeTcell_traffickidney-(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y70-  
ka_kidney*y98*y70*vv_kidney+kd_kidney*y71*vv_kidney-disinf_kidney*y70*vv_kidney)/  
vv_kidney+Ka*Vint8-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y70');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f71', '(ka_kidney*y98*y70*vv_kidney-  
kd_kidney*y71*vv_kidney+p_kidney/kk*y71*vv_kidney-disinfa_kidney*y71*vv_kidney)/  
vv_kidney-Kint*y71');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f121', '(Q_kidney*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-  
(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y121*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_kidney*ac*Vint8/(y98+1)  
*vv_kidney+mt_kidney*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_kidney-d_kidney*y121*vv_kidney)/vv_kidney');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f98', '-  
ka_kidney*y98*y70+kd_kidney*y71');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f74', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y5-  
(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y74-  
ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels+kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels-  
disinf_Cardiac_vessels*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels+Ka*Vint9-0.1  
*KsACE2*sACE2*y74');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f75',  
'(ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels-  
kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels+p_Cardiac_vessels/kk*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels-  
disinfa_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels-Kint*y75');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f124',  
'(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)  
*y124*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Cardiac_vessels*ac*Vint9/(y125+1)  
*vv_Cardiac_vessels+mt_Cardiac_vessels*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_Cardiac_vessels-  
d_Cardiac_vessels*y124*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f125', '-  
ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74+kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75');  
  
model.component('comp1').physics('cox_oxygen').active(false);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode2').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode3').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode4').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode7').field('dimensionless').component({'y105'  
'y2'});  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode7').field('dimensionless').component(2, 'y1052');  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode7').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode7').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '1e-2 [1/d]  
*y105', 1);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode7').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f105-1e-2[1/d]  
*y105', 0);
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model.component('comp1').physics('dode9').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode10').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode11').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode11').field('dimensionless').component({'y107' ↵  
'y2'});  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode11').field('dimensionless').component(2, 'y1072');  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode11').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f107-1e-2[1/d] ↵  
*y107', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode11').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '1e-2[1/d] ↵  
*y107', 1);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode12').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode13').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode14').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode15').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode15').field('dimensionless').component({'y108' ↵  
'y2'});  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode15').field('dimensionless').component(2, 'y1082');  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode15').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '1e-2[1/d] ↵  
*y108', 1);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode15').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f108-1e-2[1/d] ↵  
*y108', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode16').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode17').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode18').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode19').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode19').field('dimensionless').component({'y109' ↵  
'y2'});  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode19').field('dimensionless').component(2, 'y1092');  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode19').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f109-1e-2[1/d] ↵  
*y109', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode19').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '1e-2[1/d] ↵  
*y109', 1);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode20').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode21').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode22').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode24').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);
```

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model.component('comp1').physics('dode23').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode23').field('dimensionless').component({'y110' ↵  
'y2'});  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode23').field('dimensionless').component(2, 'y1102');  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode23').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '1e-2[1/d] ↵  
*y110', 1);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode23').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f110-1e-2[1/d] ↵  
*y110', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode25').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode26').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode27').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode27').field('dimensionless').component({'y111' ↵  
'y2'});  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode27').field('dimensionless').component(2, 'y1112');  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode27').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f111-1e-2[1/d] ↵  
*y111', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode27').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '1e-2[1/d] ↵  
*y111', 1);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode28').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode29').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode30').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode31').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode31').field('dimensionless').component({'y117' ↵  
'y2'});  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode31').field('dimensionless').component(2, 'y1172');  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode31').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f117-1e-2[1/d] ↵  
*y117', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode31').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '1e-2[1/d] ↵  
*y117', 1);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode32').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode33').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode34').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode35').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode35').field('dimensionless').component({'y119' ↵  
'y2'});  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode35').field('dimensionless').component(2, 'y1192');  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode35').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f119-1e-2[1/d] ↵  
*y119', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode35').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '1e-2[1/d] ↵
```

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*y119', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode36').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'M/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode37').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'M/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode38').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'M/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode38').field('dimensionless').component({'y121'
'y2'});
model.component('comp1').physics('dode38').field('dimensionless').component(2, 'y1212');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode38').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f121-1e-2[1/d]
*y121', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode38').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '1e-2[1/d]
*y121', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode39').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'M/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode40').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'M/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode41').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'M/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode42').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'M/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode42').field('dimensionless').component({'y124'
'y2'});
model.component('comp1').physics('dode42').field('dimensionless').component(2, 'y1242');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode42').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f124-1e-2[1/d]
*y124', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode42').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '1e-2[1/d]
*y124', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode43').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'M/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode44').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'M/s', 0, 0);

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var6').set('bHe', '1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var6').set('bKa', '1');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg42').run;
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
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model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y124');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y1242');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('patient1_New.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('patient1_New_55.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', {'u36'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('CD4');
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'T4');
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit',
'1');
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity',
'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').prop('Units').setIndex
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'g/cm^3', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'g/cm^3/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'ST4+(1T4*T4*a/
(Ka+a))*(1/(1+PD1bPDL1/KT))-dT4*T4-KT4*CI*T4', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', {'u37'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('InCD4');
model.component('comp1').physics('InCD4').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'ICD4');
model.component('comp1').physics('InCD4').prop('Units').set
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.component('comp1').physics('InCD4').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity',
'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('InCD4').prop('Units').setIndex
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'g/cm^3', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('InCD4').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'g/cm^3/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('InCD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KT4*Ci*T4-
bT4*IT4', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('InCD4').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'IT4');
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', {'u38'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
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model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('CD8');
model.component('comp1').physics('CD8').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit',
'1');
model.component('comp1').physics('CD8').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity',
'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('CD8').prop('Units').setIndex
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'g/cm^3', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD8').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'g/cm^3/S', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD8').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'T8');
model.component('comp1').physics('CD8').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(1T4*T4*a/(Ka+a))
*(1/(1+PD1bPDL1/KT))-dT4*T4-KT4*CI*T4', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD8').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(1T8*T8*a/(Ka+a))
*(1/(1+PD1bPDL1/KT))-dT8*T8-KT8*CI*T8', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', ('u39'));

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').prop('Units').set
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity',
'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').prop('Units').setIndex
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'g/cm^3', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'g/cm^3/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('InCD8');
model.component('comp1').physics('InCD8').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'IT8');
model.component('comp1').physics('InCD8').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KT8*Ci*T8-
bT8*IT8', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', ('u40'));

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('PD1');
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'PD1');
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'PD1/(T4+T8)*
(1T4*T4+1T8*T8)*(a/(Ka+a))*(1/(1+PD1BPDL1/KT))-PD1/(T4+T8)*(dT4*T4+dT8*T8)-
mP*PD1*antiPD1+r*In/(phi+In)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', ('u41'));

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit',
'1');
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity',

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'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').prop('Units').setIndex
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'g/cm^3', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'g/cm^3/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('PDL1');
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL1').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'PDL1');
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'PDL1/(T4+T8)*
(1T4*T4+1T8*T8)*(a/(Ka+a))*(1/(1+PD1BPDL1/KT))-PDL1/(T4+T8)*(dT4*T4+dT8*T8)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', {'u42'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').prop('Units').set
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity',
'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').prop('Units').setIndex
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'g/cm^3', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'g/cm^3/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').field('dimensionless').component(1,
'PD1bPDL1');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').field('dimensionless').component(1,
'PD1BPDL1');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'aPL*PD1*PDL1-
dQ*PD1BPDL1', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('PD1BPDL1');
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode46', 'DomainODE', {'u43'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode46', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode46', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').identifier('dode46');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').prop('Units').set
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity',
'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').prop('Units').setIndex
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'g/cm^3', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'g/cm^3/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').field('dimensionless').component(1,
'antiPD1');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'gA-
mA*PD1*antiPD1-dA*antiPD1', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').tag('antiPD1');
model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-
Kd*Ci+Kin*In*bin+KT4*IT4*bT$+KT8*T8*bT8', 0);
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model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-
Kd*Ci+Kin*In*bin+KT4*IT4*bT4+KT8*T8*bT8', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('a').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'Kg*phi_a*ma*n+Sang17*MAsbAng17-gam_a*a+KaT4*T4', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n-
phict1*In*(T4+T8)*0-Kin*In', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n-
phict1*In*(T4+T8)*0-Kin*In-phiT8*T8', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable.create('var23');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').label('CD4CD8');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('ST4', '0.1[1/d/mm^3]*T40');

model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(1T4*T4*a/(Ka+a)
*(1/(1+PD1bPDL1/KT))-dT4*T4-KT4*CI*T4', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('1T4', '0.25[1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('Ka', '2.37e-11[g/cm^3]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('KT', '1.365e-18[g/cm^3]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('dT4', '0.197[1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('KT4', '0.0027[1/mm^3/d]');

model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(1T4*T4*a/(Ka+a)
*(1/(1+PD1bPDL1/KT))-dT4*T4-KT4*Ci*T4', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(1T4*T4*a/(Ka+a)
*(1/(1+PD1bPDL1/KT))-dT4*T4', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'dT4*T4-
KT4*Ci*T4', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(1T4*T4*a/(Ka+a)
*(1/(1+PD1bPDL1/KT))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(1T4*T4*a/(Ka+a)
*(1/(1+PD1bPDL1/KT))-dT4*T4-KT4*Ci*T4', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(1T4*T4*a/(Ka+a)
*(1/(1+PD1bPDL1/KT))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(1T4*T4*a/(Ka+a)
*(1/(1+PD1BPDL1/KT))-dT4*T4-KT4*Ci*T4', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(1T4*T4*a/(Ka+a)
*(1/(1+PD1BPDL1/KT))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(1T4*T4*a/(Ka+a)
*(1/(1+PD1BPDL1/KT))-dT4*T4-KT4*Ci*T4', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(1T4*T4*a/(Ka+a)
*(1/(1+PD1BPDL1/KT))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('da', '-dT4*T4-
KT4*Ci*T41', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('da', '-dT4*T4-
KT4*Ci*T4', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(1T4*T4*a/
(Ka1+a))*(1/(1+PD1BPDL1/KT))', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var23').rename('Ka', 'Ka1');

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model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('da', 1, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(1T4*T4*a/(Ka1+a))* (1/(1+PD1BPDL1/KT))-dT4*T4-KT4*Ci*T4', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('KT4', '0.0027[mm^3/d/mole]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('bT4', '0.3[1/d]');

model.component('comp1').physics('CD8').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(1T8*T8*a/(Ka1+a))* (1/(1+PD1bPDL1/KT))-dT8*T8-KT8*CI*T8', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('lT8', '4.15[1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('dT8', '0.18[1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('KT8', '0.0027[mm^3/d/mole]');

model.component('comp1').physics('CD8').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(1T8*T8*a/(Ka1+a))* (1/(1+PD1bPDL1/KT))-dT8*T8-KT8*Ci*T8', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD8').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(1T8*T8*a/(Ka1+a))* (1/(1+PD1BPDL1/KT))-dT8*T8-KT8*Ci*T8', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD8').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'g/cm^3/s', 0, 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('bT8', '0.3[1/d]');

model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'PD1/(T4+T8)*(1T4*T4+lT8*T8)*(a/(Ka1+a))* (1/(1+PD1BPDL1/KT))-PD1/(T4+T8)*(dT4*T4+dT8*T8)-mP*PD1*antiPD1+r*In/(phi+In)', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('mP', '6.87e6[cm^3/g/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('phi', '1[1]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('r', '1');

model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'PD1/(T4+T8)*(1T4*T4+lT8*T8)*(a/(Ka1+a))* (1/(1+PD1BPDL1/KT))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'PD1/(T4+T8)*(1T4*T4+lT8*T8)*(a/(Ka1+a))* (1/(1+PD1BPDL1/KT))-PD1/(T4+T8)*(dT4*T4+dT8*T8)-mP*PD1*antiPD1', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'PD1/(T4+T8)*(1T4*T4+lT8*T8)*(a/(Ka1+a))* (1/(1+PD1BPDL1/KT))-PD1/(T4+T8)*(dT4*T4+dT8*T8)-mP*PD1*antiPD1+r*In/(phi+In)', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('phi', '1[1/mm^3]');

model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'PD1/(T4+T8)*(1T4*T4+lT8*T8)*(a/(Ka1+a))* (1/(1+PD1BPDL1/KT))-PD1/(T4+T8)*(dT4*T4+dT8*T8)-mP*PD1*antiPD1+r*In/(phicd+In)', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var23').rename('phi', 'phicd');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('r', '1[g/mm^3/s]');

model.component('comp1').physics('PDL1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'PDL1/(T4+T8)*
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(1T4*T4+1T8*T8)*(a/(Ka1+a))*(1/(1+PD1BPDL1/KT))-PDL1/(T4+T8)*(dT4*T4+dT8*T8)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL1').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit',
'1');
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL1').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity',
'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL1').prop('Units').setIndex(
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'g/cm^3', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL1').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'g/cm^3/s', 0, 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('aPL', '0.258[mm^3/g/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('dQ', '0.1[1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('gA', '1e-10[g/cm^3/d]');

model.component('comp1').physics('antiPD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'gA-
mP*PD1*antiPD1-dA*antiPD1', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('dA', '0.0462[1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('phiT8', '0.874[1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('dA', '0.0462[1/g/d]');

model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n-
Kin*In-phiT8*T8', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n-
Kin*In-phiT8*T8-phict1*In*(T4+T8)*0', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').remove('phiT8');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('phiT8', '0.874[1/d/g]');

model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n-
Kin*In-phiT8*T8', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n-
Kin*In-phiT8*T8-phict1*In*(T4+T8)*0', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('phict1', '2.3e-10[ml/h/g]');

model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-
Kd*Ci+Kin*In*bin+KT41*IT4*bT4+KT81*T8*bT8', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('KT41', '0.2542[mole/g]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('KT81', '0.2542[mole/g]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('KaT4', '0.25[1/d]');

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').feature('init1').set('T4', '4e-3[g/cm^3]');
model.component('comp1').physics('CD8').feature('init1').set('T8', '2e-3[g/cm^3]');
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('init1').set('PD1', '11.2e-10[g/cm^3]');
```

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model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('patient1_New_55_CD4.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f105', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*y105+mt_lung*ac*Vint/(ACE2+1)*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_lung-
d_lung*y105*vv_lung+Kcy*(c/(c+1)))/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f111', '(Q_intestin*y85-(Q_intestin-
L_intestin)*y111+mt_Intestine*ac*Vint5/(y103+1)*vv_intestin+mt_Intestine*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)
*vv_intestin-d_Intestine*y111*vv_intestin+Kcy*(c/(c+1)))/vv_intestin');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f108', '(Q_spleen*y85-(Q_spleen-L_spleen)
*y108+mt_spleen*ac*Vint2/(y102+1)*vv_spleen+mt_spleen*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_spleen-
d_spleen*y108*vv_spleen+Kcy*(c/(c+1)))/vv_spleen');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f109', '(Q_Upper_body*y85-(Q_Upper_body-
L_Upper_body)*y109+mt_Upper_body*ac*Vint3/(y92+1)*vv_Upper_body+mt_Upper_body*ac*IL6/
(IL6+1)*vv_Upper_body-d_Upper_body*y109*vv_Upper_body+Kcy*(c/(c+1)))/vv_Upper_body');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f110', '(Q_Torso*y85-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)
*y110+mt_Torso*ac*Vint4/(y90+1)*vv_Torso+mt_Torso*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_Torso-
d_Torso*y110*vv_Torso+Kcy*(c/(c+1)))/vv_Torso');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f117', '(Q_Lower_body*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-
(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y117*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Lower_body*ac*Vint6/(y94+1)
*vv_Lower_body+mt_Lower_body*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_Lower_body-
d_Lower_body*y117*vv_Lower_body+Kcy*(c/(c+1)))/vv_Lower_body');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f119', '(Q_brain*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-
(Q_brain-L_brain)*y119*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Brain*ac*Vint7/(y96+1)*vv_brain+mt_Brain*ac*IL6/
(IL6+1)*vv_brain-d_Brain*y119*vv_brain+Kcy*(c/(c+1)))/vv_brain');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f121', '(Q_kidney*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-
(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y121*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_kidney*ac*Vint8/(y98+1)
*vv_kidney+mt_kidney*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_kidney-d_kidney*y121*vv_kidney+Kcy*(c/(c+1))
/vv_kidney');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f124',
'(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y85*rf_IL2_Ltumor-(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)
*y124*rf_IL2_Ltumor+mt_Cardiac_vessels*ac*Vint9/(y125+1)
*vv_Cardiac_vessels+mt_Cardiac_vessels*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
d_Cardiac_vessels*y124*vv_Cardiac_vessels+Kcy*(c/(c+1)))/vv_Cardiac_vessels');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f107', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y111+
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y108+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y85-(Q_liver-
L_liver)*y107+mt_liver*ac*Vint1/(y87+1)*vv_liver+mt_liver*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_liver-
d_liver*y107*vv_liver+Kcy*(c/(c+1)))/vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f85', '((Q_lung-L_lung)*y105-
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q
_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Inode)*y85+Kcy*(c/(c+1)))/vv_ventricle');
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model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f86', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y106+
(Q_liver-L_liver)*y107+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)*y112+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)*y113)+(Q_tumor-
L_tumor)*y104+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LTorso)*y114+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y110+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)
*y115+(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y109+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y116+(Q_Lower_body-
L_Lower_body)*y117+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y118+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y119+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)
*y120+(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y121+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y124+
(L_Cardiac_vessels*y125*rf_kidney)*heaviside(y125-1e-3*first)+(L_lung+L_Llung)
*y99*rf_aLlung+(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y101*rf_aLintestin+
(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*y80*rf_aLtumor+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)*y89*rf_aLTorso+
(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y91*rf_aLUpper_body+(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)
*y93*rf_aLLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y95*rf_aLbrain+(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)
*y97*rf_aLkidney-(Q_lung)*y86*heaviside(y86-1e-3*first)+Kcy*(c/(c+1))/vv_ventricle');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f105', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*y105+mt_lung*ac*Vint/(ACE2+1)*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_lung-
d_lung*y105*vv_lung+Kcy*(c/(c+1)))/vv_lung');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'vv_lung');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kcy', '1[m^3/pg/s]');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Kcy*(c/(c+1))');

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kcy', '1[mole/s]');

model.component('comp1').physics('AT1R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SAT1-
KonAT1AngII*AngII*AT1R+KoffAT1AngII*AT1bAngII-dAT1R*AT1R', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('AT2R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SAT2R-
KonAT2AngII*AngII*AT2R+KoffAT2AngII*AT2bAngII-dAT2R*AT2R', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('MAsR').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SMAsR-
KonMAs*Ang17*MAsR+KoffMAs*MAsbAng17-dMAsR*MAsR', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('AT4R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SAT4R-
KonAT4R*AngIV*AT4R+KoffAT4R*AT4bAngIVhttps://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Z2qBipa5qmE', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('AT4R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SAT4R-
KonAT4R*AngIV*AT4R+KoffAT4R*AT4bAngIV-dAT4R*AT4R', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('IL6').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-
gam_IL6*IL6-KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6+KoffsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6-
KonsIL6R*sIL6R*IL6+KIL6TN*Tn+KIL6IEC*IEC+', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('IL6').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-
gam_IL6*IL6-KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6+KoffsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6-
KonsIL6R*sIL6R*IL6+KIL6TN*Tn+KIL6IEC*IEC+KIL6TE*Te', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('IL6R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SIL6R-
KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6-KsIL6R*IL6R-dIL6R*IL6R', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('sIL6R').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KsIL6R*IL6R-
KoffsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('VEGF').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'SVEGF+KVEGF*sIL6RbIL6-dVEGF*VEGF+KVEGF*(100-SPO2)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('VEGF').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
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'SVEGF+KVEGF*sIL6RbIL6-dVEGF*VEGF+KVEGF*(100-SPb)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('sACE2').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '-↙
KsACE2*sACE2*Ci+KAdam17*ACE2-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y14-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y18-0.1↙
*KsACE2*sACE2*y22-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y26-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y30-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y54-0.1↙
*KsACE2*sACE2*y62-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y70-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y74-dsACE2*sACE2', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ACE2').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SACE2R*ToCell-↙
KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-KAdam17*ACE2-KonACE2AngI*AngI*ACE2+KoffACE2AngI*ACE2bAngI-↙
KonACE2AngII*AngII*ACE2+KoffACE2AngII*ACE2bAngII', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ↙
'p_lung/kk*Vint+Kint*Cb-Kin*In*bIn', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ↙
'p_lung/kk*Vint+Kint*Cb-Kin*In*bin', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0) ↙
*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)-dc*c-KAT1RMAsR*MAAsR', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0) ↙
*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)-dc*c-', 0);

model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'KAT1RMAsR*MAAsR');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0) ↙
*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)-dc*c-KAT1RMAsR*MAAsR*1[pg/fmole]', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0) ↙
*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)-dc*c-KAT1RMAsR*MAAsR*1[pg/fmol]', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0) ↙
*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)-dc*c-KAT1RMAsR*MAAsR*1[pg/fmol]-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0) ↙
*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)-dc*c-KAT1RMAsR*MAAsR*1[pg/fmol]-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1↙
[pg/fmol]', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0) ↙
*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)-dc*c-KAT1RMAsR*MAAsR*1[pg/fmol]-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1↙
[pg/fmol]+IL6bsIL6R', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0) ↙
*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)-dc*c-KAT1RMAsR*MAAsR*1[pg/fmol]-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1↙
[pg/fmol]+sIL6bIL6R', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0) ↙
*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)-dc*c-KAT1RMAsR*MAAsR*1[pg/fmol]-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1↙
[pg/fmol]+sIL6RbIL6R', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0) ↙
*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)-dc*c-KAT1RMAsR*MAAsR*1[pg/fmol]-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1↙
[pg/fmol]+KcIL6RsIL6RbIL6', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0) ↙
*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)-dc*c-KAT1RMAsR*MAAsR*1[pg/fmol]-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1↙
[pg/fmol]+KcIL6R*sIL6RbIL6', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0) ↙
*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)-dc*c-KAT1RMAsR*MAAsR*1[pg/fmol]-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1↙
[pg/fmol]+KcIL6R*sIL6RbIL6*(KcEC*EC+KcH*H)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'RH*H-(Kb*H*Ci)-↙
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phic*H*n*(KH*(c-alpha)+1)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ctl').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pv*In*(t>5[d])*
(t-5[d])/1[d]-dcl*Ctl+xIL6ctl*xIL6RbIL6+KCTL*c', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)-
gam_n*n+xIL6*IL6RbIL6*1000', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ma').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xm*c-
gam_n1*ma+xIL6ma*IL6RbIL6', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').field('dimensionless').component(('ec' 'ec2'));
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').field('dimensionless').component(('ec' 'ec2'
'ec3'));
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').field('dimensionless').component(('ec' 'ec2' 'ec3'
'ec4'));
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').field('dimensionless').component(('ec' 'ec2' 'ec3'
'ec4' 'ec5'));
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').field('dimensionless').component(('ec' 'ec2' 'ec3'
'ec4' 'ec5' 'ec6'));
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').field('dimensionless').component(('ec' 'ec2' 'ec3'
'ec4' 'ec5' 'ec6' 'ec7'));
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').field('dimensionless').component(('ec' 'ec2' 'ec3'
'ec4' 'ec5' 'ec6' 'ec7' 'ec8'));
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').field('dimensionless').component(('ec' 'ec2' 'ec3'
'ec4' 'ec5' 'ec6' 'ec7' 'ec8' 'ec9'));
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').field('dimensionless').component(('ec' 'ec2' 'ec3'
'ec4' 'ec5' 'ec6' 'ec7' 'ec8' 'ec9' 'ec10'));
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').field('dimensionless').component(('ec' 'ec2' 'ec3'
'ec4' 'ec5' 'ec6' 'ec7' 'ec8' 'ec9' 'ec10' ...
'ec11'));
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').field('dimensionless').component(('ec' 'ec2' 'ec3'
'ec4' 'ec5' 'ec6' 'ec7' 'ec8' 'ec9' 'ec10' ...
'ec11' 'ec12'));
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
Kiec*y5*ec', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
Kiec*y62*ec', 2);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
Kiec*74*ec', 3);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
Kiec*y74*ec', 3);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
Kiec*y30*ec', 4);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
Kiec*y70*ec', 5);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
Kiec*y14*ec', 6);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
Kiec*y34*ec', 7);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
Kiec*y18*ec', 8);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
Kiec*y26*ec', 9);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
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Kiec*y22*ec', 10);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
Kiec*y78*ec', 11);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').field('dimensionless').component(('iec' 'iec2'));
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').field('dimensionless').component(('iec' 'iec2'
'iec3'));
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').field('dimensionless').component(('iec' 'iec2'
'iec3' 'iec4'));
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').field('dimensionless').component(('iec' 'iec2'
'iec3' 'iec4' 'iec5'));
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').field('dimensionless').component(('iec' 'iec2'
'iec3' 'iec4' 'iec5' 'iec6'));
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').field('dimensionless').component(('iec' 'iec2'
'iec3' 'iec4' 'iec5' 'iec6' 'iec7'));
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').field('dimensionless').component(('iec' 'iec2'
'iec3' 'iec4' 'iec5' 'iec6' 'iec7' 'iec8'));
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').field('dimensionless').component(('iec' 'iec2'
'iec3' 'iec4' 'iec5' 'iec6' 'iec7' 'iec8' 'iec9'));
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').field('dimensionless').component(('iec' 'iec2'
'iec3' 'iec4' 'iec5' 'iec6' 'iec7' 'iec8' 'iec9' 'iec10'));
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').field('dimensionless').component(('iec' 'iec2'
'iec3' 'iec4' 'iec5' 'iec6' 'iec7' 'iec8' 'iec9' 'iec10' ...
'iec11'));
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').field('dimensionless').component(('iec' 'iec2'
'iec3' 'iec4' 'iec5' 'iec6' 'iec7' 'iec8' 'iec9' 'iec10' ...
'iec11' 'iec12'));
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kiec*y5*ec', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kiec*y62*ec', 2);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kiec*ec*y74', 3);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kiec*ec*y30', 4);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kiec*ec*y70', 5);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kiec*ec*y14', 6);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kiec*ec*y34', 7);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kiec*ec*y18', 8);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kiec*ec*y26', 9);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kiec*ec*y22',
10);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kiec*ec*y78',
11);
model.component('comp1').physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'RH*H-(Kb*H*Ci)-
phic*H*n*(KH*(c-alpha1)+1)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').active(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('InCD4').active(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD8').active(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('InCD8').active(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').active(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL1').active(false);
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', {'u44'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);
```

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model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'TN');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'STN-hTE*TN*
(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1BPDL1').field('dimensionless').component(1,
'PD1bPDL1');
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1BPDL1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'aPL*PD1*PDL1-dQ*PD1bPDL1', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1BPDL1').tag('PD1bPDL1');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'STN-hTE*TN*
(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dT*TN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode46', 'DomainODE', {'u45'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode46', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode46', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hTE*TN*(As/
(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-eTE*TE*PD1bPDL1/As', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode47', 'DomainODE', {'u46'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode47', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode47', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('NaiveTcell');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').tag('ActivatedTcell');
model.component('comp1').physics('ActivatedTcell').field('dimensionless').component(1,
'TE');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode47').tag('PDL_1');
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL_1').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'u46');
model.component('comp1').physics.remove('PDL1');
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL_1').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'PDL1');
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL_1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((elH-dH)*H+
(elEC-dEC)*EC+(elIn-dIn)*In)*PDL1/(H+EC+In)+hPDL1*TE', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', {'u41'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics.remove('PD1');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('PD1');
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'PD1');
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((eTE-dTE)*TE+
(elTN-dTN)*TN+(eln-dn)*n+(elma-dma)*ma)*PDL1/(TE+TN+n+ma)-mPD1*antiPD1', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').prop('Units').set
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').prop('Units').set
('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').prop('Units').setIndex
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'g/cm^3', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').prop('Units').setIndex
('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'g/cm^3/s', 0, 0);
```

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model.component('comp1').physics('ActivatedTcell').prop('Units').set
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.component('comp1').physics('ActivatedTcell').prop('Units').set
('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('ActivatedTcell').prop('Units').setIndex
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'g/cm^3', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ActivatedTcell').prop('Units').setIndex
('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'g/cm^3/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL_1').prop('Units').set
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL_1').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity',
'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL_1').prop('Units').setIndex
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'g/cm^3', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL_1').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'g/cm^3/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit',
'1');
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity',
'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').prop('Units').setIndex
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'g/cm^3', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'g/cm^3/s', 0, 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dAT1R', '2.4e-8[1/s]/100');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dAT2R', '2.4e-8[1/s]/100');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dMAsR', '2.4e-8[1/s]/100');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dAT4R', '2.4e-8[1/s]/100');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dIL6R', '2.4e-8[1/s]/100');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dVEGF', '2.4e-8[1/s]/100');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dsACE2', '2.4e-8[1/s]/100');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dTN', '2.4e-8[1/s]/100');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KH', '0.02554[ml/pg]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('alpha1', '0.0025[pg/ml]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KcIL6R', '0.03[ml/h/fmol]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KcEC', '1[1]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KcH', '1[1]');

model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0)
*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)-dc*c-KAT1RMAsR*MAsR*1[pg/fmol]-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1
[pg/fmol]+KcIL6R*sIL6RbIL6*(KcEC*ec+KcH*H)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0)
*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)-dc*c-KAT1RMAsR*MAsR*1[pg/fmol]-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1
[pg/fmol]', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Sc/V0)
*Vint+SAT1R*AT1bAngII+Sn*(n+ma+In)-dc*c-KAT1RMAsR*MAsR*1[pg/fmol]-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1
[pg/fmol]+KcIL6R*sIL6RbIL6*(KcEC*ec+KcH*H)', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KcEC', '1[pg]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KcH', '1[pg]');
```

```
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KCTL', '5.22[1/h/pg]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('ToCell', 'H/H0+In/H0+c/c0+n/n0+ma/ma0');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KIL6TN', '0.02554[mol/pg/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KIL6In', '0.02554[mol/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KIL6IEC', '0.02554[mol/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KIL6TE', '0.02554[mol/pg/s]');

model.component('comp1').physics('IL6').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-
gam_IL6*IL6-KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6+KoffsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6-
KonsIL6R*sIL6R*IL6+KIL6TN*TN+KIL6IEC*IEC+KIL6TE*TE', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('IL6').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-
gam_IL6*IL6-KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6+KoffsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6-
KonsIL6R*sIL6R*IL6+KIL6TN*TN+KIL6IEC*iec+KIL6TE*TE', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('VEGF').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'SVEGF+KVEGF*sIL6RbIL6-dVEGF*VEGF+KVEGF1*(100-SPb)', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KVEGF1', '0.0152[mol/ml/h]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('STN', '0.235[pg/ml/h]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('hTE', '0.00254[pg/ml/h]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('As', '1[1]');

model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'STN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'STN-
hTE*TN*(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'STN-
hTE*TN*(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dTN*TN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').feature('dodel').setIndex('da', 'hTE*TN*
(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').feature('dodel').setIndex('da', 1, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').feature('dodel').setIndex('da', '(c/
(1+c)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').feature('dodel').setIndex('da', '(c/
(1+c))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').feature('dodel').setIndex('da', 1, 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('hTE', '0.00254[1/h]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('eTE', '0.01575[cm^3/g/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('elH', '0.154[pg/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dH', '0.00215[pg/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('elEC', '0.154[pg/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dEC', '0.00215[pg/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('elIn', '0.154[pg/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dIn', '0.00215[pg/s]');

model.component('comp1').physics('PDL_1').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '((elH-dH)*H+
(elEC-dEC)*ec+(elIn-dIn)*In)*PDL1/(H+ec+In)+hPDL1*TE', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL_1').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '((elH-dH)*H+
(elEC-dEC)*ec+(elIn-dIn)*In)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL_1').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '((elH-dH)*H+
(elEC-dEC)*ec+(elIn-dIn)*In)*PDL1/(H+ec+In)+hPDL1*TE', 0);
```

```
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('elH', '0.154[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dH', '0.00215[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('elEC', '0.154[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dEC', '0.00215[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('elIn', '0.154[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dIn', '0.00215[1/s]');

model.component('comp1').physics('PDL_1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((elH-dH)*H+
(elEC-dEC)*ec+(elIn-dIn)*In)*PDL1/(H+ec+In)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL_1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((elH-dH)*H+
(elEC-dEC)*ec+(elIn-dIn)*In)*PDL1/(H+ec+In)+hPDL1*TE', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('hPDL1', '0.154[1/s]');

model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((elTE-dTE)*TE+
(elTN-dTN)*TN+(eln-dn)*n+(elma-dma)*ma)*PDL1/(TE+TN+n+ma)-mPD1*antiPD1', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('elTE', '0.154[1/s/g]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dTE', '0.00215[1/s/g]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('elTN', '0.154[1/s/g]');

model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((elTE-dTE)*TE+
(elTN-dTN)*TN)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((elTE-dTE)*TE+
(elTN-dTN*1[1/g])*TN)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((elTE-dTE)*TE+
(elTN-dTN*1[1/g])*TN+(eln-dn)*n+(elma-dma)*ma)*PDL1/(TE+TN+n+ma)-mPD1*antiPD1', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('elN', '0.154[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('elma', '0.154[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').rename('elN', 'eln');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dn', '0.00215[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dma', '0.00215[1/s]');

model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((elTE-dTE)*TE+
(elTN-dTN*1[1/g])*TN+(eln-dn)*n+(elma-dma)*ma)*PDL1/(TE*1[1/g]+TN*1[1/g]+n+ma)-
mPD1*antiPD1', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((elTE-dTE)*TE+
(elTN-dTN*1[1/g])*TN+(eln-dn)*n+(elma-dma)*ma)*PDL1/(TE*1[1/g]+TN*1[1/g]+n+ma)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((elTE-dTE)*TE+
(elTN-dTN*1[1/g])*TN+(eln-dn)*n+(elma-dma)*ma)*PDL1/(TE*1[1/g]+TN*1[1/g]+n+ma)-
mPD1*antiPD1', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('mPD1', '0.00215[1/s]');

model.component('comp1').physics('antiPD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'gA', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('antiPD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'gA-
mP*PD1*antiPD1', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('antiPD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'gA-
mP*PD1*antiPD1-dA*antiPD1', 0);
```

```
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('dA', '0.0462[1/d]');

model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n-  
Kin*In-phiT8*T8-phictl*In*Ctl', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n-  
Kin*In-phictl*In*Ctl', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n-  
Kin*In', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dodel').setIndex('da', '-phictl*In*Ctl',  
0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dodel').setIndex('da', 1, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kb*H*Ci+phic*H*n-  
Kin*In-phictl*In*Ctl', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('phictl', '2.3e-10[ml/h]');

model.label('patient1_New_55_new.mph');

model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-  
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-  
Kd*Ci+Kin*In*bin', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('a').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',  
'Kg*phi_a*ma*n+Sang17*MAsbAng17-gam_a*a', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'first', 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'manual', 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dTE', '0.00215e-3[1/s/g]');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PD1bPDL1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PD1');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('mPD1', '0.00215e-3[1/s]');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PDL1');
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dAT1R', '2.4e-8[1/s]*1e-5');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dAT2R', '2.4e-8[1/s]*1e-5');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dMAsR', '2.4e-8[1/s]*1e-5');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dAT4R', '2.4e-8[1/s]*1e-5');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dIL6R', '2.4e-8[1/s]*1e-5');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dVEGF', '2.4e-8[1/s]*1e-5');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dsACE2', '2.4e-8[1/s]*1e-5');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dTN', '2.4e-8[1/s]*1e-5');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dH', '0.00215[1/s]*1e-5');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dEC', '0.00215[1/s]*1e-5');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dIn', '0.00215[1/s]*1e-5');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dTE', '0.00215e-3[1/s/g]*1e-5');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dn', '0.00215[1/s]*1e-5');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dma', '0.00215[1/s]*1e-5');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KH', '0.02554[ml/pg]*1e-10');

model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('PDL_1').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('ActivatedTcell').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('antiPD1').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1bPDL1').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('phic', '2.3e-9[ml/h]*1e-5');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kd', '2.4e-8[1/s]*1e-5');

model.component('comp1').physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'RH*H-(Kb*H*Ci)-
phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'RH*H-(Kb*H*Ci)-phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)
+1)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KH', '0.02554[ml/pg]*1e-20');
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'iec');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KonACE2V', '17 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('bin', '1e6[1]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kin', '(1/24)*1e-6[fmol/h]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kint', '5.78e-1[1/s]');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PD1');
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PDL1');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').feature('init1').set('TN', '4e-3');
model.component('comp1').physics('ActivatedTcell').feature('init1').set('TE', '2e-3'↵
[g/cm^3]');
model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').feature('init1').set('TN', '4e-3'↵
[g/cm^3]');

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'SPb');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('VEGF').active(false);

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('ActivatedTcell').feature('init1').set('TE', '2e-6'↵
[g/cm^3]');
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('init1').set('PD1', '11.2e-10[g/cm^3]');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').feature('init1').set('TN', '4e-8'↵
[g/cm^3]');
model.component('comp1').physics('ActivatedTcell').feature('init1').set('TE', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').feature('init1').set('TN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ctl').active(false);

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Ctl', 'TE');

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE*1[1/pg]');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE*1[1/ng]');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE*1[1/fg]');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE*1e4[1/fg]');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('CD8', 'TE*1e4[1/fg]/1e9');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE*1e4[1/fg]/1e9');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE*0.3e4[1/fg]/1e9');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE*0.3e4[1/fg]/3e9');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('CD8', 'TE*0.3e4[1/fg]/3e9');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tlist', 'range(0,1,20)');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE*0.3e4[1/fg]/5e9');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE*0.3e4[1/fg]/6e9');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE*0.3e4[1/fg]/8e9');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE*0.3e4[1/fg]/9e9');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE*0.2e4[1/fg]/9e9');
model.result('pg40').run;
```

```
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('CD8', 'TE*0.2e4[1/fg]/9e9');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6*23.718[g/mol]');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6*23.718e-23[g/mol]');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6*23.718e-23[g/mol]/1.1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6*23.718e-23[g/mol]/1.2');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6*23.718e-23[g/mol]/1.15');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('IL6_pgml', 'IL6*23.718e-23[g/mol]/1.15');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'n/1e9');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'n/0.9e9');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'n/0.85e9');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'n/0.8e9');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'n/0.75e9');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'n/0.78e9');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('n_L', 'n/0.78e9');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'a/1e9');
model.result('pg40').run;
```

```
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'a/0.9e9');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'a/1.1e9');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'a/1.2e9');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('IL10', 'a/1.2e9');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('Cb').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '+KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2-  
KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Cb/100-Kint*Cb-disinfa_lung*Cb', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KonACE2V', '25 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kint', '5.78e2 [1/s]');

model.sol('sol54').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(c-a)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg40').run;
```



```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Pb');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PD1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/PD1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PD1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '60+PD1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PD1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '60E-6+PD1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '60E-6-abs(PD1)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'manual', 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [1], 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [2], 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21], 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'first', 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'all', 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '100-Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci/0.04');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '100-Ci/0.04*100');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '100-Ci/0.02*100');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '100-Ci/0.2*100');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'CD8');
model.result('pg40').run;
```

```
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'CD8/120');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '100-CD8/120*100');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '100-CD8/150*100');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '100-CD8/160*100');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '100-CD8/160*100+Ci/0.2*100');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '150-CD8/160*100+Ci/0.2*100');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '97-CD8/160*100+Ci/0.2*100');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '97-CD8/160*100+Ci/0.2*100*(t>5)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '97-CD8/160*100+Ci/0.2*100*(t>5[d])');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '97-CD8/160*100');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '97-CD8/190*100');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Spo2', '97-CD8/190*100');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '97-CD8/190*100*log(5)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'log(5)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'log(Ci)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'log(1/Ci)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'log(CD8)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'log(CD8)/4');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'abs(log(CD8))/4');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'abs(log(CD8))/6');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'abs(log(CD8))');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'abs(log(CD8))/24');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1-abs(log(CD8))/24');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '100-(1-abs(log(CD8))/24)*100');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '100-(1-abs(log(CD8))/24)*10');
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'manual', 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '100-(1-abs(log(CD8))/24)*20');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '100-(1-abs(log(CD8))/50)*20');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [3], 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21], 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(100-(1-abs(log(CD8))/50)*20)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(100-(1-abs(log(CD8))/50))*100');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(100-(1-abs(log(CD8))/50))');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(1-(1-abs(log(CD8))/50))');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/50))');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/50))*1e3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/50))*0.8e3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/50))*0.9e3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/50))*0.89e3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/50))*0.88e3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/40))*0.88e3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/20))*0.88e3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/10))*0.88e3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/2))*0.88e3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/0.6))*0.88e3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/0.4))*0.88e3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/0.4))*0.9e3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/0.4))*0.99e3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/0.2))*0.99e3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/0.2))*1.199e3');
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/0.2))*1.1e3');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Spo2', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/0.2))*1.1e3';

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Spo2', '1/(10-(1-abs(log(CD8))/0.2))*1.1e3';

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [1], 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21], 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'all', 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '1/Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'CD8');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PD1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'abs(PD1)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'abs(PD1)+Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'abs(PD1)+CD8');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'CD8');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'CD8+abs(PD1)*1e6');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'CD8+abs(PD1)*1e8');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'CD8+abs(PD1)*1e7');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'CD8');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'abs(PD1)*1e7');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'abs(PD1)*1e6');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'abs(PD1)*1e6+CD8');
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('viral_load', 'abs(PD1)*1e6+CD8
[fmol/ml]');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').label('1D Plot ALL');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'CD8');
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', '1/uL');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'CD8/1e9');
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'CD8');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result.duplicate('pg44', 'pg40');
model.result('pg44').run;
model.result('pg44').label('1D Plot CD8');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg44').run;
model.result('pg43').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result.remove('pg41');
model.result.remove('pg42');
model.result.remove('pg43');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL6_pgml');
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result.duplicate('pg45', 'pg40');
model.result('pg45').run;
model.result('pg45').label('1D Plot IL6');
model.result('pg45').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'n_L');
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', '1/L');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'manual', 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [2], 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13
14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21], 0);
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result.duplicate('pg46', 'pg40');
model.result('pg46').run;
model.result('pg46').label('1D Plot neutrophils');
model.result('pg46').run;
model.result('pg46').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'all', 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IL10');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', 'pg/ml');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result.duplicate('pg47', 'pg40');
model.result('pg47').run;
model.result('pg47').label('1D Plot IL10');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'cyto');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result.duplicate('pg48', 'pg40');
model.result('pg48').run;
model.result('pg48').label('1D Plot cyto');
model.result('pg48').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'micro_lung');
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', 'fmol/ml');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result.duplicate('pg49', 'pg40');
model.result('pg49').run;
model.result('pg49').label('1D Plot microthrombi in lung');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Spo2');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'manual', 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [3], 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevel', [3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21], 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result.duplicate('pg50', 'pg40');
model.result('pg50').run;
model.result('pg50').label('1D Plot SPO2');
model.result('pg50').run;
model.result('pg50').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
```

```
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'all', 0);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'viral_load');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result.duplicate('pg51', 'pg40');
model.result('pg51').run;
model.result('pg51').label('1D Plot viral load');
model.result('pg51').run;
model.result('pg44').run;
model.result('pg44').feature('ptgr2').label('CD8');
model.result('pg46').run;
model.result('pg45').run;
model.result('pg45').feature('ptgr2').label('IL6');
model.result('pg46').run;
model.result('pg46').feature('ptgr2').label('Neutrophils');
model.result('pg46').run;
model.result('pg46').label('1D Plot Neutrophils');
model.result('pg46').run;
model.result('pg47').run;
model.result('pg47').feature('ptgr2').label('IL10');
model.result('pg48').run;
model.result('pg48').feature('ptgr2').label('Cytokines');
model.result('pg49').run;
model.result('pg48').run;
model.result('pg48').run;
model.result('pg48').run;
model.result('pg48').label('1D Plot Cytokines');
model.result('pg49').run;
model.result('pg48').run;
model.result('pg49').run;
model.result('pg49').run;
model.result('pg49').feature('ptgr2').label('microthrombi in lung');
model.result('pg50').run;
model.result('pg50').run;
model.result('pg50').feature('ptgr2').label('SPO2');
model.result('pg51').run;
model.result('pg51').feature('ptgr2').label('Viral Load');

model.label('patient1_baseline_severe1.mph');

model.result('pg51').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KoffACE2AngII', '15.66[1/h]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KsACE2', '17[ml/h/nmol]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KonACE2V', '17 [ml/h/nmol]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kd', '4.8e-5[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('bin', '10[1]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kint', '5.78e-4[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('phic', '2.3e-9[ml/h]');

model.label('patient1_baseline_severe1.mph');
```

```
model.sol('sol54').clearSolutionData;

model.label('Final_baseline.mph');

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f105', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*y105+mt_lung*ac*Vint/(ACE2+1)*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*NETs/
(NETs+1)*vv_lung-d_lung*y105*vv_lung+Kcy*(c/(c+1)))/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('ToCell', 'H/H0+ec/ec0');

model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci+Ka', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci+Ka*(1-', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci+Ka*(1-IF/
(Kif-IF)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci+Ka*(1-IF/
(Kif+IF)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci+Ka*(1-IF/
(Kif+IF))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci+Ka*(1-IF/
(Kif+IF))8Vint', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci+Ka*(1-IF/
(Kif+IF))*Vint', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '
'p_lung/kk*Vint+Kint*Cb-Kin*In*bin-Ka*(1-IF/(Kif+IF))*Vint', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'RH*H-(Kb*H*Vint)-
phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'RH*H-(Kb*H*Vint)-
phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)+phiCTL', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'RH*H-(Kb*H*Vint)-
phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)+phiCTL*In*Te', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'RH*H-(Kb*H*Vint)-
phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)+phiCTL*In*TE', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('H').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'RH*H-(Kb*H*Vint)-
phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n-Kin*In-phictl*In*Ctl', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n-Kin*In-phictl*In*TE', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-Kin*In-phictl*In*TE', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*In*TE', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*In*TE', 0);
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'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phict1*In*TE', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phict11*In*TE', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phict1*In*TE', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('phict1', '2.3e-10[1/h]/1[g/cm^3]');

model.component('comp1').physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)-✓
gam_n*n+xIL6*IL6RbIL6*1000-', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)-✓
gam_n*n+xIL6*IL6RbIL6*1000', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)-✓
gam_n*n*()+xIL6*IL6RbIL6*1000', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)-✓
gam_n*n*(1)+xIL6*IL6RbIL6*1000', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)-✓
gam_n*n*(1+bn*Ci/(Ci+1))+xIL6*IL6RbIL6*1000', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', {'u40'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').prop('Units').set ✓
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', ✓
'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').prop('Units').setIndex ✓
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1/mm^3', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ✓
'1/mm^3/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').field('dimensionless').field('NETs');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'NETs');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'gam_n*n* ✓
(1+bn*Ci/(Ci+1))-dNETs*NETs', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'STN- ✓
hTE*TN*(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dTN*TN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ActivatedTcell').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'hTE*TN*(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-eTE*TE*PD1bPDL1/As', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('NETs');
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode46', 'DomainODE', {'u40'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode46', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode46', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').identifier('dode46');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').prop('Units').set ✓
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', ✓

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'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').prop('Units').setIndex
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'g/cm^3', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'g/cm^3/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').field('dimensionless').field('IF');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'IF');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'aIF*(iec)',
0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'iec', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'aIF*(iec+In)-
dIF*IF', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').tag('IF');
model.component('comp1').physics('IF').feature('dode1').setIndex('da', 'iec+In', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('aIF', '2.1e-2[pg/h]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dIF', '8.3e-1[1/h]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('bn', '1[1]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dNETs', '8.3e-1[1/h]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kif', '8.3e-1[1/h]');

model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'p_lung/kk*Vint+Kint*Cb-Kin*In*bin', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'p_lung/kk*Vint+Kint*Cb-Kin*In*bin-Ka*(1-IF/(Kif+IF))*Vint', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'p_lung/kk*Vint+Kint*Cb-Kin*In*bin-Ka*Vint', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'p_lung/kk*Vint+Kint*Cb-Kin*In*bin-Ka*(1-IF/(Kif+IF))*Vint', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kif', '2.1e-2[pg/h]');

model.sol('sol54').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'p_lung/kk*Vint+Kint*Cb-Kin*In*bin-Ka*Vint', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(1-IF/(Kif+IF))');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('IF').feature('dode1').setIndex('da', 1, 0);

model.sol('sol54').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
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model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IF/(Kif+IF)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IF');

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('ActivatedTcell').feature('dode1').setIndex('da', 'IF/
(Kif+IF)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ActivatedTcell').feature('dode1').setIndex('da',
'(Kif+IF)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ActivatedTcell').feature('dode1').setIndex('da', 1, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ActivatedTcell').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'hTE*TN*(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-eTE*TE*PD1bPDL1/As', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ActivatedTcell').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'hTE*TN*(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-eTE*TE*PD1bPDL1/As', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Kif');

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kif', '0.0025[pg/ml]');

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IF');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('Final_baseline.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('Final_baseline_solution.mph');
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model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol154').clearSolutionData;

model.label('Voutouri C et al_baseline.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci+Ka*(1-IF/
(Kif+IF))*Vint-Kv*Ci*A', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci+Ka*(1-IF/
(Kif+IF))*Vint-Ci*A', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci+Ka*(1-IF/
(Kif+IF))*Vint-Kv*Ci*A', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kv', '4e-3 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('A', '110.2');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').remove('A');

model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*In*TE-Kf', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*In*TE-Kf1*In*IF', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kif1', '4.2 [1/d/g/cm^3]');

model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*In*TE-Kif1*In*IF', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kif1', '4.2 [cm^3/d/g]');

model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', {'u40'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('DC');
model.component('comp1').physics('DC').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'1/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('DC').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('DC').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'DC');
model.component('comp1').physics('DC').field('dimensionless').field('DC');
model.component('comp1').physics('DC').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SDC-bD*DC*V-
dDC*DC', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', {'u47'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
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model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').field('dimensionless').field('u47');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').field('dimensionless').field('u47');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').field('dimensionless').field('DCi');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'DCi');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('DCi');
model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵
'1/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bD-DC*Ci', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('DC').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SDC-bD*DC*Ci-↵
dDC*DC', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bD*DC*Ci-↵
dDCi*Dci', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bD*DC*Ci-↵
dDCi*DCi', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('bD', '1e-2 [M/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dDC', '1e-3 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dDCi', '2.9 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('SDC', 'dD*D0');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('D0', '1e3');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('SDC', 'dDC*D0');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('bD', '1e-2 [1/d/M]');

model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode46', 'DomainODE', {'u40'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode46', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode46', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').identifier('dode46');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode46').tag('ThN');
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵
'1/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').field('dimensionless').field('ThN');
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'ThN');
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'STN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'STN-', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'STN-hTE*ThN*(As/↵
(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dTn*ThN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hTE*ThN*(As/↵
(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dTn*ThN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SThN-hTE*ThN*(As/↵
(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dTn*ThN', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('SThN', 'dThN*ThN0');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dThN', '0.4 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('ThN0', '1e-3');

model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SThN-hTE*ThN*(As/↵
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(1+As))* (c/(1+c))* (IF/(Kif+IF))* (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dThN*ThN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', ('u40'));

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('The');
model.component('comp1').physics('The').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'1/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('The').field('dimensionless').field('The');
model.component('comp1').physics('The').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'The');
model.component('comp1').physics('The').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hTE*ThN*(As/
(1+As))* (c/(1+c))* (IF/(Kif+IF))* (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))+rN*The*(As/(1+As))* (c/(1+c))* (IF/
(Kif+IF))* (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('The').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hTE*ThN*(As/
(1+As))* (c/(1+c))* (IF/(Kif+IF))* (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))+rN*The*(As/(1+As))* (c/(1+c))* (IF/
(Kif+IF))* (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-eTE*The*PD1bPDL1/As', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('The').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hTE*DCi*ThN*(As/
(1+As))* (c/(1+c))* (IF/(Kif+IF))* (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))+rN*The*(As/(1+As))* (c/(1+c))* (IF/
(Kif+IF))* (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-eTE*The*PD1bPDL1/As', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('The').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hTE*DCi*ThN*(As/
(1+As))* (c/(1+c))* (IF/(Kif+IF))* (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('The').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hTE*DCi*ThN*(As/
(1+As))* (c/(1+c))* (IF/(Kif+IF))* (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))+rN*The*(As/(1+As))* (c/(1+c))* (IF/
(Kif+IF))* (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-eTE*The*PD1bPDL1/As', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('rN', 'hTE');

model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', ('u40'));

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('TN');
model.component('comp1').physics('TN').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'1/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TN').field('dimensionless').field('TN');
model.component('comp1').physics('TN').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'u40');
model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').field('dimensionless').component(1,
'TN1');
model.component('comp1').physics('TN').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'TN');
model.component('comp1').physics('TN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'STN-hTE*DCi*TN*
(As/(1+As))* (c/(1+c))* (IF/(Kif+IF))* (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dTN*TN', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').rename('STN', 'STN1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('STN', 'dTN*TN0');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').rename('dTN', 'dTN1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dTN', '0.75 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('TN0', '1e3');

model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', ('u40'));
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model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('TE');
model.component('comp1').physics('TE').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'1/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TE').field('dimensionless').field('TE');
model.component('comp1').physics('TE').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'u40');
model.component('comp1').physics('ActivatedTcell').field('dimensionless').component(1,
'TE1');
model.component('comp1').physics('TE').field('dimensionless').field('TE1');
model.component('comp1').physics('TE').field('dimensionless').field('TE');
model.component('comp1').physics('TE').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'TE');
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SThN-hTE*DCi*ThN*
(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dThN*ThN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SThN-hTE*DCi*ThN*
(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dThN*ThN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TE').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hT*DCi*TN*(As/
(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))+rT*TE*(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/
(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-eTE*TE*PD1bPDL1/As', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'STN-hT*DCi*TN*(As/
(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dT*TN', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('hT', 'hTE');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('rT', 'rN');

model.component('comp1').physics('TE').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('TN').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThE').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('IF').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('NETs').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 2);
model.component('comp1').physics('IF').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 2);
model.component('comp1').physics('DC').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 2);
model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 2);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 2);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThE').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 2);
model.component('comp1').physics('TN').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 2);
model.component('comp1').physics('TE').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 2);
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', {'u40'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('BN');
model.component('comp1').physics('BN').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'1/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('BN').field('dimensionless').field('BN');
model.component('comp1').physics('BN').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'BN');
model.component('comp1').physics('BN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SB-hT*DCi*ThE*(As/
```

```
(1+As))* (c/(1+c))* (IF/(Kif+IF))* (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dB*BN', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('SB', 'STN');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dB', '2e-3 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('SB', 'B0*dB');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('B0', '1e3');

model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', {'u40'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('BA');
model.component('comp1').physics('BA').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'1/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('BA').field('dimensionless').field('BA');
model.component('comp1').physics('BA').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'BA');
model.component('comp1').physics('BA').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hT*DCi*The*(As/
(1+As))* (c/(1+c))* (IF/(Kif+IF))* (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))+rB*The*BA-dBA*BA-pB*BA-pL*The*BA', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('rB', '1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dBA', '1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('pS', '1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('pL', '1');

model.component('comp1').physics('BA').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hT*DCi*The*(As/
(1+As))* (c/(1+c))* (IF/(Kif+IF))* (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))+rB*The*BA-dBA*BA-pS*BA-pL*The*BA', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('rB', '2e-3 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dBA', '2e-3 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('rB', '2.6 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dBA', '0.9 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('pS', '1e-3 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('pL', '8e-9 [1/d]');

model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', {'u40'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('PL');
model.component('comp1').physics('PL').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'1/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PL').field('dimensionless').field('PL');
model.component('comp1').physics('PL').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'PL');
model.component('comp1').physics('PL').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pL*The*BA', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PL').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pL*The*BA-dL*PL',
0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dL', '3e-2 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dS', '0.1 [1/d]');
```

```
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', {'u40'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('PS');
model.component('comp1').physics('PS').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'1/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PS').field('dimensionless').field('PS');
model.component('comp1').physics('PS').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'PS');
model.component('comp1').physics('PS').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pS*BA', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PS').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pS*BA-dS*PS', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', {'u40'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('A');
model.component('comp1').physics('A').field('dimensionless').field('A');
model.component('comp1').physics('A').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'A');
model.component('comp1').physics('A').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'1/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('A').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pAS*PS+pAL*PL-
dA*A', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('pAS', '1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('pAL', '1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dA', '1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('pAS', '0.06 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('pAL', '0.8 [1/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dA', '0.04 [1/d]');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('A').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*A)/vv_lung+pAS*PS+pAL*PL-dA*A', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('A').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*A-(Q_lung-
L_lung)*A)/vv_lung+pAS*PS+pAL*PL-dA*A', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', {'u40'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('y200');
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y200');
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'1/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f200', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component({'y200' 'u2'});
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(2, 'y201');
```

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model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(('y200' 'y201'↵
'u3'));
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(3, 'y210');
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(3, 'y202');
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(('y200' 'y201'↵
'y202' 'u4'));
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(('y200' 'y201'↵
'y202' 'u4' 'u5'));
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(('y200' 'y201'↵
'y202' 'u4' 'u5' 'u6'));
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(('y200' 'y201'↵
'y202' 'u4' 'u5' 'u6' 'u7'));
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(('y200' 'y201'↵
'y202' 'u4' 'u5' 'u6' 'u7' 'u8'));
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(('y200' 'y201'↵
'y202' 'u4' 'u5' 'u6' 'u7' 'u8' 'u9'));
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(('y200' 'y201'↵
'y202' 'u4' 'u5' 'u6' 'u7' 'u8' 'u9' 'u10'));
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(('y200' 'y201'↵
'y202' 'u4' 'u5' 'u6' 'u7' 'u8' 'u9' 'u10' ...
'u11'));
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(4, 'y203');
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(5, 'y204');
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(6, 'y205');
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(7, 'y206');
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(8, 'y207');
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(9, 'y208');
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(10, 'y209');
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').field('dimensionless').component(11, 'y210');
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'f201', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'f202', 2);
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'f203', 3);
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'f204', 4);
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'f205', 5);
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'f206', 6);
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'f207', 7);
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'f208', 8);
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'f209', 9);
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'f210', 10);

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f200', '((Q_lung-L_lung)*A-↵
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q↵
_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode)*y200-Kay*y5*y200*vv_ventricle)/vv_ventricle');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('Kay', 'Kv');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f200', '((Q_lung-L_lung)*A-↵
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q↵
_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode)*y200-Kay*y5*y200*vv_ventricle)/vv_ventricle');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('asd', 'y10');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('Kay', '1[m^3/mol/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').remove('asd');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f201', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y106+↵
```

```
(Q_liver-L_liver)*y202+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)*y112+((Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)*y113)+(Q_tumor-  
L_tumor)*y104+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LTorso)*y114+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y209+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)   
*y115+(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y210+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y116+(Q_Lower_body-  
L_Lower_body)*y208+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y118+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y203+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)   
*y120+(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y205+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y206+  
(L_Cardiac_vessels*y125*rf_kidney)*heaviside(y125-1e-3*first)+(L_lung+L_Llung)   
*y99*rf_aLlung+(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y101*rf_aLintestin+  
(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*y80*rf_aLtumor+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)*y89*rf_aLTorso+  
(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y91*rf_aLUpper_body+(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)   
*y93*rf_aLLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y95*rf_aLbrain+(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)   
*y97*rf_aLkidney-(Q_lung)*y201*heaviside(y201-1e-3*first)+Kay*y78*y201*vv_ventricle)   
/vv_ventricle');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f202', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y207+  
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y204+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*200-(Q_liver-  
L_liver)*y202-Kay*y15*y202*vv_liver)/vv_liver');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f203', '(Q_brain*y200-(Q_brain-L_brain)   
*y203-Kay*y62*y203*vv_brain)/vv_brain');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f204', '(Q_spleen*y200-(Q_spleen-  
L_spleen)*y204-Kay*y18*y204*vv_brain)/vv_brain');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f205', '(Q_kidney*y200-(Q_kidney-  
L_kidney)*y205-Kay*y18*y205*vv_kidney)/vv_kidney');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f204', '(Q_spleen*y200-(Q_spleen-  
L_spleen)*y204-Kay*y18*y204*vv_spleen)/vv_spleen');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f205', '(Q_kidney*y200-(Q_kidney-  
L_kidney)*y205-Kay*y70*y205*vv_kidney)/vv_kidney');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f206', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y200-  
(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y206-Kay*y112*y206*vv_Cardiac_vessels)   
/vv_Cardiac_vessels');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f207', '(Q_intestin*y200-(Q_intestin-  
L_intestin)*y207-Kay*y30*y207*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f206', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y200-  
(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y206-Kay*y74*y206*vv_Cardiac_vessels)   
/vv_Cardiac_vessels');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f208', '(Q_Lower_body*y200-(Q_Lower_body-  
L_Lower_body)*y208-Kay*y54*y208*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f209', '(Q_Torso*y200-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)   
*y209-Kay*y26*y209*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f210', '(Q_Upper_body*y200-(Q_Upper_body-  
L_Upper_body)*y210-Kay*y22*y210*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').remove('dA');  
  
model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');  
  
model.result('pg40').run;  
  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('Kvy', 'Kay');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f5', '((Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci-  
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q   
_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode)*y5-Kvy*y5*y200*vv_ventricle)/vv_ventricle');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('Kvy', '1[1/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f78', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y10+(Q_liver-  
L_liver)*y104+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LTorso)*y114+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y209+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)   
*y115+(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y210+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y116+(Q_Lower_body-  
L_Lower_body)*y208+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y118+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y203+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)   
*y120+(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y205+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y206+  
(L_Cardiac_vessels*y125*rf_kidney)*heaviside(y125-1e-3*first)+(L_lung+L_Llung)   
*y99*rf_aLlung+(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y101*rf_aLintestin+  
(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*y80*rf_aLtumor+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)*y89*rf_aLTorso+  
(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y91*rf_aLUpper_body+(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)   
*y93*rf_aLLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y95*rf_aLbrain+(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)   
*y97*rf_aLkidney-(Q_lung)*y201*heaviside(y201-1e-3*first)+Kay*y78*y201*vv_ventricle)   
/vv_ventricle');
```

```
L_liver)*y14+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)* y34+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)* y38+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)* y1+
(Q_Lnode/8-L_LTorso)* y42+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)* y46+
(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y22+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y50+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)
*y54+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y58+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)*y66+(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y70+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)
*y74+L_Cardiac_vessels*y77*rf_Cardiac_vessels+(L_lung+L_Llung)*y13*rf_Llung+
(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y37*rf_Lintestin+(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*
(rf_Ltumor*y41*heaviside(-y41+500)+1*y41*heaviside(y41-501))+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)
*y45*rf_LTorso+(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y49*rf_LUpper_body+
(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)*y53*rf_LLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y61*rf_Lbrain+
(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)*y69*rf_Lkidney-(Q_lung)*y78-Kvy*y78*y201*vv_ventricle)
/vv_ventricle');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f201', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y106+
(Q_liver-L_liver)*y202+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)*y112+((Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)*y113)+(Q_tumor-
L_tumor)*y104+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LTorso)*y114+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y209+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)
*y115+(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y210+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y116+(Q_Lower_body-
L_Lower_body)*y208+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y118+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y203+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)
*y120+(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y205+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y206+
(L_Cardiac_vessels*y125*rf_kidney)*heaviside(y125-1e-3*first)+(L_lung+L_Llung)
*y99*rf_aLlung+(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y101*rf_aLintestin+
(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)*y80*rf_aLtumor+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)*y89*rf_aLTorso+
(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y91*rf_aLUpper_body+(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)
*y93*rf_aLLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y95*rf_aLbrain+(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)
*y97*rf_aLkidney-(Q_lung)*y201*heaviside(y201-1e-3*first)-Kay*y78*y201*vv_ventricle)
/vv_ventricle');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f14', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30+
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y18+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)
*y5*freeTcell_trafficliver-(Q_liver-L_liver)*y14-
ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver+kd_liver*y15*vv_liver-disinf_liver*y14*vv_liver-
Kvy*y14*y202*vv_liver)/vv_liver+Ka*Vint1-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y14');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f18',
'(Q_spleen*y5*freeTcell_traffic spleen-(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y18-
ka_spleen*y102*y18*vv_spleen+kd_spleen*y19*vv_spleen-disinf_spleen*y18*vv_spleen-
Kvy*y18*y204*vv_spleen)/vv_spleen+Ka*Vint2-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y18');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f22',
'(Q_Upper_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficUpper_body-(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y22-
ka_Upper_body*y92*y22*vv_Upper_body+kd_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body-
disinf_Upper_body*y22*vv_Upper_body-Kvy*y22*y210*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body+Ka*Vint3-
0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y22');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f26',
'(Q_Torso*y5*freeTcell_trafficTorso-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26-
ka_Torso*y90*y26*vv_Torso+kd_Torso*y27*vv_Torso-disinf_Torso*y26*vv_Torso-
Kvy*y26*y209*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso+Ka*Vint4-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y26');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f30',
'(Q_intestin*y5*freeTcell_trafficintestine-(Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30-
ka_intestin*y103*y30*vv_intestin+kd_intestin*y31*vv_intestin-
disinf_Intestine*y30*vv_intestin-Kvy*y30*y207*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin+Ka*Vint5-0.1
*KsACE2*sACE2*y30');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f54',
'(Q_Lower_body*y5*freeTcell_trafficLower_body-(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54-
ka_Lower_body*y94*y54*vv_Lower_body+kd_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body-
```

```
disinf_Lower_body*y54*vv_Lower_body-Kvy*y54*y208*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body+Ka*Vint6-  
0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y54');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f62',  
'(Q_brain*y5*freeTcell_trafficbrain-(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62-  
ka_brain*y96*y62*vv_brain+kd_brain*y63*vv_brain-disinf_Brain*y62*vv_brain-  
Kvy*y62*y203*vv_brain)/vv_brain+Ka*Vint7-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y62');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f70',  
'(Q_kidney*y5*freeTcell_traffickidney-(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y70-  
ka_kidney*y98*y70*vv_kidney+kd_kidney*y71*vv_kidney-disinf_kidney*y70*vv_kidney-  
Kvy*y70*y205*vv_kidney)/vv_kidney+Ka*Vint8-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y70');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f74', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y5-  
(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y74-  
ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels+kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels-  
disinf_Cardiac_vessels*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels-Kvy*y74*y206*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/  
vv_Cardiac_vessels+Ka*Vint9-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y74');  
  
model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');  
  
model.result('pg40').run;  
  
model.component('comp1').physics('ActivatedTcell').active(false);  
model.component('comp1').physics('NaiveTcell').active(false);  
  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('Kvy', '1e-3*60*24 [1/mM/d]');  
  
model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');  
  
model.result('pg40').run;  
  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('Kay', '1e-3*60*24 [1/mM/d]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('Kvy', '1e-1 [1/d]');  
  
model.component('comp1').physics('DC').feature('init1').set('DC', 'DC0');  
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').feature('init1').set('ThN', 'ThN0');  
model.component('comp1').physics('TN').feature('init1').set('TN', 'TN0');  
model.component('comp1').physics('BN').feature('init1').set('BN', 'B0');  
model.component('comp1').physics('A').feature('init1').set('A', 110.2);  
model.component('comp1').physics('DC').feature('init1').set('DC', 'D0');  
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((elTE-dTE)*TE+  
(elTN-dTN)*TN+(eln-dn)*n+(elma-dma)*ma)*PDL1/(TE*1[1/g]+TN*1[1/g]+n+ma)-mPD1*antiPD1',  
0);  
  
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('elTE', '2.9e-2 [pg/ml/h]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('elTN', '2.9e-2 [pg/ml/h]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dTE', '2.9e-2 [pg/ml/h]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dTN', '2.9e-2 [pg/ml/h]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').descr('dTN', 'z');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KIL6TE', '0.57 [fmol/ml/h]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KIL6TN', '0.57 [fmol/ml/h]');  
  
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((elTE-dTE)*TE+
```

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(elTN-dTN)*TN+(eln-dn)*n+(elma-dma)*ma)*PDL1/(TE+TN+n+ma)-mPD1*antiPD1', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((elTE-dTE)*TE+
(elTN-dTN)*TN+(eln-dn)*n+(elma-dma)*ma)*PDL1/(TE*1[g/m^3]+TN*1[g/m^3]+n+ma)-
mPD1*antiPD1', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((elTE-dTE)*TE+
(elTN-dTN)*TN+(eln-dn)*n+(elma-dma)*ma)*PDL1/(TE*1[1/m^3]+TN*1[1/m^3]+n+ma)-
mPD1*antiPD1', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((eln-dn)*n+
(elma-dma)*ma)*PDL1/(TE*1[1/m^3]+TN*1[1/m^3]+n+ma)-mPD1*antiPD1', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('da', '(elTE-dTE)*TE+
(elTN-dTN)*TN+', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('da', '(elTE-dTE)*TE+
(elTN-dTN)*TN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('da', 1, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((elTE-dTE)*TE+
(elTN-dTN)*TN+(eln-dn)*n+(elma-dma)*ma)*PDL1/(TE*1[1/m^3]+TN*1[1/m^3]+n+ma)-
mPD1*antiPD1', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('da', '(eln-dn)*n', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('da', 1, 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('elTE', '2.9e-2[1/ml/h]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('elTN', '2.9e-5[1/ml/h]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('elTE', '2.9e-5[1/ml/h]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dTE', '2.9e-5[1/ml/h]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dTN', '2.9e-5[1/ml/h]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dTN1', '2.9e-5[1/ml/h]');

model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '((elTE-dTE)*TE+
(elTN-dTN1)*TN+(eln-dn)*n+(elma-dma)*ma)*PDL1/(TE*1[1/m^3]+TN*1[1/m^3]+n+ma)-
mPD1*antiPD1', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dTN', '0.75 [1/d]');

model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('da', 'phict1*In*TE',
0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('da', 1, 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('phict1', '2.3e-10[1/h]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('hPDL1', '2.9e-2[pg/ml/h]');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PS');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PL');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BA');
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'SB-hT*DCi*ThE*(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*
(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dB*BN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'ThE');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'ThN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'SThN-hTE*DCi*ThN*(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))
*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dThN*ThN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DCi');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DC');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IF');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kiec*Ci*ec+', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kiec*Ci*ec', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'Kiec*Ci*ec+phic*ec*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*iec*TE-Kifl*iec*IF', 0);

model.label('New Covid model_value.mph');

model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', ('u47'));

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'1/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('THM');
model.component('comp1').physics('THM').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'THM');
model.component('comp1').physics('THM').field('dimensionless').field('THM');
model.component('comp1').physics('THM').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'pThM*ThE-
dThM*ThM', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('pThM', 'pS');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dThM', 'dS');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('pThM', 'pL');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dThM', 'dL');
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model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', {'u48'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').field('dimensionless').field('u48');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('TM');
model.component('comp1').physics('TM').field('dimensionless').field('TM');
model.component('comp1').physics('TM').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'TM');
model.component('comp1').physics('TM').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'1/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TM').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pTM*TM', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TM').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pTM*TM-dTM*TM',
0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('pTM', 'pThM');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dTM', 'dThM');

model.component('comp1').physics('PL').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pL*(ThE+ThM)*BA-
dL*PL', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('THM').tag('ThM');
model.component('comp1').physics('ThM').field('dimensionless').field('ThM');
model.component('comp1').physics('ThM').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'ThM');
model.component('comp1').physics('BA').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hT*DCi*ThE*(As/
(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))+rB*ThE*BA-dBA*BA-pS*BA-pL*(ThE+ThM)
*BA', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TE').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hT*DCi*TN*(As/
(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))+rT*TE*(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/
(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-pThM*TE-eTE*TE*PD1bPDL1/As', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TM').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pTM*TE-dTM*TM',
0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThE').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hTE*DCi*ThN*(As/
(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))+rN*ThE*(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/
(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-pThM*ThE-eTE*ThE*PD1bPDL1/As', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TE').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hT*DCi*TN*(As/
(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))+rT*TE*(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/
(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-pTM*TE-eTE*TE*PD1bPDL1/As', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'Kiec*Ci*ec+phic*ec*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*iec*TE-Kifl*iec*IF-KInM*iec*TM', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KInM', 'phictl');

model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*In*TE-Kifl*In*IF-KInM*TM', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*In*TE-Kifl*In*IF-KInM*TM*In', 0);

model.label('New Covid model_value.mph');

model.component('comp1').physics('TM').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThM').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
```

```
model.component('comp1').physics('y200').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('A').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('PS').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('PL').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('BA').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('BN').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('TE').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('TN').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThE').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('DC').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('IF').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('NETs').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('PD1').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('InCD8').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD8').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('InCD4').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('CD4').prop('ShapeProperty').set('order', 1);

model.sol('sol154').clearSolutionData;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KInM', 'phict1/10');

model.label('New Covid model_value_clear.mph');

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('pThM', 'pL/10');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dThM', 'dL/100');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KInM', 'phict1/100');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dIF', '8.3e-1[1/h]/100');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dNETs', '8.3e-1[1/h]/100');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('aIF', '2.1e-2[pg/h]*10');

model.component('comp1').physics('IF').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 1, 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('IF').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', 1, 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('IF').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bf*(iec+In)-dIF*IF', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('IF').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bf*(iec+In)-dIF2*IF', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('bf', '9.6e-10 [1/d]/H0');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dif2', '1');

model.component('comp1').physics('IF').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bf*(iec+In)-dif2*IF', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('dif2', '1.9[1/d]');

model.result('pg40').run;
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model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ↵
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*In*TE', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ↵
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*In*TE-Kif1*In*IF', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ↵
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*In*TE-Kif2*In*IF-KInM*TM*In', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ↵
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*In*TE-kif2*In*IF-KInM*TM*In', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ↵
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*In*TE-Kif1*In*IF-KInM*TM*In', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ↵
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*In*TE-Kif1*In*IF', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ↵
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*In*TE-Kif1*In*IF-KInM*TM*In', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kif2', '4.2[1/d]');

model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ↵
'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*In*TE-Kif2*In*IF-KInM*TM*In', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ↵
'Kiec*Ci*ec+phic*ec*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)-phictl*iec*TE-Kif2*iec*IF-KInM*iec*TM', 0);

model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').create('sel', 'Segregated');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss1', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_NETs' 'comp1_IF' 'comp1_DC' 'comp1_DCi' 'comp1_ThN' 'comp1_ThE' 'comp1_TN' ↵
'comp1_TE' 'comp1_BN' 'comp1_BA' ...
'comp1_PL' 'comp1_PS' 'comp1_A' 'comp1_y200' 'comp1_y201' 'comp1_y202' 'comp1_y203' ↵
'comp1_y204' 'comp1_y205' 'comp1_y206' ...
'comp1_y207' 'comp1_y208' 'comp1_y209' 'comp1_y210' 'comp1_ThM' 'comp1_TM'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ssDef').set('segvar', (↵
'comp1_a' ↵
'comp1_ACE2' 'comp1_ACE2bAngI' 'comp1_ACE2bAngII' 'comp1_AGT' 'comp1_Ang17' 'comp1_Ang19' ↵
'comp1_AngI' 'comp1_AngII' 'comp1_AngIII' ...
'comp1_AngIV' 'comp1_AT1bAngII' 'comp1_AT1R' 'comp1_AT2bAngII' 'comp1_AT2R' ↵
'comp1_AT4bAngIV' 'comp1_AT4R' 'comp1_c' 'comp1_Cb' 'comp1_Ci' ...
'comp1_ec' 'comp1_H' 'comp1_iec' 'comp1_IL6' 'comp1_IL6R' 'comp1_IL6RbIL6' 'comp1_In' ↵
'comp1_ma' 'comp1_MAsbAng17' 'comp1_MAsR' ...
'comp1_n' 'comp1_Renin' 'comp1_sACE2' 'comp1_sIL6R' 'comp1_sIL6RbIL6' 'comp1_Vint' ↵
'comp1_y5' 'comp1_y78' 'comp1_y85' 'comp1_y86' ...
'comp1_y105' 'comp1_y14' 'comp1_y15' 'comp1_y107' 'comp1_y87' 'comp1_y18' 'comp1_y19' ↵
'comp1_y108' 'comp1_y102' 'comp1_y22' ...
'comp1_y23' 'comp1_y109' 'comp1_y92' 'comp1_y26' 'comp1_y27' 'comp1_y110' 'comp1_y90' ↵
'comp1_y30' 'comp1_y31' 'comp1_y111' ...
'comp1_y103' 'comp1_y54' 'comp1_y55' 'comp1_y117' 'comp1_y94' 'comp1_y62' 'comp1_y63' ↵
'comp1_y119' 'comp1_y70' 'comp1_y71' ...
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'comp1_y121' 'comp1_y98' 'comp1_y74' 'comp1_y75' 'comp1_y124' 'comp1_y125' 'comp1_y96'↵
'comp1_Vint1' 'comp1_Vint2' 'comp1_Vint3' ...
'comp1_Vint4' 'comp1_Vint5' 'comp1_Vint6' 'comp1_Vint7' 'comp1_Vint8' 'comp1_Vint9'↵
'comp1_y1052' 'comp1_y1072' 'comp1_y1082' 'comp1_y1092' ...
'comp1_y1102' 'comp1_y1112' 'comp1_y1172' 'comp1_y1192' 'comp1_y1212' 'comp1_y1242'↵
'comp1_PD1bPDL1' 'comp1_antiPD1' 'comp1_ec2' 'comp1_ec3' ...
'comp1_ec4' 'comp1_ec5' 'comp1_ec6' 'comp1_ec7' 'comp1_ec8' 'comp1_ec9' 'comp1_ec10'↵
'comp1_ec11' 'comp1_ec12' 'comp1_iec2' ...
'comp1_iec3' 'comp1_iec4' 'comp1_iec5' 'comp1_iec6' 'comp1_iec7' 'comp1_iec8'↵
'comp1_iec9' 'comp1_iec10' 'comp1_iec11' 'comp1_iec12' ...
'comp1_PDL1' 'comp1_PD1'));

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IF');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('segvarspec', 'all');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ssDef').set('segvar', {'comp1_a'↵
'comp1_ACE2' 'comp1_ACE2bAngI' 'comp1_ACE2bAngII' 'comp1_AGT' 'comp1_Ang17' 'comp1_Ang19'↵
'comp1_AngI' 'comp1_AngII' 'comp1_AngIII' ...
'comp1_AngIV' 'comp1_AT1bAngII' 'comp1_AT1R' 'comp1_AT2bAngII' 'comp1_AT2R'↵
'comp1_AT4bAngIV' 'comp1_AT4R' 'comp1_c' 'comp1_Cb' 'comp1_Ci' ...
'comp1_ec' 'comp1_H' 'comp1_iec' 'comp1_IL6' 'comp1_IL6R' 'comp1_IL6RbIL6'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss2', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').set('segvar', {'comp1_In'↵
'comp1_ma' 'comp1_MASbAng17' 'comp1_MASr' 'comp1_n' 'comp1_Renin' 'comp1_sACE2'↵
'comp1_sIL6R' 'comp1_sIL6RbIL6' 'comp1_Vint' ...
'comp1_y5' 'comp1_y78' 'comp1_y85' 'comp1_y86' 'comp1_y105' 'comp1_y14' 'comp1_y15'↵
'comp1_y107' 'comp1_y87' 'comp1_y18' ...
'comp1_y19' 'comp1_y108' 'comp1_y102' 'comp1_y22' 'comp1_y23' 'comp1_y109'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss3', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss3').set('segvar', {'comp1_y92'↵
'comp1_y26' 'comp1_y27' 'comp1_y110' 'comp1_y90' 'comp1_y30' 'comp1_y31' 'comp1_y111'↵
'comp1_y103' 'comp1_y54' ...
'comp1_y55' 'comp1_y117' 'comp1_y94' 'comp1_y62' 'comp1_y63' 'comp1_y119' 'comp1_y70'↵
'comp1_y71' 'comp1_y121' 'comp1_y98' ...
'comp1_y74' 'comp1_y75' 'comp1_y124' 'comp1_y125' 'comp1_y96'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss4', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss4').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_Vint1' 'comp1_Vint2' 'comp1_Vint3' 'comp1_Vint4' 'comp1_Vint5' 'comp1_Vint6'↵
'comp1_Vint7' 'comp1_Vint8' 'comp1_Vint9' 'comp1_y1052' ...
'comp1_y1072' 'comp1_y1082' 'comp1_y1092' 'comp1_y1102' 'comp1_y1112' 'comp1_y1172'↵
'comp1_y1192' 'comp1_y1212' 'comp1_y1242'});
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss5', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss5').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_PD1bPDL1' 'comp1_antiPD1' 'comp1_ec2' 'comp1_ec3' 'comp1_ec4' 'comp1_ec5'↵
```

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'comp1_ec6' 'comp1_ec7' 'comp1_ec8' 'comp1_ec9' ...
'comp1_ec10' 'comp1_ec11' 'comp1_ec12' 'comp1_iec2' 'comp1_iec3' 'comp1_iec4' ↵
'comp1_iec5' 'comp1_iec6' 'comp1_iec7' 'comp1_iec8' ...
'comp1_iec9' 'comp1_iec10' 'comp1_iec11' 'comp1_iec12' 'comp1_PDL1' 'comp1_PD1'}});
model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kv', '4e-3 [1/d]/100');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IF');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'ThN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-↵
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci-Kv*Ci*A', ↵
0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-↵
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci-↵
Kv*Ci*A+Ka*(1-IF/(Kif+IF))*Vint', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kif', '0.0025');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Ka', '5.78e2[1/s]/bKa');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kd', '8.1e-2[1/d]');

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').set('showlegendsmaxmin', true);
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model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').set('legendpos', 'upperright');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'last', 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'all', 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('autoexpr', false);
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'last', 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').setIndex('looplevelinput', 'all', 0);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vint1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vint2');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('KonACE2V', '17 [ml/h/nmol]/100');

model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('fcl').active(true);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'IF');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('fcl').active(false);
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').active(true);
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('dDef').set('linsolver', 'pardiso');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ssDef').set('subdtype', 'auto');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('subdtype', 'auto');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').set('subdtype', 'auto');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss3').set('subdtype', 'auto');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss4').set('subdtype', 'auto');
model.sol('sol54').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss5').set('subdtype', 'const');
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model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss4').set('subdtype', 'const');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss3').set('subdtype', 'const');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').set('subdtype', 'const');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('subdtype', 'const');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ssDef').set('subdtype', 'const');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci-Kv*Ci*A+Ka*(1-IF/(Kif+IF))*Vint', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kv', '4e-3 [1/d]/1000');

model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci-Kv*Ci*A+Ka*(1-IF/(Kif+IF))*Vint*0', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('l11', 'LowerLimit');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature.remove('l11');

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('gam_n1', 'gam_n/1000');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'MASbAng17');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'MASR');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'n');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'sACE2');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Ka', '5.78e2[1/s]/bKa/100');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kin', '(1/24)*1e-6[fmol/h]/100');
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('Kint', '5.78e-4[1/s]*100');
```

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model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(Q_lung*y78-(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci) /vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci*0-Kv*Ci*A+Ka*(1-IF/(Kif+IF))*Vint*0');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(Q_lung*y78-(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci) /vv_lung');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(Q_lung*y78)');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(-(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '((Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y78');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Q_lung*y78');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '((Q_Lnode/8-L_Llung)*y10+(Q_liver-L_liver)*y14+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lliver)* y34+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Ltumor)* y38+(Q_tumor-L_tumor)* y1+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LTorso)* y42+(Q_Torso-L_Torso)*y26+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LUpper_body)* y46+(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y22+(Q_Lnode/8-L_LLower_body)*y50+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lbrain)*y58+(Q_brain-L_brain)*y62+(Q_Lnode/8-L_Lkidney)*y66+(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y70+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y74+L_Cardiac_vessels*y77*rf_Cardiac_vessels+(L_lung+L_Llung)*y13*rf_Llung+(L_liver+L_spleen+L_intestin+L_Lliver)*y37*rf_Lintestin+(L_tumor+L_Ltumor)* (rf_Ltumor*y41*heaviside(-y41+500)+1*y41*heaviside(y41-501))+(L_Torso+L_LTorso)*y45*rf_LTorso+(L_Upper_body+L_LUpper_body)*y49*rf_LUpper_body+(L_LLower_body+L_Lower_body)*y53*rf_LLower_body+(L_Lbrain+L_brain)*y61*rf_Lbrain+(L_Lkidney+L_kidney)*y69*rf_Lkidney-(Q_lung)*y78-Kvy*y78*y201*vv_ventricle) /vv_ventricle');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y78');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(Q_lung*y78-(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci) /vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci*0-Kv*Ci*A+Ka*(1-IF/(Kif+IF))*Vint*0');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(Q_lung*y78-(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci) /vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci*0-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci*0-Kv*Ci*A+Ka*(1-IF/(Kif+IF))*Vint*0');
model.result('pg40').run;
```

```
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(Q_lung*y78-(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)
/vv_lung');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(Q_lung*y78-(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)
/vv_lung/10000');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung/1000-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci*0-
Kv*Ci*A+Ka*(1-IF/(Kif+IF))*Vint*0', 0);

model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature.remove('sel');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').feature('fc1').active(true);

model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode45', 'DomainODE', {'u47'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode45', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode45', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode45').tag('y300');
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').field('y300');
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'1/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'y300');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y18');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y34');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('ieec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kiec*ec*y54', 7);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
Kiec*y54*ec', 7);

model.sol('sol154').clearSolutionData;

model.label('New Covid model_value_newPK.mph');

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f78', '((Q_liver-L_liver)*y14+(Q_Torso-
L_Torso)*y26+(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y22+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y54+(Q_brain-
L_brain)*y62+(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y70+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y74-(Q_lung)
*y78-Kvy*y78*y201*vv_ventricle)/vv_ventricle');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f85', '((Q_lung-L_lung)*y105-
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q
_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode)*y85)/vv_ventricle');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f86', '((Q_liver-L_liver)*y107+(Q_Torso-
L_Torso)*y110+(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y109+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y117+(Q_brain-
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L_brain)*y119+(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y121+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y124-  
(Q_lung)*y86)/vv_ventricle');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f201', '((Q_liver-L_liver)*y202+(Q_Torso-  
L_Torso)*y209+(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y210+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y208+(Q_brain-  
L_brain)*y203+(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y205+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y206-  
(Q_lung)*y201-Kay*y78*y201*vv_ventricle)/vv_ventricle');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f14', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y30+  
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y18+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y5-(Q_liver-  
L_liver)*y14-ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver+kd_liver*y15*vv_liver-disinf_liver*y14*vv_liver-  
Kvy*y14*y202*vv_liver+Ka*Vint1*vv_liver-0.1*KsACE2*sACE2*y14*vv_liver)/vv_liver');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('y6', 'Ci');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('y100', 'ACE2');  
  
model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');  
  
model.result('pg40').run;  
  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').remove('f6');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').remove('f7');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').remove('f100');  
  
model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');  
  
model.result('pg40').run;  
  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',  
'p_liver*y15+Kint*y15-Ka*Vint1', 1);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',  
'p_spleen*y19+Kint*y19-Ka*Vint2', 2);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',  
'p_Upper_body*y23+Kint*y23-Ka*Vint3', 3);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',  
'p_Torso*y27+Kint*y27-Ka*Vint4', 4);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',  
'p_Intestine*y31+Kint*y31-Ka*Vint5', 5);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',  
'p_Lower_body*y55+Kint*y55-Ka*Vint6', 6);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',  
'p_Brain*y63+Kint*y63-Ka*Vint7', 7);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',  
'p_kidney*y71+Kint*y71-Ka*Vint8', 8);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',  
'p_Cardiac_vessels*y75+Kint*y75-Ka*Vint9', 9);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',  
'p_lung*Cb+Kint*Cb-Kin*In*bin-Ka*Vint', 0);  
  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f15', '(ka_liver*y87*y14*vv_liver-  
kd_liver*y15*vv_liver-disinf_liver*y15*vv_liver-Kint*y15*vv_liver)/vv_liver');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f107', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y111+  
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y108+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y85-(Q_liver-  
L_liver)*y107+mt_liver*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_liver+mt_liver*ac*y302/(y302+1)*vv_liver+ktte*
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(TE+n+ma)*vv_liver+ktiec*iec7*vv_liver+kta*y202*vv_liver+ktec*y202*ec7*vv_liver-  
e_liver*y107*vv_liver-d_liver*y107*vv_liver)/vv_liver');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('ktte', '1');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('ktiec', '1');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kta', '1');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('ktec', '1');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('e_liver', '1');  
  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(('y300' 'y2'));  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(('y300' 'y2' '  
'y3'));  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(('y300' 'y2' '  
'y3' 'y4'));  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(('y300' 'y2' '  
'y3' 'y4' 'y8'));  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(('y300' 'y2' '  
'y3' 'y4' 'y8' 'y9'));  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(('y300' 'y2' '  
'y3' 'y4' 'y8' 'y9' 'y10'));  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(('y300' 'y2' '  
'y3' 'y4' 'y8' 'y9' 'y10' 'y11'));  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(('y300' 'y2' '  
'y3' 'y4' 'y8' 'y9' 'y10' 'y11' 'y12'));  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(('y300' 'y2' '  
'y3' 'y4' 'y8' 'y9' 'y10' 'y11' 'y12' 'y13'));  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(('y300' 'y2' '  
'y3' 'y4' 'y8' 'y9' 'y10' 'y11' 'y12' 'y13' ...  
'y16'));  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(2, 'y301');  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(3, 'y302');  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(4, 'y303');  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(5, 'y304');  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(6, 'y305');  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(7, 'y306');  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(8, 'y307');  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(9, 'y308');  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(10, 'y309');  
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').field('dimensionless').component(11, 'y310');  
  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('ktte', '1[1/s]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('ktiec', '1[1/s]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kta', '1[1/s]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('ktec', '1[1/s]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('e_liver', '1[1/s]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f107', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y111+  
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y108+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y85-(Q_liver-  
L_liver)*y107+mt_liver*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_liver+mt_liver*ac*y302/(y302+1)*vv_liver+ktte*  
(TE+n+ma)*vv_liver+ktiec*iec7*vv_liver+kta*y202*vv_liver+ktec*y202*ec7*vv_liver-  
e_liver*y107*vv_liver-d_liver*y107*vv_liver)/vv_liver');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('aaaaa', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y111+  
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y108+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y85-(Q_liver-
```

```
L_liver)*y107+mt_liver*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_liver)/vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('ktte', '1[mole/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('t5', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y111+
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y108+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y85-(Q_liver-
L_liver)*y107+mt_liver*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_liver+mt_liver*ac*y302/(y302+1)*vv_liver+ktte*
(TB*n+n+ma)*vv_liver+ktiec*iec7*vv_liver+kta*y202*vv_liver+ktec*y202*ec7*vv_liver-
e_liver*y107*vv_liver-d_liver*y107*vv_liver)/vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('t6', '+ktiec*iec7*vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f107', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y111+
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y108+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y85-(Q_liver-
L_liver)*y107+mt_liver*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_liver+mt_liver*ac*y302/(y302+1)*vv_liver+ktte*
(TB*n+n+ma)*vv_liver+ktiec*iec7*vv_liver+kta*y202*vv_liver+ktec*y202*ec7*vv_liver-
e_liver*y107*vv_liver-d_liver*y107*vv_liver)/vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('ktiec', '1[mole/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kta', '1[mole/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('ktec', '1[mole/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('e_liver', '1[mole/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('aaaaa', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y111+
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y108+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y85-(Q_liver-
L_liver)*y107+mt_liver*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_liver+mt_liver*ac*y302/(y302+1)*vv_liver+ktte*
(TB*n+n+ma)*vv_liver+ktiec*iec7*vv_liver)/vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('t5', '+kta*y202*vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kta', '1[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('t5', '+kta*y202*vv_liver/vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kta', '1[M/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('t5',
'+kta*y202*vv_liver+ktec*y202*ec7*vv_liver-e_liver*y107*vv_liver-d_liver*y107*vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('t6',
'+kta*y202*vv_liver+ktec*y202*ec7*vv_liver-e_liver*y107*vv_liver-d_liver*y107*vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('t5',
'+kta*y202*vv_liver+ktec*y202*ec7*vv_liver-e_liver*y107*vv_liver-d_liver*y107*vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('t6', 'e_liver*y107*vv_liver/vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('e_liver', '1[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var23').set('aaaaa', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y111+
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y108+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y85-(Q_liver-
L_liver)*y107+mt_liver*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_liver+mt_liver*ac*y302/(y302+1)*vv_liver+ktte*
(TB*n+n+ma)*vv_liver+ktiec*iec7*vv_liver+kta*y202*vv_liver+ktec*y202*ec7*vv_liver-
e_liver*y107*vv_liver-d_liver*y107*vv_liver)/vv_liver');

model.label('New Covid model_value_newPK.mph');

model.component('comp1').physics('y300').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f300', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f301', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f302', 2);
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f303', 3);
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f304', 4);
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f305', 5);
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f306', 6);
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f307', 7);
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f308', 8);
model.component('comp1').physics('y300').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f309', 9);
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model.component('comp1').physics('y300').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f310', 10);

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f300', '((Q_lung-L_lung)*c/c0-
(Q_liver+L_intestin+L_spleen+Q_kidney+Q_tumor+Q_Torso+Q_Lower_body+Q_Upper_body+Q_brain+Q
_Cardiac_vessels+Q_Lnode)*y300)/vv_ventricle');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f301', '((Q_liver-L_liver)*y302+(Q_Torso-
L_Torso)*y309+(Q_Upper_body-L_Upper_body)*y310+(Q_Lower_body-L_Lower_body)*y308+(Q_brain-
L_brain)*y303+(Q_kidney-L_kidney)*y305+(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y306-
(Q_lung)*y301)/vv_ventricle');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f107', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y111+
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y108+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y85- (Q_liver-
L_liver)*y107+mt_liver*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_liver+mt_liver*ac*y302/(y302+1)
*vv_liver+ktiec*iec7*vv_liver+ktiecte*(TE)*iec7*vv_liver-e_liver*y107*vv_liver-
d_liver*y107*vv_liver)/vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').rename('kte', 'ktiecte');

model.component('comp1').physics('dode11').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f107', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode11').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'(d_liver*y107*vv_liver-e_liver*y1072*vv_liver)/vv_liver', 1);

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f87', '+kd_liver*y15-ka_liver*y87*y14');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f202', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y207+
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y204+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*200- (Q_liver-
L_liver)*y202-Kavy*y14*y202*vv_liver-kaiec*iec7*y202*vv_liver-kay*y202*vv_liver)
/vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kavy', '1e-3*60*24 [1/mM/d]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').rename('kavy', 'Kavy');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').rename('ktiec', 'kaiec');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('faaf', 'Kavy*y14*y202*vv_liver-
kaiec*iec7*y202*vv_liver-kay*y202*vv_liver');

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').rename('kaiec', 'ktiec');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kaiec', '1[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('faaf', 'Kavy*y14*y202*vv_liver-
Kay*y202*vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('aaa', '-kaiec*iec7*y202*vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('faaf', 'Kavy*y14*y202*vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('aaaaa', '-Kay*y202*vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('faaf', 'Kavy*y14*y202');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('aaa', '-kaiec*iec7*y202');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('aaaaa', '-Kay*y202');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kaiec', '1[m^3/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kaa', 'Kay');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').rename('kaa', 'kaay');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kaay', '1[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('aaaaa', '-kaay*y202');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('faaf', 'Kavy*y14*y202-kaiec*iec7*y202-

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kaay*y202');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f202', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y207+
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y204+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*200-(Q_liver-
L_liver)*y202-Kavy*y14*y202*vv_liver-kaiec*iec7*y202*vv_liver-kaay*y202*vv_liver)
/vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').remove('aaa');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').remove('aaaaa');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').remove('faaf');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f302', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y307+
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y304+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*300-(Q_liver-
L_liver)*y302+Kc_innate*(n+ma)
*vv_liver+kciec*iec7*vv_liver+kcil6*ILL6bsIL6R*KcEC*ec*vv_liver-d_s*y302*vv_liver)
/vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('Kv_innate', '1[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').rename('Kv_innate', 'Kc_innate');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('aaaaa', 'KcEC');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').remove('aaaaa');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', 'Kc_innate*(n+ma)
*vv_liver+kciec*iec7*vv_liver+kcil6*ILL6bsIL6R*KcEC*ec*vv_liver-d_s*y302*vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kciec', '1[1/s]');

model.sol('sol54').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kcil6', '1[1/s]');

model.sol('sol54').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', 'Kc_innate*(n+ma)
*vv_liver+kciec*iec7*vv_liver+kcil6*sIL6RbIL6*KcEC*ec*vv_liver-d_s*y302*vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('aaa', '(Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y307');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').remove('aaa');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', 'Kc_innate*(n+ma)*vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test2', 'kciec*iec7*vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test3',
'kcil6*sIL6RbIL6*KcEC*ec*vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test4', '-d_s*y302*vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('d_s', '1[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kciec', '1[m^3/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('Kc_innate', '1[m^3/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kcil6', '1[1/M*kg*s]');

model.sol('sol54').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kcil6', '1[m^3/M/s/kg]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f302', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y307+
```

```
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y304+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*300-(Q_liver-  
L_liver)*y302+Kc_innate*(n+ma) ✓  
*vv_liver+kciec*iec7*vv_liver+kcil6*sIL6RbIL6*KcEC*ec*vv_liver-d_s*y302*vv_liver) ✓  
/vv_liver');
```

```
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec7-  
Kecb*ec7*Vint1-phiciec*ec7*n*(KHIEC(y302-a)+1)', 6);
```

```
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', 'Kec*ec7-Kecb*ec7*Vint1-  
phiciec*ec7*n*(KHIEC(y302-a)+1)');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('Kecb', '1[1/s]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('phiciec', '1[1/s]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('KHIEC', 'KH');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', 'Kec*ec7');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test2', 'Kecb*ec7*Vint1');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test3', 'phiciec*ec7*n*(KHIEC*(y302-a) ✓  
+1)');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', 'Kec*ec7-Kecb*ec7*Vint1-  
phiciec*ec7*n*(KHIEC*(y302-a)+1)');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test3', 'phiciec*ec7*n*(KHIEC*(y302-  
a/a0/1[kg])+1)');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', 'Kec*ec7-Kecb*ec7*Vint1-  
phiciec*ec7*n*(KHIEC*(y302-a/a0/1[kg])+1)');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('Kecb', '1[1/M/s]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test3', 'phiciec*ec7*n*(KHIEC*(y302-  
a/a_0)+1)');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('phiciec', '1[kg/s]');
```

```
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec7-  
Kecb*ec7*Vint1-phiciec*ec7*n*(KHIEC*(y302-a/a0/1[kg])+1)', 6);
```

```
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', 'Kec*ec7-Kecb*ec7*Vint1-  
phiciec*ec7*n*(KHIEC*(y302-a/a_0)+1)');
```

```
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec7-  
Kecb*ec7*Vint1-phiciec*ec7*n*(KHIEC*(y302-a/a_0)+1)', 6);  
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', ✓  
'Kecb*ec7*Vint1+phiciec*ec7*n*(KHIEC*(y302-a/a_0)+1)-Kif2*iec7*IF-KInM*iec7*TM-  
KTIEC*iec7-KTiecte*TE*iec7', 6);
```

```
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', 'Kecb*ec7*Vint1+phiciec*ec7*n* ✓  
(KHIEC*(y302-a/a_0)+1)-Kif2*iec7*IF-KInM*iec7*TM-KTIEC*iec7-KTiecte*TE*iec7');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('KTIEC', '1[1/s]');  
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('KTiecte', '1[1/s]');
```

```
model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
```

```
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung) ✓  
*y105+mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*(ec+H)*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*(c/(c+1))*(ec+H) ✓
```

```
*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*NETs/(NETs+1)*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', '+Ktiecin*(iecin+In)
*vv_lung+KtiecinTe*TE*(iecin+In)*vv_lung-e_lung*y105*vv_lung-d_lung*y105*vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test2', 'mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*(ec+H)');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*y105+mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*(ec+H)+mt_lung*ac*(c/(c+1))*(ec+H)+mt_lung*ac*NETs/(NETs+1)
*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test3', 'Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*y105');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*y105+mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*(ec+H)*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*(c/(c+1))*(ec+H)
*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*NETs/(NETs+1)*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test2', 'mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*(ec+H)
*vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var19').set('ac', '1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test2', 'mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*(ec+H)/
(H0+ec0)*vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*y105+mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*(ec+H)/(H0+ec0)*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*(c/(c+1))*(ec+H)
*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*NETs/(NETs+1)*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test2', 'mt_lung*ac*(c/(c+1))');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*y105+mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*(ec+H)/(H0+ec0)*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*(c/(c+1))*(ec+H)/(ec0+H0)
*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*NETs/(NETs+1)*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f105', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*y105+mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*(ec+H)/(H0+ec0)*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*(c/(c+1))*(ec+H)/(ec0+H0)
*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*NETs/(NETs+1)*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('Ktiecin', '1[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('KtiecinTe', '1[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('e_lung', '1[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test2', '+Ktiecin*(iecin+In)*vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('Ktiecin', '1[mole/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test2', 'KtiecinTe*TE*(iecin+In)*vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('KtiecinTe', '1[mole/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*y105+mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*(ec+H)/(H0+ec0)*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*(c/(c+1))*(ec+H)/(ec0+H0)
*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*NETs/(NETs+1)*vv_lung+Ktiecin*(iecin+In)*vv_lung+KtiecinTe*TE*(iecin+In)
*vv_lung-e_lung*y105*vv_lung-d_lung*y105*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f105', '(Q_lung*y86-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*y105+mt_lung*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*(ec+H)/(H0+ec0)*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*(c/(c+1))*(ec+H)/(ec0+H0)
*vv_lung+mt_lung*ac*NETs/(NETs+1)*vv_lung+Ktiecin*(iecin+In)*vv_lung+KtiecinTe*TE*(iecin+In)
*vv_lung-e_lung*y105*vv_lung-d_lung*y105*vv_lung)/vv_lung');

model.component('comp1').physics('dode7').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f105', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode7').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'(d_lung*y105*vv_lung-e_lung*y1052*vv_lung)/vv_lung', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('A').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y201-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*A+pAS*PS+pAL*PL-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung-Kaiecin*(iecin+In)*A*vv_lung-Ka*A*vv_lung)
/vv_lung', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', '(Q_lung*y201-(Q_lung-L_lung)
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*A+pAS*PS+pAL*PL-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung-KaiecIn*(iec+In)*A*vv_lung-Ka*A*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', '+pAS*PS+pAL*PL-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung-
KaiecIn*(iec+In)*A*vv_lung-Ka*A*vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', '(Q_lung*y201-(Q_lung-L_lung)*A)
/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', '+pAS*PS+pAL*PL-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung-
KaiecIn*(iec+In)*A*vv_lung-Ka*A*vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test2', '-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kav', 'Kavy');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', '+pAS*PS+pAL*PL-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung-
KaiecIn*(iec+In)*A*vv_lung-Ka*A*vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kav', '1[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', '+pAS*PS+pAL*PL-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung-
KaiecIn*(iec+In)*A*vv_lung-Ka*A*vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test3', 'pAL*PL');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kav', '1[1/mole/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test2', '-KaiecIn*(iec+In)*A*vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kaiecIn', '1[1/mole/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').rename('kaiecIn', 'KaiecIn');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('KaiecIn', '1[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', '+pAS*PS+pAL*PL-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung-
KaiecIn*(iec+In)*A*vv_lung-Ka*A*vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test2', '-Ka*A*vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test4', '(Q_lung-L_lung)*A');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('kav', '1[m^3/mole/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', '+pAS*PS*vv_lung+pAL*PL*vv_lung-
kav*Ci*A*vv_lung-KaiecIn*(iec+In)*A*vv_lung-Ka*A*vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('KaiecIn', '1[m^3/s]');

model.component('comp1').physics('A').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y201-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*A+pAS*PS*vv_lung+pAL*PL*vv_lung-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung-KaiecIn*(iec+In)
*A*vv_lung-Ka*A*vv_lung)/vv_lung', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y301-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*c+Kc_innate*(n+ma)*vv_lung+kciec*(iec+In)
*vv_lung+SAT1R*AT1bAngII*vv_lung+ KcIL6R*sIL6RbIL6*(KcEC*ec+KcH*H)*vv_lung-
KAT1RMAsR*MAsR*1[pg/fmol]*vv_lung- KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1[pg/fmol]-d_s*C*vv_lung)/vv_lung', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y301-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*c)/vv_lung', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y301-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*c+Kc_innate*(n+ma)*vv_lung+kciec*(iec+In)
*vv_lung+SAT1R*AT1bAngII*vv_lung+ KcIL6R*sIL6RbIL6*(KcEC*ec+KcH*H)*vv_lung-
KAT1RMAsR*MAsR*1[pg/fmol]*vv_lung- KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1[pg/fmol]-d_s*C*vv_lung)/vv_lung', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', '(Q_lung*y301-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*c+Kc_innate*(n+ma)*vv_lung+kciec*(iec+In)*vv_lung+SAT1R*AT1bAngII*vv_lung+
KcIL6R*sIL6RbIL6*(KcEC*ec+KcH*H)*vv_lung- KAT1RMAsR*MAsR*1[pg/fmol]*vv_lung-
KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1[pg/fmol]-d_s*C*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', 'Q_lung*y301*c0');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', '(Q_lung*y301*c0-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*c+Kc_innate*(n+ma)*vv_lung+kciec*(iec+In)*vv_lung+SAT1R*AT1bAngII*vv_lung+
KcIL6R*sIL6RbIL6*(KcEC*ec+KcH*H)*vv_lung- KAT1RMAsR*MAsR*1[pg/fmol]*vv_lung-

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KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1[pg/fmol]-d_s*C*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', 'Kc_innate*(n+ma)*vv_lung*c0');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', '(Q_lung*y301*c0-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*c+Kc_innate*(n+ma)*vv_lung*c0+kciec*(iec+In)*vv_lung+SAT1R*AT1bAngII*vv_lung+
KcIL6R*sIL6RbIL6*(KcEC*ec+KcH*H)*vv_lung- KAT1RMAsR*MArR*1[pg/fmol]*vv_lung-
KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1[pg/fmol]-d_s*C*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', 'kciec*(iec+In)*vv_lung*c0');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', '(Q_lung*y301*c0-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*c+Kc_innate*(n+ma)*vv_lung*c0+kciec*(iec+In)*vv_lung*c0+SAT1R*AT1bAngII*vv_lung+
KcIL6R*sIL6RbIL6*(KcEC*ec+KcH*H)*vv_lung- KAT1RMAsR*MArR*1[pg/fmol]*vv_lung-
KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1[pg/fmol]-d_s*C*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', '- KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1[pg/M]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', '(Q_lung*y301*c0-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*c+Kc_innate*(n+ma)*vv_lung*c0+kciec*(iec+In)*vv_lung*c0+SAT1R*AT1bAngII*vv_lung+
KcIL6R*sIL6RbIL6*(KcEC*ec+KcH*H)*vv_lung- KAT1RMAsR*MArR*1[pg/fmol]*vv_lung-
KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1[pg/M]-d_s*Ci*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', 'd_s*Ci*vv_lung*1[pg/mole]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', '(Q_lung*y301*c0-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*c+Kc_innate*(n+ma)*vv_lung*c0+kciec*(iec+In)*vv_lung*c0+SAT1R*AT1bAngII*vv_lung+
KcIL6R*sIL6RbIL6*(KcEC*ec+KcH*H)*vv_lung- KAT1RMAsR*MArR*1[pg/fmol]*vv_lung-
KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1[pg/M]-d_s*Ci*vv_lung*1[pg/mole])/vv_lung');

model.component('comp1').physics('c').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y301*c0-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*c+Kc_innate*(n+ma)*vv_lung*c0+kciec*(iec+In)
*vv_lung*c0+SAT1R*AT1bAngII*vv_lung+ KcIL6R*sIL6RbIL6*(KcEC*ec+KcH*H)*vv_lung-
KAT1RMAsR*MArR*1[pg/fmol]*vv_lung- KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1[pg/M]-d_s*Ci*vv_lung*1[pg/mole])
/vv_lung', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
Kecb*ec*Vint-phiciec*ec*n*(Khiec*(Ci-a)+1)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
Kecb*ec*Vint-phiciec*ec*n*(KHiec*(Ci-a)+1)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
Kecb*ec*Vint-phiciec*ec*n*(khiec*(Ci-a)+1)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
Kecb*ec*Vint-phiciec*ec*n*(KHIEC*(Ci-a)+1)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec-
Kecb*ec*Vint-phic*ec*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kecb*ec*Vint+
phic*ec*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)- Kif2*iec*IF- KInM*iec*TM- KtiegIn*iec- KtiegInTe*TE*iec', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', 'Kecb*ec*Vint+ phic*ec*n*(KH*(c-a)
+1)- Kif2*iec*IF- KInM*iec*TM');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', '- KtiegIn*iec/1[mole]-
KtiegInTe*TE*iec/1[mole]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', 'Kecb*ec*Vint+ phic*ec*n*(KH*(c-a)
+1)- Kif2*iec*IF- KInM*iec*TM- KtiegIn*iec/1[mole]- KtiegInTe*TE*iec/1[mole]');

model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kecb*ec*Vint+
phic*ec*n*(KH*(c-a)+1)- Kif2*iec*IF- KInM*iec*TM- KtiegIn*iec/1[mole]- KtiegInTe*TE*iec/1
[mole]', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('In').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',

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'Kb*H*Vint+phic*H*n*(KH*(c-a)+1) -Kif2*In*IF-KInM*TM*In-KTiecTE *In-phictl*In*TE', 0);

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f19', '(ka_spleen*y102*y18*vv_spleen-
kd_spleen*y19*vv_spleen-disinfa_spleen*y19*vv_spleen)/vv_spleen-Kint*y19');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f23',
'(ka_Upper_body*y92*y22*vv_Upper_body-kd_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body-
disinfa_Upper_body*y23*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body-Kint*y23');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f27', '(ka_Torso*y90*y26*vv_Torso-
kd_Torso*y27*vv_Torso-disinfa_Torso*y27*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso-Kint*y27');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f31', '(ka_intestin*y103*y30*vv_intestin-
kd_intestin*y31*vv_intestin-disinfa_Intestine*y31*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin-Kint*y31');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f55',
'(ka_Lower_body*y94*y54*vv_Lower_body-kd_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body-
disinfa_Lower_body*y55*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body-Kint*y55');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f63', '(ka_brain*y96*y62*vv_brain-
kd_brain*y63*vv_brain-disinfa_Brain*y63*vv_brain)/vv_brain-Kint*y63');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f71', '(ka_kidney*y98*y70*vv_kidney-
kd_kidney*y71*vv_kidney-disinfa_kidney*y71*vv_kidney)/vv_kidney-Kint*y71');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f75',
'(ka_Cardiac_vessels*y125*y74*vv_Cardiac_vessels-
kd_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels-disinfa_Cardiac_vessels*y75*vv_Cardiac_vessels)
/vv_Cardiac_vessels-Kint*y75');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f107', '((Q_intestin-L_intestin)*y111+
(Q_spleen-L_spleen)*y108+(Q_liver-Q_intestin-Q_spleen+L_intestin+L_spleen)*y85-(Q_liver-
L_liver)*y107+mt_liver*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_liver*ec7/ec0+mt_liver*ac*y302/(y302+1)
*vv_liver*ec7/ec0+ktiec*iec7*vv_liver+ktiecte*(TE)*iec7*vv_liver-e_liver*y107*vv_liver-
d_liver*y107*vv_liver)/vv_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f108', '(Q_spleen*y85-(Q_spleen-L_spleen)
*y108+mt_spleen*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_spleen*ec9/ec0+ mt_spleen*ac*y302/(y302+1)
*vv_spleen*ec9/ec0+ktiec*iec9*vv_spleen+ktiecte*(TE)*iec9*vv_spleen-
e_spleen*y108*vv_spleen-d_spleen*y108*vv_spleen)/vv_spleen');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('e_spleen', 'e_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('d_spleen', 'd_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f109', '(Q_Upper_body*y85-(Q_Upper_body-
L_Upper_body)*y109+mt_Upper_body*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_Upper_body*ec11/ec0+
mt_Upper_body*ac*y310/(y310+1)*vv_Upper_body*ec11/ec0+ktiec*iec11*vv_Upper_body+ktiecte*
(TE)*iec11*vv_Upper_body-e_Upper_body*y109*vv_Upper_body-d_Upper_body*y109*vv_Upper_body)
/vv_Upper_body');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f108', '(Q_spleen*y85-(Q_spleen-L_spleen)
*y108+mt_spleen*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_spleen*ec9/ec0+ mt_spleen*ac*y304/(y304+1)
*vv_spleen*ec9/ec0+ktiec*iec9*vv_spleen+ktiecte*(TE)*iec9*vv_spleen-
e_spleen*y108*vv_spleen-d_spleen*y108*vv_spleen)/vv_spleen');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('e_Upper_body', 'e_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('d_Upper_body', 'd_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f110', '(Q_Torso*y85-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)
*y110+mt_Torso*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_Torso*ec10/ec0+ mt_Torso*ac*y309/(y309+1)
*vv_Torso*ec10/ec0+ktiec*iec10*vv_Torso+ktiecte*(TE)*iec10*vv_Torso-
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e_Torso*y110*v_v_Torso-d_Torso*y110*v_v_Torso)/v_v_Torso');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('e_liver', 'e_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('d_liver', 'd_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f111', '(Q_intestin*y85-(Q_intestin-
L_intestin)*y111+mt_intestin*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*v_v_intestin*ec5/ec0+ mt_intestin*ac*y307/
(y307+1)*v_v_intestin*ec5/ec0+ktiec*iec5*v_v_intestin+ktiecte*(TE)*iec5*v_v_intestin-
e_intestin*y111*v_v_intestin-d_intestin*y111*v_v_intestin)/v_v_intestin');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('e_liver', 'e_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('d_liver', 'd_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f111', '(Q_intestin*y85-(Q_intestin-
L_intestin)*y111+mt_Intestine*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*v_v_intestin*ec5/ec0+ mt_Intestine*ac*y307/
(y307+1)*v_v_intestin*ec5/ec0+ktiec*iec5*v_v_intestin+ktiecte*(TE)*iec5*v_v_intestin-
e_intestin*y111*v_v_intestin-d_intestin*y111*v_v_intestin)/v_v_intestin');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f117', '(Q_Lower_body*y85-(Q_Lower_body-
L_Lower_body)*y117+mt_Lower_body*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*v_v_Lower_body*ec8/ec0+
mt_Lower_body*ac*y308/(y308+1)*v_v_Lower_body*ec8/ec0+ktiec*iec8*v_v_Lower_body+ktiecte*
(TE)*iec8*v_v_Lower_body-e_Lower_body*y117*v_v_Lower_body-d_Lower_body*y117*v_v_Lower_body)
/v_v_Lower_body');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('e_liver', 'e_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('d_liver', 'd_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f119', '(Q_brain*y85-(Q_brain-L_brain)
*y119+mt_brain*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*v_v_brain*ec3/ec0+ mt_brain*ac*y303/(y303+1)
*v_v_brain*ec3/ec0+ktiec*iec3*v_v_brain+ktiecte*(TE)*iec3*v_v_brain-e_brain*y119*v_v_brain-
d_brain*y119*v_v_brain)/v_v_brain');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('e_liver', 'e_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('d_liver', 'd_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f119', '(Q_brain*y85-(Q_brain-L_brain)
*y119+mt_Brain*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*v_v_brain*ec3/ec0+ mt_Brain*ac*y303/(y303+1)
*v_v_brain*ec3/ec0+ktiec*iec3*v_v_brain+ktiecte*(TE)*iec3*v_v_brain-e_brain*y119*v_v_brain-
d_brain*y119*v_v_brain)/v_v_brain');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f121', '(Q_kidney*y85-(Q_kidney-L_kidney)
*y121+mt_kidney*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*v_v_kidney*ec6/ec0+ mt_kidney*ac*y305/(y305+1)
*v_v_kidney*ec6/ec0+ktiec*iec6*v_v_kidney+ktiecte*(TE)*iec6*v_v_kidney-
e_kidney*y121*v_v_kidney-d_kidney*y121*v_v_kidney)/v_v_kidney');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('e_liver', 'e_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('d_liver', 'd_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f124', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y85-
(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y124+mt_Cardiac_vessels*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)
*v_v_Cardiac_vessels*ec4/ec0+ mt_Cardiac_vessels*ac*y306/(y306+1)
*v_v_Cardiac_vessels*ec4/ec0+ktiec*iec4*v_v_Cardiac_vessels+ktiecte*(TE)
*iec4*v_v_Cardiac_vessels-e_Cardiac_vessels*y124*v_v_Cardiac_vessels-
d_Cardiac_vessels*y124*v_v_Cardiac_vessels)/v_v_Cardiac_vessels');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('e_liver', 'e_liver');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('d_liver', 'd_liver');

model.component('comp1').physics('dode15').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f108', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode15').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'(d_liver*y108*v_v_liver-e_liver*y1072*v_v_liver)/v_v_liver', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode15').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'(d_liver*y108*v_v_liver-e_liver*y1082*v_v_liver)/v_v_liver', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode15').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
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'(d_spleen*y108*vv_spleen-e_spleen*y1082*vv_spleen)/vv_spleen', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode19').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f109', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode19').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_Upper_body*y107*vv_liver-e_liver*y1072*vv_liver)/vv_liver', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode19').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_Upper_body*y107*vv_Upper_body-e_Upper_body*y1072*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode23').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f110', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode23').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 1, 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode23').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_torso*y107*vv_Upper_body-e_Upper_body*y1072*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode23').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_Torso*y107*vv_Upper_body-e_Upper_body*y1072*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode23').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_Torso*y107*vv_Torso-e_Torso*y1072*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode27').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f111', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode27').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_Torso*y107*vv_Torso-e_Torso*y1072*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode27').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_intestin*y107*vv_intestin-e_intestin*y1072*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode31').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f117', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode31').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_Lower_Body*y107*vv_intestin-e_intestin*y1072*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode31').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_Lower_body*y107*vv_intestin-e_intestin*y1072*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode31').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_Lower_body*y107*vv_Lower_body-e_Lower_body*y1072*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode35').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f119', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode35').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_Lower_body*y107*vv_Lower_body-e_Lower_body*y1072*vv_Lower_body)/vv_brain', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode35').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_brain*y107*vv_brain-e_brain*y1072*vv_brain)/vv_brain', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode38').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f121', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode38').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_Lower_body*y107*vv_Lower_body-e_Lower_body*y1072*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Kidney', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode38').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_Lower_body*y107*vv_Lower_body-e_Lower_body*y1072*vv_Lower_body)/vv_kidney', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode38').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_kidney*y107*vv_kidney-e_kidney*y1072*vv_kidney)/vv_kidney', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode42').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'f124', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode42').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_cardiac_vessel*y107*vv_kidney-e_kidney*y1072*vv_kidney)/vv_kidney', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode42').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_Cardiac_vessels*y107*vv_Cardiac_vessels-e_Cardiac_vessels*y1072*vv_Cardiac_vessels) ✓
/vv_Cardiac_vessels', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode42').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_Cardiac_vessels*y124*vv_Cardiac_vessels-e_Cardiac_vessels*y1242*vv_Cardiac_vessels) ✓
/vv_Cardiac_vessels', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode35').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_brain*y119*vv_brain-e_brain*y1192*vv_brain)/vv_brain', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode31').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ✓
'(d_Lower_body*y117*vv_Lower_body-e_Lower_body*y1172*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body', 1);
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model.component('comp1').physics('dode27').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ↵
'(d_intestin*y111*vv_intestin-e_intestin*y1112*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode23').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ↵
'(d_Torso*y110*vv_Torso-e_Torso*y1102*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode19').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ↵
'(d_Upper_body*y109*vv_Upper_body-e_Upper_body*y1092*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body', 1);

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f203', '(Q_brain*y200-(Q_brain-L_brain) ↵
*y203-Kay*y62*y203*vv_brain-Kaiec*iec3*y203*vv_brain-Kay*203*vv_brain)/vv_brain');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('Kaiec', '1[1/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f203', '(Q_brain*y200-(Q_brain-L_brain) ↵
*y203-Kay*y62*y203*vv_brain-Kaiec*iec3*y203*vv_brain-Kay*203*vv_brain)/vv_brain');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', '(Q_brain*y200-(Q_brain-L_brain) ↵
*y203-Kay*y62*y203*vv_brain-Kaiec*iec3*y203*vv_brain-Kay*203*vv_brain)/vv_brain');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', 'Kay*203');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('Kaiec', 'Ka');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', '(Q_brain*y200-(Q_brain-L_brain) ↵
*y203-Kay*y62*y203*vv_brain)/vv_brain');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', '-Kaiec*iec3*y203*vv_brain');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test2', '-Ka*y203*vv_brain');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', '-Kaiec*iec3*y203*vv_brain- ↵
Ka*y203*vv_brain');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test', '(Q_brain*y200-(Q_brain-L_brain) ↵
*y203-Kay*y62*y203*vv_brain-Kaiec*iec3*y203*vv_brain-Ka*y203*vv_brain)/vv_brain');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('test1', '-Kaiec*iec3*y203*vv_brain');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('Kaiec', '1[m^3/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f203', '(Q_brain*y200-(Q_brain-L_brain) ↵
*y203-Kay*y62*y203*vv_brain-Kaiec*iec3*y203*vv_brain-Ka*y203*vv_brain)/vv_brain');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f204', '(Q_spleen*y200-(Q_spleen- ↵
L_spleen)*y204-Kay*y18*y204*vv_spleen-Kaiec*iec9*y204*vv_spleen-Ka*y204*vv_spleen) ↵
/vv_spleen');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f206', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y200- ↵
(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y206-Kay*y74*y206*vv_Cardiac_vessels- ↵
Kaiec*iec4*y206*vv_Cardiac_vessels-Ka*y206*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f207', '(Q_intestin*y200-(Q_intestin- ↵
L_intestin)*y207-Kay*y30*y207*vv_intestin-Kaiec*iec5*y207*vv_intestin- ↵
Ka*y207*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f208', '(Q_Lower_body*y200-(Q_Lower_body- ↵
L_Lower_body)*y208-Kay*y54*y208*vv_Lower_body-Kaiec*iec8*y208*vv_Lower_body- ↵
Ka*y208*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f205', '(Q_kidney*y200-(Q_kidney- ↵
L_kidney)*y205-Kay*y70*y205*vv_kidney-Kaiec*iec6*y205*vv_kidney-Ka*y205*vv_kidney) ↵
/vv_kidney');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f209', '(Q_Torso*y200-(Q_Torso-L_Torso) ↵
*y209-Kay*y26*y209*vv_Torso-Kaiec*iec10*y209*vv_Torso-Ka*y209*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f210', '(Q_Upper_body*y200-(Q_Upper_body- ↵
L_Upper_body)*y210-Kay*y22*y210*vv_Upper_body-Kaiec*iec11*y210*vv_Upper_body- ↵
Ka*y210*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f303', '1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f304', '1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f305', '1');
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model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f307', '1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f308', '1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f309', '1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f310', '1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f306', '1');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f303', '(Q_brain*y300-(Q_brain-L_brain)
*y303+Kc_innate*(n+ma)*vv_brain+kciec*iec3*vv_brain+kcil6*sIL6RbIL6*KcEC*ec3*vv_brain-
d_s*y303*vv_brain)/vv_brain');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f304', '(Q_spleen*y300-(Q_spleen-
L_spleen)*y304+Kc_innate*(n+ma)
*vv_spleen+kciec*iec9*vv_spleen+kcil6*sIL6RbIL6*KcEC*ec9*vv_spleen-d_s*y304*vv_spleen)
/vv_spleen');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f305', '(Q_kidney*y300-(Q_kidney-
L_kidney)*y305+Kc_innate*(n+ma)
*vv_kidney+kciec*iec6*vv_kidney+kcil6*sIL6RbIL6*KcEC*ec6*vv_kidney-d_s*y305*vv_kidney)
/vv_kidney');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f306', '(Q_Cardiac_vessels*y300-
(Q_Cardiac_vessels-L_Cardiac_vessels)*y306+Kc_innate*(n+ma)
*vv_Cardiac_vessels+kciec*iec4*vv_Cardiac_vessels+kcil6*sIL6RbIL6*KcEC*ec4*vv_Cardiac_ves
sels-d_s*y306*vv_Cardiac_vessels)/vv_Cardiac_vessels');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f307', '(Q_intestin*y300-(Q_intestin-
L_intestin)*y307+Kc_innate*(n+ma)
*vv_intestin+kciec*iec5*vv_intestin+kcil6*sIL6RbIL6*KcEC*ec5*vv_intestin-
d_s*y307*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f308', '(Q_Lower_body*y300-(Q_Lower_body-
L_Lower_body)*y308+Kc_innate*(n+ma)
*vv_Lower_body+kciec*iec8*vv_Lower_body+kcil6*sIL6RbIL6*KcEC*ec8*vv_Lower_body-
d_s*y308*vv_Lower_body)/vv_Lower_body');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f309', '(Q_Torso*y300-(Q_Torso-L_Torso)
*y309+Kc_innate*(n+ma)*vv_Torso+kciec*iec10*vv_Torso+kcil6*sIL6RbIL6*KcEC*ec10*vv_Torso-
d_s*y309*vv_Torso)/vv_Torso');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f310', '(Q_Upper_body*y300-(Q_Upper_body-
L_Upper_body)*y310+Kc_innate*(n+ma)
*vv_Upper_body+kciec*iec11*vv_Upper_body+kcil6*sIL6RbIL6*KcEC*ec11*vv_Upper_body-
d_s*y310*vv_Upper_body)/vv_Upper_body');

model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec2-
Kecb*ec2*Vint1-phiciec*ec2*n*(KHIEC*(y302-a/a_0)+1)', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec3-
Kecb*ec3*Vint1-phiciec*ec3*n*(KHIEC*(y307-a/a_0)+1)', 2);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec7-
Kecb*ec7*Vint1-phiciec*ec7*n*(KHIEC*(y302-a/a_0)+1)', 3);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec4-
Kecb*ec4*Vint1-phiciec*ec7*n*(KHIEC*(y302-a/a_0)+1)', 3);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec3-
Kecb*ec3*Vint1-phiciec*ec3*n*(KHIEC*(y303-a/a_0)+1)', 2);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec2-
Kecb*ec2*Vint1-phiciec*ec2*n*(KHIEC*(y300-a/a_0)+1)', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec3-
Kecb*ec3*Vint7-phiciec*ec3*n*(KHIEC*(y303-a/a_0)+1)', 2);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec4-
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Kecb*ec4*Vint9-phiciec*ec4*n*(KHIEC*(y306-a/a_0)+1)', 3);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec5-
Kecb*ec5*Vint5-phiciec*ec5*n*(KHIEC*(y307-a/a_0)+1)', 4);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec6-
Kecb*ec6*Vint8-phiciec*ec6*n*(KHIEC*(y305-a/a_0)+1)', 5);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec8-
Kecb*ec8*Vint6-phiciec*ec6*n*(KHIEC*(y308-a/a_0)+1)', 7);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec9-
Kecb*ec9*Vint8-phiciec*ec8*n*(KHIEC*(y305-a/a_0)+1)', 8);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec8-
Kecb*ec8*Vint6-phiciec*ec8*n*(KHIEC*(y308-a/a_0)+1)', 7);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec9-
Kecb*ec9*Vint2-phiciec*ec9*n*(KHIEC*(y304-a/a_0)+1)', 8);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec10-
Kecb*ec10*Vint4-phiciec*ec10*n*(KHIEC*(y309-a/a_0)+1)', 9);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec11-
Kecb*ec11*Vint3-phiciec*ec11*n*(KHIEC*(y310-a/a_0)+1)', 10);
model.component('comp1').physics('ec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kec*ec12-
Kecb*ec12*Vint8-phiciec*ec12*n*(KHIEC*(y301-a/a_0)+1)', 11);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'Kecb*ec2*Vint1+phiciec*ec2*n*(KHIEC*(y302-a/a_0)+1)-Kif2*iec2*IF-KInM*iec2*TM-
KTIEC*iec2-KTieTE*TE*iec2', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'Kecb*ec3*Vint7+phiciec*ec3*n*(KHIEC*(y303-a/a_0)+1)-Kif2*iec3*IF-KInM*iec3*TM-
KTIEC*iec3-KTieTE*TE*iec3', 2);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'Kecb*ec4*Vint9+phiciec*ec4*n*(KHIEC*(y306-a/a_0)+1)-Kif2*iec4*IF-KInM*iec4*TM-
KTIEC*iec4-KTieTE*TE*iec4', 3);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'Kecb*ec5*Vint5+phiciec*ec5*n*(KHIEC*(y307-a/a_0)+1)-Kif2*iec5*IF-KInM*iec5*TM-
KTIEC*iec5-KTieTE*TE*iec5', 4);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'Kecb*ec6*Vint8+phiciec*ec6*n*(KHIEC*(y305-a/a_0)+1)-Kif2*iec6*IF-KInM*iec6*TM-
KTIEC*iec6-KTieTE*TE*iec6', 5);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'Kecb*ec8*Vint6+phiciec*ec8*n*(KHIEC*(y308-a/a_0)+1)-Kif2*iec8*IF-KInM*iec8*TM-
KTIEC*iec8-KTieTE*TE*iec8', 7);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'Kecb*ec9*Vint2+phiciec*ec9*n*(KHIEC*(y304-a/a_0)+1)-Kif2*iec9*IF-KInM*iec9*TM-
KTIEC*iec9-KTieTE*TE*iec9', 8);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'Kecb*ec10*Vint4+phiciec*ec10*n*(KHIEC*(y309-a/a_0)+1)-Kif2*iec10*IF-KInM*iec10*TM-
KTIEC*iec10-KTieTE*TE*iec10', 9);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'Kecb*ec11*Vint3+phiciec*ec11*n*(KHIEC*(y310-a/a_0)+1)-Kif2*iec11*IF-KInM*iec11*TM-
KTIEC*iec11-KTieTE*TE*iec11', 10);
model.component('comp1').physics('iec').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'Kecb*ec12*Vint3+phiciec*ec12*n*(KHIEC*(y301-a/a_0)+1)-Kif2*iec12*IF-KInM*iec12*TM-
KTIEC*iec12-KTieTE*TE*iec12', 11);

model.component('comp1').variable('var22').remove('d_spleen');
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model.component('comp1').variable('var22').remove('d_Upper_body');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').remove('d_Torso');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').remove('d_intestin');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').remove('d_Lower_body');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').remove('d_brain');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').remove('d_kidney');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').remove('d_Cardiac_vessels');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f111', '(Q_intestin*y85-(Q_intestin-
L_intestin)*y111+mt_Intestine*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_intestin*ec5/ec0+ mt_Intestine*ac*y307/
(y307+1)*vv_intestin*ec5/ec0+ktiec*iec5*vv_intestin+ktiecte*(TE)*iec5*vv_intestin-
e_intestin*y111*vv_intestin-d_Intestine*y111*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin');
model.component('comp1').variable('var22').set('f119', '(Q_brain*y85-(Q_brain-L_brain)
*y119+mt_Brain*ac*IL6/(IL6+1)*vv_brain*ec3/ec0+ mt_Brain*ac*y303/(y303+1)
*vv_brain*ec3/ec0+ktiec*iec3*vv_brain+ktiecte*(TE)*iec3*vv_brain-e_brain*y119*vv_brain-
d_Brain*y119*vv_brain)/vv_brain');

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('dode27').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'(d_Intestine*y111*vv_intestin-e_intestin*y1112*vv_intestin)/vv_intestin', 1);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode35').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'(d_Brain*y119*vv_brain-e_brain*y1192*vv_brain)/vv_brain', 1);

model.label('New Covid model_value_newPK - Copy.mph');

model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').set('initialstepbdfactive', true);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').set('initialstepbdf', 0.01);
model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('New Covid model_value_newPK - Coprun initial time stepy.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dodel').setIndex('f',
'p_lung*Cb+Kint*Cb-Ka*Vint', 0);

model.label('New Covid model_value_newPK - full check.mph');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
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model.label('New Covid model_value_newPK - full check_run.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('New Covid model_value_newPK - full check_run_clear.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics.remove('VEGF');
model.component('comp1').physics.remove('Ctl');
model.component('comp1').physics.remove('cox_oxygen');
model.component('comp1').physics.remove('dode5');
model.component('comp1').physics.remove('dode6');
model.component('comp1').physics.remove('dode8');
model.component('comp1').physics.remove('CD4');
model.component('comp1').physics.remove('InCD4');
model.component('comp1').physics.remove('CD8');
model.component('comp1').physics.remove('InCD8');
model.component('comp1').physics.remove('NaiveTcell');
model.component('comp1').physics.remove('ActivatedTcell');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg44').run;
model.result.remove('pg44');
model.result.remove('pg45');
model.result.remove('pg46');
model.result.remove('pg47');
model.result.remove('pg48');
model.result.remove('pg49');
model.result.remove('pg50');
model.result.remove('pg51');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result.table.create('tbl2', 'Table');
model.result.table.remove('tbl2');
model.result.numerical.create('pev1', 'EvalPoint');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y301');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('New Covid model_value_newPK - full check_run_clear_1.mph');

model.component('comp1').physics('IL6').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KIL6*ma*Ci-  
gam_IL6*IL6-KonIL6*IL6*IL6R+KoffIL6*IL6RbIL6+KoffsIL6R*sIL6RbIL6-  
KonsIL6R*sIL6R*IL6+KIL6TN*TN+KIL6IEC*iec+KIL6TE*TE+KIL6In*In', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-  
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung/1000-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci-  
Kv*Ci*A+Ka*(1-IF/(Kif+IF))*Vint', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
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'p_lung*Cb+Kint*Cb-Ka*(1-KifIF/(Kif+IF))*Vint', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ↵
'p_lung*Cb+Kint*Cb-Ka*(1-Kif*IF/(Kif+IF))*Vint', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', ↵
'p_lung*Vint+Kint*Cb-Ka*(1-Kif*IF/(Kif+IF))*Vint', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('n').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'xn*c/(1+a/a0)-↵
gam_n*n*(1+bn*Ci/(Ci+1))+xIL6*IL6RbIL6', 0);

model.label('New Covid model_value_newPK - full check_run_clear_1.mph');
model.label('Covid vaccines model.mph');

model.sol('sol54').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol54').clearSolutionData;

model.label('Covid vaccines model_clearsolution.mph');

model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode5', 'DomainODE', {'u9'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode5', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode5', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'Va');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').tag('Va');
model.component('comp1').physics('Va').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', ↵
'1/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Va').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*Va-↵
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Va)/vv_lung/1000-Koncellva*Va*H-↵
KonAPCva*Va*DCi+Koffcellva*Va*H+KoffAPCva*Va*H-Kd*Va', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable.create('var24');
model.component('comp1').variable('var24').label('vaccine');
model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('Koncellva', 'KonACE2V');
model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('KonAPCva', 'KonACE2V');
model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('Koffcellva', 'KoffACE2V');
model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('KoffAPCva', 'KoffACE2V');
model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('Kdva', 'Kd');

model.component('comp1').physics('Va').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*Va-↵
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Va)/vv_lung/1000-Koncellva*Va*H-↵
KonAPCva*Va*DCi+Koffcellva*Va*H+KoffAPCva*Va*H-Kdva*Va', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('Koncellva', 'KonACE2V*1[mole]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('Koffcellva', 'KoffACE2V*1[m^3]');

model.component('comp1').physics('Va').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*Va-↵
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Va)/vv_lung/1000-Koncellva*Va*H-↵
KonAPCva*Va*DCi+Koffcellva*Va*H+KoffAPCva*Va*DCi-Kdva*Va', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Va').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', ↵

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```
'1');
model.component('comp1').physics('Va').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity',
'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('Va').prop('Units').setIndex
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Va').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'M/s', 0, 0);

model.sol('sol154').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('Va').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*Va-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Va)/vv_lung/1000', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Va').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*Va-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Va)/vv_lung/1000-Koncellva*Va*H', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Va').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*Va-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Va)/vv_lung/1000-Koncellva*Va*H-KonAPCva*Va*DCi', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Va').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*Va-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Va)/vv_lung/1000-Koncellva*Va*H-
KonAPCva*Va*DCi+Koffcellva*Va*H+KoffAPCva*Va*DCi-Kdva*Va', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('KonAPCva', 'KoffACE2V');

model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode6', 'DomainODE', {'u19'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode6', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode6', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode6').identifier('dode6');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode6').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'Vab');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode6').tag('Vab');
model.component('comp1').physics('Vab').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'+Koncellva*Va*H+KonAPCva*Va*DCi-Koffcellva*Va*H-KoffAPCva*Va*DCi-KintVa*Vab', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('KintVa', 'Kint');

model.component('comp1').physics('Vab').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit',
'1');
model.component('comp1').physics('Vab').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity',
'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('Vab').prop('Units').setIndex
('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vab').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'm^-
2');
model.component('comp1').physics('Vab').prop('Units').set('SourceTermQuantity', 'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('Vab').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'm^-
2');
model.component('comp1').physics('Vab').prop('Units').set('SourceTermQuantity', 'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('Vab').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'M/s', 0, 0);
```

```
model.component('comp1').physics('Va').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SVa+(Q_lung*Va-  
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Va)/vv_lung/1000-Koncellva*Va*H-  
KonAPCva*Va*DCi+Koffcellva*Va*H+KoffAPCva*Va*DCi-Kdva*Va', 0);  
  
model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('SVa', '1[M/s]');  
  
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode5', 'DomainODE', {'u36'});  
  
model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode5', true);  
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode5', true);  
  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'Vaint');  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').tag('Vaint');  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vaint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KintVa', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vaint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KintVa*Vab',  
0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vaint').prop('Units').set  
( 'CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1' );  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vaint').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity',  
'none');  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vaint').prop('Units').setIndex  
( 'CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0 );  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vaint').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'm^-  
2' );  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vaint').prop('Units').set('SourceTermQuantity',  
'none');  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vaint').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',  
'M/s', 0, 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vaint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KintVa*Vab-',  
0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vaint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KintVa*Vab-  
KTran*', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('Vaint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KintVa*Vab-  
KTran*Vaint', 0);  
  
model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('KTran', 'KintVa/100');  
  
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode6', 'DomainODE', {'u37'});  
  
model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode6', true);  
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode6', true);  
  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode6').identifier('dode6');  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode6').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'VaTran');  
model.component('comp1').physics('dode6').tag('VaTran');  
model.component('comp1').physics('VaTran').prop('Units').set  
( 'CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1' );  
model.component('comp1').physics('VaTran').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity',  
'none');  
model.component('comp1').physics('VaTran').prop('Units').setIndex  
( 'CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0 );
```

```
model.component('comp1').physics('VaTran').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'm^-2');
model.component('comp1').physics('VaTran').prop('Units').set('SourceTermQuantity', 'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('VaTran').prop('Units').set('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'm^-2');
model.component('comp1').physics('VaTran').prop('Units').set('SourceTermQuantity', 'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('VaTran').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'M/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('VaTran').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Ktran*Vaint-', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('VaTran').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Ktran*Vaint-Kpro*VaTran', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('Kpro', 'KTran/100');

model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode5', 'DomainODE', ('u38'));

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode5', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode5', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'VaPro');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').prop('Units').set('CustomDependentVariableUnit', '1');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').prop('Units').set('DependentVariableQuantity', 'none');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomDependentVariableUnit', 'M', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit', 'M/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').tag('VaPro');
model.component('comp1').physics('VaPro').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kpro*VaTran', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('VaTran').active(false);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vaint').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'KintVa*Vab-Kpro*Vaint', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('VaPro').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Kpro*Vaint', 0);

model.label('Covid vaccines model_mRNA.mph');

model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('SVa', '1[M/d]*(t>0[d])*(t<1[d])+1[M/d]*(t>21[d])*(t<22[d])');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Va');
model.result('pg40').run;
```

```
model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tlist', 'range(0,1,40)');

model.sol('sol54').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'VaPro');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('As', 'VaPro/1000[mol/m^3]');

model.component('comp1').physics('VaPro').feature('init1').set('VaPro', 'eps');

model.sol('sol54').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'As');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DCi');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'ThN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'ThE');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('As', 'VaPro/1[mol/m^3]');

model.sol('sol54').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'ThN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'As');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').active(false);

model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('Ci', '0[M]');

model.sol('sol54').runAll;
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vab');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vaint');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('Covid vaccines model_mRNA_run_As_nonvirus.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'As');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'SVa');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'As');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Va');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'VaPro');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').set('maxstepconstraintbdf', 'const');
model.sol('sol154').feature('t1').set('maxstepbdf', 1);
model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('Covid vaccines model_mRNA_run_As_nonvirus_timestep_1d.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('Cb').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '+KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2-
KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Cb/100-Kint*Cb', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Cb').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '+KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2-
KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Cb-Kint*Cb', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').feature('cdeq1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y78-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Ci)/vv_lung-KsACE2*sACE2*Ci-KonACE2V*Ci*ACE2+KoffACE2V*Cb-Kd*Ci-
Kv*Ci*A+Ka*(1-IF/(Kif+IF))*Vint', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('DC').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SDC-bD*DC*Ci-
dDC*DC-KTregDC*Treg*DC', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics.create('dode5', 'DomainODE', {'u39'});

model.study('std1').feature('param').activate('dode5', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('dode5', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').field('dimensionless').component(1, 'Treg');
model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').prop('Units').setIndex('CustomSourceTermUnit',
'1/s', 0, 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'Streg', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('dode5').feature('dode1').setIndex('f',
'STreg+pTreg*Treg*(a/(1+c))-dTreg*Treg', 0);
```

```
model.component('comp1').variable.create('var25');
model.component('comp1').variable('var25').set('KTregDC', 'hT');
model.component('comp1').variable('var25').set('STreg', 'SDC');
model.component('comp1').variable('var25').set('pTreg', 'hT');
model.component('comp1').variable('var25').set('dTreg', 'dDC');

model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bD*DC*Ci-  
dDCi*DCiKTregDC*Treg*DCi', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bD*DC*Ci-  
dDCi*DCi-KTregDC*Treg*DCi', 0);

model.sol('sol154').clearSolutionData;

model.label('Covid vaccines model_mRNA_Treg.mph');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'As');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'ThN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'ThE');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DC');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DCi');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Treg');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').feature('init1').set('DCi', 1.5);

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DC');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DCi');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'ThN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'ThE');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'VaPro');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('Covid vaccines model_mRNA_Treg_run.mph');
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Va');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vab');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vaint');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'VaPro');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y200');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y201');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y202');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y203');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y204');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y205');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'y206');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('phic', '2.3e-9 [ml/h]*0');

model.sol('sol54').clearSolutionData;

model.label('Covid vaccines model_mRNA_Treg_run_phic0 - Copy.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol54').runAll;
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('Covid vaccines model_mRNA_Treg_run_phic0 - Copy_run.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'H');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SThN-hTE*DCi*ThN*
((VaPro/(1+VaPro))(As/(1+As)))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dThN*ThN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SThN-hTE*DCi*ThN*
((VaPro/(1+VaPro))(As/(1+As)))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dThN*ThN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SThN-hTE*DCi*ThN*
((VaPro/(1+VaPro))+(As/(1+As)))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dThN*ThN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('The').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'hTE*DCi*ThN*
((VaPro/(1+VaPro))+(As/(1+As)))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))+rN*The*(As/
(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-pThM*The-eTE*The*PD1bPDL1/As', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TN').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'STN-hT*DCi*TN*
((VaPro/(1+VaPro))+(As/(1+As)))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dT*TN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TE').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'hT*DCi*TN*((VaPro/
(1+VaPro))+(As/(1+As)))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))+rT*TE*(As/(1+As))*(c/
(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-pTM*TE-eTE*TE*PD1bPDL1/As', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('BN').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SB-hT*DCi*The*
((VaPro/(1+VaPro))+(As/(1+As)))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-dB*BN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('BA').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'hT*DCi*The*
((VaPro/(1+VaPro))+(As/(1+As)))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))+rB*The*BA-
dBA*BA-pS*BA-pL*(The+ThM)*BA', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Va').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SVa+(Q_lung*Va-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*Va)/vv_lung/1000-Koncellva*Va*H+Koffcellva*Va*H-Kdva*Va', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vab').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '+Koncellva*Va*H-
Koffcellva*Va*H-KintVa*Vab', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vab').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '+Koncellva*Va*H-
Koffcellva*Va*H-KintVa*Vab-Kdva*Va', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vaint').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KintVa*Vab-
daint', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('Vaint').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'KintVa*Vab-
dVaint', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('VaPro').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'Kpro*Vaint-
dVaPro', 0);

model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('Kdva', 'Kdva');
model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('dVaint', '1e-6[mole/m^3/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('dVaPro', 'dVaint');

model.sol('sol154').clearSolutionData;
```

```
model.label('Covid vaccines model_mRNA_Treg_run_phic0 - Copy_run_degradation.mph');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'VaPro');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vaint');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Vab');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Va');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'VaPro');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('dVaint', '1e-2[mole/m^3/s]');
model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('dVaPro', 'dVaint/2');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tlist', 'range(0,1,140)');

model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('dVaint', '3e-4[mole/m^3/s]');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'SB-hT*DCi*ThE*((VaPro/(1+VaPro))+(As/(1+As))) * (c/(1+c)) * (IF/(Kif+IF)) * (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1)) -dB*BN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'SB');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'SB-hT*DCi*ThE*((VaPro/(1+VaPro))+(As/(1+As))) * (c/(1+c)) * (IF/(Kif+IF)) * (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1)) -dB*BN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'SB-dB*BN');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').variable('var1').set('SB', 'B0*1[1/s]');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BA');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BA');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'SB-hT*DCi*ThE*((VaPro/(1+VaPro))+(As/(1+As))) * (c/(1+c)) * (IF/(Kif+IF)) * (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1)) -dB*BN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'hT*DCi*ThE*((VaPro/(1+VaPro))+(As/(1+As))) * (c/(1+c)) * (IF/(Kif+IF)) * (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'c');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'c0');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(Q_lung*y301*c0-(Q_lung-L_lung) *c+Kc_innate*(n+ma)*vv_lung*c0+kciec*(iec+In)*vv_lung*c0+SAT1R*AT1bAngII*vv_lung+KcIL6R*sIL6RbIL6*(KcEC*ec+KcH*H)*vv_lung- KAT1RMAsR*MASR*1[pg/fmol]*vv_lung-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1[pg/M]-d_s*Ci*vv_lung*1[pg/mole])/vv_lung');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(Q_lung*y301*c0-(Q_lung-L_lung) *c+Kc_innate*(n+ma)*vv_lung*c0+kciec*(iec+In)*vv_lung*c0+SAT1R*AT1bAngII*vv_lung+KcIL6R*sIL6RbIL6*(KcEC*ec+KcH*H)*vv_lung- KAT1RMAsR*MASR*1[pg/fmol]*vv_lung-KAT1RAT2R*AT2R*1[pg/M]-d_s/1000*Ci*vv_lung*1[pg/mole])/vv_lung');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Q_lung*y301*c0-(Q_lung-L_lung)*c');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BA');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'SB-hT*DCi*ThE*((VaPro/(1+VaPro))+(As/(1+As))) * (c/(1+c)) * (IF/(Kif+IF)) * (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1)) -dB*BN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'hT*DCi*ThE*((VaPro/(1+VaPro))+(As/(1+As))) * (c/(1+c)) * (IF/(Kif+IF)) * (KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'hT*DCi*ThE*((VaPro/(1+VaPro))+(As/(1+As)))');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'VaPro');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DC');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DCi');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bd*DC*Ci-dDCi*DCi-KTregDC*Treg*DCi/1000', 0);
```

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model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bD*DC*Ci-
dDCi*DCi/100-KTregDC*Treg*DCi/1000', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bD*DC*Ci-
dDCi*DCi-KTregDC*Treg*DCi+bD*DC*(VaPro/(1+VaPro))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bD*DC*Ci-
dDCi*DCi-KTregDC*Treg*DCi+bD*DC*(VaPro/(1+VaPro))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bD*DC*Ci-
dDCi*DCi-KTregDC*Treg*DCi+1e-2[1/s]*DC*(VaPro/(1+VaPro))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('DC').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SDC-bD*DC*Ci-
dDC*DC-KTregDC*Treg*DC-1e-2[1/s]*DC*(VaPro/(1+VaPro))', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BA');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('BA').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hT*DCi*ThE*
((VaPro/(1+VaPro))+(As/(1+As)))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))+rB*ThE*BA-
dBA/100*BA-pS*BA-pL*(ThE+ThM)*BA', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature.duplicate('ptgr3', 'ptgr2');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr3').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr3').active(false);
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature.remove('ptgr3');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DC');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DCi');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bD*DC*Ci-
dDCi*DCi/100-KTregDC*Treg*DCi/100+1e-2[1/s]*DC*(VaPro/(1+VaPro))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('DC').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SDC-bD*DC*Ci-
dDC*DC/100-KTregDC*Treg*DC/100-1e-2[1/s]*DC*(VaPro/(1+VaPro))', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DC');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'hT*DCi*ThE*((VaPro/(1+VaPro))+(As/

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(1+As)) * (c / (1+c)) * (IF / (Kif+IF)) * (KT / (KT+PD1bPDL1))');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BA');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DCi');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PS');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PL');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('BA').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hT*100*DCi*ThE*
((VaPro / (1+VaPro)) + (As / (1+As))) * (c / (1+c)) * (IF / (Kif+IF)) * (KT / (KT+PD1bPDL1)) + rB*ThE*BA-
dBA/10000*BA-pS*BA-pL*(ThE+ThM)*BA', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BA');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('BN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SB-hT*100*DCi*ThE*
((VaPro / (1+VaPro)) + (As / (1+As))) * (c / (1+c)) * (IF / (Kif+IF)) * (KT / (KT+PD1bPDL1)) - dB*BN', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DCi');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'ThE');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bd*DC*Ci-
dDCi*DCi/1000-KTregDC*Treg*DCi/1000+1e-2[1/s]*DC*(VaPro / (1+VaPro))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('DC').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SDC-bd*DC*Ci-
dDC*DC/1000-KTregDC*Treg*DC/1000-1e-2[1/s]*DC*(VaPro / (1+VaPro))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SThN-hTE*DCi*ThN*
((VaPro / (1+VaPro)) + (As / (1+As))) * (c / (1+c)) * (IF / (Kif+IF)) * (KT / (KT+PD1bPDL1)) - dThN*ThN/100',
0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThE').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hTE*DCi*ThN*
((VaPro / (1+VaPro)) + (As / (1+As))) * (c / (1+c)) * (IF / (Kif+IF)) * (KT / (KT+PD1bPDL1)) + rN*ThE*(As /
(1+As)) * (c / (1+c)) * (IF / (Kif+IF)) * (KT / (KT+PD1bPDL1)) - pThM*ThE/100-eTE*ThE*PD1bPDL1/As', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DCi');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BN');
model.result('pg40').run;
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model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BA');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'SVa');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'VaPro');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PS');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PL');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('A').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y201-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*A+pAS*PS*vv_lung*1000+pAL*PL*vv_lung*1000-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung-KaiecIn*
(iec+In)*A*vv_lung-Ka*A*vv_lung)/vv_lung', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('A').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y201-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*A+pAS*PS*vv_lung*1000+pAL*PL*vv_lung*1000-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung-KaiecIn*
(iec+In)*A*vv_lung-Ka/1000*A*vv_lung)/vv_lung', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'In');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('A').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y201-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*A*0+pAS*PS*vv_lung*1000+pAL*PL*vv_lung*1000-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung*0-KaiecIn*
(iec+In)*A*vv_lung*0-Ka*0*A*vv_lung)/vv_lung', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(Q_lung*y201-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*A*0+pAS*PS*vv_lung*1000+pAL*PL*vv_lung*1000-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung*0-KaiecIn*(iec+In)
*A*vv_lung*0-Ka*0*A*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '(Q_lung*y201-(Q_lung-L_lung)
*A*0+pAS*PS*vv_lung*1000+pAL*PL*vv_lung*1000-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung*0-KaiecIn*(iec+In)
*A*vv_lung*0-Ka*0*A*vv_lung)/vv_lung');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr',
'pAS*PS*vv_lung*1000+pAL*PL*vv_lung*1000');
model.result('pg40').run;
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model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'pAS*PS*vv_lung*1000');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '+pAL*PL*vv_lung*1000');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PS');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.label('Covid vaccines model_mRNA_Treg_run_phic0 - Copy_run_degradation_run2.mph');

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'VaPro');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('DC').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SDC-bD*DC*Ci-
dDC*DC-KTregDC*Treg*DC-1e-2[1/s]*DC*(VaPro/(1+VaPro))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bD*DC*Ci-
dDCi*DCi-KTregDC*Treg*DCi+1e-2[1/s]*DC*(VaPro/(1+VaPro))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SThN-hTE*DCi*ThN*
((VaPro/(1+VaPro)))-dThN*ThN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThE').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hTE*DCi*ThN*
((VaPro/(1+VaPro)))+rN*ThE*(As/(1+As))*(c/(1+c))*(IF/(Kif+IF))*(KT/(KT+PD1bPDL1))-
pThM*ThE/100-eTE*ThE*PD1bPDL1/As', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThE').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hTE*DCi*ThN*
((VaPro/(1+VaPro)))-pThM*ThE-eTE*ThE*PD1bPDL1', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'STN-hT*DCi*TN*
((VaPro/(1+VaPro)))-dTn*TN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'STN-hT*DCi*TN*
((VaPro/(1+VaPro)))-dTn*TN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TE').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hT*DCi*TN*((VaPro/
(1+VaPro))-pTM*TE-eTE*TE*PD1bPDL1', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TE').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hT*DCi*TN*((VaPro/
(1+VaPro)))-pTM*TE-eTE*TE*PD1bPDL1', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('BN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SB-hT*100*DCi*ThE*
((VaPro/(1+VaPro)))-dB*BN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('BA').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hT*100*DCi*ThE*
((VaPro/(1+VaPro)))+rB*ThE*BA-dBA*BA-pS*BA-pL*(ThE+ThM)*BA', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('A').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y201*0-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*A*0+pAS*PS*vv_lung+pAL*PL*vv_lung-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung-KaiecIn*(iec+In)
*A*vv_lung-Ka*A*vv_lung)/vv_lung', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PL');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PS');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'VaPro');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BA');

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model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'ThE');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DC');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DCi');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Treg');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'a');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '((VaPro/(1+VaPro)))');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'VaPro');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro)))');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('DC').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SDC-bD*DC*Ci-
dDC*DC-KTregDC*Treg*DC-1e-2[1/s]*DC*((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro)))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'bD*DC*Ci-
dDCi*DCi-KTregDC*Treg*DCi+1e-2[1/s]*DC*((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro)))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SThN-hTE*DCi*ThN*
((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro)))-dThN*ThN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThE').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'hTE*DCi*ThN*
((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro)))-pThM*ThE-eTE*ThE*PD1bPDL1', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TN').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'STN-hT*DCi*TN*
((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro)))-dTN*TN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TE').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'hT*DCi*TN*
((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro)))-pTM*TE-eTE*TE*PD1bPDL1', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('BN').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'SB-hT*100*DCi*ThE*
((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro)))-dB*BN', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('BA').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', 'hT*100*DCi*ThE*
((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro)))+rB*ThE*BA-dBA*BA-pS*BA-pL*(ThE+ThM)*BA', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', '');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', '1');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BA');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DC');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DCi');
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model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('DC').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SDC-bd*DC*Ci*0-  
dDC*DC/100-KTregDC*Treg*DC*0-1e-2[1/s]*DC*((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bd*DC*Ci*0-  
dDCi*DCi*0-KTregDC*Treg*DCi*0+1e-2[1/s]*DC*((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('DCi').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'bd*DC*Ci*0-  
dDCi*DCi/100-KTregDC*Treg*DCi*0+1e-2[1/s]*DC*((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro))', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SThN-hTE*DCi*ThN*  
((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro))-dThN*ThN/100', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('The').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hTE*DCi*ThN*  
((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro))-pThM*The-eTE*The*PD1bPDL1*0', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'STN-hT*DCi*TN*  
((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro))-dTN*TN/100', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TE').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hT*DCi*TN*  
((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro))-pTM*TE-eTE*TE*PD1bPDL1*0', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('BN').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'SB-hT*100*DCi*The*  
((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro))-dB*BN/100', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('BA').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'hT*100*DCi*The*  
((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro))+rB*The*BA-dBA*BA/10000-pS*BA-pL*(The+ThM)*BA', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PL').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pL*(The+ThM)*BA-  
dL*PL/100', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('PS').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pS*BA-dS*PS/100',  
0);
model.component('comp1').physics('A').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y201*0-  
(Q_lung-L_lung)*A*0+pAS*PS*vv_lung+pAL*PL*vv_lung-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung-KaiecIn*(iec+In)  
*A*vv_lung-Ka*A*vv_lung/1000)/vv_lung', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('ThM').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pThM*The-  
dThM*ThM/100', 0);
model.component('comp1').physics('TM').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', 'pTM*TE-  
dTM*TM/100', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PL');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PS');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('A').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y201*0-  
(Q_lung-L_lung)*A*0+pAS*PS*vv_lung+pAL*PL*vv_lung-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung-KaiecIn*(iec+In)  
*A*vv_lung-Ka*A*vv_lung/10000)/vv_lung', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PL');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('A').feature('dode1').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y201*0-  
(Q_lung-L_lung)*A*0+pAS*PS*vv_lung+pAL*PL*vv_lung-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung-KaiecIn*(iec+In)  
*A*vv_lung-Ka*A*vv_lung*0)/vv_lung', 0);
```

```
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'iec');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('A').feature('dodel').setIndex('f', '(Q_lung*y201*0-
(Q_lung-L_lung)*A*0+pAS*PS*vv_lung+pAL*PL*vv_lung-kav*Ci*A*vv_lung*0-KaiecIn*(iec+In)
*A*vv_lung*0-Ka*A*vv_lung*0)/vv_lung', 0);

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'VaPro');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', '((VaPro/(7000[mole/m^3]+VaPro)))');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'PL');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'BA');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'DCi');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'ThE');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'VaPro');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TN');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'TE');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.study.create('std2');
model.study('std2').create('time', 'Transient');
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('AGT', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('Renin', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('AngI', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('AngII', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('Ang17', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('Ang19', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('AngIII', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('AngIV', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('AT1bAngII', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('AT2bAngII', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('AT4bAngIV', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('MAsbAng17', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('Cb', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('H', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('Vint', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('In', true);
```



```
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('dode35', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('dode36', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('dode37', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('dode38', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('dode39', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('dode40', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('dode41', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('dode42', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('dode43', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('dode44', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('PD1bPDL1', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('antiPD1', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('PDL_1', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('PD1', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('NETs', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('IF', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('DC', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('DCi', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('ThN', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('ThE', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('TN', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('TE', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('BN', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('BA', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('PL', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('PS', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('A', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('y200', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('ThM', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('TM', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('y300', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('Va', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('Vab', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('Vaint', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('VaTran', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('VaPro', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('dode5', true);

model.sol.create('sol55');
model.sol('sol55').study('std2');

model.study('std2').feature('time').set('notlistsolnum', 1);
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('notsolnum', '1');
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('listsolnum', 1);
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('solnum', '1');

model.sol('sol55').create('st1', 'StudyStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('st1').set('study', 'std2');
model.sol('sol55').feature('st1').set('studystep', 'time');
model.sol('sol55').create('v1', 'Variables');
model.sol('sol55').feature('v1').set('control', 'time');
```

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model.sol('sol155').create('t1', 'Time');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('tlist', 'range(0,0.1,1)');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('plot', 'off');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('plotgroup', 'pg40');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('plotfreq', 'tout');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('probesel', 'all');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('probes', {});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('probefreq', 'tsteps');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('atolglobalvaluemethod', 'factor');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('endtimeinterpolation', true);
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('control', 'time');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').create('sel', 'Segregated');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature.remove('ssDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss1', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_A'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45r');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss2', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_a'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 2b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss3', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss3').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_ACE2'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss3').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss3').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 5b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss4', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss4').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_ACE2bAngI'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss4').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss4').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 6b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss5', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss5').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_ACE2bAngII'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss5').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss5').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 7a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss6', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss6').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_AGT'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss6').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss6').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 2');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss7', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss7').set('segvar', ↙
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{'comp1_Ang17'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss7').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss7').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 5');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss8', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss8').set('segvar',
{'comp1_Ang19'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss8').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss8').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 15');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss9', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss9').set('segvar',
{'comp1_AngI'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss9').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss9').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 3');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss10', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss10').set('segvar',
{'comp1_AngII'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss10').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss10').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 4');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss11', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss11').set('segvar',
{'comp1_AngIII'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss11').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss11').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 16');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss12', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss12').set('segvar',
{'comp1_AngIV'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss12').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss12').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 6');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss13', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss13').set('segvar',
{'comp1_antiPD1'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss13').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss13').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 46');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss14', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss14').set('segvar',
{'comp1_AT1bAngII'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss14').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss14').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 7');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss15', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss15').set('segvar',
{'comp1_AT1R'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss15').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss15').label('Domain ODEs and
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DAEs 19');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss16', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss16').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_AT2bAngII'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss16').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss16').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 8');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss17', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss17').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_AT2R'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss17').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss17').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 2c');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss18', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss18').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_AT4bAngIV'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss18').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss18').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 17');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss19', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss19').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_AT4R'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss19').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss19').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 4b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss20', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss20').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_BA'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss20').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss20').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45o');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss21', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss21').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_BN'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss21').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss21').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45n');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss22', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss22').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_c'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss22').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss22').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 12');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss23', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss23').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_Cb'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss23').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss23').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 9');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss24', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss24').set('segvar', ↙
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{'compl_DC'}));
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss24').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss24').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 45i');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss25', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss25').set('segvar',
{'compl_DCi'}));
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss25').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss25').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 45j');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss26', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss26').set('segvar',
{'compl_y5'}));
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss26').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss26').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 23');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss27', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss27').set('segvar',
{'compl_y15'}));
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss27').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss27').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 10a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss28', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss28').set('segvar',
{'compl_y107' 'compl_y1072'}));
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss28').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss28').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 11a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss29', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss29').set('segvar',
{'compl_y87'}));
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss29').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss29').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 12a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss30', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss30').set('segvar',
{'compl_y18'}));
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss30').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss30').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 13a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss31', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss31').set('segvar',
{'compl_y19'}));
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss31').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss31').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 14a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss32', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss32').set('segvar',
{'compl_y108' 'compl_y1082'}));
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss32').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss32').label('Domain ODEs and
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DAEs 15a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss33', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss33').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_y102'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss33').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss33').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 16a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss34', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss34').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_y22'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss34').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss34').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 17a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss35', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss35').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_y23'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss35').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss35').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 18a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss36', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss36').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_y109' 'compl_y1092'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss36').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss36').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 19a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss37', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss37').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_y78'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss37').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss37').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 2h');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss38', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss38').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_y92'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss38').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss38').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 20a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss39', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss39').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_y26'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss39').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss39').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 21a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss40', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss40').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_y27'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss40').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss40').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 22a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss41', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss41').set('segvar', ↙
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{'comp1_y110' 'comp1_y1102'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss41').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss41').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 23a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss42', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss42').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y90'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss42').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss42').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 24');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss43', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss43').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y30'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss43').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss43').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 25');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss44', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss44').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y31'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss44').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss44').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 26');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss45', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss45').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y111' 'comp1_y1112'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss45').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss45').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 27');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss46', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss46').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y103'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss46').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss46').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 28');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss47', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss47').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y54'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss47').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss47').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 29');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss48', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss48').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y85'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss48').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss48').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 3d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss49', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss49').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y55'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss49').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss49').label('Domain ODEs and
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DAEs 30');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss50', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss50').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y117' 'comp1_y1172'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss50').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss50').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 31');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss51', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss51').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y94'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss51').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss51').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 32');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss52', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss52').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y62'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss52').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss52').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 33');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss53', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss53').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y63'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss53').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss53').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 34');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss54', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss54').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y119' 'comp1_y1192'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss54').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss54').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 35');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss55', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss55').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y70'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss55').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss55').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 36');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss56', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss56').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y71'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss56').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss56').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 37');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss57', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss57').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y121' 'comp1_y1212'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss57').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss57').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 38');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss58', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss58').set('segvar', ↙
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{'compl_y98'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss58').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss58').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 39');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss59', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss59').set('segvar',
{'compl_y86'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss59').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss59').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 4a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss60', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss60').set('segvar',
{'compl_y74'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss60').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss60').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 40');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss61', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss61').set('segvar',
{'compl_y75'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss61').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss61').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 41');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss62', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss62').set('segvar',
{'compl_y124' 'compl_y1242'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss62').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss62').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 42');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss63', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss63').set('segvar',
{'compl_y125'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss63').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss63').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 43');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss64', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss64').set('segvar',
{'compl_y96'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss64').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss64').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 44');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss65', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss65').set('segvar',
{'compl_Treg'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss65').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss65').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 5f');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss66', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss66').set('segvar',
{'compl_y105' 'compl_y1052'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss66').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss66').label('Domain ODEs and
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DAEs 7b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss67', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss67').set('segvar', ←
{'comp1_y14'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss67').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss67').label('Domain ODEs and ←
DAEs 9a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss68', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss68').set('segvar', ←
{'comp1_ec' ←
'comp1_ec2' 'comp1_ec3' 'comp1_ec4' 'comp1_ec5' 'comp1_ec6' 'comp1_ec7' 'comp1_ec8' ←
'comp1_ec9' 'comp1_ec10' ...
'comp1_ec11' 'comp1_ec12'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss68').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss68').label('Domain ODEs and ←
DAEs 22');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss69', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss69').set('segvar', ←
{'comp1_H'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss69').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss69').label('Domain ODEs and ←
DAEs 2a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss70', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss70').set('segvar', ←
{'comp1_iec' 'comp1_iec2' 'comp1_iec3' 'comp1_iec4' 'comp1_iec5' 'comp1_iec6' ←
'comp1_iec7' 'comp1_iec8' 'comp1_iec9' 'comp1_iec10' ...
'comp1_iec11' 'comp1_iec12'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss70').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss70').label('Domain ODEs and ←
DAEs 2g');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss71', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss71').set('segvar', ←
{'comp1_IF'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss71').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss71').label('Domain ODEs and ←
DAEs 46c');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss72', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss72').set('segvar', ←
{'comp1_IL6'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss72').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss72').label('Domain ODEs and ←
DAEs 20');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss73', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss73').set('segvar', ←
{'comp1_IL6R'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss73').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss73').label('Domain ODEs and ←
DAEs 2d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss74', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss74').set('segvar', ←
{'comp1_IL6RbIL6'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss74').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss74').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 3c');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss75', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss75').set('segvar', {'compl_In'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss75').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss75').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 6a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss76', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss76').set('segvar', {'compl_ma'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss76').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss76').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 11');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss77', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss77').set('segvar', {'compl_MAsbAng17'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss77').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss77').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 18');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss78', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss78').set('segvar', {'compl_MAsR'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss78').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss78').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 3b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss79', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss79').set('segvar', {'compl_n'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss79').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss79').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 10');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss80', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss80').set('segvar', {'compl_NETs'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss80').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss80').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45e');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss81', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss81').set('segvar', {'compl_PD1'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss81').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss81').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45f');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss82', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss82').set('segvar', {'compl_PD1bPDL1'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss82').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss82').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45g');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss83', 'SegregatedStep');
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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss83').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_PDL1'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss83').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss83').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 47');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss84', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss84').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_PL'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss84').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss84').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 45p');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss85', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss85').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_PS'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss85').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss85').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 45q');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss86', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss86').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_Renin'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss86').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss86').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 14');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss87', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss87').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_sACE2'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss87').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss87').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 2f');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss88', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss88').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_sIL6R'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss88').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss88').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 21');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss89', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss89').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_sIL6RbIL6'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss89').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss89').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss90', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss90').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_TE'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss90').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss90').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 45m');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss91', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss91').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_ThE'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss91').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
```

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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss91').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45k');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss92', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss92').set('segvar', {'compl_ThM'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss92').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss92').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45t');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss93', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss93').set('segvar', {'compl_ThN'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss93').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss93').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 46d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss94', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss94').set('segvar', {'compl_TM'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss94').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss94').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45u');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss95', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss95').set('segvar', {'compl_TN'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss95').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss95').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45l');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss96', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss96').set('segvar', {'compl_Va'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss96').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss96').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 5c');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss97', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss97').set('segvar', {'compl_Vab'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss97').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss97').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 6d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss98', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss98').set('segvar', {'compl_Vaint'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss98').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss98').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 5d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss99', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss99').set('segvar', {'compl_VaPro'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss99').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss99').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 5e');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss100', 'SegregatedStep');
```

```
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss100').set('segvar',  
{'comp1_Vint' 'comp1_Vint1' 'comp1_Vint2' 'comp1_Vint3' 'comp1_Vint4' 'comp1_Vint5'  
'comp1_Vint6' 'comp1_Vint7' 'comp1_Vint8' 'comp1_Vint9'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss100').set('linsolver',  
'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss100').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 3a');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss101', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss101').set('segvar',  
{'comp1_y200' 'comp1_y201' 'comp1_y202' 'comp1_y203' 'comp1_y204' 'comp1_y205'  
'comp1_y206' 'comp1_y207' 'comp1_y208' 'comp1_y209' ...  
'comp1_y210'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss101').set('linsolver',  
'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss101').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 45s');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss102', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss102').set('segvar',  
{'comp1_y300' 'comp1_y301' 'comp1_y302' 'comp1_y303' 'comp1_y304' 'comp1_y305'  
'comp1_y306' 'comp1_y307' 'comp1_y308' 'comp1_y309' ...  
'comp1_y310'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss102').set('linsolver',  
'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss102').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 45v');  
model.sol('sol155').feature.remove('fcDef');  
model.sol('sol155').attach('std2');  
  
model.study('std1').create('time2', 'Transient');  
model.study('std1').feature('time2').set('useinitsol', true);  
model.study('std1').feature('time2').set('initstudy', 'std1');  
model.study('std1').feature('time2').set('solnum', 'last');  
model.study('std1').feature('time2').set('usesol', true);  
model.study('std1').feature('time2').active(false);  
  
model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').active(true);  
  
model.study('std2').feature('time').setIndex('activate', false, 205);  
model.study('std2').feature('time').setIndex('activate', false, 201);  
model.study('std2').feature('time').setIndex('activate', false, 199);  
model.study('std2').feature('time').setIndex('activate', false, 197);  
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('tlist', 'range(0,5,140)');  
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('tunit', 'd');  
model.study('std2').feature('time').setIndex('activate', false, 33);  
model.study('std2').feature('time').setIndex('activate', true, 197);  
model.study('std2').feature('time').setIndex('activate', true, 199);  
model.study('std2').feature('time').setIndex('activate', true, 201);  
model.study('std2').feature('time').setIndex('activate', true, 205);  
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('useinitsol', true);  
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('initmethod', 'sol');  
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('initstudy', 'std1');
```

```
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('solnum', 37);
model.study('std1').feature('time').setIndex('activate', false, 205);
model.study('std1').feature('time').setIndex('activate', false, 201);
model.study('std1').feature('time').setIndex('activate', false, 199);
model.study('std1').feature('time').setIndex('activate', false, 197);
model.study('std1').feature('time').set('tlist', 'range(0,1,40)');
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('solnum', 'last');
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('usesol', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('notsolmethod', 'init');
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('usesol', false);

model.component('comp1').variable('var24').remove('Ci');

model.sol('sol55').study('std2');

model.study('std2').feature('time').set('notlistsolnum', 1);
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('notsolnum', '1');
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('listsolnum', 1);
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('solnum', 'last');

model.sol('sol55').feature.remove('t1');
model.sol('sol55').feature.remove('v1');
model.sol('sol55').feature.remove('st1');
model.sol('sol55').create('st1', 'StudyStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('st1').set('study', 'std2');
model.sol('sol55').feature('st1').set('studystep', 'time');
model.sol('sol55').create('v1', 'Variables');
model.sol('sol55').feature('v1').set('control', 'time');
model.sol('sol55').create('t1', 'Time');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').set('tlist', 'range(0,5,140)');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').set('plot', 'off');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').set('plotgroup', 'pg40');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').set('plotfreq', 'tout');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').set('probesel', 'all');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').set('probes', {});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').set('probefreq', 'tsteps');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').set('atolglobalvaluemethod', 'factor');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').set('endtimeinterpolation', true);
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').set('control', 'time');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').create('sel', 'Segregated');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature.remove('ssDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss1', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_A'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 45r');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss2', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_a'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
```

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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss2').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 2b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss3', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss3').set('segvar',
{'compl_ACE2'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss3').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss3').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 5b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss4', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss4').set('segvar',
{'compl_ACE2bAngI'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss4').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss4').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 6b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss5', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss5').set('segvar',
{'compl_ACE2bAngII'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss5').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss5').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 7a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss6', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss6').set('segvar',
{'compl_AGT'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss6').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss6').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 2');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss7', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss7').set('segvar',
{'compl_Ang17'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss7').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss7').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 5');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss8', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss8').set('segvar',
{'compl_Ang19'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss8').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss8').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 15');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss9', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss9').set('segvar',
{'compl_AngI'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss9').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss9').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 3');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss10', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss10').set('segvar',
{'compl_AngII'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss10').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss10').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 4');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss11', 'SegregatedStep');
```

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model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss11').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_AngIII'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss11').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss11').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 16');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss12', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss12').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_AngIV'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss12').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss12').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 6');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss13', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss13').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_antiPD1'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss13').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss13').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 46');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss14', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss14').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_AT1bAngII'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss14').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss14').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 7');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss15', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss15').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_AT1R'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss15').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss15').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 19');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss16', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss16').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_AT2bAngII'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss16').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss16').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 8');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss17', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss17').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_AT2R'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss17').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss17').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 2c');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss18', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss18').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_AT4bAngIV'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss18').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss18').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 17');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss19', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss19').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_AT4R'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss19').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
```

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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss19').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 4b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss20', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss20').set('segvar', {'compl_BA'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss20').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss20').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45o');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss21', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss21').set('segvar', {'compl_BN'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss21').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss21').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45n');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss22', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss22').set('segvar', {'compl_c'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss22').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss22').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 12');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss23', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss23').set('segvar', {'compl_Cb'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss23').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss23').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 9');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss24', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss24').set('segvar', {'compl_DC'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss24').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss24').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45i');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss25', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss25').set('segvar', {'compl_DCi'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss25').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss25').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45j');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss26', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss26').set('segvar', {'compl_y5'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss26').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss26').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 23');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss27', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss27').set('segvar', {'compl_y15'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss27').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss27').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 10a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss28', 'SegregatedStep');
```

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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss28').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y107' 'comp1_y1072'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss28').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss28').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 11a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss29', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss29').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y87'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss29').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss29').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 12a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss30', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss30').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y18'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss30').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss30').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 13a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss31', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss31').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y19'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss31').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss31').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 14a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss32', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss32').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y108' 'comp1_y1082'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss32').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss32').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 15a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss33', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss33').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y102'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss33').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss33').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 16a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss34', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss34').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y22'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss34').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss34').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 17a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss35', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss35').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y23'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss35').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss35').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 18a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss36', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss36').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y109' 'comp1_y1092'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss36').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss36').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 19a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss37', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss37').set('segvar', {'compl_y78'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss37').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss37').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 2h');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss38', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss38').set('segvar', {'compl_y92'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss38').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss38').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 20a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss39', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss39').set('segvar', {'compl_y26'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss39').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss39').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 21a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss40', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss40').set('segvar', {'compl_y27'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss40').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss40').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 22a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss41', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss41').set('segvar', {'compl_y110' 'compl_y1102'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss41').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss41').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 23a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss42', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss42').set('segvar', {'compl_y90'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss42').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss42').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 24');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss43', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss43').set('segvar', {'compl_y30'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss43').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss43').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 25');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss44', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss44').set('segvar', {'compl_y31'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss44').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss44').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 26');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss45', 'SegregatedStep');
```

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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss45').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y111' 'comp1_y1112'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss45').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss45').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 27');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss46', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss46').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y103'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss46').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss46').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 28');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss47', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss47').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y54'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss47').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss47').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 29');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss48', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss48').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y85'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss48').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss48').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 3d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss49', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss49').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y55'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss49').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss49').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 30');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss50', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss50').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y117' 'comp1_y1172'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss50').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss50').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 31');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss51', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss51').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y94'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss51').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss51').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 32');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss52', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss52').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y62'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss52').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss52').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 33');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss53', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss53').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y63'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss53').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss53').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 34');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss54', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss54').set('segvar', {'compl_y119' 'compl_y1192'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss54').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss54').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 35');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss55', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss55').set('segvar', {'compl_y70'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss55').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss55').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 36');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss56', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss56').set('segvar', {'compl_y71'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss56').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss56').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 37');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss57', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss57').set('segvar', {'compl_y121' 'compl_y1212'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss57').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss57').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 38');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss58', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss58').set('segvar', {'compl_y98'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss58').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss58').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 39');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss59', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss59').set('segvar', {'compl_y86'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss59').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss59').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 4a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss60', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss60').set('segvar', {'compl_y74'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss60').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss60').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 40');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss61', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss61').set('segvar', {'compl_y75'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss61').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss61').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 41');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss62', 'SegregatedStep');
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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss62').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_y124' 'comp1_y1242'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss62').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss62').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 42');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss63', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss63').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_y125'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss63').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss63').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 43');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss64', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss64').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_y96'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss64').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss64').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 44');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss65', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss65').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_Treg'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss65').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss65').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 5f');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss66', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss66').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_y105' 'comp1_y1052'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss66').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss66').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 7b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss67', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss67').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_y14'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss67').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss67').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 9a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss68', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss68').set('segvar', {'comp1_ec' ↵
'comp1_ec2' 'comp1_ec3' 'comp1_ec4' 'comp1_ec5' 'comp1_ec6' 'comp1_ec7' 'comp1_ec8' ↵
'comp1_ec9' 'comp1_ec10' ...
'comp1_ec11' 'comp1_ec12'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss68').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss68').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 22');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss69', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss69').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_H'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss69').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss69').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 2a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss70', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss70').set('segvar', ↵
```

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{'comp1_iec' 'comp1_iec2' 'comp1_iec3' 'comp1_iec4' 'comp1_iec5' 'comp1_iec6'↵
'comp1_iec7' 'comp1_iec8' 'comp1_iec9' 'comp1_iec10' ...
'comp1_iec11' 'comp1_iec12'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss70').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss70').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 2g');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss71', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss71').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_IF'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss71').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss71').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 46c');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss72', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss72').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_IL6'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss72').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss72').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 20');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss73', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss73').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_IL6R'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss73').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss73').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 2d');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss74', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss74').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_IL6RbIL6'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss74').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss74').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 3c');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss75', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss75').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_In'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss75').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss75').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 6a');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss76', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss76').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_ma'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss76').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss76').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 11');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss77', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss77').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_MASbAng17'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss77').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss77').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 18');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss78', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss78').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_MASR'});
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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss78').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss78').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 3b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss79', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss79').set('segvar', {'compl_n'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss79').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss79').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 10');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss80', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss80').set('segvar', {'compl_NETs'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss80').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss80').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45e');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss81', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss81').set('segvar', {'compl_PD1'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss81').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss81').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45f');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss82', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss82').set('segvar', {'compl_PD1bPDL1'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss82').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss82').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45g');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss83', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss83').set('segvar', {'compl_PDL1'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss83').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss83').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 47');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss84', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss84').set('segvar', {'compl_PL'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss84').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss84').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45p');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss85', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss85').set('segvar', {'compl_PS'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss85').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss85').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45q');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss86', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss86').set('segvar', {'compl_Renin'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss86').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss86').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 14');
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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss87', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss87').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_sACE2'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss87').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss87').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 2f');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss88', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss88').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_sIL6R'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss88').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss88').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 21');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss89', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss89').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_sIL6RbIL6'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss89').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss89').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss90', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss90').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_TE'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss90').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss90').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45m');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss91', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss91').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_ThE'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss91').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss91').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45k');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss92', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss92').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_ThM'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss92').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss92').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45t');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss93', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss93').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_ThN'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss93').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss93').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 46d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss94', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss94').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_TM'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss94').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss94').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45u');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss95', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss95').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_TN'});
```

```
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss95').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss95').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 45l');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss96', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss96').set('segvar',
{'compl_Va'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss96').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss96').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 5c');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss97', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss97').set('segvar',
{'compl_Vab'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss97').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss97').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 6d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss98', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss98').set('segvar',
{'compl_Vaint'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss98').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss98').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 5d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss99', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss99').set('segvar',
{'compl_VaPro'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss99').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss99').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 5e');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss100', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss100').set('segvar',
{'compl_Vint' 'compl_Vint1' 'compl_Vint2' 'compl_Vint3' 'compl_Vint4' 'compl_Vint5'
'compl_Vint6' 'compl_Vint7' 'compl_Vint8' 'compl_Vint9'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss100').set('linsolver',
'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss100').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 3a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss101', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss101').set('segvar',
{'compl_y200' 'compl_y201' 'compl_y202' 'compl_y203' 'compl_y204' 'compl_y205'
'compl_y206' 'compl_y207' 'compl_y208' 'compl_y209' ...
'compl_y210'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss101').set('linsolver',
'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss101').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 45s');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss102', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss102').set('segvar',
{'compl_y300' 'compl_y301' 'compl_y302' 'compl_y303' 'compl_y304' 'compl_y305'
'compl_y306' 'compl_y307' 'compl_y308' 'compl_y309' ...
'compl_y310'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss102').set('linsolver',
'dDef');
```

```
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss102').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45v');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature.remove('fcDef');
model.sol('sol155').attach('std2');

model.result.create('pg41', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg41').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg41').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg41').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result.create('pg42', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg42').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg42').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg42').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result.create('pg43', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg43').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg43').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg43').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result.create('pg44', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg44').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg44').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg44').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result.create('pg45', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg45').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg45').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg45').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result.create('pg46', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg46').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg46').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg46').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang19');
model.result.create('pg47', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg47').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg47').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg47').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIII');
model.result.create('pg48', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg48').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg48').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg48').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
model.result.create('pg49', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg49').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg49').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg49').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result.create('pg50', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg50').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg50').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg50').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result.create('pg51', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg51').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg51').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg51').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
model.result.create('pg52', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg52').set('data', 'dset5');
```

```
model.result('pg52').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg52').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsbAng17');
model.result.create('pg53', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg53').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg53').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg53').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result.create('pg54', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg54').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg54').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg54').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result.create('pg55', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg55').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg55').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg55').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result.create('pg56', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg56').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg56').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg56').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result.create('pg57', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg57').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg57').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg57').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result.create('pg58', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg58').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg58').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg58').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result.create('pg59', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg59').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg59').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg59').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result.create('pg60', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg60').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg60').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg60').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result.create('pg61', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg61').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg61').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg61').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result.create('pg62', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg62').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg62').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg62').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2R');
model.result.create('pg63', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg63').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg63').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg63').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MAsR');
model.result.create('pg64', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg64').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg64').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg64').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4R');
model.result.create('pg65', 'PlotGroup3D');
```

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model.result('pg65').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg65').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg65').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2');
model.result.create('pg66', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg66').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg66').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg66').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngI');
model.result.create('pg67', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg67').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg67').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg67').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngII');
model.result.create('pg68', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg68').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg68').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg68').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result.create('pg69', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg69').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg69').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg69').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result.create('pg70', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg70').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg70').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg70').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result.create('pg71', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg71').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg71').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg71').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6RbIL6');
model.result.create('pg72', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg72').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg72').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg72').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result.create('pg73', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg73').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg73').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg73').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sACE2');
model.result.create('pg74', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg74').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg74').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg74').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result.create('pg75', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg75').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg75').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg75').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'iec');
model.result.create('pg76', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg76').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg76').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg76').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y5');
model.result.create('pg77', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg77').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg77').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg77').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y78');
```

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model.result.create('pg78', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg78').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg78').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg78').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y85');
model.result.create('pg79', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg79').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg79').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg79').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y86');
model.result.create('pg80', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg80').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg80').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg80').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y105');
model.result.create('pg81', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg81').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg81').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg81').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y14');
model.result.create('pg82', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg82').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg82').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg82').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y15');
model.result.create('pg83', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg83').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg83').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg83').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y107');
model.result.create('pg84', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg84').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg84').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg84').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y87');
model.result.create('pg85', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg85').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg85').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg85').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y18');
model.result.create('pg86', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg86').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg86').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg86').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y19');
model.result.create('pg87', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg87').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg87').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg87').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y108');
model.result.create('pg88', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg88').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg88').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg88').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y102');
model.result.create('pg89', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg89').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg89').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg89').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y22');
model.result.create('pg90', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg90').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg90').create('slc1', 'Slice');
```

```
model.result('pg90').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y23');
model.result.create('pg91', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg91').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg91').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg91').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y109');
model.result.create('pg92', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg92').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg92').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg92').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y92');
model.result.create('pg93', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg93').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg93').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg93').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y26');
model.result.create('pg94', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg94').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg94').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg94').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y27');
model.result.create('pg95', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg95').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg95').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg95').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y90');
model.result.create('pg96', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg96').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg96').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg96').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y110');
model.result.create('pg97', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg97').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg97').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg97').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y30');
model.result.create('pg98', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg98').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg98').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg98').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y31');
model.result.create('pg99', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg99').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg99').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg99').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y111');
model.result.create('pg100', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg100').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg100').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg100').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y103');
model.result.create('pg101', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg101').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg101').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg101').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y54');
model.result.create('pg102', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg102').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg102').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg102').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y55');
model.result.create('pg103', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg103').set('data', 'dset5');
```

```
model.result('pg103').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg103').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y117');
model.result.create('pg104', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg104').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg104').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg104').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y94');
model.result.create('pg105', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg105').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg105').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg105').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y62');
model.result.create('pg106', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg106').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg106').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg106').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y63');
model.result.create('pg107', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg107').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg107').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg107').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y119');
model.result.create('pg108', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg108').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg108').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg108').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y70');
model.result.create('pg109', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg109').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg109').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg109').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y71');
model.result.create('pg110', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg110').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg110').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg110').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y121');
model.result.create('pg111', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg111').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg111').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg111').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y98');
model.result.create('pg112', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg112').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg112').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg112').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y74');
model.result.create('pg113', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg113').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg113').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg113').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y75');
model.result.create('pg114', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg114').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg114').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg114').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y124');
model.result.create('pg115', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg115').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg115').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg115').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y125');
model.result.create('pg116', 'PlotGroup3D');
```

```
model.result('pg116').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg116').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg116').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y96');
model.result.create('pg117', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg117').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg117').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg117').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'PD1bPDL1');
model.result.create('pg118', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg118').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg118').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg118').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'antiPD1');
model.result.create('pg119', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg119').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg119').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg119').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'PDL1');
model.result.create('pg120', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg120').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg120').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg120').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'PD1');
model.result.create('pg121', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg121').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg121').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg121').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'NETs');
model.result.create('pg122', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg122').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg122').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg122').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IF');
model.result.create('pg123', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg123').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg123').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg123').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'DC');
model.result.create('pg124', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg124').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg124').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg124').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'DCi');
model.result.create('pg125', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg125').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg125').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg125').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ThN');
model.result.create('pg126', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg126').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg126').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg126').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ThE');
model.result.create('pg127', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg127').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg127').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg127').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'TN');
model.result.create('pg128', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg128').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg128').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg128').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'TE');
```

```
model.result.create('pg129', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg129').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg129').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg129').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'BN');
model.result.create('pg130', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg130').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg130').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg130').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'BA');
model.result.create('pg131', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg131').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg131').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg131').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'PL');
model.result.create('pg132', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg132').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg132').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg132').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'PS');
model.result.create('pg133', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg133').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg133').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg133').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'A');
model.result.create('pg134', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg134').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg134').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg134').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y200');
model.result.create('pg135', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg135').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg135').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg135').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ThM');
model.result.create('pg136', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg136').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg136').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg136').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'TM');
model.result.create('pg137', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg137').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg137').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg137').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y300');
model.result.create('pg138', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg138').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg138').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg138').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Va');
model.result.create('pg139', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg139').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg139').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg139').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vab');
model.result.create('pg140', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg140').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg140').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg140').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vaint');
model.result.create('pg141', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg141').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg141').create('slc1', 'Slice');
```

```
model.result('pg141').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'VaPro');
model.result.create('pg142', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg142').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg142').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg142').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Treg');

model.sol('sol155').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

model.study('std2').feature('time').set('plot', true);

model.sol('sol155').study('std2');

model.study('std2').feature('time').set('notlistsolnum', 1);
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('notsolnum', '1');
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('listsolnum', 1);
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('solnum', 'last');

model.sol('sol155').feature.remove('t1');
model.sol('sol155').feature.remove('v1');
model.sol('sol155').feature.remove('st1');
model.sol('sol155').create('st1', 'StudyStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('st1').set('study', 'std2');
model.sol('sol155').feature('st1').set('studystep', 'time');
model.sol('sol155').create('v1', 'Variables');
model.sol('sol155').feature('v1').set('control', 'time');
model.sol('sol155').create('t1', 'Time');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('tlist', 'range(0,5,140)');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('plot', 'on');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('plotgroup', 'pg40');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('plotfreq', 'tout');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('probesel', 'all');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('probes', {});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('probefreq', 'tsteps');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('atolglobalvaluemethod', 'factor');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('endtimeinterpolation', true);
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('control', 'time');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').create('sel', 'Segregated');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature.remove('ssDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss1', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('segvar', ←
{'compl_A'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').label('Domain ODEs and ←
DAEs 45r');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss2', 'SegregatedStep');
```

```
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss2').set('segvar',  
{'compl_a'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss2').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss2').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 2b');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss3', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss3').set('segvar',  
{'compl_ACE2'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss3').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss3').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 5b');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss4', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss4').set('segvar',  
{'compl_ACE2bAngI'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss4').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss4').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 6b');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss5', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss5').set('segvar',  
{'compl_ACE2bAngII'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss5').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss5').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 7a');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss6', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss6').set('segvar',  
{'compl_AGT'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss6').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss6').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 2');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss7', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss7').set('segvar',  
{'compl_Ang17'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss7').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss7').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 5');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss8', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss8').set('segvar',  
{'compl_Ang19'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss8').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss8').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 15');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss9', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss9').set('segvar',  
{'compl_AngI'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss9').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss9').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 3');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss10', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss10').set('segvar',  
{'compl_AngII'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss10').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
```

```
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss10').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 4');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss11', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss11').set('segvar', {'compl_AngIII'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss11').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss11').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 16');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss12', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss12').set('segvar', {'compl_AngIV'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss12').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss12').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 6');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss13', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss13').set('segvar', {'compl_antiPD1'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss13').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss13').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 46');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss14', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss14').set('segvar', {'compl_AT1bAngII'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss14').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss14').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 7');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss15', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss15').set('segvar', {'compl_AT1R'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss15').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss15').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 19');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss16', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss16').set('segvar', {'compl_AT2bAngII'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss16').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss16').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 8');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss17', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss17').set('segvar', {'compl_AT2R'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss17').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss17').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 2c');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss18', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss18').set('segvar', {'compl_AT4bAngIV'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss18').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss18').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 17');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss19', 'SegregatedStep');
```

```
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss19').set('segvar',  
{'compl_AT4R'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss19').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss19').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 4b');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss20', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss20').set('segvar',  
{'compl_BA'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss20').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss20').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 45o');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss21', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss21').set('segvar',  
{'compl_BN'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss21').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss21').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 45n');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss22', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss22').set('segvar',  
{'compl_c'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss22').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss22').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 12');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss23', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss23').set('segvar',  
{'compl_Cb'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss23').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss23').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 9');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss24', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss24').set('segvar',  
{'compl_DC'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss24').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss24').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 45i');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss25', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss25').set('segvar',  
{'compl_DCi'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss25').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss25').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 45j');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss26', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss26').set('segvar',  
{'compl_y5'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss26').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss26').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 23');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss27', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss27').set('segvar',  
{'compl_y15'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss27').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
```

```
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss27').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 10a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss28', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss28').set('segvar', {'compl_y107' 'compl_y1072'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss28').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss28').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 11a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss29', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss29').set('segvar', {'compl_y87'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss29').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss29').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 12a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss30', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss30').set('segvar', {'compl_y18'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss30').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss30').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 13a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss31', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss31').set('segvar', {'compl_y19'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss31').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss31').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 14a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss32', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss32').set('segvar', {'compl_y108' 'compl_y1082'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss32').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss32').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 15a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss33', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss33').set('segvar', {'compl_y102'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss33').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss33').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 16a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss34', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss34').set('segvar', {'compl_y22'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss34').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss34').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 17a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss35', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss35').set('segvar', {'compl_y23'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss35').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss35').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 18a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss36', 'SegregatedStep');
```

```
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss36').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y109' 'comp1_y1092'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss36').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss36').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 19a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss37', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss37').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y78'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss37').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss37').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 2h');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss38', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss38').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y92'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss38').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss38').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 20a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss39', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss39').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y26'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss39').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss39').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 21a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss40', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss40').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y27'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss40').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss40').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 22a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss41', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss41').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y110' 'comp1_y1102'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss41').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss41').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 23a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss42', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss42').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y90'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss42').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss42').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 24');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss43', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss43').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y30'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss43').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss43').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 25');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss44', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss44').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y31'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss44').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss44').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 26');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss45', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss45').set('segvar', {'comp1_y111' 'comp1_y1112'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss45').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss45').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 27');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss46', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss46').set('segvar', {'comp1_y103'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss46').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss46').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 28');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss47', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss47').set('segvar', {'comp1_y54'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss47').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss47').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 29');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss48', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss48').set('segvar', {'comp1_y85'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss48').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss48').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 3d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss49', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss49').set('segvar', {'comp1_y55'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss49').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss49').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 30');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss50', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss50').set('segvar', {'comp1_y117' 'comp1_y1172'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss50').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss50').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 31');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss51', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss51').set('segvar', {'comp1_y94'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss51').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss51').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 32');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss52', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss52').set('segvar', {'comp1_y62'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss52').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss52').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 33');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss53', 'SegregatedStep');
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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss53').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y63'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss53').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss53').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 34');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss54', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss54').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y119' 'comp1_y1192'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss54').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss54').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 35');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss55', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss55').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y70'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss55').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss55').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 36');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss56', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss56').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y71'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss56').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss56').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 37');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss57', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss57').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y121' 'comp1_y1212'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss57').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss57').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 38');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss58', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss58').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y98'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss58').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss58').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 39');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss59', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss59').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y86'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss59').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss59').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 4a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss60', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss60').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y74'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss60').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss60').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 40');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss61', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss61').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y75'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss61').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss61').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 41');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss62', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss62').set('segvar', {'compl_y124' 'compl_y1242'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss62').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss62').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 42');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss63', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss63').set('segvar', {'compl_y125'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss63').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss63').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 43');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss64', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss64').set('segvar', {'compl_y96'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss64').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss64').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 44');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss65', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss65').set('segvar', {'compl_Treg'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss65').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss65').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 5f');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss66', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss66').set('segvar', {'compl_y105' 'compl_y1052'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss66').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss66').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 7b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss67', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss67').set('segvar', {'compl_y14'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss67').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss67').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 9a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss68', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss68').set('segvar', {'compl_ec' 'compl_ec2' 'compl_ec3' 'compl_ec4' 'compl_ec5' 'compl_ec6' 'compl_ec7' 'compl_ec8' 'compl_ec9' 'compl_ec10' ... 'compl_ec11' 'compl_ec12'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss68').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss68').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 22');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss69', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss69').set('segvar', {'compl_H'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss69').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss69').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 22');
```

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DAEs 2a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss70', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss70').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_iec' 'compl_iec2' 'compl_iec3' 'compl_iec4' 'compl_iec5' 'compl_iec6' ↙
'compl_iec7' 'compl_iec8' 'compl_iec9' 'compl_iec10' ...
'compl_iec11' 'compl_iec12'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss70').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss70').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 2g');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss71', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss71').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_IF'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss71').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss71').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 46c');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss72', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss72').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_IL6'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss72').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss72').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 20');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss73', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss73').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_IL6R'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss73').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss73').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 2d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss74', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss74').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_IL6RbIL6'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss74').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss74').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 3c');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss75', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss75').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_In'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss75').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss75').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 6a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss76', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss76').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_ma'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss76').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss76').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 11');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss77', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss77').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_MAsbAng17'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss77').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss77').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 18');
```

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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss78', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss78').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_MAsR'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss78').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss78').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 3b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss79', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss79').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_n'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss79').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss79').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 10');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss80', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss80').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_NETs'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss80').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss80').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45e');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss81', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss81').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_PD1'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss81').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss81').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45f');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss82', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss82').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_PD1bPDL1'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss82').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss82').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45g');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss83', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss83').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_PDL1'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss83').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss83').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 47');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss84', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss84').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_PL'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss84').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss84').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45p');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss85', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss85').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_PS'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss85').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss85').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45q');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss86', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss86').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_Renin'});
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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss86').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss86').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 14');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss87', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss87').set('segvar',
{'compl_sACE2'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss87').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss87').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 2f');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss88', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss88').set('segvar',
{'compl_sIL6R'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss88').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss88').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 21');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss89', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss89').set('segvar',
{'compl_sIL6RbIL6'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss89').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss89').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss90', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss90').set('segvar',
{'compl_TE'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss90').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss90').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 45m');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss91', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss91').set('segvar',
{'compl_ThE'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss91').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss91').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 45k');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss92', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss92').set('segvar',
{'compl_ThM'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss92').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss92').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 45t');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss93', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss93').set('segvar',
{'compl_ThN'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss93').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss93').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 46d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss94', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss94').set('segvar',
{'compl_TM'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss94').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss94').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 45u');
```

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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss95', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss95').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_TN'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss95').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss95').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45l');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss96', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss96').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_Va'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss96').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss96').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 5c');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss97', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss97').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_Vab'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss97').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss97').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 6d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss98', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss98').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_Vaint'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss98').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss98').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 5d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss99', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss99').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_VaPro'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss99').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss99').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 5e');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss100', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss100').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_Vint' 'compl_Vint1' 'compl_Vint2' 'compl_Vint3' 'compl_Vint4' 'compl_Vint5' ↙
'compl_Vint6' 'compl_Vint7' 'compl_Vint8' 'compl_Vint9'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss100').set('linsolver', ↙
'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss100').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 3a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss101', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss101').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_y200' 'compl_y201' 'compl_y202' 'compl_y203' 'compl_y204' 'compl_y205' ↙
'compl_y206' 'compl_y207' 'compl_y208' 'compl_y209' ...
'compl_y210'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss101').set('linsolver', ↙
'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss101').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45s');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss102', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss102').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_y300' 'compl_y301' 'compl_y302' 'compl_y303' 'compl_y304' 'compl_y305' ↙
'compl_y306' 'compl_y307' 'compl_y308' 'compl_y309' ...
```

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'comp1_y310'));
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss102').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss102').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45v');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature.remove('fcDef');
model.sol('sol155').attach('std2');
model.sol('sol155').study('std2');

model.study('std2').feature('time').set('notlistsolnum', 1);
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('notsolnum', '1');
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('listsolnum', 1);
model.study('std2').feature('time').set('solnum', 'last');

model.sol('sol155').feature.remove('t1');
model.sol('sol155').feature.remove('v1');
model.sol('sol155').feature.remove('st1');
model.sol('sol155').create('st1', 'StudyStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('st1').set('study', 'std2');
model.sol('sol155').feature('st1').set('studystep', 'time');
model.sol('sol155').create('v1', 'Variables');
model.sol('sol155').feature('v1').set('control', 'time');
model.sol('sol155').create('t1', 'Time');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('tlist', 'range(0,5,140)');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('plot', 'on');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('plotgroup', 'pg40');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('plotfreq', 'tout');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('probesel', 'all');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('probes', {});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('probefreq', 'tsteps');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('atolglobalvaluemethod', 'factor');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('endtimeinterpolation', true);
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').set('control', 'time');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').create('sel', 'Segregated');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature.remove('ssDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss1', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('segvar', {'comp1_A'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45r');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss2', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').set('segvar', {'comp1_a'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 2b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss3', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss3').set('segvar', {'comp1_ACE2'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss3').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
```

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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss3').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 5b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss4', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss4').set('segvar',
{'compl_ACE2bAngI'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss4').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss4').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 6b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss5', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss5').set('segvar',
{'compl_ACE2bAngII'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss5').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss5').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 7a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss6', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss6').set('segvar',
{'compl_AGT'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss6').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss6').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 2');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss7', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss7').set('segvar',
{'compl_Ang17'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss7').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss7').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 5');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss8', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss8').set('segvar',
{'compl_Ang19'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss8').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss8').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 15');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss9', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss9').set('segvar',
{'compl_AngI'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss9').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss9').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 3');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss10', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss10').set('segvar',
{'compl_AngII'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss10').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss10').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 4');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss11', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss11').set('segvar',
{'compl_AngIII'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss11').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss11').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 16');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss12', 'SegregatedStep');
```

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model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss12').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_AngIV'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss12').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss12').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 6');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss13', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss13').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_antiPD1'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss13').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss13').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 46');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss14', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss14').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_AT1bAngII'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss14').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss14').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 7');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss15', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss15').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_AT1R'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss15').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss15').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 19');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss16', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss16').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_AT2bAngII'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss16').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss16').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 8');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss17', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss17').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_AT2R'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss17').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss17').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 2c');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss18', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss18').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_AT4bAngIV'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss18').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss18').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 17');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss19', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss19').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_AT4R'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss19').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss19').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 4b');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss20', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss20').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_BA'});
model.sol('sol55').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss20').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
```

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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss20').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45o');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss21', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss21').set('segvar', {'compl_BN'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss21').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss21').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45n');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss22', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss22').set('segvar', {'compl_c'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss22').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss22').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 12');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss23', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss23').set('segvar', {'compl_Cb'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss23').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss23').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 9');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss24', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss24').set('segvar', {'compl_DC'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss24').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss24').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45i');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss25', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss25').set('segvar', {'compl_DCi'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss25').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss25').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45j');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss26', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss26').set('segvar', {'compl_y5'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss26').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss26').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 23');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss27', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss27').set('segvar', {'compl_y15'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss27').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss27').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 10a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss28', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss28').set('segvar', {'compl_y107' 'compl_y1072'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss28').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss28').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 11a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss29', 'SegregatedStep');
```

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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss29').set('segvar',  
{'compl_y87'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss29').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss29').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 12a');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss30', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss30').set('segvar',  
{'compl_y18'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss30').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss30').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 13a');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss31', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss31').set('segvar',  
{'compl_y19'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss31').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss31').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 14a');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss32', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss32').set('segvar',  
{'compl_y108' 'compl_y1082'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss32').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss32').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 15a');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss33', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss33').set('segvar',  
{'compl_y102'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss33').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss33').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 16a');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss34', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss34').set('segvar',  
{'compl_y22'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss34').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss34').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 17a');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss35', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss35').set('segvar',  
{'compl_y23'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss35').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss35').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 18a');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss36', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss36').set('segvar',  
{'compl_y109' 'compl_y1092'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss36').set('linsolver', 'dDef');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss36').label('Domain ODEs and  
DAEs 19a');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss37', 'SegregatedStep');  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss37').set('segvar',  
{'compl_y78'});  
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss37').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
```

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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss37').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 2h');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss38', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss38').set('segvar', {'compl_y92'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss38').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss38').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 20a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss39', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss39').set('segvar', {'compl_y26'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss39').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss39').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 21a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss40', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss40').set('segvar', {'compl_y27'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss40').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss40').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 22a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss41', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss41').set('segvar', {'compl_y110' 'compl_y1102'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss41').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss41').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 23a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss42', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss42').set('segvar', {'compl_y90'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss42').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss42').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 24');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss43', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss43').set('segvar', {'compl_y30'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss43').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss43').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 25');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss44', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss44').set('segvar', {'compl_y31'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss44').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss44').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 26');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss45', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss45').set('segvar', {'compl_y111' 'compl_y1112'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss45').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss45').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 27');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss46', 'SegregatedStep');
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model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss46').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y103'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss46').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss46').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 28');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss47', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss47').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y54'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss47').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss47').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 29');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss48', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss48').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y85'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss48').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss48').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 3d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss49', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss49').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y55'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss49').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss49').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 30');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss50', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss50').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y117' 'comp1_y1172'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss50').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss50').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 31');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss51', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss51').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y94'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss51').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss51').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 32');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss52', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss52').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y62'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss52').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss52').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 33');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss53', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss53').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y63'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss53').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss53').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 34');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss54', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss54').set('segvar',↵
{'comp1_y119' 'comp1_y1192'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss54').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
```

```
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss54').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 35');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss55', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss55').set('segvar', {'compl_y70'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss55').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss55').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 36');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss56', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss56').set('segvar', {'compl_y71'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss56').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss56').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 37');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss57', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss57').set('segvar', {'compl_y121' 'compl_y1212'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss57').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss57').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 38');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss58', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss58').set('segvar', {'compl_y98'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss58').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss58').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 39');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss59', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss59').set('segvar', {'compl_y86'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss59').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss59').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 4a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss60', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss60').set('segvar', {'compl_y74'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss60').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss60').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 40');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss61', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss61').set('segvar', {'compl_y75'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss61').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss61').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 41');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss62', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss62').set('segvar', {'compl_y124' 'compl_y1242'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss62').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss62').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 42');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss63', 'SegregatedStep');
```

```
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss63').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_y125'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss63').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss63').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 43');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss64', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss64').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_y96'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss64').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss64').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 44');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss65', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss65').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_Treg'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss65').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss65').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 5f');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss66', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss66').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_y105' 'comp1_y1052'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss66').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss66').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 7b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss67', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss67').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_y14'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss67').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss67').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 9a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss68', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss68').set('segvar', {'comp1_ec' ↵
'comp1_ec2' 'comp1_ec3' 'comp1_ec4' 'comp1_ec5' 'comp1_ec6' 'comp1_ec7' 'comp1_ec8' ↵
'comp1_ec9' 'comp1_ec10' ...
'comp1_ec11' 'comp1_ec12'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss68').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss68').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 22');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss69', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss69').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_H'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss69').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss69').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 2a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss70', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss70').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_iec' 'comp1_iec2' 'comp1_iec3' 'comp1_iec4' 'comp1_iec5' 'comp1_iec6' ↵
'comp1_iec7' 'comp1_iec8' 'comp1_iec9' 'comp1_iec10' ...
'comp1_iec11' 'comp1_iec12'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss70').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss70').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 2g');
```

```
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss71', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss71').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_IF'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss71').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss71').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 46c');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss72', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss72').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_IL6'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss72').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss72').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 20');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss73', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss73').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_IL6R'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss73').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss73').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 2d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss74', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss74').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_IL6RbIL6'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss74').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss74').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 3c');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss75', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss75').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_In'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss75').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss75').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 6a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss76', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss76').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_ma'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss76').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss76').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 11');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss77', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss77').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_MASbAng17'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss77').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss77').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 18');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss78', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss78').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_MASr'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss78').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss78').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 3b');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').create('ss79', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('sel').feature('ss79').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_n'});
```

```
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss79').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss79').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 10');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss80', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss80').set('segvar',
{'compl_NETs'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss80').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss80').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 45e');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss81', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss81').set('segvar',
{'compl_PD1'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss81').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss81').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 45f');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss82', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss82').set('segvar',
{'compl_PD1bPDL1'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss82').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss82').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 45g');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss83', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss83').set('segvar',
{'compl_PDL1'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss83').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss83').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 47');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss84', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss84').set('segvar',
{'compl_PL'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss84').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss84').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 45p');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss85', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss85').set('segvar',
{'compl_PS'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss85').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss85').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 45q');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss86', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss86').set('segvar',
{'compl_Renin'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss86').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss86').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 14');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss87', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss87').set('segvar',
{'compl_sACE2'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss87').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss87').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 2f');
```

```
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss88', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss88').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_sIL6R'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss88').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss88').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 21');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss89', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss89').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_sIL6RbIL6'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss89').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss89').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss90', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss90').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_TE'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss90').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss90').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45m');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss91', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss91').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_ThE'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss91').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss91').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45k');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss92', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss92').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_ThM'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss92').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss92').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45t');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss93', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss93').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_ThN'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss93').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss93').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 46d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss94', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss94').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_TM'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss94').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss94').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45u');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss95', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss95').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_TN'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss95').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss95').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 45l');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss96', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss96').set('segvar', ↙
{'compl_Va'});
```

```
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss96').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss96').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 5c');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss97', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss97').set('segvar',
{'compl_Vab'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss97').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss97').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 6d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss98', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss98').set('segvar',
{'compl_Vaint'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss98').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss98').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 5d');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss99', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss99').set('segvar',
{'compl_VaPro'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss99').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss99').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 5e');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss100', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss100').set('segvar',
{'compl_Vint' 'compl_Vint1' 'compl_Vint2' 'compl_Vint3' 'compl_Vint4' 'compl_Vint5'
'compl_Vint6' 'compl_Vint7' 'compl_Vint8' 'compl_Vint9'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss100').set('linsolver',
'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss100').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 3a');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss101', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss101').set('segvar',
{'compl_y200' 'compl_y201' 'compl_y202' 'compl_y203' 'compl_y204' 'compl_y205'
'compl_y206' 'compl_y207' 'compl_y208' 'compl_y209' ...
'compl_y210'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss101').set('linsolver',
'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss101').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 45s');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').create('ss102', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss102').set('segvar',
{'compl_y300' 'compl_y301' 'compl_y302' 'compl_y303' 'compl_y304' 'compl_y305'
'compl_y306' 'compl_y307' 'compl_y308' 'compl_y309' ...
'compl_y310'});
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss102').set('linsolver',
'dDef');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('se1').feature('ss102').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 45v');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature.remove('fcDef');
model.sol('sol155').attach('std2');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').create('fc1', 'FullyCoupled');
model.sol('sol155').feature('t1').feature('dDef').set('linsolver', 'pardiso');
```

```
model.sol('sol155').runAll;

model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').setIndex('looplevel', 29, 0);
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg41').set('looplevel', [37]);
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'VaPro');
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ci');
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').set('looplevel', [2]);
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').setIndex('looplevel', 29, 0);
model.result('pg41').run;

model.component('comp1').physics('Ci').active(false);

model.component('comp1').variable('var24').set('Ci', '0[M]');

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
```

```
model.result('pg41').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'VaPro');
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').set('data', 'dset4');
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').setIndex('looplevel', 41, 0);
model.result('pg41').run;

model.sol('sol55').runAll;

model.result('pg42').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').set('data', 'dset5');
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').setIndex('looplevel', 4, 0);
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').setIndex('looplevel', 13, 0);
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg41').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'A');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'pAS');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('unit', '1/d');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'pAL');
model.result('pg40').run;

model.study('std1').feature.remove('param');
model.study('std1').create('sens', 'Sensitivity');
model.study('std1').feature('sens').set('optobj', {'comp1.KtiecIn'});
model.study('std1').feature('sens').set('descr', {' '});
model.study('std1').feature('sens').set('optobj', {'comp1.KtiecIn' 'comp1.↙
AT4RbANGIV__0'});
model.study('std1').feature('sens').set('descr', {' ' '});
model.study('std1').feature('sens').set('gradientMethod', 'adjoint');
model.study('std1').feature('sens').set('optobj', {'comp1.KtiecIn' 'comp1.AT4RbANGIV__0'↙
'comp1.disinf_Intestine'});
model.study('std1').feature('sens').set('descr', {' ' ' '});

model.component('comp1').physics.create('sens', 'Sensitivity', 'geom1');

model.study('std1').feature('sens').activate('sens', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time').activate('sens', true);
model.study('std1').feature('time2').activate('sens', true);
model.study('std2').feature('time').activate('sens', true);

model.component('comp1').physics('sens').create('cvar1', 'ControlVariableField', 3);
```

```
model.component('comp1').physics('sens').feature('cvar1').set('shapeFunctionType', ↵  
'shdisc');  
model.component('comp1').physics('sens').feature('cvar1').set('order', 0);  
model.component('comp1').physics('sens').feature('cvar1').selection.set([1]);  
model.component('comp1').physics('sens').feature('cvar1').selection.all;  
  
model.sol('sol54').runAll;  
  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg142').run;  
model.result('pg142').run;  
model.result('pg142').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'fsens(p)');  
model.result('pg142').run;  
model.result('pg142').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'fsens(A)');  
model.result('pg142').run;  
model.result('pg142').run;  
model.result('pg142').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'KtiecIn');  
model.result('pg142').run;  
model.result('pg142').run;  
model.result('pg142').set('data', 'dset4');  
model.result('pg142').run;  
model.result('pg142').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'fsens(KtiecIn)');  
model.result('pg142').feature.remove('slc1');  
model.result('pg142').run;  
model.result('pg142').create('voll1', 'Volume');  
model.result('pg142').run;  
model.result('pg142').feature('voll1').set('expr', 'p');  
model.result('pg142').run;  
model.result('pg142').feature('voll1').set('expr', 'fsens(KtiecIn)');  
model.result('pg142').run;  
model.result('pg142').setIndex('looplevel', 'interp', 0);  
model.result('pg142').setIndex('looplevel', 41, 0);  
model.result('pg142').set('data', 'dset5');  
model.result('pg142').run;  
model.result('pg142').feature('voll1').set('expr', 'fsens(p)');  
model.result('pg142').feature('voll1').set('data', 'dset4');  
  
model.study('std1').feature('time').set('pdistrib', false);  
  
model.component('comp1').physics('sens').feature('cvar1').set('fieldVariableName', ↵  
'psen');  
model.component('comp1').physics('sens').feature('cvar1').set('order', 2);  
  
model.sol('sol54').runAll;  
  
model.result('pg40').run;  
model.result('pg142').run;  
model.result('pg142').set('data', 'dset4');  
  
model.component('comp1').variable('var1').rename('dB', 'dB_old');
```

```
model.component('comp1').physics('sens').feature('cvar1').set('fieldVariableName', 'dB');
model.component('comp1').physics('sens').feature('cvar1').set('initialValue', '2e-3
[1/d]');
model.component('comp1').physics('sens').feature('cvar1').set('scale', '1e-4');

model.sol('sol54').runFromTo('st1', 'v1');

model.result('pg40').run;

model.sol('sol54').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg142').run;
model.result('pg142').feature('vol1').set('expr', 'fsens(dB)');
model.result('pg142').feature('vol1').setIndex('looplevel', 41, 0);
model.result('pg142').feature('vol1').set('expr', 'dB');
model.result('pg142').run;
model.result('pg142').run;
model.result('pg142').run;
model.result('pg142').setIndex('looplevel', 41, 0);
model.result('pg142').run;
model.result('pg142').run;
model.result('pg142').feature('vol1').set('solutionparams', 'manual');
model.result('pg142').run;
model.result('pg142').run;
model.result('pg142').feature('vol1').set('expr', 'fsens(dB)');
model.result('pg142').run;
model.result('pg142').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'dB');
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').feature('ptgr2').set('expr', 'fsens(dB)');

model.study('std2').create('sens', 'Sensitivity');
model.study('std2').feature.remove('sens');
model.study('std1').create('stat', 'Stationary');
model.study('std1').feature.remove('sens');
model.study('std1').feature.remove('stat');
model.study.create('std3');
model.study('std3').create('stat', 'Stationary');
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('AGT', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('Renin', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('AngI', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('AngII', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('Ang17', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('Ang19', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('AngIII', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('AngIV', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('AT1bAngII', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('AT2bAngII', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('AT4bAngIV', true);
```

```
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('MAsbAng17', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('Cb', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('H', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('Vint', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('In', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('Ci', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('n', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('ma', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('c', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('a', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('AT1R', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('AT2R', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('MASR', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('AT4R', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('ACE2', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('ACE2bAngI', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('ACE2bAngII', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('IL6', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('IL6R', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('IL6RbIL6', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('sIL6RbIL6', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('sIL6R', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('sACE2', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('ec', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('iec', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode2', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode3', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode4', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode7', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode9', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode10', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode11', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode12', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode13', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode14', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode15', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode16', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode17', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode18', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode19', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode20', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode21', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode22', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode24', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode23', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode25', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode26', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode27', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode28', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode29', true);
```

```
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode30', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode31', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode32', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode33', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode34', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode35', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode36', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode37', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode38', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode39', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode40', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode41', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode42', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode43', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode44', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('PD1bPDL1', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('antiPD1', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('PDL_1', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('PD1', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('NETs', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('IF', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('DC', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('DCi', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('ThN', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('ThE', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('TN', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('TE', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('BN', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('BA', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('PL', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('PS', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('A', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('y200', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('ThM', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('TM', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('y300', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('Va', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('Vab', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('Vaint', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('VaTran', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('VaPro', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('dode5', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').activate('sens', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').set('useinitsol', true);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').set('initmethod', 'sol');
model.study('std3').feature('stat').set('initstudy', 'std3');
model.study('std3').feature('stat').set('solnum', 'last');
model.study('std3').create('sens', 'Sensitivity');
model.study('std3').feature('sens').set('optobj', {'comp1.Kif'});
model.study('std3').feature('sens').set('descr', {''});
model.study('std3').feature('sens').set('optobj', {'comp1.KtiecIn'});
```

```
model.study('std3').feature('sens').set('descr', {' '});
model.study('std3').feature('sens').set('optobj', {'comp1.KtiecIn' 'comp1.KtiecIn'});
model.study('std3').feature('sens').set('descr', {' ' '});
model.study('std3').feature('sens').remove('descr', 0);
model.study('std3').feature('sens').remove('optobjEvaluateFor', 0);
model.study('std3').feature('sens').remove('optobj', [0]);
model.study('std3').feature('sens').set('optobj', {'comp1.KtiecIn' 'comp1.Kif'});
model.study('std3').feature('sens').set('descr', {' ' '});
model.study('std3').feature('stat').set('initstudy', 'std1');

model.sol.create('sol56');
model.sol('sol56').study('std3');

model.study('std3').feature('stat').set('notlistsolnum', 1);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').set('notsolnum', '1');
model.study('std3').feature('stat').set('listsolnum', 1);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').set('solnum', 'last');

model.sol('sol56').create('st1', 'StudyStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('st1').set('study', 'std3');
model.sol('sol56').feature('st1').set('studystep', 'stat');
model.sol('sol56').create('v1', 'Variables');
model.sol('sol56').feature('v1').set('control', 'stat');
model.sol('sol56').create('s1', 'Stationary');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').create('sn1', 'Sensitivity');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sn1').set('control', 'sens');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').create('sel', 'Segregated');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sel').feature.remove('ssDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sel').create('ss1', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('segvar', {'comp1_A' ←
'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sel').feature('ss1').label('Domain ODEs and ←
DAEs 45r');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sel').create('ss2', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').set('segvar', {'comp1_a' ←
'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sel').feature('ss2').label('Domain ODEs and ←
DAEs 2b');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sel').create('ss3', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sel').feature('ss3').set('segvar', ←
{'comp1_ACE2' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sel').feature('ss3').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sel').feature('ss3').label('Domain ODEs and ←
DAEs 5b');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sel').create('ss4', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sel').feature('ss4').set('segvar', ←
{'comp1_ACE2bAngI' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sel').feature('ss4').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('sel').feature('ss4').label('Domain ODEs and ←
```

```
DAEs 6b');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss5', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss5').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_ACE2bAngII' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss5').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss5').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 7a');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss6', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss6').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_AGT' ↙
'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss6').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss6').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 2');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss7', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss7').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_Ang17' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss7').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss7').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 5');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss8', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss8').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_Ang19' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss8').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss8').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 15');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss9', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss9').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_AngI' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss9').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss9').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 3');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss10', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss10').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_AngII' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss10').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss10').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 4');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss11', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss11').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_AngIII' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss11').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss11').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 16');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss12', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss12').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_AngIV' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss12').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss12').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 6');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss13', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss13').set('segvar', ↙
```

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{'comp1_antiPD1' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss13').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss13').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 46');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss14', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss14').set('segvar',
{'comp1_AT1bAngII' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss14').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss14').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 7');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss15', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss15').set('segvar',
{'comp1_AT1R' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss15').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss15').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 19');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss16', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss16').set('segvar',
{'comp1_AT2bAngII' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss16').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss16').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 8');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss17', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss17').set('segvar',
{'comp1_AT2R' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss17').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss17').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 2c');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss18', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss18').set('segvar',
{'comp1_AT4bAngIV' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss18').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss18').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 17');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss19', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss19').set('segvar',
{'comp1_AT4R' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss19').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss19').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 4b');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss20', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss20').set('segvar', {'comp1_BA'
'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss20').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss20').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 45o');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss21', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss21').set('segvar', {'comp1_BN'
'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss21').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss21').label('Domain ODEs and
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DAEs 45n');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss22', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss22').set('segvar', {'comp1_c'↵
'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss22').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss22').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 12');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss23', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss23').set('segvar', {'comp1_Cb'↵
'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss23').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss23').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 9');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss24', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss24').set('segvar', {'comp1_DC'↵
'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss24').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss24').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 45i');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss25', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss25').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_DCi' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss25').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss25').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 45j');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss26', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss26').set('segvar', {'comp1_y5'↵
'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss26').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss26').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 23');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss27', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss27').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_y15' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss27').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss27').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 10a');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss28', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss28').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_y107' 'comp1_y1072' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss28').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss28').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 11a');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss29', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss29').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_y87' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss29').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss29').label('Domain ODEs and↵
DAEs 12a');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss30', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss30').set('segvar', ↵
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{'comp1_y18' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss30').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss30').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 13a');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss31', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss31').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y19' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss31').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss31').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 14a');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss32', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss32').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y108' 'comp1_y1082' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss32').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss32').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 15a');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss33', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss33').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y102' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss33').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss33').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 16a');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss34', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss34').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y22' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss34').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss34').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 17a');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss35', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss35').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y23' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss35').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss35').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 18a');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss36', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss36').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y109' 'comp1_y1092' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss36').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss36').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 19a');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss37', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss37').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y78' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss37').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss37').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 2h');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss38', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss38').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y92' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss38').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss38').label('Domain ODEs and
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DAEs 20a');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss39', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss39').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y26' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss39').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss39').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 21a');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss40', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss40').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y27' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss40').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss40').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 22a');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss41', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss41').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y110' 'comp1_y1102' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss41').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss41').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 23a');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss42', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss42').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y90' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss42').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss42').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 24');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss43', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss43').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y30' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss43').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss43').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 25');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss44', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss44').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y31' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss44').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss44').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 26');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss45', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss45').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y111' 'comp1_y1112' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss45').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss45').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 27');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss46', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss46').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y103' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss46').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss46').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 28');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss47', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss47').set('segvar', ↙
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{'comp1_y54' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss47').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss47').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 29');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss48', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss48').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y85' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss48').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss48').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 3d');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss49', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss49').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y55' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss49').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss49').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 30');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss50', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss50').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y117' 'comp1_y1172' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss50').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss50').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 31');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss51', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss51').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y94' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss51').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss51').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 32');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss52', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss52').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y62' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss52').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss52').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 33');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss53', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss53').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y63' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss53').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss53').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 34');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss54', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss54').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y119' 'comp1_y1192' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss54').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss54').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 35');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss55', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss55').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y70' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss55').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss55').label('Domain ODEs and
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DAEs 36');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss56', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss56').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y71' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss56').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss56').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 37');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss57', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss57').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y121' 'comp1_y1212' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss57').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss57').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 38');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss58', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss58').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y98' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss58').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss58').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 39');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss59', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss59').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y86' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss59').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss59').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 4a');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss60', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss60').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y74' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss60').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss60').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 40');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss61', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss61').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y75' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss61').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss61').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 41');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss62', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss62').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y124' 'comp1_y1242' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss62').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss62').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 42');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss63', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss63').set('segvar', ↙
{'comp1_y125' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss63').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss63').label('Domain ODEs and ↙
DAEs 43');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss64', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss64').set('segvar', ↙
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{'comp1_y96' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss64').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss64').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 44');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss65', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss65').set('segvar',
{'comp1_Treg' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss65').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss65').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 5f');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss66', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss66').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y105' 'comp1_y1052' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss66').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss66').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 7b');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss67', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss67').set('segvar',
{'comp1_y14' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss67').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss67').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 9a');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss68', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss68').set('segvar', {'comp1_ec'
'comp1_ec2' 'comp1_ec3' 'comp1_ec4' 'comp1_ec5' 'comp1_ec6' 'comp1_ec7' 'comp1_ec8'
'comp1_ec9' 'comp1_ec10' ...
'comp1_ec11' 'comp1_ec12' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss68').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss68').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 22');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss69', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss69').set('segvar', {'comp1_H'
'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss69').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss69').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 2a');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss70', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss70').set('segvar',
{'comp1_iec' 'comp1_iec2' 'comp1_iec3' 'comp1_iec4' 'comp1_iec5' 'comp1_iec6'
'comp1_iec7' 'comp1_iec8' 'comp1_iec9' 'comp1_iec10' ...
'comp1_iec11' 'comp1_iec12' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss70').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss70').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 2g');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss71', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss71').set('segvar', {'comp1_IF'
'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss71').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss71').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 46c');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss72', 'SegregatedStep');
```

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model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss72').set('segvar',
{'comp1_IL6' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss72').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss72').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 20');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss73', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss73').set('segvar',
{'comp1_IL6R' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss73').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss73').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 2d');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss74', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss74').set('segvar',
{'comp1_IL6RbIL6' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss74').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss74').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 3c');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss75', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss75').set('segvar', ('comp1_In'
'comp1_dB'));
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss75').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss75').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 6a');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss76', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss76').set('segvar', ('comp1_ma'
'comp1_dB'));
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss76').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss76').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 11');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss77', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss77').set('segvar',
{'comp1_MAsbAng17' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss77').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss77').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 18');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss78', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss78').set('segvar',
{'comp1_MAsR' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss78').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss78').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 3b');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss79', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss79').set('segvar', ('comp1_n'
'comp1_dB'));
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss79').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss79').label('Domain ODEs and
DAEs 10');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss80', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss80').set('segvar',
{'comp1_NETs' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss80').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
```

```
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss80').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45e');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss81', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss81').set('segvar', {'comp1_PD1' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss81').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss81').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45f');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss82', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss82').set('segvar', {'comp1_PD1bPDL1' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss82').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss82').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45g');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss83', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss83').set('segvar', {'comp1_PDL1' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss83').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss83').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 47');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss84', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss84').set('segvar', {'comp1_PL' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss84').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss84').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45p');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss85', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss85').set('segvar', {'comp1_PS' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss85').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss85').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45q');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss86', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss86').set('segvar', {'comp1_Renin' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss86').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss86').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 14');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss87', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss87').set('segvar', {'comp1_sACE2' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss87').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss87').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 2f');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss88', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss88').set('segvar', {'comp1_sIL6R' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss88').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss88').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 21');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss89', 'SegregatedStep');
```

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model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss89').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_sIL6RbIL6' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss89').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss89').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss90', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss90').set('segvar', {'comp1_TE' ↵
'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss90').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss90').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 45m');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss91', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss91').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_ThE' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss91').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss91').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 45k');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss92', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss92').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_ThM' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss92').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss92').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 45t');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss93', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss93').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_ThN' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss93').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss93').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 46d');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss94', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss94').set('segvar', {'comp1_TM' ↵
'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss94').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss94').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 45u');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss95', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss95').set('segvar', {'comp1_TN' ↵
'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss95').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss95').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 45l');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss96', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss96').set('segvar', {'comp1_Va' ↵
'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss96').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss96').label('Domain ODEs and ↵
DAEs 5c');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss97', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss97').set('segvar', ↵
{'comp1_Vab' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol56').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss97').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
```

```
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss97').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 6d');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss98', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss98').set('segvar', {'comp1_Vaint' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss98').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss98').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 5d');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss99', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss99').set('segvar', {'comp1_VaPro' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss99').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss99').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 5e');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss100', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss100').set('segvar', {'comp1_Vint' 'comp1_Vint1' 'comp1_Vint2' 'comp1_Vint3' 'comp1_Vint4' 'comp1_Vint5' 'comp1_Vint6' 'comp1_Vint7' 'comp1_Vint8' 'comp1_Vint9' ... 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss100').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss100').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 3a');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss101', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss101').set('segvar', {'comp1_y200' 'comp1_y201' 'comp1_y202' 'comp1_y203' 'comp1_y204' 'comp1_y205' 'comp1_y206' 'comp1_y207' 'comp1_y208' 'comp1_y209' ... 'comp1_y210' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss101').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss101').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45s');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').create('ss102', 'SegregatedStep');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss102').set('segvar', {'comp1_y300' 'comp1_y301' 'comp1_y302' 'comp1_y303' 'comp1_y304' 'comp1_y305' 'comp1_y306' 'comp1_y307' 'comp1_y308' 'comp1_y309' ... 'comp1_y310' 'comp1_dB'});
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss102').set('linsolver', 'dDef');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature('se1').feature('ss102').label('Domain ODEs and DAEs 45v');
model.sol('sol156').feature('s1').feature.remove('fcDef');
model.sol('sol156').attach('std3');

model.result.create('pg143', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg143').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg143').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg143').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AGT');
model.result.create('pg144', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg144').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg144').create('slc1', 'Slice');
```

```
model.result('pg144').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Renin');
model.result.create('pg145', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg145').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg145').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg145').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngI');
model.result.create('pg146', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg146').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg146').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg146').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngII');
model.result.create('pg147', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg147').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg147').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg147').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang17');
model.result.create('pg148', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg148').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg148').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg148').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Ang19');
model.result.create('pg149', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg149').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg149').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg149').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIII');
model.result.create('pg150', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg150').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg150').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg150').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AngIV');
model.result.create('pg151', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg151').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg151').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg151').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1bAngII');
model.result.create('pg152', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg152').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg152').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg152').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2bAngII');
model.result.create('pg153', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg153').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg153').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg153').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4bAngIV');
model.result.create('pg154', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg154').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg154').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg154').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MASbAng17');
model.result.create('pg155', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg155').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg155').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg155').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Cb');
model.result.create('pg156', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg156').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg156').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg156').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'H');
model.result.create('pg157', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg157').set('data', 'dset6');
```

```
model.result('pg157').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg157').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vint');
model.result.create('pg158', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg158').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg158').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg158').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'In');
model.result.create('pg159', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg159').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg159').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg159').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'n');
model.result.create('pg160', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg160').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg160').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg160').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ma');
model.result.create('pg161', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg161').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg161').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg161').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'c');
model.result.create('pg162', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg162').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg162').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg162').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'a');
model.result.create('pg163', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg163').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg163').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg163').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT1R');
model.result.create('pg164', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg164').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg164').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg164').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT2R');
model.result.create('pg165', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg165').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg165').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg165').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'MASR');
model.result.create('pg166', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg166').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg166').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg166').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'AT4R');
model.result.create('pg167', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg167').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg167').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg167').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2');
model.result.create('pg168', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg168').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg168').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg168').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngI');
model.result.create('pg169', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg169').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg169').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg169').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ACE2bAngII');
model.result.create('pg170', 'PlotGroup3D');
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model.result('pg170').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg170').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg170').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6');
model.result.create('pg171', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg171').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg171').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg171').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6R');
model.result.create('pg172', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg172').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg172').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg172').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IL6RbIL6');
model.result.create('pg173', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg173').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg173').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg173').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6RbIL6');
model.result.create('pg174', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg174').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg174').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg174').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sIL6R');
model.result.create('pg175', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg175').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg175').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg175').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'sACE2');
model.result.create('pg176', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg176').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg176').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg176').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ec');
model.result.create('pg177', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg177').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg177').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg177').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'iec');
model.result.create('pg178', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg178').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg178').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg178').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y5');
model.result.create('pg179', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg179').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg179').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg179').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y78');
model.result.create('pg180', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg180').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg180').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg180').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y85');
model.result.create('pg181', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg181').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg181').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg181').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y86');
model.result.create('pg182', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg182').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg182').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg182').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y105');
```

```
model.result.create('pg183', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg183').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg183').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg183').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y14');
model.result.create('pg184', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg184').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg184').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg184').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y15');
model.result.create('pg185', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg185').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg185').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg185').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y107');
model.result.create('pg186', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg186').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg186').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg186').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y87');
model.result.create('pg187', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg187').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg187').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg187').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y18');
model.result.create('pg188', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg188').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg188').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg188').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y19');
model.result.create('pg189', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg189').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg189').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg189').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y108');
model.result.create('pg190', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg190').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg190').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg190').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y102');
model.result.create('pg191', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg191').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg191').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg191').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y22');
model.result.create('pg192', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg192').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg192').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg192').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y23');
model.result.create('pg193', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg193').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg193').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg193').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y109');
model.result.create('pg194', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg194').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg194').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg194').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y92');
model.result.create('pg195', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg195').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg195').create('slc1', 'Slice');
```

```
model.result('pg195').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y26');
model.result.create('pg196', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg196').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg196').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg196').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y27');
model.result.create('pg197', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg197').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg197').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg197').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y90');
model.result.create('pg198', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg198').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg198').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg198').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y110');
model.result.create('pg199', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg199').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg199').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg199').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y30');
model.result.create('pg200', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg200').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg200').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg200').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y31');
model.result.create('pg201', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg201').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg201').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg201').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y111');
model.result.create('pg202', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg202').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg202').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg202').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y103');
model.result.create('pg203', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg203').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg203').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg203').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y54');
model.result.create('pg204', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg204').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg204').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg204').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y55');
model.result.create('pg205', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg205').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg205').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg205').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y117');
model.result.create('pg206', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg206').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg206').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg206').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y94');
model.result.create('pg207', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg207').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg207').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg207').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y62');
model.result.create('pg208', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg208').set('data', 'dset6');
```

```
model.result('pg208').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg208').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y63');
model.result.create('pg209', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg209').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg209').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg209').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y119');
model.result.create('pg210', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg210').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg210').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg210').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y70');
model.result.create('pg211', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg211').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg211').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg211').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y71');
model.result.create('pg212', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg212').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg212').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg212').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y121');
model.result.create('pg213', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg213').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg213').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg213').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y98');
model.result.create('pg214', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg214').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg214').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg214').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y74');
model.result.create('pg215', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg215').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg215').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg215').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y75');
model.result.create('pg216', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg216').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg216').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg216').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y124');
model.result.create('pg217', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg217').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg217').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg217').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y125');
model.result.create('pg218', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg218').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg218').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg218').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y96');
model.result.create('pg219', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg219').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg219').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg219').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'PD1bPDL1');
model.result.create('pg220', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg220').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg220').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg220').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'antiPD1');
model.result.create('pg221', 'PlotGroup3D');
```

```
model.result('pg221').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg221').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg221').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'PDL1');
model.result.create('pg222', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg222').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg222').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg222').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'PD1');
model.result.create('pg223', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg223').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg223').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg223').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'NETs');
model.result.create('pg224', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg224').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg224').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg224').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'IF');
model.result.create('pg225', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg225').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg225').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg225').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'DC');
model.result.create('pg226', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg226').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg226').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg226').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'DCi');
model.result.create('pg227', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg227').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg227').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg227').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ThN');
model.result.create('pg228', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg228').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg228').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg228').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ThE');
model.result.create('pg229', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg229').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg229').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg229').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'TN');
model.result.create('pg230', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg230').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg230').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg230').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'TE');
model.result.create('pg231', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg231').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg231').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg231').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'BN');
model.result.create('pg232', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg232').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg232').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg232').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'BA');
model.result.create('pg233', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg233').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg233').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg233').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'PL');
```

```
model.result.create('pg234', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg234').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg234').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg234').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'PS');
model.result.create('pg235', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg235').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg235').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg235').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'A');
model.result.create('pg236', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg236').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg236').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg236').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y200');
model.result.create('pg237', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg237').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg237').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg237').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'ThM');
model.result.create('pg238', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg238').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg238').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg238').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'TM');
model.result.create('pg239', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg239').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg239').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg239').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'y300');
model.result.create('pg240', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg240').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg240').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg240').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Va');
model.result.create('pg241', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg241').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg241').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg241').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vab');
model.result.create('pg242', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg242').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg242').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg242').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Vaint');
model.result.create('pg243', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg243').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg243').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg243').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'VaPro');
model.result.create('pg244', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg244').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg244').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg244').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'Treg');
model.result.create('pg245', 'PlotGroup3D');
model.result('pg245').set('data', 'dset6');
model.result('pg245').create('slc1', 'Slice');
model.result('pg245').feature('slc1').set('expr', 'fsens(dB)');
model.result('pg245').feature('slc1').set('descr', 'Sensitivity w.r.t. dB');
model.result.remove('pg165');
model.result.remove('pg164');
```

```
model.result.remove('pg167');
model.result.remove('pg200');
model.result.remove('pg166');
model.result.remove('pg169');
model.result.remove('pg202');
model.result.remove('pg168');
model.result.remove('pg201');
model.result.remove('pg204');
model.result.remove('pg203');
model.result.remove('pg161');
model.result.remove('pg160');
model.result.remove('pg163');
model.result.remove('pg162');
model.result.remove('pg176');
model.result.remove('pg175');
model.result.remove('pg178');
model.result.remove('pg211');
model.result.remove('pg177');
model.result.remove('pg210');
model.result.remove('pg213');
model.result.remove('pg179');
model.result.remove('pg212');
model.result.remove('pg215');
model.result.remove('pg214');
model.result.remove('pg170');
model.result.remove('pg172');
model.result.remove('pg171');
model.result.remove('pg174');
model.result.remove('pg173');
model.result.remove('pg206');
model.result.remove('pg205');
model.result.remove('pg208');
model.result.remove('pg207');
model.result.remove('pg209');
model.result.remove('pg143');
model.result.remove('pg145');
model.result.remove('pg144');
model.result.remove('pg147');
model.result.remove('pg146');
model.result.remove('pg149');
model.result.remove('pg148');
model.result.remove('pg154');
model.result.remove('pg153');
model.result.remove('pg156');
model.result.remove('pg155');
model.result.remove('pg158');
model.result.remove('pg157');
model.result.remove('pg159');
model.result.remove('pg150');
model.result.remove('pg152');
model.result.remove('pg151');
```

```
model.result.remove('pg242');
model.result.remove('pg241');
model.result.remove('pg244');
model.result.remove('pg243');
model.result.remove('pg245');
model.result.remove('pg240');
model.result.remove('pg239');
model.result.remove('pg238');
model.result.remove('pg187');
model.result.remove('pg220');
model.result.remove('pg186');
model.result.remove('pg189');
model.result.remove('pg222');
model.result.remove('pg188');
model.result.remove('pg221');
model.result.remove('pg224');
model.result.remove('pg223');
model.result.remove('pg226');
model.result.remove('pg225');
model.result.remove('pg181');
model.result.remove('pg180');
model.result.remove('pg183');
model.result.remove('pg182');
model.result.remove('pg185');
model.result.remove('pg184');
model.result.remove('pg217');
model.result.remove('pg216');
model.result.remove('pg219');
model.result.remove('pg218');
model.result.remove('pg198');
model.result.remove('pg231');
model.result.remove('pg197');
model.result.remove('pg230');
model.result.remove('pg233');
model.result.remove('pg199');
model.result.remove('pg232');
model.result.remove('pg235');
model.result.remove('pg234');
model.result.remove('pg237');
model.result.remove('pg236');
model.result.remove('pg190');
model.result.remove('pg192');
model.result.remove('pg191');
model.result.remove('pg194');
model.result.remove('pg193');
model.result.remove('pg196');
model.result.remove('pg195');
model.result.remove('pg228');
model.result.remove('pg227');
model.result.remove('pg229');
```

```
model.study('std3').feature('stat').setIndex('activate', false, 1);
model.study('std3').feature('stat').setIndex('activate', true, 1);
model.study.create('std4');
model.study('std4').create('time', 'Transient');
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('AGT', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('Renin', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('AngI', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('AngII', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('Ang17', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('Ang19', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('AngIII', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('AngIV', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('AT1bAngII', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('AT2bAngII', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('AT4bAngIV', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('MASbAng17', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('Cb', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('H', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('Vint', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('In', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('Ci', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('n', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('ma', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('c', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('a', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('AT1R', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('AT2R', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('MASR', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('AT4R', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('ACE2', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('ACE2bAngI', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('ACE2bAngII', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('IL6', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('IL6R', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('IL6RbIL6', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('sIL6RbIL6', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('sIL6R', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('sACE2', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('ec', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('iec', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('dode', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('dode2', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('dode3', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('dode4', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('dode7', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('dode9', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('dode10', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('dode11', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('dode12', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('dode13', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('dode14', true);
```



```
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('Va', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('Vab', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('Vaint', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('VaTran', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('VaPro', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('dode5', true);
model.study('std4').feature('time').activate('sens', true);
model.study('std3').create('time', 'Transient');
model.study('std4').create('sens', 'Sensitivity');
model.study.remove('std4');
model.study.remove('std3');
model.study('std1').create('stat', 'Stationary');
model.study('std1').feature('stat').set('useinitsol', true);
model.study('std1').feature('stat').set('initmethod', 'sol');
model.study('std1').feature('stat').set('initstudy', 'std2');
model.study('std1').feature('stat').set('solnum', 'last');
model.study('std1').feature('stat').set('initstudy', 'std1');
model.study('std1').create('sens', 'Sensitivity');
model.study('std1').feature('sens').set('optobj', {'compl.Kif'});
model.study('std1').feature('sens').set('descr', {''});
model.study('std1').feature('sens').set('optobj', {'compl.Kif' 'compl.KtiegIn'});
model.study('std1').feature('sens').set('descr', {' '});

model.sol('sol154').runAll;

model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;
model.result('pg40').run;

out = model;
```